

Amphibians

One amphibian, the Great Basin spadefoot toad (*Spea intermontana*), occurs on the facility. Great Basin spadefoots occur primarily in shrub-steppe. A variety of aquatic habitats are used for breeding including slow flowing springs, seasonal pools, irrigation ditches and ponds.

Spadefoots are nocturnal and completely terrestrial, only returning to water for breeding. At the installation, spadefoots had utilized Toad Pond (when it was functioning) and intermittent ponds that develop in Juniper Canyon during wet years as a breeding location and for egg-laying. Spadefoots are adapted to survive in arid climates by spending long periods of time buried under ground. They are able to quickly bury themselves in loose soils by using their hind legs in a circular motion to back into the soil. They can remain buried for months at a time and can tolerate high levels of water loss. Activity is reported to be primarily associated with rains and periods of high humidity, however, in many areas of the Columbia Basin, it is common to find individuals on roads at night without precipitation.

Great basin spadefoots start breeding in late March in the Columbia Basin. Typically, all breeding is completed in a period of a few days. Breeding duration at each site varies with conditions such as water temperature and hydro-period. Eggs hatch typically in 2-3 days, but development can take longer if water temperatures are cooler. Tadpole development typically takes 1-2 months, but can accelerate with high temperatures if pool drying threatens to strand developing larvae. Spadefoots remain active until late October-early November.

Reptiles

Three lizards and three snakes have been verified as occurring on the facility (Table 2-4).

Table 2-4. Reptiles known to inhabit NWSTF Boardman.

Short-horned Lizard (GF, SB, SD, AL)	Racer (GF, BG, LS, BB, SB, JU)
Northern Sagebrush Lizard (SB, BB, SD)	Gopher Snake (GF, BG, LS, BB, SB, JU)
Side-blotched Lizard (GF, SB)	Western Rattlesnake (GF, SB)

Habitat Types: GF = annual grass/forb, BG = bunchgrass, LS = open low shrub, BB = bitterbrush, SB = sagebrush, JU = juniper, SD = sand dune, AL = alkali.

Short-horned Lizard - The distinctive short-horned lizard, commonly called a "horned toad," is occasionally observed on the facility. This lizard may be more common on the facility than is

apparent because their cryptic color patterns make them very difficult to detect. Although short-horned lizards may occur anywhere on the facility where there is soil loose enough for them to burrow, they have been most often observed in open sagebrush communities in the vicinity of Juniper Canyon (especially the south half), or in the sandy bitterbrush community of the north end of the facility. Many of the sightings have been of animals on the roads, especially on the old Oregon Trail. Several horned lizards have been found skewered on barbed wire or dead sagebrush by loggerhead shrikes, a major predator of this species on the facility.

Short-horned lizards commence breeding immediately following emergence from hibernation in spring, but do not bear young until late summer or early fall. Grasshoppers, crickets, harvester ants, and beetles are important prey items for this species.

Northern Sagebrush Lizard - Northern sagebrush lizards are the most commonly observed and probably the most ecologically important reptile on the facility due to their high population levels

and source of food for predators. Their importance at NWSTF Boardman led to targeting this species for special study in 1995 (Green et al. 1995). The results of the 1995 study on the facility showed that sagebrush lizards were found almost exclusively in big sagebrush or bitterbrush shrub communities with a high percentage (approximately 50-60 percent) of sandy bare ground (see Appendix N for full report). They largely avoided areas of high grass, litter, and lichen coverage. In general, sagebrush

lizards were found where large shrubs covered semi-active dune systems. A sensitive species survey for sagebrush preferring species was conducted in 2009 by Oregon State University and The Nature Conservancy after the 2008 wildfire that burned much of the remaining sagebrush habitat (The Nature Conservancy 2009). Many detections of sagebrush lizards were recorded mostly in and around the remaining unburned patches of sagebrush habitat (see Figure 2-22 and Appendix M for full report). Figure 2-22 shows the distribution of this lizard on the facility.

Observations of lizards skewered on barbed-wire fences indicate that the loggerhead shrike is an important predator of sagebrush lizards. Sagebrush lizards are also probably important in the diet of racers, gopher snakes, and possibly American kestrels. Green et al. (1993) did not find sagebrush lizards in local owl diets, possibly because the lizards are highly diurnal (and the owls are not).

Side-blotched Lizard - Side-blotched lizards occur at four small, isolated populations on the facility. In all cases, they have been found in association with road cuts where they used exposed rodent and arthropod burrows for cover. Two of the populations were also associated with sagebrush. A population along Juniper Canyon Road, near the Oregon Trail crossing, is probably more associated with adjacent rocks than the actual road cut. Ants, beetles, true bugs, grasshoppers, and spiders dominate the diet of this species.

Racer - The racer is relatively common inhabitant of the facility. It has been observed in the cheatgrass and bitterbrush habitats on the north end of the facility, and in the sagebrush habitats of Juniper Canyon. This fast-moving snake feeds largely on large insects (especially grasshoppers), small lizards, and mice (Brown and Parker 1982, Nussbaum et al. 1983). Northern sagebrush lizards are probably an important prey item.

Gopher Snake - Gopher snakes are the most commonly observed snake on the facility. These generally diurnal snakes feed largely on mice (Brown and Parker 1982, Diller and Johnson 1988), and have been found in all habitat types on the facility. As described elsewhere (Nussbaum et al. 1983) these snakes spend half or more of the year wintering in abandoned mammal burrows. Females also nest in abandoned mammal burrows, sometimes communally with other gopher snakes or other snake species (Nussbaum et al. 1983).

Figure 2-22
Northern Sagebrush
Lizard Distribution
at NWSTF Boardman

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Western Rattlesnake - Grazing lessees have described occasional encounters with western rattlesnakes on the facility, and G. Green photographed a large adult at a rock outcrop in south Juniper Canyon in May 1995. It is unlikely that this species is very common on the facility; its distribution is limited by the sporadic presence of rock outcrops. Like other local snakes, it spends over half the year in winter dens, commonly with other snakes. Local rattlesnakes probably feed largely on ground squirrels and mice (Diller and Johnson 1988).

Mammals

At least 20 species of mammals occur on the facility, 18 of which are expected to breed and occur year-round (Table 2-5). Because of the lack of detailed habitat use information available on the smaller species, and the wide range of habitat use by the larger species, habitat use by mammals was not quantified.

Table 2-5. Mammals Known to Inhabit NWSTF Boardman.

Vagrant Shrew	Sagebrush Vole
Black-tailed Jackrabbit	Montane Vole
Nuttall's Cottontail	House Mouse
Washington Ground Squirrel	Porcupine
Northern Pocket Gopher	Red Fox ¹
Great Basin Pocket Mouse	Coyote
Ord's Kangaroo Rat	Long-tailed Weasel
Western Harvest Mouse	Badger
Deer Mouse	Rocky Mountain Elk ¹
Northern Grasshopper Mouse	Mule Deer
Bushy-tailed Woodrat	Pronghorn Antelope

¹Probably not breeding at NWSTF Boardman.

Vagrant Shrew - The presence of the vagrant shrew on the facility is based upon a single individual found in the diet of a pair of burrowing owls nesting on the north end of the facility in 1981 (G. Green, unpubl. data), and two found in the diet of Juniper Canyon barn owls in 1997 (see Appendix L for full details). This shrew is perhaps the most ubiquitous shrew in the Pacific Northwest, using a wide variety of habitats. Green (unpubl. data) found this species relatively common on the Umatilla National Wildlife Refuge in 1981. However, the arid shrub-steppe habitats occurring on the facility is unlikely to support significant populations of this species due to lack of water.

Black-tailed Jackrabbit - The black-tailed jackrabbit is one of the more common mammals on the facility, especially during years of peak densities. Like other hares, black-tailed jackrabbit populations fluctuate greatly over an approximate six-to-ten year cycle (Gross et al. 1974).

Black-tailed jackrabbits are largely distributed throughout the facility wherever bitterbrush, sagebrush, and rabbitbrush cover occurs. Previous studies (Orr 1940, Lechleitner 1958) have shown that jackrabbits commonly forage at night in grasslands, then retreat back to shrub habitats by day. These rabbits are generalist herbivores, but are regionally selective. A majority of publications show that forbs and grasses are most important during the spring, while shrubs become important during the fall and winter. Although apparently not highly preferred, Sandberg bluegrass was also found in the diet in bitterbrush communities. Stewart and Hull (1949) have

suggested that jackrabbit grazing, especially during peak densities and/or in combination with livestock grazing, can strongly influence the development and maintenance of cheatgrass cover by removing perennial grasses and preventing them from invading cheatgrass communities.

Black-tailed jackrabbits are probably the major food source for coyotes, golden eagles, ferruginous hawks, and winter populations of rough-legged hawks on facility, and somewhat important to the diet of Swainson's hawks (Stoddart 1970, Wagner and Stoddart 1972, Smith and Murphy 1973, Platt 1976, Fitzner et al. 1977). The annual use of the facility by relatively high numbers of immature golden eagles is probably directly attributable to the presence of jackrabbits. Furthermore, the near complete lack of nesting by ferruginous hawks on facility in 1995 might also be attributed to the very low densities of jackrabbits that year.

Nuttall's Cottontail - The Nuttall's cottontail is relatively common on the facility, especially around buildings, materials piles, and used munitions accumulation areas, which they use for shelter. This rabbit is also common in the dense sagebrush areas of south Juniper Canyon where they inhabit abandoned badger burrows, especially in road cuts. They have also been found sheltering under caliche (hard calcareous deposits) extrusions in Juniper Canyon. Unlike pygmy rabbits, Nuttall's cottontails are not known to excavate their own underground burrows (Chapman 1975). Orr (1940) found that while these cottontails preferred grass over all other vegetation in the spring and early summer, sagebrush and junipers were important the rest of the year. This may account for the rabbit's presence in south Juniper Canyon. Golden eagles, Swainson's hawks, ferruginous hawks, and coyotes are probably major predators of cottontails on the facility.

Washington Ground Squirrel - The Washington ground squirrel inhabits arid sagebrush and grassland regions of the Oregon and Washington Columbia Plateau (Rickart and Yensen 1992). Their range is restricted, however, to the sandy soil regions of the Columbia Basin south and east of the Columbia River (Bailey 1936, Howell 1938). Washington ground squirrels are an important component in the diet of local predators, especially badgers, ferruginous hawks, and

golden eagles (G. Green, pers. obs.). Presently, one of the largest collection of colonies occurs at NWSTF Boardman (Quade 1994), where it has become a focal species in recent years because of its status (federal candidate for listing as threatened or endangered).

Olterman and Verts (1972) concluded that this species no longer occurred in Oregon based on a 1971 search. However, Rohweder et al. (1979) "rediscovered" the squirrel on NWSTF Boardman in 1978. In the following year, Carlson et. al. (1980) found 17 colonies in Oregon, including several at NWSTF Boardman. Ten years later, Betts (1990) confirmed the presence of 35 colonies in Oregon, but he showed that most historical sites in Oregon and Washington no longer support Washington ground squirrels. Quade (1994) followed up on the Carlson et al. (1980) studies and found squirrel densities at the original colony sites to be low. However, Quade (1994) did find Washington ground squirrels at 19 additional locations at NWSTF Boardman. Furthermore, Eric Greene (E. Greene, pers. com., Greene et. al. 2009) located and studied 59 colonies at NWSTF Boardman in 1996 and 1997, and found that the majority occurred in sagebrush habitats interspersed with bunchgrasses. A survey for Washington ground squirrels in the general vicinity of the proposed locations for potential Oregon National Guard range

support facilities was conducted in the Spring of 2005 (NWC 2005). This survey identified a large number of potentially active burrows in the northern part of the installation.

Figure 2-23 shows a composite map of known Washington ground squirrel locations at NWSTF Boardman from a compilation of all incidental sightings, all recorded historic colony locations and the results of 2006 surveys conducted through ODFW. Washington ground squirrels appear to prefer deep loamy soils for burrowing. The higher density of this species in the southern part of the NWSTF Boardman, as shown in Figure 2-23 likely corresponds to the presence of gradually deeper loamy soils (Warden soil – see Figure 2-6) toward the south on the range (Marr 2001, see Appendix K for full report). This region of the range also tends to receive a little more precipitation than areas farther north, which may also be a reason the population appears denser in the southern portion of the range. The blue dots in Figure 2-23 indicate locations where squirrels have been present in the past and are part of regular survey efforts. In some cases, the dots represent colonies. In other cases, they represent only an incidental sighting, where there may or may not be a colony.

Several recent graduate researchers studied Washington ground squirrels at NWSTF Boardman. Klein (2005) investigated dispersal patterns of Washington ground squirrels and found that juvenile male dispersal ranged from 40-3521 m. from the natal burrow with an average dispersal distance of 880 m. (see Appendix K for full report). Delavan (2008) studied Washington ground squirrel home range size and movement patterns on NWSTF Boardman and surrounding areas and found that core use areas for individual squirrels ranged from 46-8181 m² and home range size ranged from 435-77,021 m² (see Appendix K for full report).

Results of the above studies indicate that (1) Washington ground squirrel populations have rebounded at NWSTF Boardman after an apparent decline in the 1980s and early 1990s (probably due to drought conditions during those years); and (2) the facility supports the majority of Oregon's remaining populations of this squirrel. However, during a brief site visit in 1998, ground squirrel experts Drs. Paul Sherman (Cornell) and Eric Yensen (Albertson College, Idaho) were not encouraged by what they saw in terms of long-term survival of the species on the facility. To them, squirrel densities appeared very low as compared to inhabited areas in Washington.

Like most rodent species, Washington ground squirrel populations are expected to be regularly or intermittently cyclical based on environmental factors, both physical (precipitation, etc.) and biological (food quantity, diseases, etc.). Based on the results of previous survey work, dispersal distances, and home range size, it is reasonable to assume the all of NWSTF Boardman is suitable Washington ground squirrel habitat (especially during high years of a population cycle). At lower ends of a population cycle, it would be expected that the species use of NWSTF Boardman would shrink into “core” areas that provide higher quality and more stable habitat during those less than optimal conditions. Maintaining habitat quantity and quality for both end of the population cycles is vitally important to maintaining a long-term viable Washington ground squirrel population at NWSTF Boardman and adjacent suitable habitat.

Washington ground squirrels are important components of ecological ecosystems. Washington ground squirrels are a prey base for predator food chains, reduce soil compaction, loosen and aerate soils, and increase the rate of water infiltration into soil. Additionally, they increase soil fertility, bring nutrients from deep soil layers to the surface, increase plant productivity, increase plant diversity by bringing buried seeds near the surface, and increase diversity of microhabitats. Predation of Washington ground squirrels by badgers

creates burrows that are reused by many species including snakes, lizards, ground squirrels, insects, and burrowing owls (USFWS 2011).

Washington ground squirrel surveys will be conducted at necessary repeated time intervals in order to determine the activity status of historical Washington ground squirrel sites. Using the ODFW monitoring protocol, surveys will provide information confirming species presence, geographic extent of active sites, estimates of burrow abundance at active sites, and can be compared to previous survey work for the species. Survey protocol can be found in Morgan and Nugent (1999) and Greene (1999) (see Appendix K for full reports). Further modifications of those survey protocols may be made in coordination with ODFW and USFWS to adapt them to meet additional monitoring goals that may be developed in the future.

Northern Pocket Gopher - While no formal distribution or density surveys for northern pocket gophers have been conducted on the facility, they probably occur in all habitats except the highly arid sand habitats. This species has a very broad range of soil tolerance compared to other North American gophers (Miller 1964). It prefers easily-dug soils with large herbage yields (Reid 1973), especially succulent forbs, the preferred food (Chase et al. 1982). On the facility, pocket gophers appear to be most common in the sagebrush, rabbitbrush, and bunchgrass habitats (G. Green, pers. obs. 1998) where forb densities are high and vegetation roots help to prevent burrow cave-ins in the friable soils. They appear to be least common in the sandy bitterbrush and cheatgrass habitats, and where a long history of livestock use has compacted the soils. Green et al. (1993) found pocket gophers to be five times more common in the diets of burrowing owls inhabiting silty loam soil habitats than in habitats underlain with loamy sand soils.

Green et al. (1993) found this species to contribute less than one percent of the frequency of burrowing prey captures in the Columbia Basin of both Oregon and Washington, but, because of their relatively large body size, they contributed 20 percent of the biomass. Among mammalian prey alone, (which accounted for 87 percent of the total biomass), gophers contributed approximately 50 percent of the biomass consumed. In addition, pocket gophers contributed nearly half of the total biomass of prey consumed by barn owls in Juniper Canyon in 1995 (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details). In addition to owls, pocket gophers are probably an important prey item for badgers (Criddle 1930) and ferruginous hawks (Fitzner et al. 1977).

Great Basin Pocket Mouse - Great Basin pocket mice are prevalent throughout the facility, but most especially in the sandier soils in the north end where they comprised over 90 percent of the small mammal captures during studies conducted here in the early 1980s (Green 1983, Small and Verts 1983, Verts and Carraway 1986). O'Farrell et al. (1975) and Rogers and Hedlund (1980) found similar numerical dominance by pocket mice in the shrub-steppe of south-central Washington. Several researchers have noted this heteromyid's preference for sandy soils (Dalquest 1948, O'Farrell et al. 1975, Feldhammer 1979). On the central and southern portions of the facility, pocket mice share their numerical dominance with western harvest and deer mice.

Green et al. (1993) found that the pocket mice clearly dominated the diet of burrowing owls inhabiting sandy soil habitats in the Columbia Basin. This was most evident from the portion of the database specific to the north end of NWSTF Boardman where pocket mice comprised greater than 90 percent of the owl's small mammal diet. They were also the most common small mammal in the diet of barn and long-eared owls in Juniper Canyon from 1995 to 1997, when they numerically comprised 46-75 percent of the total diets (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L

Figure 2-23
Washington Ground
Squirrel Locations
from Compilation of
Recorded Surveys

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for full details). In 1980, they comprised 86 percent of the long-eared owl diet (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details).

Annual variations in pocket mice populations are apparently strongly correlated with winter precipitation and its influence on seed resources, especially cheatgrass, the primary food resource for pocket mice in the Columbia Basin (Kritzman 1974), and perennial grasses such as western needle-and-thread and bluebunch wheatgrass. Insects are also important in the spring prior to seed ripening (Kritzman 1974, O'Farrell et al. 1975). Although pocket mice can be captured year-round, the majority of these mice are active only during the warmer 8-9 months of the year. Much of the late summer activity is limited to below-ground where the small mammals are able to conserve moisture and get their food from seed caches filled earlier in the year. Regardless of their temporal and spatial variation in numbers and activity, facility-wide they are ecologically and energetically the most important vertebrate. In addition to the owls mentioned above, gopher snakes, rattlesnakes, American kestrels, long-tailed weasels, and badgers probably prey heavily on pocket mice.

Ord's Kangaroo Rat - The commonality of Ord's kangaroo rats on the facility is a bit of an enigma. Trapping studies by Green (1983), Small and Verts (1983), and Verts and Carraway (1986) found Ord's kangaroo rats to comprise only one to two percent of all small mammals captured on the north end of the facility. However, studies of the diets of local owl populations suggest a higher contribution of the kangaroo rats to the small mammal community. Green et al. (1993) found Ord's kangaroo rats to comprise five to six percent of diet of burrowing owls in the Oregon Columbia Basin (from 1980 to 1981), including the north end of the facility. Diet studies conducted on owls inhabiting Juniper Canyon from 1994 to 1997 showed the annual contribution of kangaroo rats to the total small mammal diet of barn owls to range from two to twelve percent (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details). For long-eared owls the kangaroo rats contributed one to nine percent of the diet, except in 1995 when they were 27 percent. It is likely that the Sherman livetraps used in the trapping studies were less effective in capturing this large heteromyid than the owls.

Ord's kangaroo rats are well adapted to open sandy areas in arid regions (Kritzman 1977), such as found on the north end of the facility and in Juniper Canyon. They construct elaborate underground burrows that are deep enough to maintain moisture. Field observations (G. Green, pers. obs.) suggest that sandbanks and roadcuts are important in burrow site selection. Kangaroo rats are also very nocturnal, and, like most heteromyids, are able to metabolize their moisture needs from dry foods. Because of their size, approximately 53 g (Marks 1983), their biomass contribution to the diet of many owl predators is much higher than their numerical contribution.

Western Harvest Mouse - While the presence of western harvest mice has long been suspected for NWSTF Boardman based on their presence in similar habitats in Washington (Gano and Rickard 1982), no harvest mice were captured by Green (1983), Small and Verts (1983), or Verts and Carraway (1986) during their large trapping studies on the north end of the facility. In addition, Green et al. (1993) did not find the harvest mouse in the diet of burrowing owls nesting on the north end of the facility. The first recorded observation for this species on the facility was by Quade (1994) who captured harvest mice in RNA-B in 1994 (exact number not given).

In addition, harvest mice were found to comprise 30 percent of the diet of barn owls and 16 percent for long-eared owls in Juniper Canyon in 1994. However, by 1995, the composition of harvest mice dropped to two percent for barn owls, then to 15 percent and 11 percent for 1996

and 1997. The presence of harvest mice in long-eared owl diets also dropped (six percent) in 1995, but stayed low for 1996 (two percent) and 1997 (eight percent). Also, no harvest mice were found from long-eared owl pellets collected at the same Juniper Canyon site in 1980. Consequently, harvest mice may have been uncommon facility-wide in the early 1980s, but were relatively common on the south-central part of the facility in the 1990s, although fluctuations in the population appear to occur annually. Western harvest mice prefer grassy habitats (Webster and Jones 1982) and have probably benefited from the establishment of the RNAs and the subsequent buildup of dense stands of western needle-and-thread grass. Development of dense grass stands in the past decade may account for the differences in long-eared owl diets between 1980 and 1994.

Deer Mouse - The ubiquitous deer mouse is relatively common in the shrub and dense grass habitats of the south end of the facility. Quade (1994) found deer mice on all of her trapping grids in the western needle-and-thread grass-dominated RNAs, and Green found deer mice to comprise 53 and 31 percent of the diet of long-eared and barn owls, respectively, in south Juniper Canyon in 1994. However, on the sandy soils of the north end of the facility, this mouse is relatively rare in this region dominated by arid land adapted heteromyids like pocket mice and kangaroo rats. For instance, in over 1,800 trapnights Small and Verts (1983) captured 244 individual small mammals (98 percent pocket mice), but only one deer mouse. In a follow up study at the same location on the north end of the facility, Verts and Carraway (1986) captured 306 mice (97 percent pocket mice), of which none were deer mice. Similarly, Green (unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details) found deer mice to be a very rare component (less than one percent) in the diet of burrowing owls inhabiting the north end of the facility.

Northern Grasshopper Mouse - The northern grasshopper mouse is largely predatory in nature. Approximately 80 percent of its diet is comprised of large ground-dwelling arthropods, and 10 percent other small rodents (Ingles 1965). Like most predators, grasshopper mice occur at relatively low densities (Nowack 1991). Small and Verts (1983) captured only two grasshopper mice out of a total 244 small mammal captures, and Verts and Carraway (1986) captured only two out of 306 total captures. Quade (1994) also captured grasshopper mice at RNA-B and RNA-C, but provided no numbers. Similarly, owl diet studies on the facility only found one grasshopper mouse in the food remains from burrowing owls on the north end in 1981, and one from 1994 and two from 1996 long-eared owl pellets in Juniper Canyon (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details). It is likely that this species is ubiquitous on the facility, but occurs in densities too low for frequent detection. This species is highly territorial and has a home range of about five to seven acres (Nowack 1991), which, for instance, is 60 to 120 times greater than calculated home ranges for pocket mice in Oregon (Feldhammer 1979).

Bushy-tailed Woodrat - A bushy-tailed woodrat was observed in 1996 in association with juniper trees on the western edge of the facility. It also likely occurs, or has occurred, in the rocky outcroppings where traces of urine deposits (appearing as white encrustations serving as territorial markers) have been found. Juniper trees, rock outcroppings, and abandoned buildings are favored denning sites for this species in eastern Oregon (Verts and Carraway 1998). Although this species was not found in the diet of Juniper Canyon long-eared and barn owls, other owl diet studies in eastern Oregon (see Verts and Carraway 1998) have shown that owls smaller than great horned owls rarely capture this large rodent.

Sagebrush Vole - The sagebrush vole was identified by Quade (1994) as an unrecorded species of small mammal that she expected to be present on NWSTF Boardman, although none were recorded during trapping efforts by Green (1983), Small and Verts (1983), Verts and Carraway (1986), and Quade (1994). However, G. Green found a sagebrush vole in the pellet

remains from a long-eared owl roost site in Juniper Canyon. Also, Quade (1994) identified grass runways characteristic of this species in Well Springs Canyon (which has not been trapped); however, the more common montane vole also constructs grass runways.

Montane Vole - The montane vole was not captured during any of the previous small mammal trapping studies (Green 1983, Small and Verts 1983, Verts and Carraway 1986, Quade 1994) conducted on the facility; however, it has regularly appeared in the diet of burrowing, long-eared, and barn owls (Green 1983, Green et al. 1993). Their absence from the trapping data probably reflects a patchy distribution and possibly a characteristic avoidance of live-traps. Their habitat is described as grassy meadows with grass dense enough to support runways, and with water available (Johnson and Johnson 1982). These conditions, at best, are patchy on the grazed portions of the facility, but do occur, in part, in the bunchgrass-dominated RNAs, and immediately off-facility in the agricultural areas.

House Mouse - The introduced house mouse is commonly found in the vicinity of human habitations in eastern Oregon and probably occurs among the buildings of the old headquarters and the sheep corrals. House mouse presence on the facility was confirmed by Quade (1994), when she captured a single animal on the south end (RNA-C).

Porcupine - The porcupine normally inhabits the forested environments of eastern Oregon although scattered numbers are occasionally found in the shrub-steppe habitats of the Columbia Basin (G. Green, pers. obs.). McClelland and Bedell (1987) and Quade (1994) both listed this species as occurring on the facility, although Quade did not observe in porcupines in 1994. A dead individual was observed in 1995 wedged in the crotch of a juniper tree in Juniper Canyon (G. Green, pers. obs.) and a live animal observed between Well Springs Canyon and Juniper Canyon in May 1995 (A. Holmes, pers. comm.), confirming their presence.

Red Fox - The range of the red fox in northeastern Oregon historically did not extend into north Morrow County (Samuel and Nelson 1982). However, agricultural development along the Columbia River has provided suitable habitat for this species allowing the Rocky Mountain subspecies to extend its range into the Boardman area. In the past decade, numerous damage complaints from this fox have been received from the Boardman area, and the population appears well entrenched in the lower Willow Creek drainage 12 miles to the west (R. Morgan, pers. comm. 1998). Furthermore, two red fox pups were found dead on Highway 730 (Bombing Range Road), three miles south of the facility by ODFW biologists. Its presence on the facility was confirmed in 1995 with the capture of a single individual on the north end during coyote control efforts by Wildlife Services (B. Gibson, pers. comm. 1998). There is concern that as this population builds further, foxes may become a serious threat to ground-nesting birds on the facility, including long-billed curlews and burrowing owls, especially on the north end of the facility. For this reason alone, local fox populations should be closely monitored and, if necessary, controlled if they become established on the facility.

Coyote - The coyote is an opportunistic predator that probably survives on a diet made up largely of small mammals, rabbits, and pheasants, although they most certainly prey on curlews, burrowing owls, and a variety of other birds and reptiles. Fluctuating rabbit populations probably influence the reproductive potential of coyotes. Coyotes den throughout the facility, although denning success is greatly influenced by its proximity to roads and associated human disturbance.

Long-tailed Weasel - The long-tailed weasel is a species that may be a common inhabitant of the facility but because of its secretive habits is rarely seen. Its requirement of a constant supply

of water (Hamilton 1933) may limit seasonal use of the range. Its presence on the facility was confirmed by a sighting of a single animal in Juniper Canyon in May 1995. Based on diet information collected elsewhere (Svendsen 1982), local long-tailed weasels would be expected to forage largely on various species of mice, Washington ground squirrels, and juvenile Nuttall's cottontails.

Badger - The badger is, next to the coyote, the most dominant predator on the facility. It most certainly is the major predator of Washington ground squirrels and other fossorial rodents (Lindzey 1982). In addition, badgers are a keystone species, in that its burrows provide habitat for a variety of other wildlife, including burrowing owls. In fact, burrowing owls on the facility are virtually dependent on badgers for providing nesting burrows (Green and Anthony 1989).

Badger densities in shrub-steppe habitats in Idaho and Utah were found to range between 1 and 16 animals per square mile (Lindzey 1971, Messick 1981). Lindzey (1978) found an average of 0.6 open entrance badger burrows per acre in Utah. In comparison, badger burrow studies on the facility found 0.16 open burrows per acre in 1996, and 0.44 per acre in 1997. This dramatic increase in apparent badger use was also reflected in the number of burrowing owl nest lost to badgers-two in 1996 and ten in 1997 (Holmes and Geupel 1998). (The paradoxical relationship between burrowing owls and badgers still favors the owls since an increase in badgers equates to an increase in nesting burrows, and the high reproductive output of successfully nesting birds compensates for losses due to predation.)

Rocky Mountain Elk - Although elk would not normally be considered an inhabitant of north Morrow County, a few animals are consistently observed between Willow Creek and the agricultural areas east of the facility. It is likely that many of these animals have simply wandered from their normal winter range 35 miles to the south, but it also suspected that a small population may now have established in the Russian olive groves along the Columbia River near Boardman (R. Morgan, pers. comm. 1998). There are sporadic records of these animals occurring on the facility, especially in the vicinity of Juniper Canyon. In 1980, G. Green found evidence where poachers butchered four elk in Juniper Canyon. S. Howlin, a PRBO biologist, observed tracks from two animals on RNA-C in May 1995. The grazing lessees have also reported occasionally sighting elk tracks on the facility. It is unlikely that elk will become a regular inhabitant of the facility, although animals may periodically use the sagebrush cover in Juniper Canyon as security.

Mule Deer - Mule deer are a permanent inhabitant of the facility, although population numbers have never been clearly examined. Deer, including does with small fawns, have been observed throughout the sagebrush habitats of Juniper Canyon. Deer are most conspicuous during the winter months when an estimated 100-200 animals use the facility. However, deer are much less observed during the spring and summer, either because they are scattered and more secretive, or because they move off the facility entirely. Some deer may avoid the facility during the spring when forage quality is higher on nearby crop fields. Lack of water on the facility in the late summer may also limit deer use at this time.

Pronghorn Antelope - There is much confusion on how prevalent pronghorn were in the Columbia Basin prior to arrival of European man. Daubenmire (1970) believed that any pronghorn that were present in the Columbia Basin in the early 1800s were very few and confined to the driest part of the steppe. However, Lewis and Clark indicated that pronghorn were apparently plentiful along the lower reaches of the Snake River in 1806 (Thwaites 1905). Also, pronghorn apparently survived in north Morrow County until 1946 when the last animal was observed on Finley Buttes, approximately two miles east of the facility (R. Morgan, pers. comm. 1998). Presently, pronghorn are increasing in numbers in south Morrow County and some of these animals may have moved to northern Morrow County. Pronghorn are now spotted with some regularity on NWSTF Boardman, and there may be two distinct herds, with a total of 30 animals (J. Phillips, pers. comm. 2008).

Birds

Since 1979, at least 81 species of birds have been recorded on the facility, 33 of which nest there (Table 2-6). Sagebrush habitats support the highest number of species (54) and confirmed breeders (21) (see Table 2-6) followed by annual grass/forb (35/8), bitterbrush (33/9), and juniper habitats (27/9). Sagebrush, bitterbrush, and juniper habitats exhibit high structural diversity and, consequently, more niches for different bird species. In general, species diversity was highest in the shrub habitats, while densities of breeding birds were highest in the grassland habitats (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Four species alone (western meadowlark, grasshopper sparrow, horned lark, and long-billed curlew) comprised over 98 percent of the breeding pairs found in grassland and open low shrub (rabbitbrush) habitats (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Although, grasshopper sparrows were more common in the ungrazed habitats, the reverse was true for long-billed curlews (Holmes and Geupel 1998).

Western meadowlarks were the dominant breeding bird in all shrub habitats as well, accounting for 48-77 percent of the sightings (Holmes and Geupel 1998). In grazed sagebrush habitats lark sparrows were the only other dominant breeder, while in ungrazed sagebrush grasshopper sparrows and horned larks were dominants. In the upland sagebrush habitats, characteristically different from other sagebrush habitats with its low vegetative groundcover, sage, lark, and grasshopper sparrows joined meadowlarks as dominant breeders (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Meadowlarks, lark sparrows, and Brewer's blackbirds were dominants in the bitterbrush.

Following are detailed accounts of the major bird species and assemblages found at NWSTF Boardman. Much of the information in the accounts comes from studies specifically conducted on the facility including Green and Anthony (1989, 1997), Green and Morrison (1983), Green et al. (1993), Holmes and Geupel (1998), Humple and Holmes (2001), Pampush (1980), and Pampush and Anthony (1993). Full copies of Green and Anthony (1989), Holmes and Geupel (1998), and Humple and Holmes (2001), Pampush (1980), and Pampush and Anthony (1993) are located in Appendix M for reference.

Hawks - Eleven species of hawks have been recorded on the facility. The juniper trees in Juniper Canyon provide very important breeding habitat for ferruginous and Swainson's hawks (Green and Morrison 1983, Holmes and Geupel 1998). Approximately seven pair of Swainson's hawks and two or three pair of ferruginous hawks nest here each year (Holmes and Geupel 1998). At least one pair of Swainson's hawks has used one of three artificial nesting platforms that have been provided in the area. Figure 2-24 shows all the locations that ferruginous and Swainson's hawks have nested in the past based on observations of existing nests. Like many raptors, both species rarely use the same nest in consecutive years. Ferruginous hawk nests persist much longer than Swainson's or other hawk nests, due to their being built with stronger (usually sagebrush) materials (Green and Morrison 1983).

Table 2-6. List of birds observed at NWSTF Boardman in 1979 - 2012.

Species	Habitat								Migratory Behavior
	GF	BG	LS	BB	SB	ST	JU	PO	
American Crow	P		P	P					R
American Goldfinch		P			P				R
American Kestrel					P	CB	P		R
American Robin					P		P		R
Barn Owl	P	P			CB				R
Barn Swallow	P	P			P	CB			M
Black-billed Magpie	P	P	P	CB	CB	CB	CB		R
Brown-headed Cowbird	PB	PB	PB	PB	CB			P	M
Brewer's Blackbird	P			PB	CB			P	R
Brewer's Sparrow					CB				M
Black-crowned Night Heron								P	M
Black-throated Sparrow				PB	CB				M
Blue-winged Teal								P	R
Bullock's Oriole				PB			CB		M
Burrowing Owl	CB	CB	PB	CB	CB				M
California Gull	P		P	P					M
California Quail		PB			PB				R
Caspian Tern	P		P	P					M
Chipping Sparrow			P	P	P				M
Chukar					PB				R
Cliff Swallow		P			P				M
Common Nighthawk	P	PB	P	P	PB				M
Common Poorwill				P					M
Common Raven	P	P	P	P	P	CB	CB		R
Cooper's Hawk							P		M
Dark-eyed Junco					P				M
Eastern Kingbird							P		M
European Starling	P				CB	CB	P		R
Ferruginous Hawk	P	P	P		P		CB		M
Fox Sparrow					P				M
Golden-crowned Kinglet					P		P		R
Golden Eagle	P	P	P	P	P		P		R
Gray Flycatcher		P		P	PB		P		M
Gray Partridge			CB	CB	CB				R
Grasshopper Sparrow	CB	CB	CB	PB	CB				M
Horned Lark	CB	CB	CB	CB	CB				R
House Sparrow						CB			R
Killdeer	CB							P	M
Lark Sparrow			PB	CB	CB				M
Lewis' Woodpecker							P		M
Loggerhead Shrike				CB	CB		CB		M
Long-billed Curlew	CB	CB	PB	PB	CB				M
Long-eared Owl	P	P			CB		CB		R
MacGillivray's Warbler							P		M
Mallard	CB							P	M
Merlin	P				P		P		M
Mountain Bluebird	P				P				M
Morning Dove	P			CB	CB		CB	P	M
Northern Flicker					P	P	P		R

Table 2-6. (continued).

Species	Habitat								Migratory Behavior
	GF	BG	LS	BB	SB	ST	JU	PO	
Northern Harrier	PB	PB	PB	PB	P		P		R
Northern Pintail	CB								M
Northern Rough-winged Swallow					CB				M
Orange-crowned Warbler							P		R
Prairie Falcon	P		P		P				R
Red-tailed Hawk	P	P	P	P					M
Red-winged Blackbird				P				P	M
Ring-billed Gull	P								M
Ring-necked Pheasant	PB	PB	PB	PB	CB				R
Rock Wren					PB				R
Rough-legged Hawk	P	P	P	P	P				M
Sage Sparrow					CB				M
Sage Thrasher				P	CB				M
Say's Phoebe					P				M
Savannah Sparrow	PB	PB	PB						M
Sharp-shinned hawk							P		M
Short-eared Owl	P	CB	P	PB	P				R
Spotted Sandpiper								P	M
Spotted Towhee					P		P		M
Swainson's Hawk	P	P	P		P		CB		M
Townsend's Solitaire					P		P		R
Turkey Vulture					P				M
Upland Sandpiper	P								M
Vesper Sparrow					PB				M
Violet-green Swallow					P				M
Western Kingbird				CB	PB	CB	CB		M
Western Meadowlark	CB	CB	CB	CB	CB				R
Western Sandpiper								P	M
Western Tanager							P		M
White-crowned Sparrow			P	P	P				M
Wilson's Warbler				P					M
Yellow-headed Blackbird								P	M

Key: habitat¹, breeding status², and migratory behavior³.

¹ GF = annual grass/forb, BG = bunchgrass, LS = open, low shrub, BB = bitterbrush, SB = sagebrush, ST = human structure, JU = juniper trees, PO = ponds.

² P = present, but does not breed in this habitat, PB = possible or probable breeder, CB = confirmed breeder.

³ R = resident, M = migrant.

Source: Holmes and Geupel (1998), G. Green, R. Morgan, pers. observations.

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The ODFW is in the planning phase of a Ferruginous hawk telemetry study covering parts of the Columbia Basin. This study will look at the effects of regional development projects around northcentral Oregon on nesting hawks. The Navy will partner with ODFW and Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife using NWSTF as a control area for this project. The only other hawk breeding on the facility is the American kestrel. Kestrels have been found breeding at the Old Headquarters storage building and in a gravel pit. Although unconfirmed, it is probable that northern harrier also breed on the facility. Red-tailed hawks also occur year-round on the northern edge of facility, but breed off-site in the deciduous trees near Boardman. The northern rough-legged hawk is a common winter resident, while prairie falcons, merlins, Cooper's hawks, and sharp-shinned hawks have been observed during the spring migration period.

Eagles - Golden eagles, mostly non-breeding immatures, occur year-round at NWSTF, especially in the vicinity of Juniper Canyon. Immature golden eagles are generally excluded from breeding territories (Steenhof et al. 1983); thus, the lack of a breeding territory on the facility probably accounts for the high use by immature birds. Given the importance of the facility for immature golden eagles, it is recommended that the construction of nesting platforms or other management actions that might attract a breeding pair not be undertaken. Winter reports of bald eagles have not been confirmed.

Long-billed Curlew - The long-billed curlew is the fourth most common bird at NWSTF Boardman during the breeding season (Holmes and Geupel 1998), with an estimated 300 to 400

pairs nesting here each year. The facility supports one of the largest populations of breeding curlews in the world (G. Pampush, pers. comm.). Pampush and Anthony (1993) studied curlews at NWSTF from 1978 to 1980, and Holmes and Geupel (1998) from 1995 to 1997. Both parties found curlew nest densities highest in the annual grass habitats followed in importance by grazed bunchgrass, open low shrub, and open bitterbrush. Figure 2-25 shows the nesting distribution of this bird on the facility. Curlew annual nesting success on the facility is

varied, ranging between 21 and 88 percent (Pampush and Anthony 1993, Holmes and Geupel 1998, Holmes 2011). Holmes (2011) suggested that there is a weak correlation between taller habitat types (such as bunchgrass and croplands) having higher nesting success than habitats with shorter structure (such as cheatgrass dominated areas). Avian (crows and ravens) and mammalian (coyotes and badgers) predators appear to be equally responsible for most of the curlew nest losses (Holmes and Geupel 1998). In a study of migration routes of long-billed curlews, Point Reyes Bird Observatory placed GPS transmitters on 10 curlews from NWSTF Boardman. All the curlews tagged from NWSTF Boardman migrate to and winter in the Central Valley of California (G. Page, pers. comm.). The USFWS has completed a draft action plan that describes research and conservation needs to achieve long-term rangewide conservation for the long-billed curlew. Suggested research actions and activities are specified in the Conservation Action Plan for Long-billed Curlews, located at:

http://www.fws.gov/mountain-prairie/species/birds/longbilled_curlew/Action_Plan.pdf

Other Shorebirds - Other shorebirds found on the facility are the killdeer, upland sandpiper, spotted sandpiper, and western sandpiper. Killdeers have nested near the Juniper Canyon horse corrals and the Old Headquarters buildings. They have also been regularly observed near other corrals and at the sheep camp where, presumably, they breed. A single upland sandpiper was observed in association with an unpaired curlew on the northern end of the facility both in 1995

and 1996 (see Figure 2-25). Western sandpipers have been observed at the Oregon Trail pond (G. Green, pers. obs. 1997) and spotted sandpipers at Toad Pond (A. Holmes, pers. obs. 1998).

Burrowing Owl - The burrowing owl is the most common owl found on the facility with 71 nesting attempts recorded in 1997 (Holmes and Geupel 1998; Figure 2-24). Green and Anthony (1989) studied burrowing owls on the facility 1980-1981, and found the owls to prefer annual grass or open bitterbrush habitats for nesting. Most owl pairs on the facility nested in old badger burrows, and utilized a nearby shrub (dead or alive) for perching. Green and Anthony (1989, 1997) have shown the near dependence of burrowing owls on badgers for providing nesting burrows, despite badgers being the primary predator of owl nestlings. Diet studies by Green et al. (1993) found that while burrowing owls on NWSTF Boardman feed on a wide variety of prey, pocket mice, pocket gophers, crickets, and grasshoppers are the most important prey species.

Green and Anthony (1989), Holmes and Geupel (1998) and Holmes et. al. 2003 found burrowing owl nesting success on the facility to vary between 47 and 65 percent. Green and Anthony (1989) and Holmes and Geupel (1998) found adult abandonment to be the primary cause of nesting failure, followed by predation (usually badgers), and trampling in of the burrow by livestock. A dramatic increase in badger use was noted in 1997, and coincided with an increase in the percentage of nests lost to badgers-zero and five percent in 1995 and 1996, respectively, to 29 percent in 1997. Both studies found moderate to high re-use of burrows still open and available for nesting, but that approximately half the burrows used were trampled or silted in by the following year. Holmes et. al. (2003) estimated that the nest reuse ranged between 57 and 87 percent. A sensitive species survey for sagebrush preferring species was conducted in 2009 by Oregon State University and The Nature Conservancy after the 2008 wildfire that burned much of the remaining sagebrush habitat (The Nature Conservancy 2009). Six nesting locations were recorded which were spread around the installation in mostly open grassland dominated habitats (see Figure 2-24 and Appendix M for full report). Conway et. al 2010 studied the migratory linkage between burrowing owl populations on DoD installations and surround lands, including NWSTF Boardman. Burrowing owls in southcentral Washington and northcentral Oregon appear to share migratory linkages with breeding birds from the Central Valley of California and southcentral Canada. The USFWS has completed a status assessment and conservation plan for the burrowing owl in the United States. This assessment contains conservation measures and biological information that would be applicable to NWSTF Boardman burrowing owl management. This plan is located at:

<http://www.fws.gov/mountain%2Dprairie/species/birds/wbo/Western%20Burrowing%20Owlrev73003a.pdf>

The California Burrowing Owl Consortium has developed Survey Protocol and Mitigation Guidelines to survey Burrowing Owl populations and to evaluate impacts from development projects. The following websites have survey protocol and mitigation guidelines for burrowing owl research that could be used for future burrowing owl studies on NWSTF Boardman:

http://www.energy.ca.gov/sitingcases/communitypower/documents/applicant/afc/AFC_VOLUME_2-appendices/Appendix%208.16-11.pdf

Conway et. al. 2010, through the DoD Legacy program, developed a standard monitoring protocol for burrowing owl populations on DoD lands. The protocol is listed in Appendix 1 of the report and the full report can be found in Appendix M of this INRMP.

Figure 2-25
Long-billed Curlew
Distribution at
NWSTF Boardman

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Long-eared Owl - The long-eared owl is the second most common owl on the facility with a high of 19 pairs nesting in the juniper trees of Juniper Canyon in 1997 (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Nearly all the nestings occur in old magpie nests, with annual nesting success ranging from 63-100 percent (Holmes and Geupel 1998). G. Green examined the diet of long-eared owls in Juniper Canyon, and found that from 1994-1997 these owls fed largely on pocket mice, deer mice, kangaroo rats, and harvest mice. In 1980, however, these same owls

fed almost exclusively on pocket mice (G. Green, unpubl. data, see Appendix L for full details), suggesting dramatic changes have occurred in the Juniper Canyon small mammal community over the past two decades.

Short-eared Owl - Holmes and Geupel (1998) observed paired short-eared owls in the ungrazed bunchgrass habitat during all three years of study. A successful nest was found in 1997. A grassland ground-nester, these owls probably require the dense bunchgrass vegetation of the ungrazed RNAs for successful nesting. Sightings have also occurred in low shrub, annual grass, and bitterbrush habitats, but the importance of these habitats to short-eared owls is unknown.

Barn Owl - A barn owl nest, active every year since its discovery in 1994, occurs in an earthen bank in Juniper Canyon. It is presumed that the nest was successful during all years of study, but this was verified only in 1997. G. Green studied the diet of this pair from 1994-97 and learned that pocket mice, deer mice, harvest mice, Ord's kangaroo rats, and pocket gophers were the most important prey items (see Appendix L for full details).

Upland Gamebirds - Four species of upland gamebirds have been found on the facility: ring-necked pheasant, gray partridge, chukar, and California quail. Chukars and California quail are relatively rare, and there is no evidence of them breeding on the facility (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Gray partridge, however, have been found breeding in all three shrub communities, while the pheasant is a common breeder in the sagebrush.

Black-billed Magpie - The black-billed magpie is the most common corvid breeding at NWSTF Boardman. Holmes and Geupel (1998) located 44 and 45 nests annually in 1996 and 1997, respectively, most in juniper and sagebrush with a few in bitterbrush. Only about a third of the nests were successful over the two-year period, with predation by ravens the chief cause of nesting failure.

Common Raven - Three nesting pairs of common ravens were found by Holmes and Geupel (1998), two in junipers and one on the abandoned observation Tower A. Ravens are major nest predators of other birds on the facility, especially magpies and loggerhead shrikes, although, as Holmes and Geupel (1998) have pointed out, ravens originating off facility may be primarily responsible for this predation. Raven flocks of up to 200 birds are regularly observed in the central and southern portions of the facility beginning about June.

Common Crow - Common crows do not nest at NWSTF Boardman (because of the lack of the deciduous trees they use for nesting) but do nest and roost in large numbers north of the facility near Boardman. Many of these crows have been observed foraging over the bitterbrush and

annual grass habitats of the northern third of the facility, where they are believed to be a major predator of curlew eggs (Holmes and Geupel 1998). It is further believed that the local crow population has dramatically increased in the Boardman area with the development of Columbia River riparian areas and general increase in residential and/or ornamental deciduous trees associated with increased human housing developments. They may increase even further with expansion of commercial cottonwood plantations adjacent to the facility. The long-term impact of increased crow populations on curlews should be monitored.

Shrub-steppe Passerines - NWSTF Boardman supports a number of birds characteristically associated with shrub-steppe habitats. Three species alone, western meadowlark, grasshopper sparrow, and horned lark-account for about 85 percent of the entire spring/summer bird population on the facility (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Western meadowlarks were found to be common in all habitats studied by Holmes and Geupel (1998), while grasshopper sparrows and horned larks were common only in the annual grass, bunchgrass, and ungrazed sagebrush habitats. Passerines found nesting in the junipers include the western kingbird (high of 16 in 1997), Bullock's oriole (high of four in 1996), and mourning dove (high of three in 1997). Mourning doves are common breeders in the taller bitterbrush and sagebrush communities, as well as the junipers.

Other shrub-steppe passerines include the lark sparrow, Brewer's blackbird, and white-crowned sparrow, largely found in bitterbrush and all sagebrush habitats. The sage sparrow, Brewer's sparrow, sage thrasher, and loggerhead shrike, mostly restricted to upland and ungrazed sagebrush. Black-throated sparrows, including singing males, were largely seen in the bitterbrush only, although the only confirmed nesting occurred in sagebrush on the south end of the facility in 1994. A sensitive species survey for sagebrush preferring species was conducted in 2009 by Oregon State University and The Nature Conservancy after the 2008 wildfire that burned much of the remaining sagebrush habitat (The Nature Conservancy 2009). Nineteen nesting territories were recorded for loggerhead shrikes and 8 nesting territories were recorded for sage sparrow mostly in and around the remaining unburned patches of sagebrush habitat of Juniper Canyon and along the western edge of the installation (see Figure 2-24 and Appendix M for full report). Locations of loggerhead shrike nest sites found 1995 to 1997 are also shown in Figure 2-24.

Species of Possible Occurrence

Species of possible occurrence are those that are rare, secretive, and or otherwise difficult to detect, but possibly could occur on the facility based on presence of suitable habitat and proximity of known distributional range. There are no amphibians in this group.

Snakes - Shrub-steppe snakes that occur in other portions of Morrow County or adjacent Umatilla County, but have not been recorded on NWSTF Boardman, are the striped whipsnake and night snake. Although both may be absent because of a general lack of rocky areas on the facility, like the rattlesnake, they may just be rare and not yet identified by a trained observer. This may especially be the case with the night snake as this species is easily confused with gopher snakes and is generally only active at night.

Birds - The only birds included in this group are the bald eagle, great horned owl, and snowy owl. Bald eagles and snowy owls possibly occur on the facility during some winters, but their presence is as yet unverified. Great horned owls nest north of the facility and possibly hunt the facility at night. Suitable habitat also occurs in the junipers and at the Proudfoot barn. A number of water-associated species—such as waterfowl, herons, and shorebirds—may incidentally use the ponds, but are not likely to remain for long.

Merriam's Shrew - Merriam's shrew has not been recorded to date from the facility, although Quade (1994) suggested that it might occur here given the species' range and habitat requirements (Armstrong and Jones 1971). Although Johnson and Clanton (1954) suggested that they do not inhabit areas of extreme aridity. They have apparently not been found below 1,200 feet elevation in eastern Washington (Johnson and Cassidy 1997). The presence of this species in Oregon is based on a single specimen collected in Wasco County in 1896 (Bailey 1936, Olterman and Verts 1972), and another in Deschutes County in 1972 (Gashwiler 1976). Nevertheless, this species is apparently naturally rare and difficult to catch (Johnson and Clanton 1954, Olterman and Verts 1972). Although, several have been collected in association with sagebrush in eastern Washington (Johnson and Clanton 1954). Johnson and Clanton alone collected 46 Merriam's shrews in the Columbia Basin of Washington, mostly in association with sagebrush voles. More recently this shrew has been captured during small mammal trapping efforts (Rickard et al. 1974) or found in owl diets (Fitzner et al. 1980) on the Hanford Site in south-central Washington.

Norway Rat - Norway rats are usually found in close association with humans, feeding on garbage, stored grains, and livestock feed (Verts and Carraway 1998). They are commonly trapped among the buildings at the nearby Umatilla Army Chemical Depot (G. Green, pers. obs.). There are no records of Norway rats occurring on the facility, although poisoned baits placed at the sheep sheds and other buildings, a likely place to find rats, may be preventing their establishment, or at least reducing the likelihood of detection.

Little Brown Myotis and Other Bats - The little brown myotis is a species that McClelland and Bedell (1987) listed as occurring on the facility, yet no verification was provided. It is possible that little brown myotis and other bats may roost in the older buildings and juniper trees on facility, but their presence is probably sporadic due to the lack of open water. It is more likely that bats pass through the range during migration periods. Little brown myotis and big brown bats have been collected north of the facility near Boardman (Maser and Cross 1981).

Mountain Lion and Bobcat - Both these large cats were most certainly regular inhabitants of the shrub-steppe of northern Morrow County prior to the arrival of European settlers. While today it is unlikely that either species regularly inhabits the facility, it is possible that individuals dispersing from other areas might occasionally be found using the facility as a temporary refuge. Bobcats are known to inhabit the Willow Creek area 12 miles to the west, and a stray mountain lion was observed on the Umatilla National Wildlife Refuge five miles to the northeast in the early 1980s.

Reestablishment of Extirpated Native Species

It has been over a 100 years since agricultural activities (farming and grazing) began impacting wildlife on the site of the present NWSTF Boardman. Because of a paucity of written records for this time and location, determining what species of wildlife have been extirpated from the facility is, in most cases, pure deduction, or based on unreliable local stories. Nevertheless, information is available on a few key species that we can be reasonably certain occurred in north Morrow County. These species are addressed below.

Sharp-tailed Grouse - Gabrielson and Jewett (1940) stated that by 1940 they were still occasionally seeing small flocks of Columbian sharp-tailed grouse along the north-central boundary of Oregon, including Morrow County. Apparently once extremely abundant throughout their range (Bendire 1892), especially in the Palouse of Washington (Larrison and Sonnenberg 1968), this grouse was extirpated in Oregon by 1969 (Evanich 1983). Reestablishment attempts in north-central Oregon in 1960s failed, but a 1991 reestablishment in northeastern Oregon still remains successful (V. Coggins, pers. comm. 1998). The dramatic decline of sharp-tailed grouse

populations in the Columbia Basin has been directly blamed on rampant overhunting in the late 1800s (Larrison and Sonnenberg 1968), and habitat loss to cultivation in the early 1900s (Buss and Dziedzic 1955).

The potential for reintroducing sharp-tailed grouse on the facility is not great. Based on discussions with Mike Schroeder of the Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife and John Crawford of Oregon State University, the facility probably does not provide enough of the necessary habitat requisites to hold an attraction for year-round use (e.g., year-round water, and sufficient seed-bearing forbs for chicks). Recent lessons in translocation of sharp-tailed grouse in the Pacific Northwest have shown that transplanted birds often move many miles from their translocation site, regardless of the habitat conditions at the initial site (V. Coggins, pers. comm. 1998). Furthermore, it is unlikely that any state wildlife agency would support translocation of sharp-tailed grouse to a marginal habitat site such as the facility when much better sites are available.

Sage Grouse - The original range of the sage grouse in the Columbia Basin included the sagebrush regions of northern Morrow County. Although there are no verifiable records available for northern Morrow County it is likely that they were once relatively common in this region, based on reports from early explorers (Cooper and Suckley 1860, Gabrielson and Jewett 1940, also see Tirhi 1995). The reason for their demise is unclear, although the forage and habitat destruction that occurred during the 1920s era of intense sheep grazing may have been a major contributor. Gabrielson and Jewett (1940) did not include Morrow County as a location where sage grouse populations were surviving by the 1930s, even though Jewett spent six years (1928 to 1934) conducting bird studies in northern Morrow County. Nevertheless, a few breeding sage grouse may have survived on lands immediately west of the facility into the 1970s, based on descriptions provided by local livestock grazers (R. Morgan, pers. comm. 1998). An anecdotal sighting of a pair of sage grouse in the southwest corner of the installation was received from one of the Navy personnel stationed on the range in 2003. Subsequent spring surveys for sage grouse were conducted in the southwest corner of the range from 2004-2008 and have not been able to validate the 2003 sighting. To date, no confirmed sightings of sage grouse have been observed on NWSTF Boardman (J. Phillips, pers. comm. 2008).

The potential for reestablishment of sage grouse on the facility was dismissed by McClelland and Bedell (1987), due to a lack of suitable habitat. However, that assessment may have been premature, especially with range improvements in the RNAs, and planned development of permanent water sites on the range. While subsequent analysis may show that major habitat requisites for sage grouse are lacking, the potential for reestablishment may be worth further examination.

Based on typical grouse densities found elsewhere in Oregon (Gregg 1991), the 47,432-acre facility might support between 200 and 6 00 grouse, and six or more strutting grounds or leks (Braun et al. 1977). However, the ability of the facility to support these numbers of birds is directly dependent on the availability of the bird's life requisites for each the breeding, nesting, brooding, and wintering life stages.

3.0 ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGY AND MISSION SUSTAINABILITY

3.1 Supporting Sustainability of the Military Mission and the Natural Environment

The fundamental component of natural resources management is personnel and funding. OPNAVINST 5090.1C requires each installation to have a designated (in writing) Natural Resources Manager, who is knowledgeable and trained in the particular resource issues for that area or region. The Natural Resources Manager for NWSTF Boardman is a permanent, funded position, administratively under NAS Whidbey Island. The Natural Resources Manager can call upon other environmental professionals within the Navy Region Northwest, as well as the Naval Facilities Engineering Command Northwest, to assist in the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. The NRM will integrate environmental protection, conservation, enhancement/restoration, and outdoor recreation within the constraints of Boardman's military mission. At the same time, the NRM will identify risks to the environment that may result from military activities and report these potential risks to the Command so that alternatives may be developed that reduce or eliminate the potential impacts.

This document is designed to support the military mission by meeting natural resource compliance requirements and by maintaining training lands for realistic training scenarios that can sustain impacts from those training activities. The document incorporates natural resources goals and objectives to provide mission support that should be integrated with military mission planning. Successful implementation of this INRMP requires close coordination between the installation natural resources manager and the military operators that use and maintain the facility. This document has been reviewed by the military operators and planners that manage NWSTF Boardman. All natural resource future projects and actions will be coordinated with installation operational range sustainment planners and range operators.

3.2 Compliance with Federal Requirements

3.2.1 Threatened and Endangered Species Consultation

Federal agencies are required by the Endangered Species Act (ESA) to manage federally listed threatened and endangered (T&E) species and their habitat in a manner that promotes conservation of T&E species and is consistent with plans for recovery of such species. Section 7 of the ESA requires all federal agencies to enter into consultation with the USFWS and NOAA Fisheries (also known as National Marine Fisheries Service, or NMFS) whenever proposed actions "may affect" listed T&E species of plants and animals. Although there are no federally-listed threatened or endangered species currently at NWSTF Boardman, proposed projects, operations, or other actions, are routinely scrutinized for potential impacts to *all* species through a formal review process (described below in Section 3.2.3). Should a species found on NWSTF Boardman become listed in the future, Section 7 consultations will be initiated if warranted, otherwise, written documentation that there are no effects to T&E species will be generated by the Natural Resources Manager and kept with the project files. The NRM will use this INRMP as a tool to identify at an early stage the potential impacts of planned Navy actions on endangered, threatened, candidate, and sensitive species and to provide a basis for altering the action to prevent or minimize those impacts. It is a goal that INRMPs are developed and implemented to provide benefits to federally listed species and also to prevent or lessen the threats to candidate species to reduce the need to formally list species. It is beneficial to stakeholders to address management and conservation issues for species before they become federally listed.

The FY 2004 National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) modified the critical habitat provision in the ESA to allow an approved INRMP to be used by the Department of the Interior in lieu of a critical habitat designation. The INRMPs can be more effective than the critical habitat designation because they provide a more holistic approach to species conservation and provide greater flexibility for installations to manage their lands while maintaining coordination with the FWS and all interested stakeholders.

Impacts to the military mission: If a listed species is identified or critical habitat is designated under ESA and consultation is necessary, an outcome of that regulatory process could require changes to particular activities or mitigation that could result in delays and additional costs. Because of this, it is imperative that the Command initiate early environmental/natural resources review of proposed actions, in order to assess risks, develop alternatives, and correctly identify mitigation costs both in terms of time and dollars.

3.2.2 State Threatened, Endangered, and Sensitive Species Coordination

The Sikes Act requires that the Navy partner with state fish and wildlife agencies to manage resources on each installation. At NWSTF Boardman, the Natural Resources Manager will inform the appropriate Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife manager about Navy actions that may affect fish and wildlife on the installation. This informational mechanism is more informal than the federal process, but yields the same results: identification of potential impacts of planned Navy actions on fish and wildlife, including state listed species, and provides an opportunity for an information exchange with state fish and wildlife experts that can provide a basis for altering the action to prevent or minimize those impacts.

3.2.3 Planning for National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) Compliance

The National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969 (42 USC § 4321 et seq.) requires federal agencies to evaluate the impacts of their proposed actions on the quality of the human environment. To be an effective decision-making tool, the Navy integrates the process with other Navy-Marine Corps project planning at the earliest possible time. This ensures that planning and decision-making reflect environmental values, avoid delays, and potential conflicts. .

NEPA and Navy policy require early review and coordination for environmental considerations. This is achieved at NWSTF Boardman by NAS Whidbey Island's environmental review process, which requires all new projects, programs, and operations, or changes to existing projects, programs, and operations, be reviewed by the Natural Resources Manager for potential impacts to the environment, including potential impacts to natural resources. The Natural Resources Manager reviews planned actions, identifies the risks to natural resources, and provides comments and/or alternatives to the action proponents that will minimize or eliminate the risks, if possible. The early review process also allows the Natural Resources Manager an opportunity to feed information into the appropriate NEPA documents that will be generated based on the proposed action and the alternatives and identify natural resource environmental compliance requirements.

The Natural Resources Program is not exempt from the review process, nor from the requirements of NEPA. Agricultural leases, research projects, and vegetation management, just to name a few possible natural resource actions, must all be reviewed for environmental risks and impacts, the same as if the proposed action is a building project or a new training operation.

Per Navy and DoD policy, INRMPs are planning documents subject to NEPA review and coordination. An environmental assessment (EA) was determined to be the appropriate level of NEPA documentation for this INRMP and the natural resources management actions proposed

within it. The final approved EA is on the CD in Appendix B and the Finding of No Significant Impact (FONSI) is attached in Appendix B with coordinating correspondence attached in Appendix C.

3.2.4 Sikes Act/Sikes Act Improvement Act

The Sikes Act of 1960 initially authorized each DoD installation to develop a plan to manage and maintain wildlife, fish, and game conservation and rehabilitation. In 1997, Congress passed amendments to the original Sikes Act requiring DoD to prepare and implement an INRMP for each installation in the United States with “significant natural resources.”

The SAIA requires DoD facilities to manage their natural resources so as to provide multiple uses and public access to the extent that it is consistent with the military mission. The SAIA also requires that all INRMPs and natural resources management actions are developed to ensure “no net loss” to the military mission and training activities. The Act provides a mechanism whereby DoD, the Department of Interior, and the state cooperate to manage fish and wildlife on military installations.

A tripartite cooperative agreement, under the Sikes Act, for the management of natural resources and implementation of the integrated natural resources management plan on NWSTF Boardman was developed and signed with the USFWS and ODFW in 1998. This current cooperative agreement is attached in Appendix D. Currently, no hunting occurs on the installation and no Sikes Act fishing and hunting permit fees are collected.

3.2.5 Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act (PL 76-567), as Amended 16 USC 668 Et. Seq.

The Bald Eagle Protection Act was enacted in 1940; in 1962, Congress extended the Bald Eagle Protection Act to cover golden eagles. This Act prohibits the take, possession, sale, purchase, barter, offer to sell, purchase, or barter, transport, export or import, of any bald or golden eagle, alive or dead, including any part, nest, or egg, unless allowed by permit. “Take” is defined as to “pursue, shoot, shoot at, poison, wound, kill, capture, trap, collect, molest or disturb” a bald or golden eagle. The term “disturb” under the Eagle Act was recently defined via a rule published in the *Federal Register* on June 5, 2007. “Disturb” means to agitate or bother a bald or golden eagle to a degree that causes, or is likely to cause, based on the best scientific information available, 1) injury to an eagle, 2) a decrease in its productivity, by substantially interfering with normal breeding, feeding, or sheltering behavior, or 3) nest abandonment, by substantially interfering with normal breeding, feeding, or sheltering behavior.

3.2.6 Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA), USC § 703 Et. Seq.

The MBTA is a federal statute that implements US treaties with several countries for conserving and protecting migratory birds. The number of bird species covered by the MBTA is extensive and is listed at 50 CFR § 10.13. Further, the regulatory definition of “migratory bird” is broad and includes any mutation or hybrid of a listed species, as well as any part, egg, or nest of such bird (50 CFR § 10.12). Migratory birds are not necessarily federally listed endangered or threatened birds under the ESA. The MBTA, which is enforced by the USFWS, makes it unlawful “by any means or manner, to pursue, hunt, take, capture [or] kill” any migratory bird, except as permitted by regulation. “Take” is defined under the implementing regulations as “pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture, or collect, or attempt to pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect”. In July 2006, the DoD and the US Fish and Wildlife Service signed and entered into a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) to promote the conservation of migratory birds in accordance with EO 13186 (see below). This MOU describes specific actions that should be

taken by DoD to advance migratory bird conservation; avoid or minimize the take of migratory birds; ensure DoD operations – other than military readiness activities – are consistent with the Migratory Bird Treaty Act. The final rule, Migratory Bird Permits: Take of Migratory Birds by the Armed Forces, was published as 50 CFR Part 21, in the February 21, 2007 Federal Register, pages 8931-8950 and applies to military readiness activities that occur on the installation.

3.2.7 Federal Water Pollution Control Act (aka: Clean Water Act (CWA)), PL 92-500, 33 USC §§ 1251-1387

The primary objective of the Clean Water Act (CWA) is "to restore and maintain the chemical, physical, and biological integrity of the Nation's waters." 33 U.S.C. § 1251. The CWA regulates the discharge of pollutants into the navigable waters of the United States through several programs, including the National Pollutant Discharge and Elimination System (NPDES) permit program, encouraging States to address nonpoint source pollution, and pretreatment standards for discharges to wastewater treatment plants. Section 404 of the CWA establishes the Federal regulatory program that governs dredge and fill activities. In addition, section 404 is used as the primary means of protecting wetlands. Pursuant to section 301 of the Act, discharges of dredged or fill material into waters of the U.S., including adjacent wetlands, are illegal unless permitted or exempted from the permit requirement, pursuant to regulation issued under Section 404.

No waters of the U.S. have been identified on NWSTF Boardman. During winters with heavier rain or snowfall, there can be areas of small temporary ponding that develop in central Juniper Canyon. But these extremely ephemeral water areas have no ordinary high water mark, do not connect to navigable waters nor contain wetlands adapted vegetation, so they would not be considered water of the U.S.

3.2.8 Tribal Treaty Rights and Tribal Coordination

The Boardman Bombing Range lies within the lands ceded to the United States by the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation (CTUIR) and the Yakama Nation in the 1855 Treaties between the Tribes and the United States (12 Stat. 945). Article 1 of the Treaties reserves for the CTUIR and Yakama certain rights within the ceded lands. It states:

Provided, also, That the exclusive right of taking fish in the streams running through and bordering said reservation is hereby secured to said Indians, and at all other usual and accustomed stations in common with citizens of the United States, and of erecting suitable buildings for curing the same; the privilege of hunting, gathering roots and berries and pasturing their stock on unclaimed lands in common with citizens, is also secured to them.

The Navy manages the Boardman Bombing range subject to the rights the CTUIR and Yakama reserved in the Treaties of 1855, as well as those established by statutes, regulations, executive orders, court decisions and other authorities. The Department of the Navy Policy for Consultation With Federally Recognized Tribes, dated October 11, 2005, provides that the Navy will "[c]onsult with representatives of federally recognized Tribal Governments as provided by law on all issues impacting Indian lands, protected tribal resources or rights under treaties, and issues of concern to Tribal Governments on DON lands[.]" Pursuant to this consultation policy, the CTUIR and Yakama were contacted regarding the development of the INRMP. Consultation will continue with the CTUIR and Yakama regarding the potential impacts of management activities on treaty reserved resources, historic and cultural properties, as well as other issues of concern. The Navy has an ongoing responsibility to consult with the CTUIR and Yakama on a government to government basis in recognition of tribal rights and tribal sovereignty.

This INRMP and management strategy, as well as proposed yearly funded natural resources management actions or projects, will be reviewed annually by the Sikes Act management partners and INRMP signatories. It is the Navy's intent to consult with and solicit input from the CTUIR and Yakama concerning these reviews each year prior to them being held.

3.3 Executive Orders (EO)

In addition to the laws discussed above, there are a number of other laws and regulations that must be considered in natural resources management.

3.3.1 EO 11990 – Protection of Wetlands

This EO states that federal agencies will avoid the destruction or modification of wetlands when there is a practicable alternative. Wetlands are defined in this EO as "...those areas that are inundated by surface or groundwater with a frequency sufficient to support and under normal circumstances does (sic) or would support a prevalence of vegetative or aquatic life that requires saturated or seasonally saturated soil conditions for growth and production. Wetlands generally include swamps, marshes, bogs, and similar areas such as sloughs, potholes, wet meadows, river overflows, mud flats, and natural ponds."

3.3.2 EO 11644 – Use of Off-Road Vehicles on Public Lands

This EO requires federal agencies to establish policies and provide for procedures to ensure that the use of off-road vehicles on public lands will be controlled and directed so as to protect the resources of those lands, to promote the safety of all users of those lands, and to minimize conflicts among the various uses of those lands. The EO clarifies agency authority to define zones of use by off-road vehicles on public lands by exempting fire, military, emergency, law enforcement, or combat/combat support vehicles.

3.3.3 EO 11987 – Exotic Species

To the extent permitted by law, federal agencies will restrict the introduction of exotic species into the natural ecosystems on lands and waters that they own, lease, or hold for purposes of administration, and they will encourage the states, local governments, and private citizens to prevent the introduction of exotic species into natural ecosystems of the United States.

3.3.4 EO 13112 – Invasive Species

To the extent permitted by law, federal agencies will prevent the introduction of invasive species, will detect and respond rapidly to and control populations of such species in a cost-effective and environmentally sound manner, will monitor such populations accurately and reliably, will provide for restoration of native species and habitat conditions in ecosystems that have been invaded, will conduct research on invasive species, and will promote public education on invasive species and means to address them.

3.3.5 EO 13186 – Protection of Migratory Birds

Requires that federal executive agencies implement a memorandum of understanding (MOU) with the USFWS to avoid or minimize the negative impacts of agency actions on migratory birds and to take steps to protect migratory birds and their habitats. The DoD and USFWS have developed and signed (July 2006) an MOU to promote the conservation of migratory birds.

3.4 Public Access and Outreach

Persons authorized to access NWSTF Boardman are military and civilian employees of DoD, or authorized contractors and personnel from research organizations conducting military training or

training support activities. Currently, no hunting or hunting program occurs on the installation because of range safety issues. The hunting program issues are further described in Chapter 4.0.

Limited public access and outreach is provided in the Wells Springs public access area on the south boundary of the installation and includes several cultural and natural resources information displays. Public outreach regarding natural resources is typically coordinated through efforts with the NAS Whidbey Island Public Affairs Office.

3.5 Encroachment Issues and Potential Encroachment Partnering

NWSTF Boardman exists as a bombing range for military aircraft. Large tracts of agricultural property are found to the north, east, and south of the installation. On the west side lies large open lands (23,000 acres) that the owners (Threemile Canyon Farms) agreed to have managed by TNC as habitat for the Washington ground squirrel and birds and plants, and to allow public access along the Columbia River. NWSTF Boardman's natural resources management program attempts to coordinate with TNC management of the conservation area to maximize conservation benefits. The farm's remaining 19,000 acres will remain fallow, accommodating Portland General Electric Company's coal-fired electric plant and beef feedlots.

Agricultural development immediately adjacent to NWSTF Boardman's boundaries can be consistent with military operations because of the low density nature of crop circles and the lack of noise receptors. However, in recent years there have been many incompatible development proposals that have occurred in and around NWSTF Boardman, such as nearby wind turbine developments. Incompatible development requests such as major roads across the range, tall power transmission corridors, basin-wide wind turbine installation, and water recharge and crop circle agriculture on the range have been discussed. All these development proposals can have direct impacts to military training from developments on the range and indirect affects of causing air space constraints around the installation and on nearby low level aircraft routes, or causing species that inhabit the NWSTF Boardman property to become listed as threatened or endangered.

Navy personnel will continue to partner and work with the local community to prevent incompatible development proposals on and around NWSTF Boardman to maintain a viable military training asset for current and future missions. The Encroachment Partnering program can be used to acquire restrictive use easements off-range to mitigate for external developments that could impact military mission uses of the range. The objective of encroachment partnering is to eliminate or relieve current or anticipated environmental restrictions that would or might otherwise restrict, impede, or otherwise interfere, whether directly or indirectly, with current or anticipated military training, testing, or operations on the installation (10 U.S.C. 2684a(a)(2)(B)). Encroachment Partnering is specifically the authority granted by OPNAVINST 11010.40 through 10 USC 2684a to acquire easements to resolve encroachment issues or acquire habitat conservation easements to conserve sensitive species or habitat off of military training ranges. Within the 5-year scope of this INRMP, there are no currently identified or planned acquisitions of off-site conservation easements that focus on natural resources benefits. The main purpose of this INRMP is to manage natural resources on Navy owned lands at NWSTF Boardman. Natural resources personnel will continue to work with Navy encroachment planners to identify natural resource based encroachment issues and potential off-site conservation easements that could benefit management of regional species and habitat.

3.6 State Comprehensive Wildlife Conservation Strategy (SCWCS)

During September 2005, Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW) submitted a statewide Draft Comprehensive Wildlife Conservation Strategy (CWCS) that addresses the full range of

wildlife conservation needs and their habitats. The Oregon Fish and Wildlife Commission endorsed the conservation strategy the same month.

NWSTF Boardman's natural resources management strategies, as described in this INRMP, do not conflict with the Oregon's conservation strategies, and incorporate some of the Conservation Actions that are applicable to NWSTF Boardman habitats and species (as described in Table 3-1). As a stakeholder in the management of natural resources on the installation, ODFW works closely with the Navy on various wildlife conservation issues, ranging from on-site habitat protection to invasive species control, and also cooperates with the installation on developing and conducting wildlife and habitat research and surveys.

Table 3-1. Conservation Actions Identified in the 2005 Comprehensive Wildlife Conservation Strategy.

State Conservation Actions
Work with community leaders and agency partners to ensure planned, efficient growth, and to preserve fish and wildlife habitats, farmland, forestland and rangeland, open spaces, and recreation areas.
Use, expand, and improve financial incentive programs and other voluntary conservation tools to support conservation actions taken by landowners and land managers.
Develop new voluntary conservation tools to meet identified needs.
Promote collaboration across jurisdictional and land ownership boundaries.
Work creatively within the existing regulatory framework, seeking new opportunities to foster win-win solutions.
Inform Oregonians of conservation issues and the actions everyone can take that will contribute to Oregon's collective success.
Columbia Plateau Conservation Actions
Water conservation.
Soil erosion prevention.
Habitat fragmentation prevention/restoring connectivity.
Invasive species control.
Shrub-steppe restoration and management.
Restore and maintain sagebrush habitat.
Restore and maintain grasslands.
Boardman Area Conservation Actions
Control wildfires to protect native habitats from risk of conversion to cheatgrass.
Maintain and/or initiate shrub-steppe restoration and management.
Promote early detection and suppression of invasive weeds.
Habitat Conservation Actions
Evaluate carefully the impacts that may occur from prescribed fires.
Emphasize prevention, risk assessment, early detection, and quick control of invasive species.
Manage grazing to prevent soil erosion and detrimental changes to wildlife habitat.
Conserve habitats to prevent conversion to agriculture or urban/suburban sprawl.
Maintain high priority shrub-steppe habitat patches and improve connectivity when possible.
Species Conservation Actions
Washington ground squirrel: maintain habitat; restore connectivity between habitat patches.
Brewer's sparrow: maintain sagebrush habitat; restore connectivity between habitat patches.
Ferruginous hawk: provide diverse vegetation to support prey; maintain known and potential nest site trees (junipers); minimize human disturbance during nesting season.
Grasshopper sparrow: maintain grasslands; increase plant diversity; control invasive plants; no mowing until > July 15.
Loggerhead shrike: maintain seral sagebrush habitat.
Long-billed curlew: maintain and restore short grass habitat; minimize human disturbance around nests during nesting season.
Sage sparrow: maintain ground cover
Swainson's hawk: protect nest trees; maintain ground cover for prey resources.
Western burrowing owl: maintain ground cover; establish 200' protective buffer around nests; protect badger populations.
Northern sagebrush lizard: maintain habitat patches; restore habitat connectivity.
Laurence's milk-vetch: maintain priority sites; control invasive plants.
Tygh Valley milk-vetch: mow around rather than spray; protect from grazing.

4.0 PROGRAM ELEMENTS

4.1 Personnel

The fundamental components of natural resources management are personnel and funding. OPNAVINST 5090.1C requires each Installation Commanding Officer (ICO) to designate in writing a Natural Resources Manager (NRM). This individual is to be educated, knowledgeable and trained in the particular resource issues for the installation. The NRM for NWSTF Boardman is a permanently funded position, assigned to the NAVFAC Northwest Public Works Department, Environmental Division at NAS Whidbey Island. The NRM is physically located at NAS Whidbey Island and reports to the Installation Environmental Program Director of NAS Whidbey Island, who, in turn, reports to the Public Works Officer of NAS Whidbey Island. The NRM can call upon other environmental professionals within the Navy Region Northwest, as well as the Naval Facilities Engineering Command Northwest, to assist in the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman.

4.2 Threatened and Endangered Species Management

Federal agencies are required by the Endangered Species Act (ESA) to manage federally listed threatened and endangered (T&E) species and their habitat in a manner that promotes conservation of T&E species and is consistent with plans for recovery of such species. Section 7 of the ESA requires all federal agencies to enter into consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) whenever actions are proposed that may affect listed and proposed T&E species of plants and animals.

Although there are no federally-listed threatened or endangered species at NWSTF Boardman as of the writing of this document, this INRMP is meant to be used as a tool to identify at an early stage the potential impacts of planned Navy actions on future endangered or threatened species on the installation and to provide a basis for altering the action to prevent or minimize those impacts. The following paragraphs outline the management strategy for threatened or endangered species.

Special Management and Protection of T&E Species

Special management or protection is a term that originates in the definition of *occupied* critical habitat in Section 3 of the Endangered Species Act. For occupied habitat, one first determines whether the area contains the physical and biological features essential to the conservation of the species and their area has or needs additional special management or protection. Additional special management is not required if adequate management or protection is already in place. If *unoccupied* areas were determined to be essential to the conservation of the species, the Navy would include such unoccupied areas only where special management or protection is required.

Adequate special management or protection is provided by a legally operative plan (the Navy uses the term "Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan", or INRMP; the INRMP is required by the Sikes Act) that addresses the maintenance and improvement of the primary constituent elements important to the species and manages for the long-term conservation of the species. The Navy uses the following three criteria to determine if a plan provides adequate special management or protection:

Criteria 1. Conservation Benefit

The plan provides a conservation benefit to the species. The cumulative benefits of the management activities identified in a management plan, for the length of the plan, must maintain or provide for an increase in a species' population, or the enhancement or restoration of its habitat within the area covered by the plan [i.e., those areas deemed essential to the conservation of the species]. A conservation benefit may result from reducing fragmentation of habitat, maintaining or increasing populations, insuring against catastrophic events, enhancing and restoring habitats, buffering protected areas, or testing and implementing new conservation strategies.

Criteria 2. Implementation of the Plan

The plan provides assurances that the management plan will be implemented. Persons charged with plan implementation are capable of accomplishing the objectives of the management plan and have adequate funding for the management plan. They have the authority to implement the plan and have obtained all the necessary authorizations or approvals. An implementation schedule (including completion dates) for the conservation effort is provided in the plan.

Criteria 3. Management Effectiveness

The plan provides assurances that the conservation effort will be effective. The following criteria will be considered when determining the effectiveness of the conservation effort. The plan includes (1) biological goals (broad guiding principles for the program) and objectives (measurable targets for achieving the goals); (2) quantifiable, scientifically valid parameters that will demonstrate achievement of objectives, and standards for these parameters by which progress will be measured, are identified; (3) provisions for monitoring and, where appropriate, adaptive management; (4) provisions for reporting progress on implementation (based on compliance with the implementation schedule) and effectiveness (based on evaluation of quantifiable parameters) of the conservation effort are provided (this goal will be accomplished at the annual INRMP review and update, in coordination with ODFW and USFWS); and (5) a duration sufficient to implement the plan and achieve the benefits of its goals and objectives. The INRMP for NWSTF Boardman is a five-year plan, beginning with FY 2012, but may be extended further than five years if installation mission or natural resources do not change, or changes are minimal. This is a time period long enough to seek funding for projects, implement those projects, and monitor and report progress. At the end of the five-year period the INRMP will be reviewed and updated or rewritten if necessary to continue protection and enhancement for T&E species and habitats.

4.2.1 Candidate Species

The Washington ground squirrel is a candidate species for federal listing as a threatened or endangered species. A candidate species is one for which the USFWS has on file sufficient information on biological vulnerability and threats to support a proposal to list as endangered or threatened, but for which preparation and publication of a proposal is precluded by higher-priority listing actions.

Washington Ground Squirrel

Information on the Washington ground squirrel and continued status as a candidate species is provided in the Federal Register, dated October 26, 2011 (vol. 76, number 207, pgs. 66370-66439). USFWS uses a candidate listing priority numbering system that reflects the threat to a population and prioritizes the candidate species for possible threatened or endangered status. The priority number indicates the listing priority number for each candidate species which is used to determine the most appropriate use of available USFWS resources. The lowest numbers (out of a scale of 1-10) have the highest priority. The priority number 5 for Washington ground

squirrels indicates a lesser threat to the population, hence it has a lower ranking for USFWS resources.

A management strategy for the species following the three criteria discussed in section 4.2 above will help to limit impacts to the species and help prevent future federal listing or critical habitat designation. Recent fires on the installation in 2007 and 2008 have altered 75% of known current or former occupied squirrel habitat. Washington ground squirrel surveys will be conducted at necessary repeated time intervals in order to determine the activity status of historical Washington ground squirrel sites. Using the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW) monitoring protocol, surveys will provide information confirming species presence, geographic extent of active sites, estimates of burrow abundance at active sites, and can be compared to previous survey work for the species. Survey protocol can be found in Morgan and Nugent (1999) and Greene (1999) (see Appendix K for full reports). Further modifications of those survey protocols may be made in coordination with ODFW and USFWS to adapt them to meet additional monitoring goals that may be developed in the future. This will help to identify current occupied habitats. Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weeds and preventing mechanical disturbance of habitats. Natural habitat recovery of previous and future burned areas will be monitored by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for restoration measures. Direct affect to individuals and squirrel burrows from operations will be accomplished by reviewing training and operational projects for potential impacts to squirrel locations, surveying project areas before activities, and incorporating suitable avoidance measures to reduce direct affects.

4.3 Wetlands Management

According to Executive Order (EO) 11990 (1977), the term "wetlands" means those areas that are inundated by surface or ground water with a frequency sufficient to support and under normal circumstances does or would support a prevalence of vegetative or aquatic life that requires saturated or seasonally saturated soil conditions for growth and reproduction. Wetlands generally include swamps, marshes, bogs, and similar areas such as sloughs, potholes, wet meadows, river overflows, mud flats, and natural ponds. EO 11990 requires Federal agencies to minimize the loss or degradation of wetlands and to enhance their natural values. Section 404 of the Clean Water Act prohibits discharges of dredged or filled material into waters of the U.S., including wetlands, without first obtaining a permit from the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers. According to OPNAVINST 5090.1C, the Navy will comply with the national goal of no net loss of wetlands, and will avoid loss of size, function and value of wetlands.

In order to comply with the "No Net Loss of Wetlands Policy" of the Navy, commands with land management responsibilities shall ensure the following:

- That the Navy plan all construction and operational actions to avoid adverse impacts to or destruction of wetlands. Any construction requirement that cannot be sited to avoid wetlands shall be designed to minimize wetlands degradation and shall include compensatory mitigation as required by wetlands regulatory agencies in all phases of the project's planning, programming, and budgeting process. Within this policy, use of Navy lands and lands of other entities are permissible for mitigation purposes for Navy projects when consistent with EPA and COE guidelines or permit provisions. Requests by non-Navy entities to mitigate the effects of non-Navy projects on Navy property should be reviewed on a case-by-case basis for their effect on Navy mission, the environment, and appropriateness

of economic compensation to the Navy for the long-term use of the site, all such projects need to be approved by the chain of command;

- That any action significantly affecting wetlands is addressed by the environmental review and public notification process (NEPA);
- That boundaries of legally defined wetlands, on all Navy lands, are identified and mapped with sufficient accuracy to protect them from potential unplanned impacts, and that the maps are distributed to all potential users, including facilities planners, operational units, and tenant commands. Jurisdictional maps may be required prior to actual construction if there is any potential of wetlands present in the vicinity of the project. Field verification and jurisdictional determinations should be required for all projects;
- That adequate expertise is available to installation commanding officers (COs) for the protection, management, identification, and mapping of wetlands;
- That implementation of wetlands creation or enhancement projects and wetlands banking, where compatible with the installation mission, is encouraged. Natural resource managers should identify potential wetland mitigation sites.

Wetland management strategies vary depending primarily on the wetland's classification, which is determined by the value of a particular wetland. A wetland's value is determined by the quality of the functions it provides, including its biomass production, habitat, erosion control, and storm water storage. Some of the factors used to measure the quality of these functions are the wetland's size, its location in the watershed, the amount of development in the watershed, vegetative structure and composition, rate of water flow through the wetland, the size of natural buffers, and surrounding land uses. The program/project review process identifies possible wetland area, evaluates any potential impacts to those wetlands and ensures that program/project managers are aware of the laws and regulations regarding the protection of wetlands.

To date no jurisdictional wetland areas have been identified on NWSTF Boardman. During heavy precipitation years, several very ephemeral small shallow ponds can develop in central Juniper Canyon, but the areas contain no ordinary high water marks and develop no wetland adapted vegetation so they would not be classified as jurisdictional wetlands. These ephemeral ponded areas are used by breeding spadefoot toads, so they are significant ephemeral water features.

Habitat Management

See Section 2.6.4. for a description of the habitat types on NWSTF Boardman.

Habitat Enhancement and Restoration

Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weeds and preventing mechanical habitat degradation. Natural habitat recovery of burned areas will be assessed by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the desired pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures.

Habitat Management – Water/Wetland/Riparian/Ephemeral Aquatic Areas

There are no streams or wetlands on NWSTF Boardman. The only area that has ever exhibited wetland vegetation at NWSTF Boardman is the previously described (in Section 2.6.2) Toad Pond. Because the lack of a stable natural hydrology, Toad Pond would not be classified as a jurisdictional wetland, but as noted above had water present (when the grazing water system was functioning) to establish wetland adapted vegetation. The last time the system had water was in 2006, as of 2011 the pond has been dry for 5 years and wetland vegetation is no longer present.

The pond was established as a spadefoot toad breeding location, but other wildlife species had use the pond, when functioning, as a source of water. Ephemeral ponded areas in Juniper Canyon can develop during heavy precipitation years and are sensitive areas used by breeding spadefoot toads. Because of their very ephemeral nature and shifting location based on soil depressions present during the heavy rain years, these areas are very difficult to manage. When present these shallow ponded areas will be avoided as much as possible so as not to negatively impact spadefoot toad breeding cycles.

Figure 4-1. Dry cattail stems in Toad Pond (September 2006).

Habitat Management – Developed Areas

The following items will improve wildlife habitat.

- **Where feasible, reduce the mowed areas.** Reducing areas that are mowed will allow native vegetation to grow, enhancing wildlife habitat, and may also result in a maintenance cost savings for the Navy.
- **Use native vegetation for landscaping around buildings.** Native vegetation is well-suited to the conditions of the Columbia Plateau region and will require less maintenance to keep healthy. Native vegetation provides better wildlife habitat than exotic, non-native plants and trees.
- **Reduce pesticide/herbicide/fertilizer use.** Reducing the use of chemicals will help protect surface and groundwater quality at the installation.

Habitat Management – Sand Dune

A large sand dune is a very noticeable feature of the north border of NWSTF Boardman. There is a possibility that there is movement of the dune onto adjacent privately-owned agricultural property. Although no management prescriptions are warranted at this time, it would be useful to monitor the movement of the dune over a long period of time. This can be done by periodic aerial

surveys, but a less expensive method is to install permanent markers around the perimeter to track movement. The markers should be accurately surveyed using GPS equipment so that locations of the markers may be mapped. The markers should consist of (or have close by) pipes or poles calibrated with markings to measure rate of deposition of sand (or loss of sand depending on the movement). This information can be useful to the Navy if movement of the dune off-installation becomes a future issue. Because this dune complex is a regionally sensitive habitat area, no off-road vehicle activity is allowed on the dune or in nearby habitat areas. This site is attractive to trespassers entering Navy property with off-road vehicles. The Navy personnel stationed at the range will work to prevent unauthorized access and off-road vehicle activity on the dune.

Habitat Management – Juniper Trees

Western juniper stands have been expanding in Oregon and other western states since the late 1800s (OSU 1993). This expansion has been attributed to grazing and the reduction of wildfires (OSU 1993). Juniper, if left unchecked, can shade out understory grasses and forbs and also reduce rainfall to the ground, further impacting the understory plants and resulting in bare soils around the trees. During large rainfall events, the bare soils allow for increased runoff, causing erosion and sediment loading of streams (OSU 1993). The interruption of the water cycle can result in lowered water tables and a reduction in stream flows during the drier periods of the year.

A review of aerial photos of the juniper areas and a brief field inspection in 2006 shows that the juniper tree numbers are relatively stable; that is, some trees died during the recent wildfires but there is evidence of new tree growth, too. There have never been more than approximately 200 trees on NWSTF Boardman, so the problems mentioned in the above paragraph have not been experienced, or are not of sufficient impact to warrant special management. However, the actual tree count and the expansion or contraction of juniper areas is unknown without a new survey (a planned project to survey and number all trees is described in Appendix A). A new survey will provide information as to the extent of the juniper habitat and also provide a baseline to measure change in numbers and area over time.

The juniper trees provide habitat and shade to various birds and other wildlife. The juniper trees should be protected from wildfires or other impacts. The removal of trees is not recommended as dead and live trees provide valuable wildlife habitat.

Habitat Management – Native bunchgrass

Native bunchgrass communities are composed of bluebunch wheatgrass (*Pseudoroegneria spicata* spp. *spicata* (*Agropyron spicatum*)), needle and threadgrass (*Hesperostipa* (*Stipa*) *comata*), and Sandberg's bluegrass (*Poa secunda*). These habitats are well suited for rangeland use. The bluebunch wheatgrass is preferred feed for elk, deer, and antelope throughout the year. The needle and threadgrass species are very effective grass in preventing wind erosion on sandy soils. They are also one of the first grasses to naturally establish in disturbed sandy sites. Sandberg's bluegrass is probably the most common bluegrass species in the West and is an important species for small animals and birds in the spring and fall. It is not considered an important forage species for large wildlife species.

Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weed and preventing mechanical habitat degradation. Natural habitat recovery of the burned areas will be monitored by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the desired pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures.

Habitat Management – Sagebrush

Sagebrush habitats of NWSTF Boardman are shrubland communities dominated by big sagebrush (*Artemisia tridentata*). These habitats are important for a variety of birds and wildlife. The birds in these shrublands not only add to the West's diversity of wildlife, they are important to the sagebrush ecosystem itself, providing crucial services such as dispersing seeds and preying on insects and rodents (Paige and Ritter 1999). Other wildlife species, including pronghorn and sagebrush lizard, also depend on healthy sagebrush habitat. Pronghorn, mule deer, and elk may rely heavily on sagebrush during the winter. Taller sagebrush provides cover for deer fawns, and nesting sites for many shrub-nesting birds. The sage thrasher, Brewer's sparrow, and sage sparrow nest most frequently in or beneath sagebrush (Paige and Ritter 1999).

Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weed and preventing mechanical habitat degradation. Natural habitat recovery of the burned areas will be monitored by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures.

The following table (Table 4-1) is adapted from Paige and Ritter (1999) and lists potential management actions that can reduce impacts and protect sagebrush habitats which, in turn, will foster wildlife use of the areas.

Habitat Management – Biological Soil Crusts

Biological soil crusts can be highly susceptible to disturbance, both fire and mechanical. The follow discussion on biological soil crust impacts and management is adapted from Belnap et. al. (2001).

Biological soil crusts provide little fuel to carry a fire through interspaces, thereby acting as "refugia" to slow the spread of fire and decrease its intensity (Rosentreter 1986). Unburned islands of vascular vegetation and biological soil crust provide propagules for reestablishment in burned areas. Johansen et al. (1993) observed that the crust's structural matrix was left intact following low-intensity fire, indicating that a lightly burned crust still functions to maintain stability against erosive forces for both vascular plants and biological soil crusts during the recovery period. Biological crusts are generally killed by hot ground fires, resulting in loss of biomass and visible cover (Johansen et al. 1993). Frequent fires prevent recovery of lichens and mosses, leaving only a few species of cyanobacteria (Whisenant 1990; Eldridge and Bradstock 1994). Damage to, and recovery of, biological crusts depend on the pre-fire composition, structure of the vascular plant community, as well as fuel distribution, fire intensity, and fire frequency. Many semi-arid areas are now commonly invaded by annual weeds, and unnaturally frequent, large fires that preclude crustal species' recolonization or succession. Disturbance can directly and indirectly affect many aspects of the structure and function of biological crust communities, including cover, species composition, and carbon and nitrogen fixation. The impact of a given disturbance depends on its severity, frequency, timing, and type, as well as the climatic conditions during and after it.

While most mechanical (compressional) disturbances (such as from vehicles and trampling by people or animals) result in similar types of impacts, severity can vary widely depending on disturbance source. For instance, vehicles and trampling exert compressional and shear forces; however, these forces are much greater for vehicles than trampling. In addition, vehicles often turn soils over and bury crustal organisms, while trampling tends to only compress the surface. Intensifying physical impacts (such as high-intensity, short-duration grazing) is deleterious to

Table 4-1. Sagebrush habitat management actions.

Activity	Wildlife Goal	Action
Military Activities	Reduce impact on wildlife habitat.	Protect springs from vehicle use and training exercises. Encourage use of established sites, including keeping vehicles on established trails and roads. Limit the number of roads; reclaim excess roadbeds with native vegetation.
Insecticides	Reduce wildlife mortality.	Include birds and other wildlife in integrated pest management programs. Use insecticide baits and natural pathogens instead of broad-spectrum insecticides. Avoid broadcast spraying; use ground applications rather than aerial spraying.
Recreation	Reduce impact on wildlife habitat.	Protect springs from recreational use. Encourage use of established sites, including keeping vehicles on established trails and roads.
Prescribed Fire and Wildfire	Allow reestablishment of sagebrush and native grasses and forbs.	Keep burns to a small scale and patchy distribution with strict time frames and situation in order to benefit native vegetation. Burn late in early spring or fall to take advantage of native grasses' adaptations to late season fires and to discourage cheatgrass. Reseed burns with native bunchgrass and forb species. Avoid conducting prescribed fires in early spring in areas where birds are nesting to comply with the MBTA.
	Prevent large-scale wildfires that will result in cheatgrass invasion or will destroy high-value sagebrush sites.	Use fire breaks around high quality sagebrush habitat areas. No disking allowed, fire breaks will be allowed through mowing native vegetation or retardant or herbicide application (green-stripping).

biological soil crust cover and its species richness (Johansen 1993). Disturbance that removes or kills crustal organisms results in greater impact and slower recovery than disturbance that leaves crushed crust material in place.

Recovery rates are dependent on many factors, including disturbance type, severity, and extent; vascular plant community structure; adjoining substrate condition; inoculation material availability; and climate during and after disturbance. In general, crusts are highly susceptible to hot fires; thus, recovery will depend on the size and intensity of fires. As noted previously, most compression disturbances have similar types of impacts. However, severity of mechanical disturbance can vary widely with disturbance type. Thus, on similar soils, vehicle tracks generally have longer recovery times than disturbances that do not churn the soil or make continuous tracks (Wilshire 1983; Belnap 1996). Because recolonization of disturbed areas occurs mostly from adjacent, less-disturbed areas, the size and shape of disturbance can affect recovery rates.

While total protection from disturbance is often the easiest way to maintain or improve biological soil crusts, this is not often possible or desirable. There are many factors to consider in the management of soil communities, including disturbance type, intensity, timing, frequency, duration, or extent. Proactive management is needed to prevent unnaturally large and/or frequent fires in areas where fuel build-up or annual grass invasions have occurred. Such management actions may include altering grazing regimes to prevent annual plant invasions, preventing fuel build-up, and/or restricting off-road vehicle use. Once a site has burned, evaluation is needed to determine whether recovery will occur naturally or if revegetation is needed. Many burned sites, particularly those in the Great Basin, Intermountain regions and the Columbia Plateau, require revegetation to stop exotic plant invasion, and most techniques require some soil surface disturbance. This may not appear consistent with recovery of biological crusts. However, failure to treat sites can result in irreversible dominance by annual species (such as cheatgrass), which prevents the return of well-developed biological soil crusts (Kaltenecker 1997, Kaltenecker et al. 1999a).

Biological soil crust management on NWSTF Boardman will focus on preventing fire and mechanical impacts and then restoring degraded habitats. Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weed and preventing mechanical habitat degradation. Natural habitat recovery of the burned or mechanically disturbed areas will be monitored by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the desired pre-disturbance habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures. Disturbed areas will be reseeded (either by broadcast seeding or using a no-till rangeland seed drill) and/or monitored for natural plant revegetation. Minimizing invasion by cheatgrass and other exotics or noxious plants is a primary goal of native plant restoration. Chemical control of cheatgrass and noxious weeds may be necessary to allow for native plant establishment. Revegetation treatments will be repeated as needed to establish native vegetation on the entire burned areas. Once an areas soil becomes stable and vegetation has been re-established after disturbance, the condition of the biological soil crust will be re-evaluated. If the soil crusts in the area are heavily damaged or have been destroyed with no nearby habitat for recolonization, then the site will be evaluated for soil crust restoration by spreading or introducing cyanobacteria and/or moss by application of those soil components to inoculate the soil. This has been shown to be effective in accelerating the redevelopment of biological soil crusts.

4.5 Fish and Wildlife Management

4.5.1 Hunting Program

Military Reservation and Facilities: Hunting, Fishing and Trapping Act of 1958 (Public Law 85-337, 10 U. S. C. 2671). This Act requires that all hunting, fishing, and trapping activities on military installations be conducted in accordance with the state fish and game laws in which the installation is located. Appropriate state licenses must be obtained for these activities on the installation.

Historically, limited small scale hunting for deer and birds occurred by military personnel stationed at NWSTF Boardman and for military and/or DoD civilian personnel stationed at NAS Whidbey Island and their guests. Since the late 1990s, this has been a very small informal and intermittent activity that was lightly controlled.

The Navy issued new access regulations for NWSTF Boardman, in August 2009 (NASWHIDBEYINST 8020.8), to meet current safety requirements for an active military bombing range. Because of the potential for unexploded ordnance throughout the range, access to NWSTF Boardman has been restricted to military training and direct training support activities. The suitability of any hunting program or other non-training access has been evaluated against these new safety requirements. From that evaluation, it has been determined that access for hunting on NWSTF Boardman is not consistent with and cannot meet safety and access requirements as outlined in NASWHISBEYINST 8020.8. Therefore, in November 2010 access for hunting on NWSTF Boardman has been formally closed for any and all potential participants. No hunting is authorized on NWSTF Boardman.

If access requirements and unexploded ordnance safety issues change in the future, the suitability of a hunting program on NWSTF Boardman may be re-evaluated. Should hunting become a suitable use for the range at anytime in the future, a formal hunting program could be established. Any formal hunting program development would be coordinated with the USFWS, ODFW and Tribes with treaty rights to coordinate procedures, participation, program requirements and to outline and codify requirements for access.

4.5.2 Migratory Birds

This management plan is envisioned with a large-scale habitat/ecosystem management concept. Therefore most management prescriptions and conservation actions are habitat based. This plan is designed to be in compliance with the requirements of the DoD and the US Fish and Wildlife Service MOU to promote the conservation of migratory birds in accordance with EO 13186, which was signed in July 2006. Habitat management prescriptions and species survey actions are designed to advance migratory bird conservation, species understanding and avoid or minimize the take of migratory birds.

Long-billed Curlew and Burrowing Owl

Long-billed curlews and burrowing owls are significant regional migratory bird populations that nest on NWSTF Boardman and have been the subject of many research activities (see Section 2.6.5 and Appendix M).

Similar to Washington ground squirrels, management strategy for these regionally significant bird populations focuses around a combination of population monitoring, habitat assessment, and habitat enhancement and restoration. Curlew and burrowing owl surveys will be conducted at necessary repeated time intervals in order to determine the activity status of historical nesting

locations. Using standard transect survey monitoring protocol, surveys will provide information confirming species presence, geographic extent of nesting sites, estimates of abundance in occupied habitat, and can be compared to previous survey work for the species. This will help to identify current occupied habitats. Habitat restoration and enhancement will focus on controlling noxious weeds and preventing mechanical disturbance of habitats. Natural habitat recovery of previous and future burned areas will be assessed by repeated monitoring of established vegetation plots and additional pedestrian surveys. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for restoration measures. Direct affect to individuals and nesting locations from operations will be accomplished by reviewing training and operational projects for potential impacts to known curlew and burrowing owl nesting locations, surveying project areas before activities, and incorporating suitable avoidance measures to reduce direct affects.

4.5.3 Partners in Flight

In 1990, the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation initiated the Neotropical Migratory Bird Conservation Program, known as "Partners in Flight - Aves de Las Americas." The initiative stresses the importance of international conservation partnerships to focus limited financial and human resources to provide for the long-term health of avifauna throughout the Western Hemisphere. The purpose of the program is to bring together the diverse array of groups and individuals involved in the conservation and management of birds and their habitats. The initial focus was on neo-tropical migrants, but has now spread to include most birds requiring terrestrial habitats. In the US, more than 300 partners from federal and state agencies, conservation groups, foundations, academia, and forest products companies have contributed expertise and resources to make Partners in Flight (PIF) successful in its conservation efforts. The PIF strategy for effective conservation relies on setting realistic biological priorities, using an appropriate geographic scale, and applying an ecosystem management approach.

The DoD PIF policy is to: "Promote and support our partnership role in the protection and conservation of birds and their habitats by protecting vital DoD lands and ecosystems, enhancing biodiversity, and maintaining healthy and productive natural systems consistent with the military mission". Implementation of this strategy will allow DoD natural resources managers to determine best management practices based on regional or physiographic delineations rather than on a species basis. This ecosystem management approach provides a framework to consider the biological diversity on military lands in the context of the surrounding landscape. This approach will improve long-term planning and efficiency and promote better integration of mission and resource requirements.

The primary goals and objectives of the DoD Partners in Flight program, as they are to be implemented at NWSTF Boardman, are to:

- Apply information collected from this partnership program to support DoD mission requirements;
- Take proactive management actions to prevent bird species from reaching threatened or endangered status;
- Facilitate cooperative partnership efforts consistent with the military mission;
- Determine the status of migratory and resident bird populations on DoD lands and the causes of population fluctuations;
- Reduce bird aircraft strike hazard risks through implementation of mobile radar;
- Maintain and restore priority habitats on DoD lands for migratory and resident bird populations;

- Reduce or eliminate pesticide use in sensitive habitats, especially in and around wetlands and riparian areas;
- Reduce the spread and impact to birds and their habitats of invasive and nuisance species on military lands, including feral and free-roaming cats.

For further information on the DoD Partners in Flight program go to <http://www.DoDpif.org>.

4.5.4 Bird Aircraft Strike Hazard (BASH)

There is no BASH plan for aircraft at this time because there are no fixed wing aircraft runways or helicopter pads at the installation. Helicopters could land and take off in many areas of the installation, if needed. However, helicopter landings and take-offs are rare at the installation. No specific BASH concentrated risk areas have been identified at this time and no habitat alteration, harassment and/or depredation specific to BASH functions takes place at this time on NWSTF Boardman. Any BASH incidents are reports back to the home station of aircraft using NWSTF Boardman and that information is monitored by NAS Whidbey Island BASH personnel for any impending BASH risks that may need to be addressed. BASH risk is considered with the planning of all natural resource management actions and those prescriptions are designed to not increase BASH risk.

4.6 Land Management

4.6.1 Invasive Plant Species

The term “invasive species” is defined by Presidential Executive Order (EO) 13112 to mean “an alien species whose introduction does or is likely to cause economic or environmental harm or harm to human health.” The EO goes on to define an alien species as any species not native to a particular ecosystem, including the seeds, eggs, spores, or other biological material capable of propagating that species. Exotic invasive plants and animals have the potential to cause vast ecological and economical damage, and sometimes pose human health impacts in areas they infest. EO 13112 requires that each federal agency whose actions may affect the status of invasive species shall, to the extent practicable and permitted by law:

- (1) identify such actions;
- (2) subject to the availability of appropriations, and within Administration budgetary limits, use relevant programs and authorities to: (i) prevent the introduction of invasive species; (ii) detect and respond rapidly to and control populations of such species in a cost-effective and environmentally sound manner; (iii) monitor invasive species populations accurately and reliably; (iv) provide for restoration of native species and habitat conditions in ecosystems that have been invaded; (v) conduct research on invasive species and develop technologies to prevent introduction and provide for environmentally sound control of invasive species; and (vi) promote public education on invasive species and the means to address them; and
- (3) not authorize, fund, or carry out actions that it believes are likely to cause or promote the introduction or spread of invasive species in the United States or elsewhere unless, pursuant to guidelines that it has prescribed, the agency has determined and made public its determination that the benefits of such actions clearly outweigh the potential harm caused by invasive species; and that all feasible and prudent measures to minimize risk of harm will be taken in conjunction with the actions.

To implement the above recommendations, known noxious weeds locations will be annually surveyed and controlled in a cooperative effort between the Navy and the Nature

Conservancy (mostly within RNAs). Invasive plant species occurrences will be prioritized to target limited control efforts where they will do the most good. Targeted control should be based on the below general criteria (Dave Pranger, pers. comm. 1998):

- (1) all "class A" species: rush skeletonweed, yellow starthistle, spikeweed, perennial pepperweed, Scotch thistle;
- (2) medium-density and high density areas (the southern and eastern boundaries) of diffuse knapweed in the main target;
- (3) high-density areas of diffuse knapweed outside of the main target;
- (4) low-density and very low-density areas of diffuse knapweed in the main target;
- (5) medium-density areas of diffuse knapweed outside of the main target;
- (6) low-density areas of diffuse knapweed outside of the main target;
- (7) other species: medusahead rye, cereal rye, Russian thistle;
- (8) very low-density areas of diffuse knapweed outside of the main target.

All control actions need to be in compliance with the requirements of the installation Integrated Pest Management Plan and applied herbicides have to be on the plan's approved list for use and applied by a federally licensed applicator. All installation training and facility operation actions shall be reviewed by the NRM for potential noxious weed issues. Existing installation-wide mapping of noxious weeds is outdated and in need of updating because of recent fires, habitat changes and spreading invasive plant populations. A new installation-wide assessment needs to be performed to help with targeting future control priorities (see description in Appendix A).

4.6.2 Fire Management

There are three possible ways that NWSTF Boardman can experience uncontrolled fires: 1) fires originating on the installation from operational activities; 2) fires originating from lightning strikes; and 3) fires originating off base from any source and migrating into the perimeter of the installation. With the present staffing levels and equipment at the range and issues with historically unnatural fuel loads because of non-native species in many areas, setting fires for optimum plant management purposes is not practicable. Also, because of staffing size (typically less than seven personnel) fire fighting becomes a matter of containment to smaller areas where either the range personnel have a chance of extinguishing the fire, or where outside agencies may be able to help.

Minimizing uncontrolled fires is important to management of the vegetation. Repeated burning of areas of the installation every few years can be harmful to native grasses, shrubs, and soil structure. Sagebrush and bitterbrush are highly susceptible to fire damage. Repeated burnings of desirable perennial bunchgrasses will eventually allow cheatgrass to increase. Retaining large areas of big sagebrush and reducing areas of cheatgrass are desirable management objectives for providing quality wildlife habitat. Plant communities on NWSTF Boardman were fire adapted communities. Historic fire return intervals were 50-70 years for this part of the Columbia River plateau. Because of the widespread introduction of cheatgrass and invasive weeds (such as knapweeds), the fuel loading in these historic habitats has been greatly increased. Because of this fire return intervals have been altered to an estimated 5-10 years.

The three main problems to managing wildfires at NWSTF Boardman are 1) small staff; 2) inadequate equipment; and 3) distances to water outlets. Current Navy mission requirements may not allow an increase in staff or provide funding for more fire-fighting equipment. Consequently, fire management must rely more on low maintenance containment to small areas, allowing installation personnel a chance to either extinguish the fire or obtain help from outside

agencies to come in and assist in extinguishing the fire before it spreads to larger areas. The Boardman fire strategy is use the existing road system as the staging lines at which fires will be fought. Permanent firebreaks can cause soil stability problems and are establishment areas for noxious weeds. Also as recent history in 2008 has shown, disked firebreaks are not an effective means of stopping wildfires on the Boardman range (see below photo). Typical wind driven fires for the area can easily jump a dirt road and adjacent double width disked firebreak (40 foot width) without burning the remnant vegetation in the break and continue burning across the range unimpeded.

The basic strategy under this INRMP is to fight fires at roads with wet lines, back burns, mechanical breaks (if needed), etc., rather than travelling cross-country with tankers or tractors construct new disked firebreaks. The current placement of firebreaks is a remnant of past operations and protection strategies that may no longer be prudent given the very limited success of the fire breaks and change in operation tempo. There needs to be a complete integrated review of fire break placement between the fire management strategy and integrated with the natural resource objectives of this management plan. Needed firebreaks should be focused around high use areas (targets, etc.), be established and maintained only in stable soil locations, be focused around existing roads for easy access of equipment and to utilize those existing disturbed areas, and be focused towards the purpose of initiating fire suppression actions. Those breaks need to be maintained several times a year to prevent noxious weed establishment and seed propagation. Alternative fire break technologies should be explored such as “green stripping” with selective herbicide application or planting fire resistant vegetation (such as forage Kochia) as opposed to mechanical disking or blading. Green stripping has been used successfully adjacent to existing roads by herbicide application to reduce annual and invasive

species fuel loads without disturbing the soil or by planting fire resistant vegetation. This reduces soil erosion potential, doesn't provide for the establishment of noxious weeds, and maintains some form of wildlife habitat value with the fire breaks. Any unneeded old fire breaks need to be revegetated. These old disked areas will be treated to control invasive or ruderal species, seeded with suitable perennial native grass species, and monitored with continued maintenance until desired vegetation is established.

4.6.2.1 Fire Management Strategy

A Comprehensive Wildfire Response Plan for NWSTF Boardman is recommended in order to guide 1) preventative actions such as locations, size, and maintenance plans for permanent fire access routes with the roads being the ground firefighting areas, and the airspace available for aerial application of water/retardant, and 2) reactive actions, such as logical locations for temporary fire lines, use of wet lines, and considerations for access to water sources. The federal Navy Region Northwest Federal Fire Department is leading the development the fire management strategy for NWSTF Boardman. Objectives of this INRMP need to be incorporated into the fire management strategy to include consideration of natural resource considerations into a comprehensive and integrated strategy. The plan should also identify possible rehabilitative actions to be taken after wildfires to aid recovery of areas burned or disturbed during fire suppression activities. This will include all areas of soil disturbance.

Fire Breaks

The following parameters would lessen natural resources impacts for the fire breaks:

- integrated review of fire break placement between the fire management strategy and integrated with the natural resource objectives of this management plan. Needed fire breaks should be focused around high use areas (targets, etc.), be established and maintained only in stable soil locations, be focused around existing roads for easy access of equipment and to utilize those existing disturbed areas, and be focused towards the purpose of initiating fire suppression actions.;
- fire breaks need to be maintained several times a year to prevent noxious weed establishment and seed propagation. Alternative fire break technologies should be explored such as "green stripping" with selective herbicide application or planting fire resistant vegetation (such as forage Kochia) as opposed to mechanical disking or blading;
- avoid and preserve the remnant Oregon Trail wagon tracks: where the tracks parallel road and mechanical fire breaks, focus disturbance actions on the roadside away from the wagon tracks.

Range Operating Controls

In accordance with the Pacific Northwest Training Range Complex Manual (NASWHIDBEYINST 3770.1D), the use of tracer rounds at the strafe pit is authorized between 1 October and 31 May or at other times upon written approval of the NAS Whidbey Island Operations Officer (e.g. should unit scheduling provide its own wildfire suppression personnel and equipment onsite during strafe operations, consideration will be made to permit tracer rounds use outside the normal "low fire danger" season). This broad authorization for seasonal use can sometimes allow the use of pyrotechnic ammunition during high fire conditions. Since fire conditions are dependent on weather patterns at a given time, high fire danger conditions can occur during the general October-May tracer round use period. If sufficient fire suppression resources are not available onsite during a training event, the Navy staff stationed at NWSTF Boardman should monitor weather conditions for high fire danger and be prepared to halt training operations if conditions become too likely to cause an uncontrollable wildfire from errant rounds, munitions or

pyrotechnics. Future fire management and range planning should consider using a case-by-case strategy for identifying high fire risk when scheduling training activities. A fire risk severity ranking system is identified in Appendix G that could be fitted for use in determining when certain training activities would be unwise due to fire conditions.

Post Fire Requirements

After a wildfire of any origin, all burned areas will be mapped for extent and surveyed for habitat damage. An assessment will be made as to whether revegetation treatment should be accomplished. Depending on that assessment, habitat type and the likelihood of natural revegetation of desirable species from the native soil seed bank, the area will be reseeded (either by broadcast seeding or using a no-till rangeland seed drill) and/or monitored for natural plant revegetation. Minimizing invasion by cheatgrass and other exotics or noxious plants is a primary goal of post-fire restoration. Chemical control of cheatgrass and noxious weeds may be necessary to allow for native plant establishment. Revegetation treatments will be repeated as needed to establish native vegetation on the entire burned areas. Since post-fire revegetation is fire-by-fire specific based on the conditions left after the fire, no generic post-fire prescription is being proposed and will be handled site-by-site based on the results of the post-wildfire monitoring with the all the above techniques being available for use.

Revegetation needs to incorporate re-establishing the biological soil crusts for burned areas, if they were damaged by the fire or fire suppression. Soil crusts required stable soils to develop and spread, so soil stabilization is important. As stated before in this document, the goal of habitat management is to provide naturally resilient habitats to support realistic military training. Towards this goal, the only long-term solution is to re-establish native vegetation on a burned site as quickly as possible. Since re-establishing vegetation is a function of available seed and water, this is not a quick process. If specific areas of blowing soils are causing restoration, nuisance or safety concerns, localized stabilization fixes will be explored. Placement of small scale and localized mechanical soil stabilizing features after a wildfire (such as drift fencing) could provide localized benefits in problem soil movement areas, while limiting the effect of retarding native revegetation. The NRM should be engaged in developing any stabilizing activities to provide guidance on limiting natural resource impacts from any proposed actions. The NRM should also develop alternatives and/or locations for suitable work that is consistent with the goals and objectives of this plan. Restoring stable native vegetation is the ultimate solution to reducing blowing sand issues on NWSTF Boardman. Once an area's soil becomes stable and vegetation has been re-established, after a fire, the condition of the biological soil crust will be re-evaluated. If the soil crusts in the area are heavily damaged or have been destroyed, then the site will be evaluated for soil crust restoration by spreading or introducing cyanobacteria and/or moss by application of those soil components to inoculate the soil. This has been shown to be effective in accelerating the redevelopment of biological soil crusts.

4.6.3 Agricultural Outleasing

4.6.3.1 Grazing and Crop Circles

Almost all of NWSTF Boardman was previously outleased as grazing lease areas until 2001 and three half crop circles were outleased on the northcentral boundary of the installation until 2002. The grazing leases provided an average total of 3,590 Animal Unit Months [AUMs] of grazing capacity and the crop circles provided 240 acres of irrigated ground for row crop tillage as a way of stabilizing the main active sand dune. Historically, the total AUMs available for the lessees as

stipulated in the contracts constituted about 55 percent of the potential AUM production for the lease areas (McClelland and Bedell 1987). Both sheep and cattle were historically used on the range and alfalfa was grown in the crop circles.

Since NWSTF Boardman is an active ordnance training range, all agricultural outleases must comply with the requirements of DoD Publication 6055.09-STD and NAVSEA Publication OP-5. Both publications limit access to active training ranges to necessary operational functions and set requirements for leasing ranges with potential unexploded ordnance. The requirements and reviews are extensive and the cost of meeting those requirements when weighed against the potential income and benefit generated from an agricultural outlease program would be very cost prohibitive. Because of those issues, no agricultural outlease program is operating on the range or anticipated during the duration of this management plan.

4.6.4 Research Natural Areas

The Research Natural Areas (RNAs) of NWSTF Boardman (see Figure 2-2) are part of a federal system of RNAs established for research and educational purposes. The Navy established the Boardman RNAs on September 1, 1978 to preserve high-quality examples of Columbia River Basin grassland and steppe vegetation communities and associated wildlife.

Federal Research Natural Areas provide a unique system of publicly owned and protected examples of undisturbed ecosystems where scientists can conduct research with minimal interference and reasonable assurance that investments in long-term studies will not be lost to logging, land development, or similar activities. The main purposes of RNAs are to provide:

1. baseline areas against which effects of human activities can be measured;
2. sites for study of natural processes in undisturbed ecosystems; and
3. gene pool preserves of organisms, especially rare and endangered types.

In return, a scientist wishing to use a Research Natural Area is obligated to:

1. obtain permission from the appropriate administering agency before using the area;
2. abide by the administering agency's regulations governing use;
3. inform the administering agency on progress of the research.

The management plan for the NWSTF Boardman RNAs follows much of the documentation from the original 1978 establishment report (see Appendix E for full report). The Commanding Officer, NAS Whidbey Island is the administrator of the RNAs on NWSTF Boardman. The non-commissioned Officer in Charge (NCOIC) at NWSTF Boardman and his assigned staff is responsible for coordinating access for the RNAs around scheduled military use of the facility. Access will not be granted during periods of military use that cover the areas of the subject RNAs. The principle contact for approval and coordination of research on the RNAs is the Natural Resources Manager, NAS Whidbey Island, Environmental Division, Public Works Department, NAS Whidbey Island, 1115 W. Lexington Street, Bldg. 103, Oak Harbor, WA 98278. Final approval of all research proposals will be by the Commanding Officer, NAS Whidbey Island. Per Cooperative Management Agreement between The Nature Conservancy (TNC) and the Navy signed in 1988 (see Appendix E for full agreement), the Navy will review all proposed management activities, provide fire suppression and control visitation to the RNAs. All RNAs are fenced to identify the boundaries and to control access. Access to the RNAs is subject to the following requirements:

1. approval of proposed research must be obtained from the Navy prior to using the area;
2. proposed research must be essentially non-destructive;
3. collection of plant and animal specimens will be restricted to a minimum and such collections must be deposited in a public holding institution;
4. a cooperative agreement between the Navy and the researcher must be entered into prior to use of the area;
5. researcher must obtain approval from the NCOIC at NWSTF Boardman for access to the area prior to each use;
6. periodic reports on the progress of the research and copies of published research results must be provided to the Navy;
7. specific research must be compatible with the preservation of the ecosystem and the maintenance of its processes;
8. non-indigenous and invasive plant and animal species will not be introduced into the areas;
9. permanent structure will not be constructed within the areas, but minimal temporary research facilities may be approved by the Navy;
10. no interference with normal cycles and fluctuations of wildlife populations will be allowed;
11. predator control will not be allowed within the areas without specific approval of the Navy;
12. no camping is allowed on the area or the Navy facility; and
13. no services or support will be provided by the Navy without prior request and approval.

The 1988 Cooperative Management Agreement coordinates management of the RNAs on NWSTF Boardman between TNC and the Navy. Key provisions in the agreement are that TNC will establish permanent plots and monitor vegetation trends within the RNAs, control noxious weeds within the RNA boundaries, and maintain the fences around the RNAs. TNC has reviewed and was included in the development of this INRMP. By letter (attached in Appendix E), TNC has committed to follow and advance the goals and objectives of this INRMP in their management of the RNAs under the existing cooperative management agreement. TNC and the Navy have proposed moving RNA-A due to the military activities and establishing a new RNA location. Local Navy staff will work with The Nature Conservancy on a proposal to move RNA-A from the main target and to identify the specific boundaries of a new location that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect. An area located in the more sandy soil types in the northwest portion of the NWSTF or immediately west of the current RNA location would protect exceptional examples of several critically imperiled plant community types.

4.6.5 Grounds Maintenance and Landscaping

Grounds maintenance and landscaping includes considerations for weed control and urban forestry. It is Navy policy that environmentally and economically beneficial landscaping practices be used. These practices are outlined in a Memorandum for Heads of Executive Departments and Agencies issued by the President (Presidential Memorandum) dated 26 April 1994. The Presidential Memorandum directs federal agencies to use landscaping techniques that enhance the local environment and minimize the adverse effects that landscaping can have on the environment. The Presidential Memorandum stresses use of regionally native plants and practices that conserve water and prevent pollution. Integrated measures include reducing use of fertilizers, pesticides, and water use for both economic and environmental benefits. With regard to the control of noxious weeds, Navy installations will cooperate with state programs for controlling noxious plants.

4.6.6 Integrated Pest Management

Integrated Pest Management Plans (IPMP) are reviewed and revised as needed on a yearly basis according to DoD Instruction 4150.7 and OPNAVINST 6250.4. Changes in pest management strategy, pest control methods, pesticides used, pesticide safety and pest survey techniques are discussed in the IPMP. The IPMP is prepared by the Pest Management Coordinator and reviewed by the Public Works Officer, Environmental Office and Medical Officer. Approval of the IPMP is conducted through joint review by the Naval Facilities Engineering Command Area Pest Management Consultant and Officer-in Charge, Naval Disease Vector Ecology and Control Center.

Poisonous plants and noxious weeds shall be controlled or eradicated in accordance with approved practices and applicable laws when they interfere with safe and efficient land use, endanger the health and welfare of personnel, or constitute a source of weed infestation to adjacent property. The pest control measures and approved pesticides are identified in and shall be implemented within the IPMP guidelines.

4.6.6.1 Grasshopper Control

During some years, NWSTF Boardman can have a high population level of grasshoppers that can exceed the U.S. Department of Agriculture's economic threshold levels. Outbreaks are difficult to predict because they are dependent on climatic variables such as temperature and moisture and previous wildfire occurrence. The last major outbreak on the range occurred during the 2004-2005 seasons. These levels can cause complaints from adjacent landowners and

requests that the Navy control grasshopper numbers on the range. Most adjacent landowners however conduct control operations on their own adjacent fields when these high levels occur in the area. Like all insect populations, they cycle back down again when conditions are not optimal.

Larval and adult grasshoppers are an important food source for grassland birds on NWSTF Boardman. They are readily consumed by loggerhead shrikes, long-billed curlews, burrowing owls, and many other bird species as an important protein source during the spring and summer. The loss of this food source over large areas could hamper reproductive success for those bird species during optimal forage years.

Due to the importance of the grasshopper food source to those large breeding bird populations, the fact that those breeding bird populations are geographically limited to the range for breeding, that adjoining landowners can protect their crops by controlling grasshoppers directly on their own land, and the knowledge that the grasshopper populations will cycle down on their own, no large scale grasshopper control should occur on NWSTF Boardman to protect this valuable bird forage base.

4.6.7 Off-road Vehicle Use

Recreational use of off-road vehicles (ORV), such as all terrain vehicles, dirt bikes, non-motorized mountain bikes, etc., is not authorized on NWSTF Boardman. DoD policy (OPNAVINST 5090.1C, DODDIR 4700.4) requires that any ORV use areas must be reviewed, monitored and officially designated through chain-of-command approval. There are no designated ORV use areas on NWSTF Boardman. The recreational use of ORVs, by civilians or military personnel, on the range is not considered consistent with the installation's training mission. This recreational use of the land conflicts with military land use requirements, wise land management practices, environmental values, and training sustainment activities. Use of the range is restricted to military training and their support activities. Recreational ORV use increases impacts to habitats, destabilizes the soil, promotes invasive plant species introductions and is a potential source of wildfire ignition which reduces military training capabilities and increases natural resources training sustainment costs. The restrictions on off-road vehicles do not apply to official use by an employee, agent, or designated representative of the federal government or one of its contractors in performance of their assigned duties (EO 11644). That is, the use of military or contractor provided ORVs for road and perimeter patrols, fencing repairs, ordnance clearance and invasive weed spraying or military training support activities are not subject to the ORV use restriction. All other non-training ORV use on NWSTF Boardman is not authorized and not appropriate on an active military training range. The personnel stationed at NWSTF Boardman provide security for the range and will work to prevent any trespassing on the range including preventing unauthorized ORV access and use.

5.0 IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter of the INRMP addresses how the plan will be carried out as a means of supporting the military mission through effective land stewardship. All actions contemplated in this INRMP are subject to the availability of funds properly authorized and appropriated under Federal law. Nothing in this INRMP is intended to be nor must be construed to be a violation of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S.C. 1341 *et seq.*).

A list of NWSTF Boardman proposed projects may be found in Appendix A of this INRMP.

5.1 Project Requirements and Funding

Project and management action implementation is the most important part of this management document. It is through implementation that conservation benefits are realized. A major function of implementation is funding.

All INRMP projects must be entered into the Environmental Program Requirements (EPR) web and receive approval up the chain of command prior to funding. The Navy prioritizes funding based on the Environmental Readiness Level (ERL) of a project. ERL levels go from 1-4 with 4 being the highest priority funding requirement.

All in-house Navy and external funding sources will be explored and utilized to implement this management plan, as appropriate. Major funding sources for project implementation are conducting management actions using Navy in-house labor, utilizing Navy O&MN environmental funding, legacy funding, forestry revenue funding, agricultural outlease revenue funding, or fish and wildlife fees. Non-Navy funding/labor resources or volunteer assets will also be used when available.

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APPENDIX A. Natural Resources Projects

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The following is a list of recommended projects:

Table A-1. INRMP Project Recommendations.

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
Vegetation Management			
V-1: Monitor and control noxious weeds and invasive, non-native plants. Primary efforts at control will consist of herbicide spraying. Herbicides should only be spot applied directly to plants, not broadcast from trucks or from the air. Secondary control is with manual and/or mechanical removal.	4	\$125,000 (\$25,000 each year)	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016
V-2: Count, measure, re-tag, and map all junipers. Junipers provide important habitat for nesting birds and shade habitat for other species. Mapping and tagging of junipers took place years ago. An inspection in 2006 found new, unmapped recruitment and dead tagged trees. On the ground field mapping of the junipers will help identify area expansion/reduction trends (when compared to the last mapping effort) and provide data as to the health of the trees.	3	\$6,000 and in-house labor	FY 2012
V-3: Use high-resolution aerial photography to map all vegetation; produce GIS-based vegetation map. The last vegetation map was produced at least ten years ago. Since then, grazing leases have been terminated, resulting in a change in vegetation. Wildfires have also swept parts of the range. A new mapping effort is required to identify and quantify the changes, to provide data for management purposes. The cost reflects the acquisition of imagery, ground truthing, and the production of a GIS data set for maps.	4	\$70,000	FY 2014
V-4: Recover monumented vegetation plots and resurvey vegetation using established protocol; produce GIS data layers for inclusion into Boardman GIS maps. Oregon State University established vegetation survey plots in the 1980s. These plots have been marked with monuments for recovery. This project will use the original methods to resurvey the plots. This will provide 1) ground truthing for V-3 above; 2) trend analysis for vegetation change due to the termination of grazing and to wildfire impacts; and 3) permanent locations to measure future vegetation change or stability.	4	\$60,000 (\$20,000 each year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
V-5: Monitor previous burned areas for vegetation recovery. Conduct pedestrian surveys through the previous wildfire areas and assess natural vegetation recovery. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the desired pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures to be implemented in project V-6 below.	3	In-house labor	FY 2012, 2013
V-6: Native Vegetation Restoration. Areas previously impacted by Navy mission, land management activities, or wildfire will be treated to re-establish native plant communities. This will not apply to areas encumbered by UXO.	3	\$260,000 (\$130,000 each year)	FY 2014, 2016
V-7: Move RNA-A. Local Navy staff will work with The Nature Conservancy on a proposal to move RNA-A from the main target and to identify the specific boundaries of a new location that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect. New fencing to surround the new location will need to be installed.	2	\$15,000	FY 2014
V-8: Map Noxious Weeds. Perform and installation-wide mapping of noxious weeds/invasive plant species following the protocols used in the 1997 survey. This includes creating a GIS map layer to prioritize control.	3	\$30,000	FY 2014
Wildlife			
WL-1: Conduct large mammal surveys. Pronghorn antelope have recently moved onto the range and may be permanent or semi-permanent residents. Rocky Mountain elk may also occasionally use the installation. Mule deer inhabit the range but the extent of the herd is unknown. Conduct surveys to identify the extent of the herds and to help identify impacts to range vegetation and provide data for herd management.	2	\$12,500 for equipment (\$2,500 for two surveys each year) and in-house labor	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016
WL-2: Washington ground squirrel surveys. Washington ground squirrels are a state protected species. Military training can impact the ground squirrel population on the installation. Burrow and population estimate data is available from past surveys, but new data is required to assess changes or stability due to 1) termination of grazing and resulting changes in vegetation, 2) recent fires, and 3) new mission requirements.	4	\$80,000 (\$20,000 per year)	FY 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
WL-3: Burrowing owl surveys. Burrowing owls nest in excavations in the ground and thus are susceptible to disturbance or injury from vehicles and/or training. New data is needed to identify habitat use areas for management and military training decisions, to track population trends, and to evaluate and/or alter NR enhancement actions.	2	\$30,000 (\$10,000 per year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016
WL-4: Conduct long-billed curlew surveys and monitoring. Curlews nest on the ground in open grassland areas and thus are susceptible to disturbance or injury from vehicles and/or training. New data is needed to identify current habitat use areas for management and military training decisions, to track population trends, and to evaluate and/or alter NR enhancement actions.	4	\$45,000 (\$15,000 per year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016
Fire Management			
FM-1: Fire break analysis and relocation. Develop a comprehensive assessment of fire breaks for the installation. Include the results of fire break success from the 2008 fire and alternative techniques such as "green stripping" with herbicide or fire resistant vegetation.	3	\$20,000	FY 2013
FM-2: Map and assess annual wildfires. Annually, as needed, map all wildfire perimeters and assess natural resource damage from the event to be used for future monitoring needs and restoration prioritization.	3	In-house labor	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016

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APPENDIX B. INRMP FONSI and Environmental Assessment

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**DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE
DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY**

FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR THE ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (EA) FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AN UPDATED INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP) AT NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF) BOARDMAN, OREGON

Pursuant to the Council on Environmental Quality regulations (40 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] Parts 1500-1508) implementing the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), and Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1C, the Department of the Navy (Navy) gives notice that an EA has been prepared and an Environmental Impact Statement is not required for the implementation of an updated INRMP.

The Proposed Action is to implement all objectives and recommendations of the revised INRMP including high-, medium- and low-priority objectives. High-priority objectives include: monitor and control noxious weeds and invasive, non-native plants; conduct Washington ground squirrel surveys; conduct long-billed curlew surveys; and analyze and relocate firebreaks, if necessary. Medium-priority objectives include: map noxious weeds; count, measure, re-tag and map all junipers; use high-resolution aerial photography to map all vegetation; produce geographic information system (GIS) -based vegetation map; recover monumented vegetation plots and resurvey vegetation using established protocol; produce GIS-based data layers for inclusion into Boardman GIS maps; monitor previously burned areas for vegetation recovery; create a proposal to move Research Natural Area (RNA)-A from the main target and identify the specific boundaries of a new location that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect; and map and assess annual wildfires. Low-priority objectives include: conduct large mammal and burrowing owl surveys.

The purpose of and need for the proposed action is to comply with the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997, provide management requirements for species listed under the Endangered Species Act, and meet the requirements of Department of Defense and Navy instructions. Moreover, the conservation program must be consistent with the mission-essential use of the installation and its lands and not cause a net loss of military land use. The SAIA requires the preparation of an INRMP to facilitate the conservation program. The INRMP must be cooperatively developed with the U.S Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the Oregon

FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR THE ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (EA) FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AN UPDATED INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP) AT NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF) BOARDMAN, OREGON

Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW). Finally, the SAIA requires that the INRMP be reviewed with the USFWS and ODFW annually, as to its operation and effect, and revised or re-signed at least every 5 years.

Existing Conditions: The 47,400-acre NWSTF Boardman is located in northern Morrow County approximately 3 miles south of the town of Boardman in north-central Oregon. The installation is rectangular, with a size of 12 by 6 miles and consists of two target spotting towers, a headquarters compound consisting of several buildings that house offices and workshops, several wells and water pipelines, and gravel and dirt roads. The range has been in use as a military training area since 1941. Navy aircraft, as well as aircraft from the Oregon National Guard and other Department of Defense agencies, use the range area for operational training.

Alternatives Analyzed: The Preferred Alternative (to adopt and implement all objectives and recommendations of the revised INRMP), Alternative 2 (to adopt and implement only the high and medium priority objectives and recommendations), and the No-Action Alternative were evaluated in the EA. Under the No-Action Alternative, objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP completed in 1999 would continue to be implemented and the purpose of and need for the Proposed Action would not be met.

Environmental Effects: The EA analyzed the potential effects of the Preferred Alternative, Alternative 2 and the No-Action Alternative on the environment. Potential impacts to relevant resources were evaluated for each alternative and include land use, air quality, water resources, terrestrial biology, cultural resources, socioeconomic and environmental justice, and public health and safety. Each resource area evaluated is briefly described below.

Land Use. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would have a positive impact on land condition at the NWSTF. Land formerly managed under agricultural leases would be managed for native species, providing an additional positive impact by restoring the native vegetation which provides habitat and food resources for native wildlife species. Environmentally sensitive areas are protected from livestock grazing, as this practice is no longer recommended in the revised INRMP.

FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR THE ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (EA) FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AN UPDATED INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP) AT NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF) BOARDMAN, OREGON

Air Quality. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would not have an effect on air quality. None of the recommendations in the updated INRMP would alter air quality in relation to the six criteria pollutants. The proposed land management and post fire restoration actions (i.e., alternative techniques such as "green stripping" with herbicide) should have a beneficial effect by reducing fugitive dust and blowing sand that occurs after wildfires or any vegetation removal on the range.

Water Resources. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would not impact groundwater, drinking water, or wastewater due to the lack of discharge possibilities and proximity to surface water sources. The Preferred Alternative would have no effect on water quality or resources as none of the recommendations of the updated INRMP involve changes to water resource management.

Terrestrial Biology. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would have a beneficial impact on terrestrial flora by increasing awareness of species present and implementing new projects to gain additional knowledge about the vegetation that exists, such as junipers and comprehensive vegetation mapping. Additionally, management strategies are provided for invasive species and noxious weed control. The revised INRMP recommendations also include additional goals for fire management and post wildfire restoration actions on the property, which would benefit the flora.

Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would have a positive effect on wildlife species by decreasing invasive species and increasing knowledge of their occurrence through surveys. The updated INRMP includes measures for conservation and protection of natural resources including the following: conduct Washington ground squirrel surveys; analyze and relocate firebreaks; conduct large mammal surveys; and conduct burrowing owl and long-billed curlew surveys and monitoring.

Threatened and Endangered Species. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would not impact threatened and endangered species as there are no listed species that inhabit the NWSTF, nor is there any critical habitat. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would have a beneficial impact to candidate species and other species of concern by decreasing invasive species and by conducting surveys of current populations and habitats, providing additional data to resource managers to effectively implement updated management strategies.

FINDING OF NO SIGNIFICANT IMPACT (FONSI) FOR THE ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT (EA) FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AN UPDATED INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN (INRMP) AT NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF) BOARDMAN, OREGON

Cultural Resources. Some of the management techniques proposed by the Preferred Alternative, such as techniques that are invasive of soils or may cause erosion, have the potential to adversely affect historic properties. If and when decisions are made to use these invasive techniques, and locations where they may be used are defined, then cultural resource assessments and State Historic Preservation Officer and tribal consultations may be required under section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA). Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would comply with the requirements of NHPA and if needed, proposed management actions would be modified to avoid affects to historic resources. By complying with the NHPA during implementation, the Preferred Alternative would not have an adverse effect on historic properties.

Socioeconomics and Environmental Justice. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would not have a disproportionate adverse affect on minority or low income populations in the area of the NWSTF. All recommendations in the updated INRMP would only affect NWSTF property and would not result in any negative effects to the neighboring properties.

Public Health and Safety. Implementation of the Preferred Alternative would have no effect on public or children's health and safety as children and public citizens are excluded by a fence around the perimeter of the property.

Finding: Based on the analysis presented in the EA, the Navy finds that implementation of the Proposed Action will not significantly impact the quality of the human or natural environment and an Environmental Impact Statement is not required.

The EA prepared by the Navy addressing this action is on file and interested parties may obtain a copy from: Naval Facilities Engineering Command Northwest, Public Works Department, 1115 West Lexington Drive, Oak Harbor, WA 98278 (Attention: Mrs. Jackie Queen, Environmental Planner).

5/25/2012
Date

D. T. BIESEL
Rear Admiral, U.S. Navy
Commander, Navy Region Northwest

**ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
FOR NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF)
BOARDMAN
BOARDMAN, OREGON**

February 2012

**ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT
INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN
NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY (NWSTF) BOARDMAN
BOARDMAN, OREGON**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The proposed action is to adopt and implement an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF), Boardman, Oregon for the years 2012 to 2016. The INRMP was updated in a manner that is consistent with the military use of the property and the goals and objectives established in the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997. The purpose of and need for the proposed action is to meet statutory requirements imposed by the SAIA, provide management requirements for flora and fauna species of concern, and meet the requirements of Department of Defense (DoD) and United States Navy (USN) instructions.

The Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1) is to implement all objectives and recommendations of the revised INRMP including:

- High-priority objectives
 - Monitor and control noxious weeds and invasive, non-native plants.
 - Conduct Washington ground squirrel surveys.
 - Analyze and relocate firebreaks, if necessary.
- Medium-priority objectives
 - Map noxious weeds.
 - Count, measure, re-tag and map all junipers.
 - Use high-resolution aerial photography to map all vegetation; produce geographic information system- (GIS)-based vegetation map.
 - Recover monumented vegetation plots and resurvey vegetation using established protocol; produce GIS data layers for inclusion into Boardman GIS maps.
 - Monitor previously burned areas for vegetation recovery.
 - Create a proposal to move Research Natural Area (RNA)-A from the main target and identify the specific boundaries of a new location that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect.
 - Map and assess annual wildfires.
- Low-priority objectives
 - Conduct large mammal surveys.
 - Conduct burrowing owl and long-billed curlew surveys.

With approval of the revised INRMP, the implementation of all objectives and recommendations would effectively manage natural resources at the NWSTF. Alternative 2 would adopt and implement only the high- and medium-priority objectives and recommendations of the revised INRMP. The No-Action Alternative would continue to utilize the existing INRMP (1999) as a management tool. On-going practices for natural resources management at the NWSTF would continue. Many of the management practices of the 1999 INRMP are the same as the revised INRMP, but the 1999 INRMP lacked emphasis on increasing wildlife habitat, threatened and endangered species protection, and range management thus not meeting the purpose and need to meet statutory requirements imposed by the SAIA, provide management requirements for flora and fauna species of concern and meet the requirements of DOD and USN instructions.

The Environmental Assessment was made available for public review and no comments were received.

Based on the analysis in this Environmental Assessment, the Navy has concluded that implementation of the Preferred Alternative and adoption of all recommendations of the updated INRMP would have no significant impact on the human environment and preparation of an Environmental Impact Statement is not required.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BMP	Best Management Practice
CEQ	Council on Environmental Quality
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
DOD	Department of Defense
EA	Environmental Assessment
EIS	Environmental Impact Statement
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ESA	Endangered Species Act
FONSI	Finding of No Significant Impact
FUDS	Formerly Used Defense Sites
GIS	Geographic Information System
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan
MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act
NAS	Naval Air Station
NAVFAC	Naval Facilities Engineering Command
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
NWSTF	Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility
O ₃	Ozone
ODEQ	Oregon Department of Environmental Quality
ODFW	Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
OPNAVINST	Chief of Naval Operations Instruction
OWRD	Oregon Water Resources Department
RNA	Research Natural Area
SAIA	Sikes Act Improvement Act
SECNAVINST	Secretary of the Navy Instruction
SO ₂	Sulfur Dioxide
SPCC	Spill Prevention Control and Countermeasures
T&E	Threatened and Endangered
TES	Threatened, Endangered and Sensitive
USC	United States Code
USFWS	United States Fish and Wildlife Service
USN	United States Navy
UXO	Unexploded Ordnance

CHAPTER 1

PURPOSE AND NEED FOR PROPOSED ACTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Naval Air Station (NAS) Whidbey Island proposes to adopt and implement an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) located in Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is a long-range strategic planning document that guides ecologically sound and cost-effective management of natural resources consistent with military land use of the installation.

The Proposed Action is to modify the previous INRMP for the NWSTF executed in 1999 (U.S. Navy 1999) and develop and implement a new INRMP consistent with current military use of the property. The updated INRMP was written from 2010 through 2012 in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act (SAIA) of 1997, as amended (U.S. Navy 2010). It will be approved by the NAS Whidbey Island Command, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW). The purpose of this Environmental Assessment (EA) is to analyze potential environmental impacts associated with each alternative and their effect on the quality of the human environment.

1.2 LOCATION AND DESCRIPTION OF NWSTF BOARDMAN

The NWSTF is a detachment activity of NAS Whidbey Island, Oak Harbor, Washington. The 47,400-acre NWSTF is located in northern Morrow County, eastern Oregon, approximately 3 miles south of the town of Boardman (Figure 1-1). Morrow County is located east of the Cascades in north-central Oregon and contains more than one million acres of gently rolling plains and broad plateaus south of the Columbia River. This fertile agricultural land can be roughly divided into three occupational zones—irrigated farming in the north; dry land wheat fields yielding to cattle ranches in the center; and timber products in the south.

The NWSTF is located within the transition zone of irrigated and dry land farming and is bordered to the north, east and part of the northwest by irrigated agricultural properties and to the south by dry land agricultural property. The installation is bordered to the west by land owned by Three Mile Farms; which, from the west central to southwest border, is undeveloped. This undeveloped 23,000-acre portion of the adjoining property is known as the Boardman Conservation Area and is managed by The Nature Conservancy (under a multiple species candidate conservation agreement with assurances between Three Mile Farms and the USFWS) as habitat for the Washington ground squirrel (state endangered/federal candidate for the Endangered Species Act) and multiple bird and plant species. The NWSTF and Boardman Conservation Area are one of the few remaining large, contiguous, undeveloped and native grassland and shrub steppe habitats in the Columbia Plateau. It is a significant native habitat resource on a regional landscape scale.

The NWSTF is rectangular measuring 12 by 6 miles as depicted in Figure 1-1. Infrastructure consists of three metal buildings, dirt roads, an office/trailer and utility services (e.g., telephone, water and electrical).

1.3 MILITARY MISSION

Military use of the NWSTF began in 1943 when the U.S. Army Air Corps obtained the land from the Bureau of Land Management and private landowners. The U.S. Army Air Corps and U.S. Air Force practiced aerial bombing and gunnery training until 1958 when it was transferred to the Navy for aerial bombing practice. Until 1996, the range was used regularly for bombing practice by naval aircraft from NAS Whidbey Island and gunnery practice for U.S. Air Force and Oregon Air National Guard aircraft using the strafing pit. After 1996 the range remained active, but was infrequently used by the Navy for bombing practice. Navy aircraft, as well as the Oregon National Guard and other Department of Defense agencies, continue to utilize the range area and restricted airspace for operational training.

The previous Air Force owned portions of the entire range is included in the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers inventory of Formerly Used Defense Sites (FUDS) under the title Boardman Air Force Range. Two potential ordnance sites have been located on land now belonging to non-military owners. This property is known or expected to contain military munitions and explosives of concern (i.e., unexploded ordnance).

1.4 PURPOSE AND NEED

The purpose and need of the proposed action is to comply with the SAIA of 1997, provide management requirements for species listed under the Endangered Species Act (ESA) and meet the requirements of the Department of Defense (DOD) and Navy instructions. The SAIA states that the primary purposes of a military conservation program are conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources, sustainable multipurpose use of those resources and public access to military lands subject to safety requirements and military security (16 USC.670a et seq.).

Moreover, the conservation program must be consistent with the mission-essential use of the installation and its lands and not cause a net loss of military land use. The SAIA requires the preparation of an INRMP to facilitate the conservation program. The INRMP must be cooperatively developed with the USFWS and appropriate state fish and game agency (ODFW). The resulting plan reflects the mutual agreement of these parties concerning conservation, protection, and management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. Finally, the SAIA requires that the INRMP be reviewed with the USFWS and ODFW annually, as to its operation and effect, and revised or resigned at least every 5 years.

The NWSTF INRMP implements an ecosystem-based conservation program that:

- Provides for conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources in a manner that is consistent with the military mission;
- Integrates and coordinates all natural resources management activities;
- Provides for sustainable, multipurpose uses of natural resources; and provides for public access of natural resources subject to safety and military security considerations. The management objectives are to integrate range management, fish and wildlife management and land management, as practicable and consistent with the military mission and established land uses.

Figure 1-1. NWSTF Boardman Vicinity Map

This EA documents the NWSTF's proposal to manage its natural resources under a revised INRMP by evaluating potential impacts on the human environment. The EA evaluates the Proposed Action and alternatives to the Proposed Action in accordance with NEPA, Navy regulations implementing NEPA and OPNAVINST 5090.1C. The EA was also developed to determine whether the action warrants preparation of an environmental impact statement (EIS) or supports a finding of no significant impact (FONSI).

1.5 SUMMARY OF KEY ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE REQUIREMENTS

1.5.1 National Environmental Policy Act

Chapter 5 of the Department of the Navy *Environmental and Natural Resources Program Manual* (OPNAVINST 5090.1c) states that the Navy must comply with all applicable federal, state, and local environmental laws and regulations, including NEPA. The intent of NEPA is to help decision makers make well-informed decisions based on an understanding of the potential environmental consequences and to take actions to protect, restore or enhance the environment.

The Act also established the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) which is charged with developing and implementing regulations and ensuring federal agency compliance with NEPA. The CEQ regulations mandate that all federal agencies use a prescribed, structured approach to environmental impact analysis. This approach also requires federal agencies to use an interdisciplinary and systematic approach in their decision-making process. This process evaluates potential environmental consequences associated with a Proposed Action and considers alternative courses of action.

The process for implementing NEPA is codified in 40 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) 1500-1508, *Regulations for Implementing the Procedural Provisions of the National Environmental Policy Act*. These regulations specify that an EA be prepared to briefly provide evidence and analysis for determining whether a FONSI or an EIS should be prepared. The EA can aid an agency's compliance with NEPA when an EIS is unnecessary and facilitates preparation of an EIS when one is required.

1.5.2 Other Key Environmental Compliance Requirements

The planning and decision-making process for federal agencies also involves all applicable environmental statutes and regulations. The NEPA process, however, does not replace procedural or substantive requirements of other environmental statutes and regulations. It addresses them collectively in the form of an EA or EIS, which enables the decision-maker to have a comprehensive view of major environmental issues and requirements associated with a Proposed Action. According to CEQ regulations, the requirements of NEPA must be integrated "with other planning and environmental review procedures required by law or by agency so that all such procedures run concurrently rather than consecutively" (CEQ 1978).

1.6 INTERAGENCY COORDINATION AND PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT

NEPA requirements promote the availability of environmental information to the public during the decision-making process and prior to actions being taken. The premise of NEPA is that the quality of federal decisions would be enhanced if proponents provide information to the public and involve the public in the planning process. The Intergovernmental

Cooperation Act, as amended (42 USC. 4231 et seq.) and Executive Order 12372, *Intergovernmental Review of Federal Programs*, require federal agencies to cooperate with and consider state and local views in implementing a federal proposal.

As part of the process, the Navy will notify federal, state and local agencies of the Proposed Action (Alternative 1) and will request input regarding environmental concerns they might have regarding the Proposed Action. Input from agency responses will be incorporated into the analysis of potential environmental impacts and included in Appendix A.

NEPA requirements also help ensure that environmental information is made available to the public during the decision making process and prior to actions being taken. The public involvement process augments the Navy opportunity to cooperate with and consider state and local views in implementing a federal proposal. In accordance with precedent in the Ninth Circuit, the draft EA will be made available for public comment and review prior to a FONSI being issued.

1.7 ORGANIZATION OF THE EA

The EA is organized into six sections:

Chapter 1 contains background information on NWSTF Boardman, a statement of the purpose of and need for the Proposed Action, a summary of applicable regulatory requirements, a discussion of agency coordination and public involvement, and an introduction to the organization of the EA.

Chapter 2 provides a detailed description of the Proposed Action and a discussion of the alternatives considered, including the No-Action Alternative; and a description of the decision to be made.

Chapter 3 contains a characterization of the affected environment, or baseline environmental conditions, and addresses potential environmental consequences associated with the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 and No-Action Alternative.

Chapter 4 provides an analysis of the potential cumulative impacts.

Chapter 5 presents a list of preparers and distribution list.

Chapter 6 lists the reference documents used in the preparation of the EA. In addition, various appendices that support these six sections of the EA and provide additional data and information will be included.

1.8 RESOURCE AREAS EXCLUDED FROM DETAILED ANALYSIS

In compliance with NEPA, CEQ guidelines, and 32 CFR Part 775, the evaluation of environmental impacts focuses on those resources and conditions potentially subject to impacts, and on potentially relevant environmental issues deserving of study, and deemphasizes irrelevant issues. Environmental resources that are unlikely to have impacts or impacts are negligible have been omitted from detailed analysis. Table 1-1 provides the basis for these exclusions.

Table 1-1. Issues Eliminated from Analysis

Issue Eliminated	Reason for Elimination
Geology and Soils	No impacts to geology and soils would occur as the result of the implementation of the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.
Noise	No modification or impacts to noise levels would occur as the result of the implementation of the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.
Airspace	No modification or impacts to the airspace would occur as a result of the implementation of the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 and No-Action Alternative as the alternatives are land-based.
Safety	No safety concerns are expected from the implementation of the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.
Utilities (including electricity, natural gas, water, sewer, solid waste)	No modification or impacts on infrastructure or utilities would occur as a result of the implementation of the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.
Transportation	Transportation users include enlisted personnel and various support staff and the general public is not permitted on NWSTF property. No traffic issues or effects on transportation systems would be anticipated under the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.
Hazardous materials/hazardous waste/installation restoration	The use of hazardous materials or generation of hazardous wastes is not anticipated under the Preferred Alternative (Alternative 1), Alternative 2 or No-Action Alternative.

CHAPTER 2

PROPOSED ACTION AND ALTERNATIVES

2.1 BACKGROUND

The revised INRMP replaces the previous INRMP executed in 1999 (U.S. Navy 1999). This plan satisfied the 1996 DOD requirements and involved appropriate state and federal agencies in the cooperative management of natural and outdoor recreation resources at the NWSTF.

Since 1996, some installation operations and land uses have changed. In addition, natural resource laws and DOD and Navy guidance and protocols have changed. The Washington ground squirrel has become a candidate species for federal listing as threatened or endangered since the 1999 INRMP. Protection of federally listed threatened and endangered species (T&E) is a high priority for Navy natural resource management.

The Sikes Act (16 USC 670 et seq.), amended by the SAIA in November 1997, requires the Secretary of Defense to carry out a program to provide for the conservation of natural resources on military installations. To facilitate this program, the SAIA states that all DOD facilities with natural resources will cooperate with USFWS and the appropriate state fish and wildlife agency to develop and implement an INRMP that provides sound management planning. The INRMP is to be reviewed annually and updated, or re-written or resigned, as circumstances dictate at least every 5 years. NWSTF Boardman's current INRMP was written and implemented in 1999. As mentioned in Section 1.1, the newly updated INRMP was written in collaboration with USFWS and ODFW and will be approved by all parties in 2012. The updated INRMP will be implemented upon completion of the EA process. Navy policy states that either an EA or an EIS will be prepared for the adoption and implementation of a revised INRMP.

The management objectives of the revised INRMP are to integrate range management, fish and wildlife management, and land management and outdoor recreation management. Special consideration is given to T&E species and their habitats and to the Bird Aircraft Strike Hazard management program. General management changes in the revised INRMP include:

- Initiate additional plant and wildlife surveys.
- Enhance natural resources management through best management practices (BMPs) as recommended in the INRMP.

2.2 PROPOSED ACTION

The proposed action is to adopt and implement an updated INRMP for the NWSTF in a manner that is consistent with the military use of the property to ensure a no net loss of military training capabilities and the goals and objectives established in the Sikes Act (as amended). The updated INRMP will be implemented in FY 2012 and remain in effect through FY 2016, with annual updates as needed. In FY 2017, the INRMP will be thoroughly reviewed for currency and effectiveness, and revised or resigned as necessary.

The goal of the updated INRMP is to implement an ecosystem-based conservation program that provides for conservation and rehabilitation of natural resources in a manner that is consistent with the military mission; integrates and coordinates all natural resources management activities; provides for sustainable, multipurpose uses of natural resources; and provides for public access for use of natural resources subject to safety and military security considerations. The management objectives are designed to integrate fish and wildlife management, land management and outdoor recreation management, as practicable and consistent with the military mission and established land uses.

In addition to meeting the purpose and need, the Proposed Action will have additional benefits that include: (1) better integration of the INRMP with other installation planning documents; (2) improved integration of the natural resources program with other NWSTF activities; (3) explicit goals and objectives under which ongoing and future natural resources projects will be implemented; and (4) a systematic approach to integrated natural resources management that documents present and future program implementation.

The NWSTF INRMP has developed management goals that are consistent with DOD, Navy and installation policies and guidance on how natural resources should be managed, sustained and rehabilitated where applicable. These goals are:

- **Goal 1.** Protect, conserve and manage the watersheds, wetlands, natural landscapes, soils, forests, fish and wildlife and other natural resources, as vital elements of a natural resources program.
- **Goal 2.** Protect threatened, endangered and sensitive (TES) species and critical habitats regulated by the ESA.
- **Goal 3.** Manage natural resources to provide outdoor recreation opportunities that are compatible with security, safety and operations.
- **Goal 4.** Use of and care for natural resources for the present and future needs of the U.S. and its people.
- **Goal 5.** Provide for the optimum use of land and water areas and access thereto while maintaining ecological integrity.
- **Goal 6.** Interact with the surrounding community to develop positive and productive community involvement, participation and educational opportunities.
- **Goal 7.** Increase awareness of natural resources issues, programs and responsibilities for sustaining those resources among the NWSTF employees.
- **Goal 8.** Integrate the NWSTF natural resources program with local, state and regional environmental programs and initiatives to the maximum extent practicable.
- **Goal 9.** Augment management of natural resources on the NWSTF through the installation of a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) database.

Significant changes from the 1999 INRMP include:

1. Agricultural outleases for both ranching (cattle and sheep) and croplands were halted in 2002 and have not occurred since. Livestock have been removed from the NWSTF and the removal has altered the existing land conditions and major land use. Under

the land use management recommendations of the 1999 INRMP, all grazing management recommendations are obsolete as grazing no longer occurs on the NWSTF.

2. Additional recommendations for natural resources management issues have been identified since the 1999 INRMP. There are new recommendations based on current issues, such as protection of the Washington ground squirrel. Additionally, the updated INRMP has prioritized the recommendations (high, medium and low) and proposes a schedule for implementation. The updated INRMP uses the Navy's Environmental Readiness Level (ERL) system to assess priority levels for recommended actions. ERL is also used for prioritizing funding, linking implementation need with funding need. For this analysis, ERL 4 equates to a high priority level, ERL 3 to a medium priority level and ERL 2 to a low priority level. It is expected that NWSTF Boardman will seek funding through NAS Whidbey Island and implement the high priority recommendations first, then the medium priority recommendations and finally the low priority recommendations. The recommendations are listed in Table 2.1.

Table 2-1. INRMP Recommendations

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
Vegetation Management			
V-1: Monitor and control noxious weeds and invasive, non-native plants. Primary efforts of control will consist of herbicide spraying spot applied directly to plants, not broadcast from trucks or from the air. Secondary control is with manual and/or mechanical removal.	4	\$125,000 (\$25,000 each year)	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016
V-2: Count, measure, re-tag and map all junipers. Junipers provide important habitat for nesting birds and shade habitat for other species. Mapping and tagging of junipers occurred previously. An inspection in 2006 found new, unmapped recruitment and dead, tagged trees. On the ground field mapping of the junipers will help identify area expansion/reduction trends (when compared to the last mapping effort) and provide data as to the health of the trees.	3	\$6,000 and in-house labor	FY 2012

Table 2-1. INRMP Recommendations

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
<p>V-3: Use high-resolution aerial photography to map all vegetation; produce GIS-based vegetation map. The last vegetation map was produced at least ten years ago. Since then, grazing leases have been terminated, resulting in a change in vegetation. Wildfires have also swept parts of the range. A new mapping effort is required to identify and quantify the changes, to provide data for management purposes. The cost reflects the acquisition of imagery, ground truthing, and the production of a GIS data set for maps.</p>	4	\$70,000	FY 2014
<p>V-4: Recover monumented vegetation plots and resurvey vegetation using established protocol; produce GIS data layers for inclusion into Boardman GIS maps. Oregon State University established vegetation survey plots in the 1980s. These plots have been marked with monuments for recovery. This project will use the original methods to resurvey the plots. This will provide 1) ground truthing for V-3 above; 2) trend analysis for vegetation change due to the termination of grazing and to wildfire impacts; and 3) permanent locations to measure future vegetation change or stability.</p>	4	\$60,000 (\$20,000 each year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016
<p>V-5: Monitor previously burned areas for vegetation recovery. Conduct pedestrian surveys through the previous wildfire areas and assess natural vegetation recovery. Areas that are not recovering naturally back to the desired pre-fire habitat types will be assessed for restoration success and priority ranked for potential restoration measures to be implemented in project V-6 below.</p>	3	In-house labor	FY 2012, 2013
<p>V-6: Restore native vegetation. Areas previously impacted by Navy mission, land management activities, or wildfire will be treated to re-establish native plant communities. This will not apply to areas encumbered by unexploded ordnance (UXO).</p>	3	\$260,000 (\$130,000 each year)	FY 2014, 2016
<p>V-7: Move Resource Natural Area (RNA)-A. NWSTF Boardman will coordinate with The Nature Conservancy to move RNA-A from the main target and identify the specific boundaries of a new location that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect. New fencing to surround the new location will need to be installed.</p>	2	\$15,000	FY 2013

Table 2-1. INRMP Recommendations

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
V-8: Map noxious weeds. Perform an installation-wide mapping of noxious weeds/invasive plant species following the protocols used in the 1997 survey. This includes creating a GIS map layer to prioritize control.	3	\$30,000	FY 2014
Wildlife			
WL-1: Conduct large mammal surveys. Pronghorn antelope have recently moved onto the range and may be permanent or semi-permanent residents. Rocky Mountain elk may also occasionally use the installation. Mule deer inhabit the range but the extent of the herd is unknown. Conduct surveys to identify the extent of the herds and to help identify impacts to range vegetation and provide data for herd management.	2	\$12,500 for equipment (\$2,500 for two surveys each year) and in-house labor	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016
WL-2: Conduct Washington ground squirrel surveys. Washington ground squirrels are a state protected species (in addition to a candidate federal species). Military training can impact the ground squirrel population on the installation. Burrow and population estimate data is available from past surveys, but new data is required to assess changes or stability due to 1) termination of grazing and resulting changes in vegetation, 2) recent fires, and 3) new mission requirements.	4	\$80,000 (\$20,000 per year)	FY 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016
WL-3: Conduct burrowing owl surveys and monitoring. Burrowing owls nest in excavations in the ground and thus are susceptible to disturbance or injury from vehicles and/or training. New data is needed to identify habitat use areas for management and military training decisions, to track population trends, and to evaluate and/or alter NR enhancement actions.	2	\$30,000 (\$10,000 per year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016
WL-4: Conduct long-billed curlew surveys and monitoring. Curlews nest on the ground in open grassland areas and thus are susceptible to disturbance or injury from vehicles and/or training. New data is needed to identify current habitat use areas for management and military training decisions, to track population trends, and to evaluate and/or alter NR enhancement actions.	4	\$45,000 (\$15,000 per year)	FY 2012, 2014, 2016

Table 2-1. INRMP Recommendations

Project Recommendations	ERL	Estimated Cost	Implementation Year
Fire Management			
FM-1: Analyze and relocate fire breaks. Develop a comprehensive assessment of firebreaks for the installation. Include the results of firebreak success from the 2008 fire and alternative techniques such as “green stripping” with herbicide or fire resistant vegetation.	3	\$20,000	FY 2013
FM-2: Map and assess annual wildfires. Annually, as needed, map all wildfire perimeters and assess natural resource damage from the event to be used for future monitoring needs and restoration prioritization.	3	In-house labor	FY 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016

2.3 ALTERNATIVES

2.3.1 Alternative 1 (Preferred Alternative)

Alternative 1 (the Preferred Alternative) is to adopt and implement all objectives and recommendations (described in Table 2-1) of the revised INRMP. The implementation of all objectives and recommendations would effectively manage natural resources at the NWSTF and would include wildlife and habitat surveys that would assist in future project planning and development with benefits to all wildlife species regardless of listed or protected status.

2.3.2 Alternative 2

Alternative 2 is to adopt and implement only the high and medium priority (ERL 4 and 3) objectives and recommendations (described in Table 2-1) of the revised INRMP. The implementation of only the high and medium priority objectives and recommendations would maintain the current natural resources management conditions at the NWSTF, but would focus primarily on regulatory driven resources under the ESA and Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA) requirements.

2.3.3 No-Action Alternative

The No-Action Alternative continues implementation of the objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP completed in 1999. On-going practices used for natural resources management at NWSTF Boardman would continue. Many of the management practices of the 1999 INRMP are the same as the revised INRMP, but lacks emphasis on increasing wildlife habitat, threatened and endangered species protection and range management thus not meeting the purpose and need to meet statutory requirements imposed by the SAIA, provide management requirements for flora and fauna species of concern and meet the requirements of DOD and USN instructions.

CHAPTER 3

AFFECTED ENVIRONMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES

The baseline for this environmental analysis is the current conditions at NWSTF Boardman and management methods of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman property under the 1999 INRMP (U.S. Navy).

3.1 LAND USE

3.1.1 Affected Environment

The 47,400-acre NWSTF Boardman is located in northern Morrow County approximately 3 miles south of the town of Boardman (Figure 1-1). Morrow County is located on the Columbia Plateau east of the Cascades in north-central Oregon, which contains more than one million acres of gently rolling plains and broad plateaus. This rich agricultural land can be roughly divided into three occupational zones—irrigation farming in the north; vast fields of dry land wheat yielding to cattle ranches in the center; and timber products in the south. The NWSTF land area is rectangular, with a size of 12 by 6 miles. The installation consists of two target spotting towers, a headquarters compound consisting of several buildings that house offices and workshops, several wells and water pipelines, gravel and dirt roads. The northern two-thirds of the facility gently rises in broad, flat alluvial terraces from approximately 400 feet in elevation to approximately 700 feet (U.S. Navy, 1999). The southern one-third of the facility consists of rolling hills and varies in elevation from 700 to 950 feet. Several canyons provide topographic relief. The range has been in use as a military training area since 1941. Navy aircraft, as well as the Oregon National Guard and other Department of Defense agencies, utilize the range area for operational training.

The NWSTF is largely surrounded by areas developed for various agricultural uses and remains essentially undeveloped and has one of the largest stands of Columbia Basin shrub steppe habitat in Oregon. Range vegetation consists of desert shrubs, such as sagebrush and antelope bitterbrush, and grasses, such as bluebunch wheatgrass. In former grazing and agricultural areas, cheatgrass is prominent.

Prior to 2002, agricultural outleases for grazing covered approximately 42,000 of the 47,400 acres of the NWSTF. An additional 240 acres were leased as agricultural cropland parcels. In 2002, all agricultural outlease agreements on the property were terminated. In the years that have passed, the areas once utilized for agricultural outleases have changed significantly. Without the disturbance of cattle, sheep, and agriculture, both native and invasive vegetation, has taken over these sites. Many of these areas contain a high density of exotic and invasive species.

Currently, NWSTF land is used as a military training/operations area.

3.1.2 Environmental Consequences

The implementation of Alternatives 1 or 2 would have a positive impact on land condition at the NWSTF. Under Alternative 1, land formerly managed under agricultural leases would be managed for native species, providing an additional positive impact by restoring the vegetation native conditions therefore providing habitat and food resources for native

wildlife species. All updated INRMP recommendations maintain current management processes in regards to land use. Environmentally sensitive areas are protected from livestock grazing, as this practice is no longer recommended in the revised INRMP. Under Alternative 2, large mammal and burrowing owl surveys would not be conducted as management would be focused on regulatory ESA and MBTA requirements. Surveys provide baseline data to assist in the development of management surveys as well as identify and protect breeding and foraging habitat. No new construction is planned as part of either Alternative 1 or 2.

The updated INRMP contains recommendations that address current issues at the NWSTF, including Washington ground squirrel and burrowing owl habitat, vegetation, and fire management. These recommendations provide a comprehensive look at the NWSTF's natural resources and their relationship to land use practices on the property, giving natural resource managers the tools to effectively manage Navy natural resources.

The No-Action Alternative would have a negative effect on land use because the outdated INRMP (approved in 1999) recommendations would remain the only land use management tool for natural resources. The 1999 INRMP is based on a joint land use of agricultural and military training/operations; however, because grazing no longer occurs at the NWSTF, grazing recommendations are not applicable. By not implementing the updated INRMP, the Navy will not establish updated management recommendations for land use, therefore not meeting the purpose and need to meet statutory requirements imposed by the SAIA, provide management requirements for flora and fauna species of concern and meet the requirements of DOD and USN instructions.

3.2 AIR QUALITY

3.2.1 Affected Environment

The six criteria pollutants identified by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) are: sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide, ozone (O₃), lead, and particulate matter less than 10 microns in diameter (PM₁₀), and particulate matter less than 2.5 microns in diameter (PM_{2.5}). The proposed action air basin is considered to be an air quality attainment area of the National Ambient Air Quality Standards for all criteria pollutants; therefore, a General Conformity Determination is not required. The area is regulated by the EPA, the Oregon Department of Environmental Quality (ODEQ) and the Oregon Department of Agriculture. NWSTF Boardman does not have stationary emission sources as defined in the regulations. No air pollution sources are located on the range itself.

3.2.2 Environmental Consequences

Neither of the action alternatives would have an effect on air quality. None of the recommendations in the updated INRMP involve any actions relating to an alteration in air quality in relation to the six criteria pollutants. The proposed land management and post fire restoration actions (i.e., alternative techniques such as "green stripping" with herbicide) should have a beneficial effect on fugitive dust and blowing sand that occurs after wildfires or any vegetation removal on the range.

The No-Action Alternative would have no effect on air quality as none of the management strategies under the 1999 INRMP related to air quality in relation to the six criteria pollutants due to the lack of stationary emission sources at NWSTF Boardman. There would be no improvement in fugitive dust and blowing sand as the 1999 INRMP has no recommended post fire and general land restoration actions.

3.3 WATER RESOURCES

3.3.1 Affected Environment

Water resources on NWSTF Boardman are predominantly human-made, with several water wells that historically were used for drinking water or livestock watering. Operable water wells occur at four locations, and are utilized to provide firefighting water to the range. Exposed risers (capped, above-ground extensions of the waterline system) occur intermittently along the waterlines. In the past, one of the risers fed a small depression in Juniper Canyon (Toad Pond) for six to eight weeks during April and May.

Two ephemeral ponds excavated for past livestock use capture seasonal rainwater and are located at the head of Well Springs Canyon and east of Juniper Canyon (Oregon Trail Pond). These ponds also provide seasonal water for wildlife. The only natural water occurs as rainfall runoff creating intermittent ponding in Juniper and Well Springs canyons. In some years the flow is sufficient enough to leave behind pools of standing water. Other than shallow depressions that may contain seasonal precipitation, no surface water exists on the facility (see Figure 3-1). The Columbia River is approximately 2 miles north of the range, and in an arid climate with little runoff and porous soil, this water supply is too distant to be affected by stormwater runoff. There are no industrial wastewater discharges at the range.

Groundwater

Groundwater quality has been a concern in the NWSTF region in recent years, particularly for nitrates, explosives compounds and perchlorate. The range facility, including administrative offices, uses bottled water as its potable water source. An on-site well supplied drinking water to the range facility until the mid-1990s, but drinking water use was discontinued when nitrates exceeded the 10-milligram-per-liter (mg/L) state drinking water standard. The well is still used for non-potable purposes (e.g., fire protection). Documentation of groundwater sampling and analysis for this well is available in NAS Whidbey Island Environmental Division files.

The Lower Umatilla Basin Groundwater Management Area was established in 1990 because elevated nitrate levels (above the 7 mg/L trigger) were detected in many wells within a 352,000-acre portion of Umatilla and Morrow Counties. The Columbia River basalt aquifer, which underlies the installation, is a confined aquifer. The Oregon Water Resources Department (OWRD) has designated a large Critical Groundwater Area just east of the range's eastern boundary and a Classified Groundwater Area just south of the range's southern boundary (OWRD 2009). Additional groundwater pumping in a Classified Groundwater Area is restricted to a few designated uses (OWRD 2003). A Critical Groundwater Area is one where pumping of groundwater exceeds the long-term natural replenishment of the underground water reservoir. This legal designation is designed to prevent excessive declines in ground water levels.

ODEQ has had a groundwater sampling program in this area of the Lower Umatilla Basin for a number of years, monitoring nitrate levels in the area groundwater. It is believed that agricultural practices (e.g., fertilizer use) cause the elevated nitrate concentrations. In June 2003, ODEQ performed a round of sampling at three wells on Port of Morrow property just north, and down gradient, of NWSTF Boardman's northern boundary. The samples were analyzed for nitrates and explosive compounds. Results for explosive compounds were below detection levels in all three wells, with one exception; a single detection of 10 parts per billion 1, 3-dinitrobenzene was reported in one well. However, because the compound was also detected in the associated method blank, and the detection could have been a false positive, the result was categorized as inconclusive by ODEQ.

In September 2003, ODEQ performed groundwater sampling at 133 wells in the vicinity of NWSTF Boardman. Perchlorate was detected in just over half of the wells, distributed among irrigation wells, monitoring wells and private drinking water wells. ODEQ and the Navy have been corresponding and meeting about the ODEQ sampling program since May of 2002. Although the Navy acknowledges the possibility that some undocumented use of perchlorate-based munitions may have occurred in the past, to date, the Navy is not part of the ODEQ sampling program due to a lack of documented evidence of the use of such munitions at the range.

The most recent groundwater sampling effort occurred June 2010 (USN 2011). Two new monitoring wells, plus seven monitoring wells installed in 2005, and one historical well were sampled for explosive compounds, nitroguanidine, perchlorate, nitrate, nitrite, chloride, sulfate, and bicarbonate alkalinity. Positive detections are summarized in the following bullets:

- Perchlorate was detected in all monitoring wells, except for Border Well (BW)-3, Open Burn/Open Detonation (OB/OD)-1, and the Demo Area Well. Concentrations ranged from 0.68 micrograms per liter ($\mu\text{g/L}$) at OB/OD-2 to 4.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ at BW-5. All detected concentrations for perchlorate were below the screening concentration value of 15 $\mu\text{g/L}$.
- Explosive compounds were detected at monitoring well BW-5. Nitroglycerin was detected at a concentration of 0.690 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (method detection limit [MDL] - 0.15 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and octahydro-1,3,5,7-tetranitro-1,3,5,7-tetrazocine was detected at a concentration of 0.059 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (MDL - 0.027 $\mu\text{g/L}$). BW-5 is in the northeast corner of the range and distant from all range related activities.
- All four anions were detected at virtually all the monitoring wells. The only exception was that nitrate-nitrite was not detected at monitoring well BW-3. At the nine monitoring wells where nitrate-nitrite was detected, the concentrations ranged from 0.065 mg/L at OB/OD-1 to 54.20 mg/L at BW-4.

3.3.2 Environmental Consequences

No impacts to groundwater, drinking water or wastewater are anticipated from either action alternative due to the lack of discharge possibilities and proximity to surface water sources.

Both the Preferred Alternative and Alternative 2 would have no effect on water quality or resources as none of the recommendations of the updated INRMP involve any alteration to management of water resources.

The No-Action Alternative would have no effect on water quality or water resources as none of the management strategies under the 1999 INRMP addressed water quality at the NWSTF due to the lack of permanent surface water, no use of groundwater except in limited circumstances, and no wastewater discharge sources on site.

3.4 TERRESTRIAL BIOLOGY

3.4.1 Affected Environment

Cooperative Agreement

A Cooperative Agreement was signed in September 1998 between the U.S. Navy, USFWS and ODFW. The purpose of the Agreement was to “provide a framework for the USFWS and ODFW to assist NWSTF in the coordination, development, and implementation of a Cooperative Plan for natural resources management.” The Agreement opened discussions and built relationships between state and federal agencies allowing for a more collaboration and effective management of the NWSTF natural resources and land use, especially TES species.

Flora

Vegetation on the NWSTF is described broadly as shrub-steppe. Shrub-steppe is the largest natural grassland in North America, extending from southeastern Washington and eastern Oregon, through Idaho, Nevada, and Utah, and into western Wyoming and Colorado. Shrub refers to the most abundant plant species that grows in this ecoregion. "Steppe" is a Russian word that means a vast treeless plain. In the Mid-Columbia Basin, shrub-steppe winters are cold and wet with strong winds and blowing snow. Summers are hot and dry with temperatures that can reach above 100 degrees Fahrenheit during the day and cool at night. The dominant shrubs include sagebrush (*Artemisia spp.*), spiny hopsage, bitterbrush (*Purshia tridentata*), rabbitbrush (*Crysothamnus spp.*), black greasewood, western juniper and threetip sagebrush. Native grasses are mostly large bunchgrasses. Vegetation also includes flowering forbs. However, large portions of nearly all of these native species on the NWSTF are heavily encroached with cheatgrass, an invasive annual grass species. Other invasive species on NWSTF property include Russian thistle, tumbled mustard, and whitlow-grass. There are also some largely unvegetated sand dune and “alkali” areas on the NWSTF.

In 2003 and 2004, field surveys of NWSTF Boardman were conducted to update information on all special status plant species to meet preservation requirements under the ESA and management techniques of the SAIA. Table 3-1 summarizes the results of this rare plant study. This survey also mapped out the NWSTF in terms of habitat quality for plant species.

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Table 3-1. Results of the Rare Plant Survey Conducted by the Navy in 2003-2004

Species Name	Common Name	Number of plants identified
<i>Astragalus sclerocarpus</i>	Dalles milkvetch	520
<i>Astragalus succumbens</i>	Crouching milkvetch	477
<i>A. sclerocarpus</i> & <i>A. succumbens</i>	Both of the above together	58
<i>Astragalus caricinus</i>	Buckwheat milkvetch	2
<i>Hymenopappus filifolius filifolius</i>	Columbia Cut-Leaf	5
Total Number of Rare Plants Identified		1062

Habitat conditions were evaluated with values of Low to High based on concentrations of exotic plant species versus concentrations of native plant species. Figure 3-2 portrays the results based on the following criteria:

- L Low – Area entirely comprised of exotic species
- ML Medium Low – Exotic species dominate with native plant species evident
- M Medium – Area a mix of native plant species and exotic species
- MH Medium High – Native species dominate but few exotic species present
- H High – A full component of native grasses with no exotic species present.

Wildfires are an irregular event during the hot, dry summer months and much of the vegetative structure on the facility is a result of pattern burns by wildfires. Wildfires are a natural event that in many ways can cause long-term improvements to the vegetative community by controlling invasive vegetation and reducing fuel loading. However, large uncontrolled wildfires can disrupt management strategies completely alter the vegetation stand for many years and sometime permanently unless intensive restoration actions are implemented. Since the 1999 INRMP was developed, three large wildfires and several smaller ones have burned much of the NWSTF (except for the northwest corner) and altered vegetative conditions.

Three Research Natural Areas (RNAs) exist on NWSTF Boardman (Figure 3-1). The RNAs are part of a federal government system established for research and educational purposes. Natural features are preserved for scientific purposes and natural processes are allowed to dominate. The objectives of the RNAs are to serve as baseline areas against which effects of human activities can be measured; sites for study of natural processes in undisturbed ecosystems; and as gene pool preserves of organisms, especially rare and endangered types.

Fauna

NWSTF Boardman supports an exceptional number of wildlife species. At least 81 species of birds, 21 mammals, 6 reptiles and 1 amphibian have been recorded on the facility by investigating biologists. Of these, 33 species of birds, 19 mammals, 6 reptiles and 1 amphibian are known to breed at the NWSTF. Table 3-2 shows these species, separated into the above groupings.

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The only amphibian on the NWSTF is the Great Basin spadefoot toad, which is a unique amphibian that is adapted to arid deserts and shrub-steppe habitat. No other amphibians have been recorded, or are expected to occur on the facility due to a lack of surface water sources. In the past, a small depression in Juniper Canyon (Toad Pond) was watered for six to eight weeks during April and May, forming a small seasonal breeding habitat for spadefoot toads. Three lizards and three snakes have been verified as occurring on the NWSTF.

At least 21 species of mammals occur on the facility, 18 of which are expected to breed and occur year-round. Presently, pronghorn antelope are increasing in numbers in south Morrow County and some of these animals may have moved to northern Morrow County. Pronghorn are now spotted with some regularity on the NWSTF, and there may be 2 distinct herds, with a total of approximately 30 animals.

Since 1979, at least 81 species of birds have been recorded on the facility, 33 of which nest there. Bird species listed in Table 3-2 (except for the European starling and house sparrow) are protected under the Migratory Bird Treaty Act. Sagebrush habitats support the highest number of species (54) and confirmed breeders (21) followed by annual grass/forb (35/8), bitterbrush (33/9), and juniper habitats (27/9). Sagebrush, bitterbrush, and juniper habitats exhibit high structural diversity and, consequently, more niches for different bird species. In general, species diversity was highest in the shrub habitats, while densities of breeding birds were highest in the grassland habitats (Holmes and Geupel 1998). Four species alone (western meadowlark, grasshopper sparrow, horned lark, and long-billed curlew) comprised over 98 percent of the breeding pairs found in grassland and open low shrub (rabbitbrush) habitats (Holmes and Geupel 1998).

Table 3-2. Wildlife Species Present at NWSTF Boardman

Amphibian		
Great Basin Spadefoot Toad		
Reptiles		
Short-horned Lizard	Side-blotched Lizard	Racer
Northern Sagebrush Lizard	Gopher Snake	Western Rattlesnake
Mammals		
Vagrant Shrew	Western Harvest Mouse	Red Fox
Black-Tailed Jackrabbit	Deer Mouse	Coyote
Nuttall's Cottontail	Northern Grasshopper Mouse	Long-Tailed Weasel
Washington Ground Squirrel	Sagebrush Vole	Badger
Northern Pocket Gopher	Montana Vole	Rocky Mountain Elk
Great Basin Pocket Mouse	House Mouse	Mule Deer
Ord's Kangaroo Rat	Porcupine	Pronghorn Antelope
Birds		
American Crow	European Starling	Red-tailed Hawk
American Goldfinch	Ferruginous Hawk	Red-winged Blackbird
American Kestrel	Fox Sparrow	Ring-billed Gull
American Robin	Golden-crowned Kinglet	Ring-necked Pheasant
Barn Owl	Golden Eagle	Rock Wren

Table 3-2. Wildlife Species Present at NWSTF Boardman

Birds (continued)		
Barn Swallow	Gray Flycatcher	Rough-legged Hawk
Black-billed Magpie	Gray Partridge	Sage Sparrow
Brown-headed cowbird	Grasshopper Sparrow	Sage Thrasher
Brewer's Blackbird	Horned Lark	Say's Phoebe
Brewer's Sparrow	House Sparrow	Savannah Sparrow
Black-crowned Night Heron	Killdeer	Sharp-shinned Hawk
Black-Throated Sparrow	Lark Sparrow	Short-eared Owl
Blue-Winged Teal	Lewis' Woodpecker	Spotted Sandpiper
Bullock's Oriole	Loggerhead Shrike	Spotted Towhee
Burrowing Owl	Long-billed Curlew	Swainson's Hawk
California Gull	Long-eared Owl	Townsend's Solitaire
California Quail	Macgillivray's Warbler	Turkey Vulture
Caspian Tern	Mallard	Upland Sandpiper
Chipping Sparrow	Merlin	Vesper Sparrow
Chukar	Mountain Bluebird	Violet-green Swallow
Cliff Swallow	Mourning Dove	Western Kingbird
Common Nighthawk	Northern Flicker	Western Meadowlark
Common Poorwill	Northern Harrier	Western Sandpiper
Common Raven	Northern Pintail	Wilson's Warbler
Cooper's Hawk	Northern Rough-winged	White-crowned Sparrow
Dark-Eyed Junco	Orange-crowned Warbler	Western Tanager
Eastern Kingbird	Prairie Falcon	Yellow-headed Blackbird

3.4.2 Environmental Consequences

Flora

Alternatives 1 and 2 would have a beneficial impact on terrestrial flora. Overall, the updated INRMP recommendations protect flora on the NWSTF by increasing awareness of species present and implementing new projects to gain additional knowledge about the vegetation that exists, such as junipers and comprehensive vegetation mapping. Additionally, management strategies are provided for invasive species and noxious weed control. The revised INRMP recommendations also include additional goals for fire management and post wildfire restoration actions on the property, which would benefit the flora.

The No-Action Alternative would maintain existing conditions for flora at the NWSTF as there would be no change from the outdated vegetation management strategies under the 1999 INRMP, which focused on largely agricultural land use and vegetation management for that land use regime. Since no additional measures for post-wildfire restoration would be implemented, this alternative would have a negative impact on flora.

Fauna

Recommendations in Alternative 1 of the updated INRMP would have a positive effect on wildlife species by decreasing invasive species and increasing knowledge of their occurrence through surveys. The updated INRMP includes measures for conservation and protection of natural resources including the following: conduct Washington ground squirrel surveys; analyze and relocate firebreaks; conduct large mammal surveys; and conduct burrowing owl and long-billed curlew surveys and monitoring.

Alternative 2 would have a beneficial impact on wildlife at the NWSTF as the medium and high priority projects and recommendations of the revised INRMP would be implemented. The updated INRMP contains recommendations that include additional surveys for important fauna in order to better supplement management of these species on the property. This would have a positive impact on the ESA and MBTA protected species.

By not implementing the revised INRMP, the No-Action Alternative would maintain existing conditions for fauna at the NWSTF. There would be no change from the outdated management strategies under the 1999 INRMP, which focused on agricultural land use and species management for that land use.

3.5 THREATENED AND ENDANGERED SPECIES

3.5.1 Affected Environment

There are no federally listed T&E species that are documented to occur on the NWSTF. Table 3-3 provides a list of threatened, endangered, candidate and species of concern that are found or potentially found on the NWSTF. The Washington ground squirrel (*Spermophilis washingtoni*) is a federal candidate species, meaning that the USFWS is evaluating whether it should be federally listed as a threatened or endangered species. The Washington ground squirrel inhabits the arid sagebrush and grassland regions of the Oregon and Washington Columbia Plateau. Presently, the largest collection of Washington ground squirrel colonies occurs at NWSTF Boardman (Quade 1994), where it has become a focal species in recent years because of its candidate species status. Results of recent studies indicate the following: (1) Washington ground squirrel populations have rebounded at NWSTF Boardman after an apparent decline in the 1980s and early 1990s (probably due to drought conditions during those years); and (2) the facility supports the majority of Oregon's remaining populations of this squirrel species.

There are no wetlands on the property and the surface water streams on the property are seasonal. No critical habitat for threatened and endangered species has been designated at the NWSTF.

There are no federally listed threatened or endangered species of plants, lichen or fungi occurring on the NWSTF. The only rare plant with federal status occurring in the Columbia River Basin portion of Morrow County that could occur on the range is Laurence's milk-vetch (*Astragalus collinus var. laurentii*), a federal species of concern. However, a rare plant survey conducted by the Navy in 2003 and 2004 found no specimens of this species.

Table 3-3. Threatened, Endangered, Candidate, and Species of Concern

Species	Status	
	Federal	State of Oregon
<i>Fauna</i>		
Peregrine Falcon ¹	--	Endangered
Northern Sagebrush Lizard	Species of Concern	Sensitive - Vulnerable
Ferruginous Hawk	Species of Concern	Sensitive - Critical
Swainson's Hawk	--	Sensitive - Vulnerable
Upland Sandpiper	Species of Concern	Sensitive - Critical
Long-billed Curlew	--	Sensitive - Vulnerable
Burrowing Owl	Species of Concern	Sensitive - Critical
Loggerhead Shrike	--	Sensitive - Vulnerable
Black-throated Sparrow	--	Sensitive - Peripheral
Sage Sparrow	--	Sensitive - Critical
Grasshopper Sparrow	--	Sensitive - Vulnerable
Washington Ground Squirrel	Candidate for Listing	Endangered
<i>Flora</i>		
Laurence's Milk-vetch ¹ (<i>Astragalus collinus</i> var. <i>laurentii</i>)	Species of Concern	Threatened

¹Potentially occurring at NWSTF Boardman.

3.5.2 Environmental Consequences

Alternatives 1 and 2 and the No-Action Alternative would have no impacts on threatened and endangered species as there are no listed species that inhabit the NWSTF, nor is there any critical habitat. Alternatives 1 and 2 would have a beneficial impact to candidate species and other species of concern by decreasing invasive species and conducting surveys of current populations and habitats, providing additional data to resource managers to effectively implement updated management strategies.

The No-Action Alternative would maintain existing conditions for candidate species and other species of concern. Although it provides management requirements for flora and fauna species of concern, the No-Action Alternative does not meet statutory requirements imposed by the SAIA or requirements of DOD and USN instructions.

3.6 CULTURAL RESOURCES

3.6.1 Affected Environment

Early Americans inhabited the central Columbia River basin since at least the last of the great Bretz floods 12,000 years ago (Allen et al. 1986), but little is known of the history of these people before the first European explorers arrived in the early 1800s. By this time, distinct tribes and territorial boundaries had become fully established. In 1850, the present day

location of the NWSTF fell fully within the Umatilla Tribe territory, although the Cayuse claimed land to within a very few miles of the eastern boundary of the facility (Ray 1936, 1938). Well Springs played an important role in the history of the Oregon Trail as it was the only significant source of water in the nearly 30-mile stretch between Butter and Willow creeks. Emigrants crossing this stretch in the 1840s and 1850s described the land as a barren, sandy desert and one of the worst stretches encountered during the entire journey, probably owing to the fact most wagon trains passed during the dry late summer and early fall (French 1971).

Well Springs is actually a collection of three springs. Two of the springs are a quarter mile apart and are located on the main trail. Together they are called Upper Well Spring. These two springs are bisected by the southern boundary of the facility. The third spring, Tub Spring, was originally called Lower Well Spring and is located in Juniper Canyon on the Lower Well Springs Diversion of the Oregon Trail approximately three miles north of Upper Well Spring (Lewarch et al. 1997; see Figure 3-1). The Oregon Trail ruts leading to and from these springs are clearly visible today.

Homesteading on the facility began in the 1880s when George Swaggart established a 160-acre homestead at Tub Springs. The extent to which Swaggart developed this site is unknown, although historical records show that one of his children was born at Tub Springs in 1888. Swaggart eventually lost the property in a mortgage foreclosure, when John S. Kilkenny and James Carty purchased it in a sheriff's sale in 1898. In 1900, Carty bought out Kilkenny and moved his family from Sand Hollow to Tub Springs. It is reported that Carty built a house, barn, and sheep shed at Tub Spring, although structures from the Swaggart settlement were probably still present. Carty lived at this site until about 1940 when the military acquired the land from his son (who purchased that land from his father in 1936) and demolished the buildings. Another house was built at Well Springs in the 1910s by John Harbke. This house was continuously used until it too was acquired by the military and removed in 1940. Traces of a third home site can be found in Juniper Canyon approximately two miles south of Tub Spring; however, its history is unknown. Several temporary sheep camps also occupied various locations on the facility in the late 1800s and early 1900s.

There are multiple archaeological and cultural sites present on NWSTF Boardman. The Well Spring Segment of the Oregon Trail (containing Upper Well Spring) was listed on the National Register for Historic Places (NRHP) in 1978. Additionally, there are archaeological sites at Tub Spring, the Juniper Canyon site (the "Mounds"), and the Jim Carty Homestead site. Evidence of temporary sheep camps can be found throughout the facility. There are also various remains (towers, bunkers, bomb craters, etc.) from past military activity. Also, Native American cultural sites may occur. However, a thorough facility-wide cultural resource investigation has not been conducted.

3.6.2 Environmental Consequences

Adopting the updated INRMP as a management tool under Alternatives 1 or 2 is not an undertaking under the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) that will have an adverse effect on historic properties because it does not designate any specific tasks at specific locations that can be evaluated or consulted for impacts. Thus, SHPO consultation for the adoption of the INRMP is not required.

However, some of the management techniques that are proposed within the Alternatives may affect historic properties if they are implemented. Any technique that is invasive of soils or may cause erosion (such as manual or mechanical vegetation removal, creating new fire breaks, etc.) has the potential to adversely affect historic properties. If and when decisions are made to use these invasive techniques, and locations are defined, then cultural resource assessments and SHPO and tribal consultations may be required under section 106 of the NHPA.

All alternatives will comply with the requirements of NHPA and if needed, proposed management actions would be modified to avoid affects to historic resources. No affect is anticipated to historic resources from any of the alternatives.

3.7 SOCIOECONOMICS AND ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

3.7.1 Affected Environment

The NWSTF is located in Morrow County, Oregon, in census tract 9701, an area that includes the towns of Boardman and Irrigon and the land area south and west of Boardman that encompasses the NWSTF. The U.S. Census data from the year 2000 lists this census tract population at 7,597 people. Of this total, 61.8% (4,698 people) classify themselves as Caucasian and 34% (2,586 people) classify themselves as Hispanic or Latino. The poverty level of Census Tract 9701 is 13.3% of families and 17.3% for individuals. The median household income is \$36,845.00. No residences exist on the NWSTF property.

3.7.2 Environmental Consequences

The implementation of either action alternative will not have a disproportionate adverse affect on minority or low income populations in the area of the NWSTF. All recommendations in the updated INRMP would only affect NWSTF property and would not result in any negative effects to the neighboring properties. The No-Action Alternative would have no effect on socioeconomics and environmental justice since there would be no change from present management strategies under the 1999 INRMP.

3.8 PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY

3.8.1 Affected Environment

33.1% of the population in Census Tract 9701 including Boardman and Irrigon is under the age of 18 (2,516 people). Access to the NWSTF is restricted by fences around the property lines on all four sides. No children or public citizens are permitted access to the property.

NWSTF has been used as an active bombing range in its history, and therefore the property has the potential for UXO to be present. The Boardman Air Force Range FUDS, 59,000 acres bordering the NWSTF directly to the west, has been the focus of a Preliminary Assessment / Site Investigation administered by the EPA. No metals were reported that significantly exceeded background concentrations.

Munitions removed in the past during range maintenance activities were inspected, certified free of energetic fillers, and subjected to recycling; therefore, they were characterized and determined not to be hazardous wastes.

3.8.2 Environmental Consequences

Implementation of either action alternative would have no effect on public or children's health and safety. Children and public citizens are excluded by a fence around the perimeter of the property. No aspects of either action alternative would have the potential to affect children. The No-Action Alternative would have no effect on public or children's health and safety since there would be no change from present management strategies under the 1999 INRMP.

CHAPTER 4

CUMULATIVE IMPACTS

4.1 CUMULATIVE EFFECTS

The CEQ regulations (40 CFR 1500-1508) define cumulative effects as “the impact on the environment which results from the incremental impact of the action when added to other past, present, and reasonably foreseeable actions...”. Cumulative effects are typically defined as two or more individual affects which, when considered together, compound or increase other environmental effects. The cumulative effects may go unnoticed when examined individually, but can become magnified when other projects are incorporated.

4.1.1 Identified Cumulative Actions

The Navy, in cooperation with the Oregon Military Department, is undergoing an analysis of current and future military training activities on NWSTF Boardman by the Navy and other military users. This initiative was started in October 2010 with the publication of the Notice of Intent to prepare and EIS and is scheduled to complete by the end of 2013. Depending on the scope of alternatives developed and the final alternative selected, there could be an increase in military training activities and military training facilities on NWSTF Boardman.

The Bureau of Land Management is proposing to construct a power transmission line from Hemmingway, Idaho, to Boardman, Oregon, that proposes to use NWSTF property or be located immediately adjacent to the range. The project is proposing to install an additional regional power transmission line and is currently going through EIS review with the Navy serving as a Cooperating Agency.

The U.S. Forest Service is also proposing to construct the Cascade Crossing power transmission line that proposes to use or be located immediately adjacent to the NWSTF. The project is proposing to install an additional regional power transmission line.

There are several wind power projects that have been constructed and others have been proposed near the NWSTF area, but not immediately adjacent to the boundaries of the property.

No other major projects have occurred at or near the NWSTF in the past, are presently ongoing, or are expected to occur in the reasonably foreseeable future. Routine maintenance and repairs of buildings and grounds and routine reoccurring military training are on-going activities.

4.1.2 Cumulative Effects Analysis

Development and implementation of the INRMP should have a beneficial effect to natural resources on the property by implementing a management strategy that improves natural resources on the range and supports surrounding projects by providing information on sensitive habitats and resources. Since the proposed action is expected to result in overall conservation and improvement in natural resources management on NWSTF, the project would not contribute to cumulative impacts.

4.2 IRREVERSIBLE AND IRRETRIEVABLE COMMITMENT OF RESOURCES

Implementation of the INRMP under Alternative 1 or 2 would commit resources to survey and map resources, as well as to perform vegetation restoration and removal of invasive species; it would also incorporate updated protection and conservation measures for the natural resources that exist on the NWSTF. These are identified and planned management actions that do not represent an irreversible and irretrievable commitment of resources.

Implementation of the No-Action Alternative would involve no irreversible or irretrievable commitment of resources; it would simply revert to ongoing natural resource management practices on the NWSTF.

4.3 LONG-TERM USE

The implementation of the INRMP under Alternative 1 or 2 would have long-term beneficial impacts on natural resources at the NWSTF. These alternatives would maintain and conserve and improve the natural resources present on NWSTF property and update effective management practices for these resources.

Implementation of the No-Action Alternative would continue to have some long-term beneficial impacts to the natural resources at the NWSTF. However, the beneficial impacts to natural resources would be less than with implementation of either action alternative, since the No-Action Alternative would not update conservation and management practices for natural resources from outdated 1999 conditions and practices.

4.4 COMPARISON OF IMPACTS

No significant impacts would occur to the physical environment, the biological environment, or the human environment for the Proposed Action, Alternative Action and No-Action Alternative. Table 4-1 compares the various activities under each alternative.

Based on the analysis in this EA, the Navy has concluded that implementation of the updated INRMP for the NWSTF under Alternative 1; the Preferred Alternative would have no significant impact on the human environment.

Table 4-1. Summary of Environmental Consequences

Alternatives	Preferred Alternative Implement all objectives and recommendations	Alternative 2 Implement only high and medium priority objectives and recommendations	No-Action Alternative Maintain 1999 INRMP mgmt practices
Land Use	Land formerly managed under agricultural leases would be managed towards restoration of native vegetation, providing an additional positive impact. Multiple recommendations to increase wildlife habitat and reduce soil erosion potential through plant and range management practices.	Same as Alternative 1	Possible negative affect from continued current management practices
Air Quality	No affect	No affect	Possible negative affect from continued current management practices
Water Resources	No affect	No affect	Continued current management practices
Terrestrial Biology	Beneficial affect from possible natural restoration of native vegetation due to projects and management plans providing increased habitat diversity from restoration actions. Also increase species monitoring to evaluate success of management actions.	Similar to Alternative 1, but primarily focused on ESA and priority MBTA species.	Continued current management practices
Threatened and Endangered Species	Beneficial affect from enhancement of ESA species through habitat and vegetation restoration and species monitoring.	Same as Alternative 1	Continued current management practices
Cultural Resources	No affect	No affect	No affect

Table 4-1. Summary of Environmental Consequences

Alternatives	Preferred Alternative Implement all objectives and recommendations	Alternative 2 Implement only high and medium priority objectives and recommendations	No-Action Alternative Maintain 1999 INRMP mgmt practices
Socioeconomics and Environmental Justice	Minority or low income populations would not be disproportionately affected.	Same as Alternative 1	No affect
Public Health and Safety	Public health and safety would not be disproportionately affected.	Same as Alternative 1	No affect
Cumulative Effects	Would not incrementally add to cumulative impacts in the area from now projects. Beneficial impacts towards natural resources on the property would occur from implementation of various BMPs and restoration projects	Same as Alternative 1	No affect
Irreversible and Irretrievable Commitment of Resources	None anticipated	None anticipated	None anticipated
Long-Term Use	Beneficial impact	Beneficial impact	Some beneficial impact

CHAPTER 5

LIST OF PREPARERS AND DISTRIBUTION LIST

5.1 LIST OF PREPARERS

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Tribal Historic Preservation Officer
Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation
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Pendleton, OR 97801

The Nature Conservancy
PO Box 314
The Dalles, OR 97058

Planning Director
Morrow County
P.O. Box 40
Irrigon, OR 97844

5.3 NEWSPAPER NOTICES

East Oregonian, publication date of March 13, 2011

CHAPTER 6

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**APPENDIX A. EA CORRESPONDENCE AND
COORDINATION LETTERS**

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090
Ser N44/0346
March 16, 2011

Ms. Carey Miller
Tribal Historic Preservation Officer
P.O. Box 638
Pendleton, OR 97801

Dear Ms. Miller:

In accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the Navy (Navy) is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is prepared under the Sikes Act to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broadly scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The current INRMP was signed and approved in 1999 and the plan needs to be updated to comply with current Department of Defense and Navy requirements/policies and to be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range. The updated INRMP proposes to implement projects and initiatives to meet its objectives which are classified by priority as low (ERL 2), medium (ERL 3) and high (ERL 4) priority projects.

We appreciate any comments or considerations you may have in regards to finalizing the INRMP or preparation of the EA. The projects listed in the INRMP update are developed to a coarse scale concept without sufficient detail to evaluate action specific impacts at this time. Once project development has started, we will coordinate with you directly for project specific impacts and comments to comply with Sec. 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act for each specific action to be funded and implemented. You can review a copy of the final draft of the Boardman INRMP dated January 2010 at:
<https://www.cnmc.navy.mil/Whidbey/Programs/DepartmentsSpecialAssistants/PublicWorksEnvironmental/PublicNotices/index.htm>.

The EA will address two action alternatives and a No Action Alternative. Alternative 1 (the Preferred Alternative) is to adopt and implement objectives and recommendations of the updated INRMP. Under Alternative 1, all proposed projects and management actions will be implemented and there should be a benefit to both natural resources compliance requirements and natural resources conservation issues.

5090
Ser N44/0346
March 16, 2011

Alternative 2 is to adopt and implement only the high and medium priority objectives and recommendations of the updated INRMP. Under Alternative 2, only high and medium priority projects will be implemented. Most of those projects are focused towards sensitive natural resources that are subject to listing pressures. This will provide benefits mostly for resources subjected to compliance requirements, but very little would be done for general conservation or land management initiatives.

The No Action Alternative continues implementation of the objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP of 1999. On-going practices used for natural resources management at NWSTF Boardman would continue as well as annual reviews and updates. The No Action Alternative would not improve management practices at NWSTF Boardman as there would be no change from the natural resources management practices implemented by the 1999 INRMP. By not implementing the updated INRMP, the Navy will not be successful in implementing current INRMP policies and objectives at NWSTF Boardman.

We would like to get your input on any comments or concerns you would like us to consider in regards to preparation of the EA or finalizing the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. To keep the NEPA process progressing, please respond to this request within 30 days. If you have questions regarding this request or need additional information, please contact my NWSTF Boardman Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Philips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

M. DYSART
Commander, U.S. Navy
Public Works Officer
By direction of the
Commanding Officer

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090
Ser N44/0345
March 16, 2011

Mr. Roger Roper
Deputy State Historic Preservation Officer
725 Summer Street NE Suite C
Salem, OR 97301

Dear Mr. Roper:

In accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the Navy (Navy) is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is prepared under the Sikes Act to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broadly scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The current INRMP was signed and approved in 1999 and the plan needs to be updated to comply with current Department of Defense and Navy requirements/policies and to be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range. The updated INRMP proposes to implement projects and initiatives to meet its objectives which are classified by priority as low (ERL 2), medium (ERL 3) and high (ERL 4) priority projects.

We appreciate any comments or considerations you may have in regards to finalizing the INRMP or preparation of the EA. The projects listed in the INRMP update are developed to a coarse scale concept without sufficient detail to evaluate action specific impacts at this time. Once project development has started, we will coordinate with you directly for project specific impacts and comments to comply with Sec. 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act for each specific action to be funded and implemented. You can review a copy of the final draft of the Boardman INRMP dated January 2010 at:
<https://www.cnmc.navy.mil/Whidbey/Programs/DepartmentsSpecialAssistants/PublicWorksEnvironment/PulicNotices/index.htm>.

The EA will address two action alternatives and a No Action Alternative. Alternative 1 (the Preferred Alternative) is to adopt and implement objectives and recommendations of the updated INRMP. Under Alternative 1, all proposed projects and management actions will be implemented and there should be a benefit to both natural resources compliance requirements and natural resources conservation issues.

Alternative 2 is to adopt and implement only the high and medium priority objectives and recommendations of the updated INRMP. Under Alternative 2, only high and medium priority projects will be implemented. Most of those projects are focused towards sensitive natural resources that are subject to listing pressures. This will provide benefits mostly for resources subjected to compliance requirements, but very little would be done for general conservation or land management initiatives.

The No Action Alternative continues implementation of the objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP of 1999. On-going practices used for natural resources management at NWSTF Boardman would continue as well as annual reviews and updates. The No Action Alternative would not improve management practices at NWSTF Boardman as there would be no change from the natural resources management practices implemented by the 1999 INRMP. By not implementing the updated INRMP, the Navy will not be successful in implementing current INRMP policies and objectives at NWSTF Boardman.

We would like to get your input on any comments or concerns you would like us to consider in regards to preparation of the EA or finalizing the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. To keep the NEPA process progressing, please respond to this request within 30 days. If you have questions regarding this request or need additional information, please contact my NWSTF Boardman Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Phillips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

M. DYSART
Commander, U.S. Navy
Public Works Officer
By direction of the
Commanding Officer

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090
Ser N44/0344
March 16, 2011

Mr. Steve Cherry
District Biologist
Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
P.O. Box 363
Heppner, OR 97836

Dear Mr. Cherry:

In accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the Navy (Navy) is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is prepared under the Sikes Act to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broadly scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The current INRMP was signed and approved in 1999 and the plan needs to be updated to comply with current Department of Defense and Navy requirements/policies and to be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range. The updated INRMP proposes to implement projects and initiatives to meet its objectives which are classified by priority as low (ERL 2), medium (ERL 3) and high (ERL 4) priority projects.

We appreciate any comments or considerations you may have in regards to finalizing the INRMP or preparation of the EA. The projects listed in the INRMP update are developed to a coarse scale concept without sufficient detail to evaluate action specific impacts at this time. Once project development has started, we will coordinate with you annually for project specific impacts and comments during the annual natural resources metrics review to address concerns and compliance issues. You can review a copy of the final draft of the Boardman INRMP dated January 2010 at:
<https://www.cnmc.navy.mil/Whidbey/Programs/DepartmentsSpecialAssistants/PublicWorksEnvironment/PulicNotices/index.htm>.

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Ser N44/0344
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The No Action Alternative continues implementation of the objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP of 1999. On-going practices used for natural resources management at NWSTF Boardman would continue as well as annual reviews and updates. The No Action Alternative would not improve management practices at NWSTF Boardman as there would be no change from the natural resources management practices implemented by the 1999 INRMP. By not implementing the updated INRMP, the Navy will not be successful in implementing current INRMP policies and objectives at NWSTF Boardman.

We would like to get your input on any comments or concerns you would like us to consider in regards to preparation of the EA or finalizing the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. To keep the NEPA process progressing, please respond to this request within 30 days. If you have questions regarding this request or need additional information, please contact my NWSTF Boardman Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Philips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

M. DYSART
Commander, U.S. Navy
Public Works Officer
By direction of the
Commanding Officer

Oregon

John A. Kitzhaber, MD, Governor

Department of Fish and Wildlife

Heppner District Office

PO Box 363

54173 Hwy 74

Heppner, OR 97836

(541) 676-5230

(541) 676-9075

April 6, 2011

John Phillips, Environmental Division
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, WA 98278

Dear John:

This letter is in regards to your request for comments on the final draft of the Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) for the Boardman Bombing Range and the associated Environmental Assessment (EA). I have read through the draft plan and only really have one comment to make regarding the INRMP. I appreciate the changes that were made in the draft plan to address the concerns raised by ODFW during the first comment period.

In the section regarding wildfire control and protection the INRMP suggests the use of green stripping using herbicides. I would also recommend considering using another form of green stripping using fire resistant plant species. Forage kochia (not related to the weed) has been used effectively in other shrub steppe arid areas to create firebreaks. Forage kochia stays green throughout the summer and if planted in the proper densities can provide a fire break while also still providing wildlife habitat. I would recommend that the plan include this practice as a potential use for creating firebreaks in the future.

The Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW) would also like to recommend that the Navy choose Alternative One in the EA. ODFW recognizes that money to complete projects is becoming increasingly difficult to secure but we would like to have the opportunity if money is available to implement all of the proposed activities in the INRMP.

I appreciate the opportunity to comment on this draft final plan and look forward to working with you on the implementation of the final plan. Please feel free to contact me at (541) 676-5230 if you have any questions on my comments or would like to discuss any other issues.

Respectfully,

Steve Cherry
District Biologist

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/0343

March 16, 2011

Mr. Gary Miller
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
La Grande Field Office
3502 Hwy 30
La Grande, OR 97850

Dear Mr. Miller:

In accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the Navy (Navy) is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is prepared under the Sikes Act to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broadly scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The current INRMP was signed and approved in 1999 and the plan needs to be updated to comply with current Department of Defense and Navy requirements/policies and to be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range. The updated INRMP proposes to implement projects and initiatives to meet its objectives which are classified by priority as low (ERL 2), medium (ERL 3) and high (ERL 4) priority projects.

We appreciate any comments or considerations you may have in regards to finalizing the INRMP or preparation of the EA. The projects listed in the INRMP update are developed to a coarse scale concept without sufficient detail to evaluate action specific impacts at this time. Once project development has started, we will coordinate with you annually for project specific impacts and comments during the annual natural resources metrics review to address concerns and compliance issues. You can review a copy of the final draft of the Boardman INRMP dated January 2010 at:
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The EA will address two action alternatives and a No Action Alternative. Alternative 1 (the Preferred Alternative) is to adopt and implement objectives and recommendations of the updated INRMP. Under Alternative 1, all proposed projects and management actions will be implemented and there should be a benefit to both natural resources compliance requirements and natural resources conservation issues.

5090
Ser N44/0343
March 16, 2011

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We would like to get your input on any comments or concerns you would like us to consider in regards to preparation of the EA or finalizing the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. To keep the NEPA process progressing, please respond to this request within 30 days. If you have questions regarding this request or need additional information, please contact my NWSTF Boardman Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Philips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

M. DYSART
Commander, U.S. Navy
Public Works Officer
By direction of the
Commanding Officer

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090
Ser N44/0342
March 16, 2011

Ms. Leslie Nelson
Columbia Basin Stewardship Coordinator
The Nature Conservancy
P.O. Box 314
The Dalles, OR 97058

Dear Ms. Nelson:

In accordance with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), the Department of the Navy (Navy) is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. An INRMP is prepared under the Sikes Act to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broadly scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The current INRMP was signed and approved in 1999 and the plan needs to be updated to comply with current Department of Defense and Navy requirements/policies and to be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range. The updated INRMP proposes to implement projects and initiatives to meet its objectives which are classified by priority as low (ERL 2), medium (ERL 3) and high (ERL 4) priority projects.

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Ser N44/0342
March 16, 2011

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We would like to get your input on any comments or concerns you would like us to consider in regards to preparation of the EA or finalizing the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. To keep the NEPA process progressing, please respond to this request within 30 days. If you have questions regarding this request or need additional information, please contact my NWSTF Boardman Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Philips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

M. DYSART
Commander, U.S. Navy
Public Works Officer
By direction of the
Commanding Officer

IN THE CIRCUIT COURT OF THE STATE OF OREGON
FOR UMATILLA COUNTY

} AFFIDAVIT OF PUBLICATION

STATE OF OREGON
County of Umatilla } ss

I, Dayle Stinson being duly sworn, depose and say that I am the principal clerk of the publisher of the East Oregonian a newspaper of general circulation, as defined by ORS 193.010 and published at 211 SE Byers Avenue, Pendleton, OR 97801, in the afor that the

EO-5670 NOTICE OF AVAILABILITY

a printed copy of which is hereto annexed; was published in the entire issue of said newspaper for 3 successive and consecutive issues in the following issues:

FEBRUARY 24, 26, 28, 2012

Subscribed and sworn to before me on this 27 day of

MARCH, 2012

Dayle Stinson

Stacey D Beaver
Notary Public of Oregon

EO-5670
NOTICE OF AVAILABILITY
Draft Environmental Assessment (EA) for Naval Air Station Whidbey Island for the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons System Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon.
Pursuant to Section 102 (2) (C) of the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) 1969, as implemented by the Council on Environmental Quality Regulations (40 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] Parts 1500-1508), the U.S. Department of the Navy (Navy) announces the availability for public review and comment of a Draft Environmental Assessment (EA) to implement all objectives and recommendations of the revised Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) including high-, medium- and low-priority objectives at Naval Weapons System Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. A 15-day public comment period is being held to receive written comments on the Draft EA. Members of the public, government agencies, and tribes are invited to review and comment on the Draft EA. An electronic version can be viewed or downloaded at the following website: <https://www.cnrc.navy.mil/Whidbey/OperationsAndManagement/EnvironmentalSupport/index.htm>

The EA identifies and evaluates the potential effects of implementing objectives and recommendations of the INRMP. The EA analyzes two alternatives and a No-Action alternative. The purpose of and need for the proposed action is to comply with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, provide management requirements for species listed under the Endangered Species Act and meet the requirements of the Department of Defense and Navy instructions. Moreover, the conservation program must be consistent with the mission-essential use of the installation and its lands and not cause a net loss of military land use. The EA analyzes potential direct and indirect impacts to land use, air quality, water resources, terrestrial biology, threatened and endangered species, cultural resources and socio-economics and environmental justice. Additionally, cumulative impacts and mitigation measures are addressed in the document. There is no cooperating agency for this EA. Comments on the Draft EA can be made in writing via mail or email. All comments should be forwarded to: Jackie Queen, Environmental Planner Naval Facilities Engineering Command Northwest 1115 West Lexington Drive Oak Harbor, WA 98278 Email: Jackie.queen@navy.mil To be considered, all comments must be received by 12 March 2012.. February 24, 26, 28, 2012

APPENDIX C. Correspondence

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DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/4312

November 15, 2007

Mr. Gary Miller
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
La Grande Field Office
3502 HWY 30
La Grande, OR 97850

Dear Mr. Miller:

Enclosed for your review is an early working draft of Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan. As you know from our previous meetings, we are in the process of updating this management plan and invite your agency's input on the draft. The purpose of this review is to solicit technical review early in the update process when it is easier to identify and address issues, so together we can make this a quality management plan for our installation's natural resources.

The Federal Sikes Act (codified in 16 USC 670, et. seq.) requires that military installations develop an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan in cooperation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and have the final plan approved by your agency.

Additionally, as stated in Public Law 108-136 (The Defense Authorization Act of 2004), an approved Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan that has benefits for a listed species shall take the place of designated critical habitat on the military installation. It is to all our benefit to do what we can to make these resource management plans of the highest quality.

This draft is a large document that will require a substantial commitment of your time for review. However, to keep the update process progressing, we would appreciate your comments and ideas within 30 days of this letter. We will likely hold future meetings to address comments and concerns as necessary during continued draft document development.

Your point of contact for questions and comments concerning the development of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan is Mr. John Phillips of the Environmental Division, at (360) 257-8873.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "John Mosher", with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

JOHN MOSHER
Environmental Program Manager

Enclosure: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/4313

November 15, 2007

Jodie Delavan
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
Oregon Fish and Wildlife Office
2600 SE 98th Avenue, Suite 100
Portland, Oregon 97266

Dear Ms. Delavan:

Enclosed for your review is an early working draft of Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan. As you know from our previous meetings, we are in the process of updating this management plan and invite your agency's input on the draft. The purpose of this review is to solicit technical review early in the update process when it is easier to identify and address issues, so together we can make this a quality management plan for our installation's natural resources.

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Your point of contact for questions and comments concerning the development of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan is Mr. John Phillips of the Environmental Division, at (360) 257-8873.

Sincerely,

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JOHN MOSHER
Environmental Program Manager

Enclosure: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

La Grande Field Office

3502 Highway 30

La Grande, Oregon 97850

Phone: (541) 962-8584 FAX: (541) 962-8581

Reply To: 7975.0153
File Name: Boardman INRMP Comments_02 09.doc
TS Number: 08-288
TAILS: 13420-2009-FA-0071

FEB 25 2009

John Mosher
Environmental Program Manager
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, WA 98278-5000

Subject: Review of the Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman

Dear Mr. Mosher:

This is in response to your letter, dated November 15, 2007, requesting the Fish and Wildlife Service's (Service) agreement under the Sikes Act to update the 1999 Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's (BNWSTF) Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP). Your correspondence was received by the Service on November 19, 2007. This letter is based on information received in the draft 2007 INRMP, follow-up correspondence, and discussion at the FY2008 metrics meeting on November 13, 2008. We have coordinated our comments with the Service's Office of Migratory Birds. Our comments and recommendations have been prepared under the authority of, and in accordance with, the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C 670a *et seq.*) and Sikes Act Improvement Amendments, the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, and the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (Act; 16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*).

The Service considered three criteria to determine if the INRMP provides adequate special management or protection. The three criteria include whether the plan provides a conservation benefit to species, gives assurances that the management plan will be implemented, and provides assurances that conservation efforts will be effective. A discussion of our review and recommendations follows:

Section 3.0 Environmental Management Strategy

The Service completed an action plan that describes research and conservation needs for the long-billed curlew. Please consider whether any of the activities specified in this plan are appropriate for the BNWSTF. The plan is located at:
<http://www.fws.gov/mountain%2Dprairie/species/birds/longbilled%5Fcurlew/>

The Service also completed a status assessment and conservation plan for the burrowing owl in the United States. This assessment contains conservation measures and biological information

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MAR - 2 2009

that could be useful for the BNWSTF, and is located at: <http://www.fws.gov/mountain%2Dprairie/species/birds/wbo/Western%20Burrowing%20Owrev73003a.pdf>.

Under Section 3.2, please consider Executive Order (EO) 13186, the Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds (66FR3853). This EO was signed January 10, 2001, directing executive departments and agencies to take certain actions to further implement Federal agency obligations to conserve species protected by the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA). More information regarding this EO is available at: <http://www.fws.gov/policy/720fw2.html>. Also, there is a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the Service and the Department of Defense to promote the conservation of migratory birds based on this EO. The MOU is available at: <http://www.fws.gov/migratorybirds/EO/DoDMOUfinalSignature.pdf>.

Section 4.0 Program Elements

4.1 Personnel: A Natural Resource Manager (NRM) is designated for the station but located at the Naval Air Station Whidbey Island, Washington. It is recommended in the INRMP that a full-time NRM be stationed at BNWSTF to manage the approximately 47,000-acre site. This recommendation has been given a high priority level in the implementation schedule, and is considered a "must fund" project (Environmental Readiness Level 4; pages 5-3 to 5-5).

Recommendations: We strongly support this approach.

4.2 Threatened and Endangered Species Management: No federally-listed T&E species occur at the station; however, one candidate species, the Washington ground squirrel (WGS) occurs throughout much of the installation. New activities (e.g., renewing leases) will be reviewed by the NRM, which will provide an opportunity to incorporate appropriate conservation measures for natural resources, including the WGS. The NRM will monitor the WGS population and identify areas where the military mission may overlap the WGS habitat and provide management guidance to the installation's command. Planned noxious weed control and wildfire management should also benefit this species.

Recommendations: Under Criteria 3 of Section 4.2.1.1, it states that "annual monitoring of the number, use, and location of Washington ground squirrel burrows will provide information as to the success of the conservation measures." It is unclear whether you intend to monitor all squirrel locations, or only those that overlap with military activities. It is also not clear how monitoring will occur. Will you monitor the number of active burrows at a site as a surrogate for the number of squirrels? Or will you estimate the number of squirrels at a site using mark-recapture, transect surveys, or another technique? Depending on your protocol, this could be very time intensive. We recommend continued coordination with the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife, The Nature Conservancy (TNC), and the Service to develop a WGS monitoring protocol for BNWSTF that can reasonably be accomplished, and has enough accuracy and precision to be meaningful and comparable across years.

The INRMP describes the conservation benefit to WGS as: "this plan will help conserve and protect Washington ground squirrels by integrating species and conservation measures with mission and project planning". It is not clear what type of conservation measures may be used other than monitoring sites (see paragraph immediately above), and the ability to integrate

conservation measures into new actions. We understand it is difficult to prescribe specific conservation measures at the INRMP scale, but suggest you consider listing a variety of conservation measures that you would consider using as appropriate. Table 4-1 has a more detailed approach but appears limited to sagebrush habitats.

Please note that because the WGS is not listed under the Endangered Species Act, we have not assessed its critical habitat or primary constituent elements. Therefore, we are not able to determine 1), whether there is, and if so to what extent, critical habitat for the WGS on the BNWSTF and 2) whether this management plan can exclude the BNWSTF from a critical habitat designation.

Section 2.3.1 of the INRMP should be updated to reflect the delisting of the Northern bald eagle from the Endangered Species Act (ESA). Also, please update Table 2-2 to reflect the Federal status of Swainson's hawks, golden eagles, brewers sparrows, sage sparrows, loggerhead shrikes, and long-billed curlews as "species of concern." The Service's Birds of Conservation Concern list is revised every five years by the Migratory Bird Program under the authority of the 1988 amendment to the Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act, and is a list of species, subspecies, and populations of migratory nongame birds that, without additional conservation actions, are likely to become candidates for listing under the ESA. This Birds of Conservation Concern list is available at the following website: <http://www.fws.gov/migratorybirds/reports/BCC2002.pdf>. Table 9 of this document lists species of conservation concern in the Great Basin and Table 48 has a nationwide list.

4.3 Wetlands Management: Only one potential wetland, Toad pond, occurs at the station. This depressional area is watered by Navy personnel for 6 – 8 weeks each spring to provide breeding habitat for spadefoot toads. The pond is fenced to exclude potential livestock, recreational users, and vehicles. A vegetative buffer is maintained to prevent runoff and pesticides from entering the pond.

Recommendations: Hunting has previously occurred by installation personnel in the area of Toad pond. In Section 4.4 you recommended that hunting at Toad Pond "should cease, since it is non-sporting to hunt at the only waterhole on the installation." To help ensure that hunters are aware of this recommendation, consider posting "no hunting" signs in the area as a reminder.

4.4 Habitat Management: The Navy has addressed natural resource management actions for developed areas, wetlands, sand dunes, western juniper stands, and sagebrush habitat. Projects planned in the INRMP include noxious weed control, surveying and mapping of juniper trees, vegetation monitoring and mapping, production of GIS maps, and creating firebreaks to help contain wildfires. Other management actions include limited grazing, prescribed fire, seeding with native grasses and forbs, protecting habitat from impacts by military training activities and recreational use.

Recommendations: Habitat types should also include native bunchgrass and sagebrush-grassland habitats. Sagebrush-grassland habitat mapping may not be necessary if "sagebrush habitat" is an umbrella description of all habitat types that contain sagebrush. If you have not already planned to do so, we recommend applying the results of your updated vegetation

mapping, as well as historic information on species occurrences, to update your wildlife habitat (e.g., maps like Figure 2-22).

If grazing occurs, we recommend that the grazing plan allows adequate vegetative cover to remain for small mammals. Also, if grazing occurs, this may be an opportunity to have a graduate student or other appropriate person conduct a controlled grazing study on the effects (negative, beneficial, or none) of varied grazing levels on species of concern on the facility.

When mapping juniper stands, consider documenting which trees are currently supporting larger nests (e.g., owls, hawks), and which would likely be large enough to support larger nests. This could be a beneficial starting point if the on-site NRM plans to monitor ferruginous or Swainson's hawk nest success.

Table 4-1 describes using prescribed fire to manage sagebrush habitat. Please avoid conducting prescribed fires in early spring in areas where birds are nesting to comply with the MBTA.

Please consider habitat restoration and enhancement techniques (depending on the habitat and species needs) in areas that were previously heavily impacted (bombed) and are adjacent to important wildlife habitat.

4.5 Fish and Wildlife Management: The INRMP specifically describes management of hunting, reptiles and amphibians, mammals, birds, and invasive species. Deer and bird hunting are allowed on the facility, but will follow state hunting regulations and is not open to the public. The NRM reviews all training plans, proposed projects, and operations at BNWSTF for possible impacts on wildlife species and will provide recommendations to benefit wildlife early in the planning process. No fish species occur at the station. Actions planned to control noxious weeds and to prevent the spread of wildfire will benefit species occurring at the station. Planned surveys and monitoring of wildlife populations will assist in identifying any declines in populations that warrant further investigation. Specific surveys are planned for large mammals, WGS, and burrowing owls.

Recommendations: The recommendation to cease hunting at the facility's only watering hole (i.e., Toad pond) is located in the habitat management section 4.4 (on page 4-7). As mentioned above, you might consider posting "no hunting" signs at Toad Pond to remind personnel to avoid this area. Sections 3.4 and 4.5.2. both describe the type of persons allowed to hunt on the facility; but the descriptions are not consistent. Also, the INRMP describes the amount of deer harvest (e.g., several per year), but not the species and approximate amount of bird harvest.

Human disturbance should be minimized as much as possible during the nesting season of birds. Loud noises and increased activity may disrupt breeding and cause birds to abandon their nests.

We suggest conducting burrowing owl surveys in coordination with other monitoring and evaluating measures for Birds of Conservation Concern.

On page 4-12, in the first paragraph of Section 4.5.5.1, please change unlawful to prohibited in "Under the Act, taking, killing or possessing migratory birds is unlawful prohibited."

On page 4-12, after the third paragraph regarding the MBTA, you could add language about the EO13186 and the MOU between the Service and DOD.

4.6 Land Management: Includes fire management, agricultural outleasing (e.g., grazing), Research Natural Areas (RNAs), grounds maintenance and landscaping, and integrated pest management. The installation has experienced several wildfires during recent years. Steps are planned to minimize the spread of wildfire, including: widening unpaved roads to 30 feet to serve as firebreaks (containing fires to small areas), training all personnel in wildland firefighting and in the use of firefighting equipment located at the station, and installing large water storage tanks to improve access to water for firefighting.

The grazing plan has been developed to minimize negative impacts to wildlife, soils, water resources, and native plants. Limited, seasonal grazing may benefit the species while decreasing the cheatgrass population. Toad pond will have adequate protection, and the other springs are no longer flowing. Grazing will be very limited in the southern portion of the facility; it will be on an as-needed basis only to decrease fuels in the area of junipers which are highly susceptible to fires. Grazing will be on a rotational basis, January through May 15th, and areas will be reseeded with native seeds afterwards.

Recommendations: Section 4.6.1 lists distances to water outlets as one of the main problems in managing wildfires at BNWSTF and in your Fire Management Strategy (section 4.6.1.1) you recommend installing large water storage tanks at various locations to address this issue. We recommend you include water storage tanks in your scheduled projects (Table A-1, INRMP Project Recommendations) with a high priority level due to the increased wildfire occurrence at the station in recent years. Consider monitoring and mapping areas impacted by wildfires after they occur to capture changes in vegetation. Care should be taken to monitor the amount of cover left for small mammals that are an important source of prey for many of the birds.

On page 4-18 under "Post Fire Requirements," please note that reseeded areas need periodic monitoring and may also need reseeded to be effective. Please add something in this section that accounts for effectiveness monitoring and adaptive management (e.g., reseeded).

Curlew habitat could be maintained by grazing in moderation, particularly overwinter and in early spring.

Section 5.0 Implementation

The INRMP describes the cultural history of the site on page 2-8. On page 5-6 it also mentions the ability to have archaeological investigations under the Legacy Resource Management Program. In addition, there are also several statements scattered throughout the document that articulate the need to address cultural resources. However, the strategy for addressing cultural resources (at present and before construction activities) at the BNWSTF is unclear. If you need assistance evaluating archaeological resources prior to future construction activities, we suggest you contact Gary Miller, the Field Supervisor of the La Grande Field Office (541-962-8584) or Anan Raymond, a Service archeologist in our Regional Office (503-625-4377).

Other Recommendations and Comments:

- We did not consider the effects of the proposed Oregon Military Department (OMD) shooting ranges in this comment letter. It is our understanding that these actions will be evaluated under a separate National Environmental Policy Act review, will not be part of this revised INRMP, and that the Navy will revisit the effectiveness of this INRMP with regard to a specific proposed OMD action. We have not reviewed an Environmental Assessment (EA) or Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) for this revision of the INRMP. We have submitted significant comments on the first draft of the OMD shooting ranges EA, but have not had the opportunity to review any subsequent versions of their proposal.
- Other current military training activities are not identified clearly. For example, in Section 2.1.2, the INRMP states: "After 1996 the range remained active, but was infrequently used by the Navy, although the Oregon Army and Air National Guard and other Department of Defense agencies use the area occasionally for training exercises." Also, paragraph 6 of the Wildland Fire-Potential Report (Appendix G), states, "it is understood that the Oregon National Guard expects to use the facility for training when possible every weekend during the year." It is unclear whether this increased use is related to the proposed OMD shooting ranges (which you are removing from the INRMP), or if this is already occurring on the facility. It is understandable that security needs may preclude the Navy from disclosing the details of their specific training activities but it should be noted that it limits our ability to perform a complete and accurate analysis of the effects on natural resources.
- It is not clear how the Navy determines whether military training exercises impact natural resources. Have you looked at areas before and after exercises to determine the extent to which actions increase ground disturbance, and then followed-up with a plan to address this disturbance (e.g., reseeding, spraying, or other appropriate measures)? For actions that cause ground disturbance, consider comparing vegetation at sites before and after major training activities, using a standardized (but not necessarily complicated or expensive) monitoring protocol, to assess the level of impact, to determine whether ground disturbance may result in an increase of invasive plants, so that follow-up restoration measures can be implemented when appropriate.
- It is noted in the INRMP that the U.S. Army Air Corps and U.S. Air Force previously used the facility for aerial bombing and gunnery training before it was transferred to the Navy for aerial bombing practice; however, the plan makes minimal mention of possible environmental contaminants that do or could reasonably occur on the facility. Given the historical use of the range, we recommend that a comprehensive environmental contaminants analysis be completed to determine what contaminants exist and how they may be affecting natural resources at the site (e.g., water quality, wildlife). The results should be used to determine whether remediation is warranted. Best Management Practices for dealing with potential contamination resulting from military training activities should be developed and included in the INRMP. The results of tests conducted on the 12 monitoring wells established in 2005 should be made available. The presence of unexploded ordinance at the station should be addressed in the INRMP. Location of historical training information and whether both practice and live munitions were used in the training should be disclosed if known and the types of munitions used should be listed.

- We are interested in the proposal to remove RNA-A, and add another RNA adjacent to RNA-C. While this area appears much more appropriate for a RNA, when making this decision we also encourage you to consider whether this area, along with RNA-B and RNA-C will cover all natural habitat types that occur on the facility. We think this is an important consideration in your determination since one objective of the RNA program is to "preserve examples of all significant natural ecosystems for comparison with those influenced by man,"

We appreciate your coordination with the Service in the development of this revised INRMP. If you or your staff have any questions, please contact Kim Garner or Jodie Delavan at (503) 231-6179 or me at (541) 962-8584.

Sincerely,

Gary S. Miller
Field Supervisor

cc:

John Phillips, Department of the Navy, Whidbey Island Naval Air Station, Oak Harbor,
Washington

Leslie Nelson, The Nature Conservancy, The Dalles, Oregon

Steve Cherry, Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife, Heppner, Oregon

Russ Morgan, Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife, La Grande, Oregon

Don Steffek, Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon

Mike Green, Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/4315

November 15, 2007

Mr. Steve Cherry
Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
Heppner Field Office
P.O. Box 363
Heppner, OR 97836

Dear Mr. Cherry:

Enclosed for your review is an early working draft of Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan. As you know from our previous meetings, we are in the process of updating this management plan and invite your agency's input on the draft. The purpose of this review is to solicit technical review early in the update process when it is easier to identify and address issues, so together we can make this a quality management plan for our installation's natural resources.

The Federal Sikes Act (codified in 16 USC 670, et. seq.) requires that military installations develop an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan in cooperation with the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife and have the final plan approved by your agency.

Additionally, as stated in Public Law 108-136 (The Defense Authorization Act of 2004), an approved Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan that has benefits for a listed species shall take the place of designated critical habitat on the military installation. It is to all our benefit to do what we can to make these resource management plans of the highest quality.

This draft is a large document that will require a substantial commitment of your time for review. However, to keep the update process progressing, we would appreciate your comments and ideas within 30 days of this letter. We will likely hold future meetings to address comments and concerns as necessary during continued draft document development.

Your point of contact for questions and comments concerning the development of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan is Mr. John Phillips of the Environmental Division at (360) 257-8873.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "John Mosher". The signature is fluid and cursive, with a large initial "J" and "M".

JOHN MOSHER
Environmental Program Manager

Enclosure: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/4314

November 15, 2007

Mr. Russ Morgan
Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
Northeast Regional Office
107 20th Street
La Grande, OR 97850

Dear Mr. Morgan:

Enclosed for your review is an early working draft of Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan. As you know from our previous meetings, we are in the process of updating this management plan and invite your agency's input on the draft. The purpose of this review is to solicit technical review early in the update process when it is easier to identify and address issues, so together we can make this a quality management plan for our installation's natural resources.

The Federal Sikes Act (codified in 16 USC 670, et. seq.) requires that military installations develop an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan in cooperation with the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife and have the final plan approved by your agency.

Additionally, as stated in Public Law 108-136 (The Defense Authorization Act of 2004), an approved Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan that has benefits for a listed species shall take the place of designated critical habitat on the military installation. It is to all our benefit to do what we can to make these resource management plans of the highest quality.

This draft is a large document that will require a substantial commitment of your time for review. However, to keep the update process progressing, we would appreciate your comments and ideas within 30 days of this letter. We will likely hold future meetings to address comments and concerns as necessary during continued draft document development.

Your point of contact for questions and comments concerning the development of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan is Mr. John Phillips of the Environmental Division, at (360) 257-8873.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "John Mosher", written in a cursive style.

JOHN MOSHER
Environmental Program Manager

Enclosure: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

Oregon

Theodore R. Kulongoski, Governor

Department of Fish and Wildlife

Heppner District Office

PO Box 363

54173 Hwy. 74

Heppner, OR 97836

(541) 676-5230

FAX (541) 676-9075

March 10, 2008

John Phillips, Environmental Division
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, WA 98278

Dear John:

This letter is in regards to your request for comments on your draft Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) for the Boardman Bombing Range. I have had a chance to read through the draft plan and have a few comments on some of the proposed activities on the range.

On page 4-4 it states that annual monitoring of Washington ground squirrels (WGS) will provide information on the success of the conservation measures. While ODFW feels that yearly surveys for WGS would be helpful and insightful and could potentially be involved in future ground squirrel surveys, it would however, be difficult for ODFW to help out with yearly surveys due to budgetary and time constraints on existing personnel.

On page 4-8 the plan states that it is not recommended to remove any live trees. ODFW would recommend that it would also state that any dead trees would not be removed as well. These dead trees while they do not provide as good as habitat a live tree still provide valuable wildlife habitat.

On page 4-9 table 4-1 shows that the use of prescribed fire may be used to allow reestablishment of sagebrush and native grasses and forbs. ODFW would recommend that the Navy would only use prescribed fire during strict time frames and situations where a controlled fire would benefit the native vegetation on the range.

On page 4-11 the plan proposes using grazing of cheatgrass in late winter after a wildfire to improve habitat for WGS. While it has been a common practice to graze cheatgrass stands in winter and into early spring to help promote native bunch grasses ODFW is unaware of any research that has found that grazing cheatgrass is beneficial to WGS. While ODFW agrees that this type of grazing regime may help improve the vegetative composition of a site it is unknown if this type of grazing would be beneficial to WGS.

On page 4-12 the plan it states some concern about possible impacts to vegetation for pronghorn grazing on the range. While ODFW would support the yearly surveys of pronghorn on the installation it would be questionable if the minimal amounts of native pronghorn inhabiting the area are degrading the vegetation.

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On page 4-17 of the plan it states that permanent fire breaks would be used to help control fires on the Bombing range. ODFW does not believe that this would be a useful tool to control fires on the Bombing range. It has been shown during past fires that the fire break around the target area was unable to stop wildfires from spreading across the range. ODFW would not support converting existing habitat by creating fire breaks which may or may not conserve habitat in the future.

On page 4-19 of the plan it states that grazing may occur from January 1 to May 15. ODFW feels that this grazing period would be too long for the arid conditions that exist on the Bombing range and that by grazing that late might cause adverse affects to the native bunch grasses. ODFW would recommend that grazing would only be allowed from January 1 through March 31.

On page 4-19 the plan also shows a table that outlines the rest rotation of individual pastures that involves grazing one out of every five years. ODFW would recommend increasing to two years of rest out of every five years.

On page 4-20 the plan states that each pasture will have at least two watering locations and four would be recommended so that the watering areas could be rotated to minimize the destruction around watering sites. ODFW would recommend that the same watering site or sites are used year after year so that the destruction is localized to the same area instead of changing the area every year to move the disturbance. It is doubtful that an area with the amount of disturbance that is found around watering sites would recover in a year and would therefore just be more habitat that is disturbed in the long run.

On page 4-20 the plan also states that grazing may be used as a tool in juniper tree pastures to help lower the fuel loads and protect the juniper trees from potential wildfires. ODFW would question whether grazing by limiting the grass height in an area would help control the spread of a wildfire through the juniper covered portion of the range. ODFW would however agree that cattle influence into these areas that are naturally sandy would help prevent the naturally sandier and open habitats from becoming covered with cheatgrass and therefore helping control the spread of a wildfire which may kill the existing juniper trees.

On page 4-20 the plan states that reseeding would occur in any weed and cheatgrass control areas with native seed. ODFW would also recommend that grazing is deferred on those areas that are reseeded to allow the native seed to become established without grazing to inhibit the growth in the first one to two years depending on seed establishment.

On page A-2 the plan states that the primary effort to control noxious weeds would consist of manual or mechanical removal and secondary control is with herbicides. ODFW would question that with the size of the Bombing range and the current distribution of weeds across the range if control could be attained without the use of herbicides and would recommend using herbicides were practical.

Lastly ODFW is in the planning phase of a Ferruginous hawk telemetry study that would cover parts of the Columbia Basin to look at the effects of windpower projects on nesting hawks. I believe that the Bombing range might be a good control area to also complete some of this work and would ask the Navy if they would be interested in becoming a partner in this project.

I appreciate the opportunity to comment on this draft plan and look forward to working with you on the completion and implementation of the final plan. Please feel free to contact me at (541) 676-5230 if you have any questions on my comments or would like to discuss any other issues.

Respectfully,

Steve Cherry
District Biologist

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/4316

November 15, 2007

Ms. Leslie Nelson
The Nature Conservancy
Columbia Basin Stewardship Coordinator
P.O. Box 314
The Dalles, OR 97058

Dear Ms. Nelson:

Enclosed for your review is an early working draft of Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility - Boardman's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan. As you know from our previous meetings, we are in the process of updating this management plan and invite your agency's input on the draft. The purpose of this review is to solicit technical review early in the update process when it is easier to identify and address issues, so together we can make this a quality management plan for our installation's natural resources.

The Federal Sikes Act (codified in 16 USC 670, et. seq.) requires that military installations develop an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan in cooperation with the appropriate federal and state resource agencies. Since you are also a natural resource management partner with the Navy on the Bombing Range, we would like to include you in this endeavor.

Additionally, as stated in Public Law 108-136 (The Defense Authorization Act of 2004), an approved Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan that has benefits for a listed species shall take the place of designated critical habitat on the military installation. It is to all our benefit to do what we can to make these resource management plans of the highest quality.

This draft is a large document that will require a substantial commitment of your time for review. However, to keep the update process progressing, we would appreciate your comments and ideas within 30 days of this letter. We will likely hold future meetings to address comments and concerns as necessary during continued draft document development.

Your point of contact for questions and comments concerning the development of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan is Mr. John Phillips of the Environmental Division, at (360) 257-8873.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "John Mosher", with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

JOHN MOSHER
Environmental Program Manager

Enclosure: Draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

The Nature Conservancy in Oregon
Columbia Basin Office
PO Box 314
The Dalles, OR 97058

tel (541) 298-1802
(541) 980-3633
fax (541) 298-1802

nature.org

April 24, 2009

John Mosher
Environmental Program Manager
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, WA 98278-5000

Re: Comments on the January 2007 draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

Dear Mr. Mosher,

I am writing on behalf of The Nature Conservancy to offer our comments and recommendations regarding the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman. As you may know, The Nature Conservancy is a non-profit conservation organization whose mission is to protect the plants, animals, and natural communities that represent the diversity of life on Earth by protecting the lands and waters they need to survive. The Conservancy has an organization-wide commitment to working with partners to accomplish this mission in a science-based, collaborative manner. The Conservancy has worked closely with the Navy under a cooperative agreement to co-manage three Research Natural Areas (RNAs) on the NWSTF since their designation in 1978. We also coordinate with the Navy on various natural resource issues, ranging from invasive species control to developing and conducting wildlife and habitat research and surveys within the RNAs and throughout the NWSTF. The Conservancy also manages the 22,640-acre Boardman Conservation Area (BCA) immediately to the west of the NWSTF.

We have reviewed the draft 2007 INRMP and appreciate the opportunity to provide comments on the document, and offer the following:

Research Natural Areas

Three RNAs were established on the NWSTF in 1978 and are co-managed by The Conservancy under a long-standing MOU with the Navy. The RNAs on the NWSTF were the first established on DoD lands. The RNA program was created to 1) preserve examples of all significant natural ecosystems for comparison with those influenced by man, 1) provide educational and research areas for ecological and environmental studies, and 3) preserve gene pools of typical and endangered plants and animals. Conservancy activities in the RNAs include research and monitoring of the native habitat types and wildlife species, as well as control of noxious weeds.

As mentioned in the draft INRMP (Section 2.3.3, page 2-25), RNA-A encompasses the main target area and is highly disturbed. In addition, military training activities in the target area limit the type of natural resources-related activities that can be conducted there. The Conservancy would like to work with the Navy to determine the feasibility of moving RNA-A and identify the specific boundaries of a new location. We would propose moving RNA-A to another part of the NWSTF that is more representative of the unique habitat types the RNAs are designed to protect. An area equal in size to the current RNA-A (approximately 2,560 acres) but located in the more sandy soil types in the northwest portion of the NWSTF would protect exceptional examples of several critically imperiled plant community types, as defined by the Oregon Natural heritage Information Center and NatureServe including:

- *Purshia tridentata* / *Agropyron dasystachyum* - *Hesperostipa comata* - *Oryzopsis hymenoides* (Columbia River bunchgrass dunes – Antelope bitterbrush / thickspike wheatgrass - needle-and-threadgrass - Indian ricegrass),
- *Purshia tridentata* / *Hesperostipa comata* (Antelope bitterbrush / needle-and-threadgrass, and
- *Hesperostipa comata* - *Poa sandbergii* (needle-and-threadgrass - Sandberg's bluegrass).

Vegetation monitoring

To track changes in grassland and shrub-steppe condition, a range monitoring program was developed at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 to 1) interpret patterns of livestock utilization and 2) measure changes in the plant communities. Data was collected at 18 permanently marked locations in 1987, and those plots were not resurveyed until 2008. In the intervening 21 years, several large fires have burned through the site, military training activities have been reduced, and the grazing program has ceased. Data collected by Conservancy staff in 2008 should now be considered a new baseline to compare subsequent monitoring and the updated report should be included in the INRMP.

In order to collect meaningful information regarding changes to the plant communities over time, we would recommend that the vegetation monitoring be repeated at least every three years and the monitoring frequency should be increased following habitat-changing events, such as wildfires.

We would also encourage the Navy to 1) complete a thorough vegetation and habitat condition map, including a comprehensive weed inventory, to guide management activities and inform future land use decisions on the NWSTF and 2) expand weed control and native plant community restoration activities to improve the ecological condition of the native habitats found on the facility.

Wildlife monitoring

Very limited monitoring of the wildlife resources on the NWSTF is proposed in the draft INRMP. The Conservancy supports the proposed monitoring of large mammal, Washington ground squirrel, and burrowing owl populations. In light of the potential impacts of the proposed Oregon Military Department training ranges, we would recommend prioritizing the Washington ground squirrel surveys. At a minimum, the current status of the squirrels on the facility should be addressed in the INRMP and monitoring techniques for the species refined so that results are compatible with area monitoring efforts by partners. This would allow a coordinated approach to monitoring this species, currently listed as a candidate for federal listing; one which some conservation groups may petition for listing in the near future. We would also recommend expanding the wildlife monitoring program to include other important and sensitive species found on the facility, including ferruginous and Swainson's hawks, sagebrush obligate species such as loggerhead shrikes, sage sparrows and sagebrush lizards, and grassland obligate species such as grasshopper sparrows and long-billed curlews.

Wildfire response planning

The native plant communities on nearly the entire NWSTF have been impacted by wildfires over the last two years. While fire is a natural occurrence in the grassland and shrub-steppe communities of the Columbia Basin Ecoregion, widespread invasion of non-native annual grasses, in particular *Bromus tectorum*, has increased the intensity and frequency of naturally occurring fires. In addition, wildfires on the facility are often wind driven and therefore can become quite large in a short span of time.

Navy personnel response to wildfires on the NWSTF has been inconsistent and somewhat ad hoc in the past. Fire breaks around the perimeter of the target area and along the east facility boundary have not been consistently maintained. Fire lines are plowed during the course of wildfires without consideration of the fragile nature of the native plant communities on the site, or the impacts to the

sensitive wildlife species that are found there. Often, in these sensitive plant communities, the damage done by personnel responding to wildfire on the site is far greater than that done by the fire.

We would encourage development of a comprehensive wildfire response plan for the facility to guide 1) preventative actions, such as locations, size, and maintenance plans for permanent fire breaks, and 2) reactive actions, such as logical locations for temporary fire lines, use of wet lines and considerations for access to water sources. The plan should also identify rehabilitative actions to be taken after wildfires to aid recovery of areas disturbed during fire suppression activities.

We would further recommend that Navy and other personnel who may respond to wildfires on the facility be trained in regards to the important natural resources found on the site and instructed to conduct wildfire response in a manner that is sensitive to those resources.

Off-road vehicle use

We would recommend including guidelines in the INRMP that would confine all vehicular travel by Navy personnel, Oregon Military Department personnel, contractors, and visitors to existing access roads.

During the course of our work on the NWSTF and adjacent BCA the last few years, Conservancy staff have noticed an alarming increase in evidence of off-road vehicle travel on the facility (that was not associated with wildfire suppression efforts). Four wheel drive vehicles and ATVs impact the fragile grassland and shrub-steppe plant communities on the NWSTF in several ways: 1) vehicles of any type crush and break the biological soil crusts composed of lichens, mosses, bacteria, and algae that function as living mulch by retaining soil moisture and discouraging weed growth, 2) travel from or through weed infested areas prior to entry into more pristine areas can spread noxious weed and non-native annual grass seeds, 3) disruption of biological soil crusts and loosening of surface soil can promote erosion, especially on hillsides, which is exacerbated by the strong winds that are common to the area, and 4) motorized vehicles can harass resident birds and mammals, disrupting breeding and rearing of young.

OMD use

Oregon Military Department training facilities that have been proposed on the NWSTF are only mentioned in passing in the draft INRMP. The Conservancy has submitted comments on the first draft of the OMD proposed facilities and we understand that the impact of those facilities will eventually be evaluated under a separate National Environmental Policy Act review. However, we recommend the INRMP should include measures to ensure current and ongoing Oregon National Guard training activities do not compromise the ecological integrity of the NWSTF.

We appreciate this opportunity to provide comments on the draft INRMP. We would like to continue to work with you to find ways to maintain and/or enhance the habitat and wildlife resources of the NWSTF. If you have any questions regarding these comments, please contact me at 541-298-1802.

Sincerely,

Leslie Nelson
Columbia Basin Project Manager
The Nature Conservancy

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090
Ser N44/0508
April 20, 2010

The Honorable Elwood H. Patawa
Chairman, Board of Trustees
Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation
46411 Timine Way
Pendleton, OR 97801

Dear Mr. Chairman:

The purpose of this letter is to inform you that Naval Air Station (NAS) Whidbey Island is in the process of preparing an Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon. The INRMP is the strategic planning document for natural resources at NWSTF Boardman and is designed to guide natural resources management planning for a 5-year period under the Federal Sikes Act.

The Navy has been working with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW) in developing this management strategy and INRMP draft, per requirements of the Federal Sikes Act. Enclosed is a copy of this draft plan for your reference and review. Since this is a strategic planning document, there is not enough detail in any project action at this point to be able to determine direct impacts to resources of tribal interest. It is our intent to engage the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation (CTUIR) each year in the late summer timeframe to gather specific input on the following years' scheduled and funded natural resource management projects. That information will be used in annual discussions with the USFWS and ODFW for updates to the plan's management strategy, modifications to individual projects and to incorporate CTUIR concerns.

The Navy believes there is minimal potential to significantly impact protected tribal resources, tribal rights or Indian lands from the development of the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. We are very interested in getting your input on this natural resources management strategy and respectfully request that you respond via written correspondence with any comments and concerns that you may have and assist the Navy in identifying protected tribal trust resources and tribal rights.

5090
Ser N44/0508
April 20, 2010

Should formal government-to-government consultation be desired, please provide, via written correspondence the name and title of the designated tribal leader and tribe officials to whom consultation should be directed. The Navy would like to receive your response within 60 days of receipt of this letter.

If you have questions, concerns or require further information regarding the proposed activity, please contact our Cultural Resources Program Manager, Ms. Jackie Queen, at (360) 257-5320 or jackie.queen@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

P. A. MEHL
Commander, U.S. Navy
Commanding Officer
Acting

Enclosure (1): Draft NWSTF Boardman INRMP

Copy to w/o enclosure: Mr. Eric Quaempts, Director, Department of Natural Resources, CTUIR

Copy to w/o enclosure: Ms. Carey L. Miller, Tribal Historic Preservation Officer, CTUIR

July 8, 2010

P. A. Mehl, Commander
U.S. Navy
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, WA 98278-5000

Dear Commander Mehl:

The Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation (CTUIR) Department of Natural Resources (DNR) appreciates the opportunity to review the draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility at Boardman, Oregon, Boardman Bombing Range Complex (BBRC). The CTUIR requests government-to-government consultation regarding the INRMP. There are several issues that are not addressed in the INRMP which should be more carefully explored in the document. These issues include the treaty rights of CTUIR members, the impacts of the project on cultural resources, potential adverse impacts of increased operations at the facility on Washington ground, and the adequacy of funding for the United States Navy's natural and cultural resource management missions of the BBRC.

Pursuant to the Treaty of 1855 between the United States and the CTUIR, 12 Stat. 945, members of the CTUIR retain the right to hunt on the BBRC. In the Treaty the CTUIR reserved the pre-existing right to hunt on "unclaimed lands." There is a great deal of precedent interpreting the meaning of "unclaimed lands." One of the more thorough decisions defining the meaning of "unclaimed lands" is *State of Washington v. Buchanan*, 138 Wash.2d 186 (1999). In that case, the Washington State Supreme Court concluded the following:

From the rulings in the various cases which discuss the issue, and in light of the treaty language, we discern that a general statement of the rule is that publicly-owned lands, which are not obviously occupied and which are put to a use which is compatible with hunting, are "open and unclaimed lands" under the terms of the Stevens Treaties. Treaty hunters have a right to hunt on such lands, unrestricted by State regulation, unless the regulations are necessary for conservation purposes. *Miller*, 102 Wash.2d 678, 689 P.2d 81. In this case, the Oak Creek Wildlife Area is publicly owned, is obviously unoccupied, and its purposes are compatible with and, in fact, include hunting. The trial court and Court of Appeals correctly determined that the Oak Creek Wildlife Area is open and unclaimed land.¹

In *United States v. Hicks*, 587 F. Supp. 1162 (W.D. Wash), the court held that "lands cease to be 'open and unclaimed' when they are put to uses incompatible with hunting." The Navy does not manage the BBRC in a way that is incompatible with hunting, as it makes these lands available for hunting to Navy personnel stationed at the BBRC and Whidbey Island, as well as their guests. INRMP, page 3-5. The 1999 INRMP made hunting on the BBRC available to non-Navy active duty personnel. 1999 INRMP, Appendix K, page 3. Since the Navy allows hunting on the BBRC, it is "unclaimed" within the meaning of the Treaty of 1855 and therefore available to CTUIR members to

¹ *State of Washington v. Buchanan*, 138 Wash.2d 186, 211 (1999).

CTUIR DNR Letter to Commander Mehl, U.S. Navy
Re: Draft INRMP for Boardman Bombing Range Complex
July 8, 2010
Page 2 of 4

hunt. Any safety concerns regarding use of the area can be addressed with training for tribal members. Similar training is given to members of the Yakama Nation who exercise treaty hunting rights on the U.S. Army Yakima Training Center.

The INRMP does not address cultural resource planning or the impacts on cultural resources associated with activities at the BBRC. Staff with the CTUIR Cultural Resources Protection Program have spoken to the Navy archaeologist with responsibilities at the BBRC who indicated that an Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) is planned for the BBRC, but currently is not funded. The CTUIR DNR would like to see a plan to identify and evaluate all historic properties within the BBRC, including historic properties of religious and cultural significance to tribes, in place prior to approving an INRMP. Because the INRMP identifies appropriate land use activities for the BBRC, it should not be approved without an accurate inventory of cultural resources on the BBRC and analysis of impacts to these resources. The Oregon State Historic Preservation Office has indicated that only a portion of the bombing range has been surveyed. The National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) contemplates the consideration of the impacts to historic properties during the planning process and should be discussed in the INRMP. Put another way, the presence or absence of cultural resources will drive land management decisions. If the INRMP is developed without consideration of impacts to historic properties, the NHPA will only be addressed, if at all, after projects are identified and implemented pursuant to the INRMP. Further, while the INRMP does not propose any public use of the complex, one of the objectives of the INRMP is to “[m]anage natural resources to provide outdoor recreation opportunities that are compatible with security, safety and operations.” INRMP, page 1-1. Obviously, any use of the BBRC requires a careful examination of the impacts to historic properties

Section 1.4.5 on page 1-3 references the obligation to coordinate wildlife management through the United States Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW). This section should also mention the obligation of the Navy to consult with the CTUIR on wildlife management decisions. The CTUIR is a co-manager with the USFWS and ODFW of wildlife resources to which we possess a treaty right. The Navy’s obligation to consult with the CTUIR on treaty-reserved resources is specifically identified in the Department of Defense American Indian and Alaska Native Policy. The policy states that the Department of Defense will build relationships with tribes by “[a]ssessing, through consultation, the effect of proposed DoD actions that may have the potential to significantly affect protected tribal resources, tribal rights, and Indian lands before decisions are made[.]” The Navy cannot know what resources the CTUIR values, the scope of tribal treaty rights, or what actions may significantly impact them without first consulting with the CTUIR.

The annotated Department of Defense American Indian and Alaska Native Policy bears out this fact by acknowledging in footnote (c):

[T]he policy anticipates a two-step process designed first, to overcome the fact that, as non-Indians, we may not always recognize the effect our actions may have on tribal interests unless we ask; and second, to permit DoD to proceed without the need for further consultation unless potentially *significant* consequences are identified during this initial discussion.

In Section 3.3 on page 3-4, under Executive Orders, the INRMP should include reference to EO 13175, "Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments."

In Section 2.2 on page 2-1, the INRMP states that "[r]enewed air-to-ground training activities are likely to meet future military training requirements." This statement raises concerns regarding impacts of air-to-ground activities on natural and cultural resources including Washington ground squirrels and other wildlife. How will the plan to renew air-to-ground activities be consistent with the need to protect and manage for wildlife and associated habitats and cultural resources? The INRMP concedes that the BBRC "supports the majority of Oregon's remaining populations of this squirrel." INRMP, page 2-65. Appendix K acknowledges that the Oregon population of Washington ground squirrels "is almost entirely on the Naval Weapons System Training Facility-Boardman[.]" INRMP, App. K, Delavan Thesis, page 13. Figure 2-23 on page 67 displays all Washington ground squirrel locations from the 2006 survey. Newer data exist from surveys of the site. Please include the most recent data in your analysis. Further, in order to adequately characterize suitable habitat for the Washington ground squirrel, the INRMP should display all detections on record, including historic and present-day data, to demonstrate where they have lived on the facility.

The Oregon Military Department has proposed in the past to utilize the BBRC for Oregon National Guard (ONG) training, but the INRMP does not specifically address this proposal or the potential for increased operations and activities. The only mention in the INRMP of ONG use of the BBRC is on page 2-1, which states that "[o]ther military units including the Oregon Army and Air National Guard and other Department of Defense agencies use the area occasionally for training exercises." The INRMP does not provide any specific detail about potential ONG or other exercise expansion at the BBRC except for Appendix G, the BBRC Wildland Fire-Potential Report, which was coincidentally written by a contractor for the Oregon Military Department. The Appendix states, "[i]t is understood that the Oregon National Guard expects to use the facility for training when possible every weekend during the year." INRMP, App. G, Section VI (no page numbers). The CTUIR requests consultation regarding the present and future plans of the ONG and other agency utilization of the BBRC.

On May 28, 2010, the *East Oregonian* in Pendleton published an article entitled "Morrow County leaders talk Navy swap." The article (attached) indicates that the Navy viewed a proposal for county use of BBRC lands positively. Certainly neither the *East Oregonian* nor Morrow County know exactly what the Navy will approve, but the CTUIR DNR would like to know whether the Navy would or could legally consider a land transfer of BBRC lands. Further, the CTUIR DNR would like to know whether the Navy is considering proposals for use of Navy land by outside organizations.

Section 4.6.3.1, page 4-14, Grazing and Crop Circles, indicates that lands in the BBRC were leased for grazing and agriculture until 2002 when those leases were terminated. The INRMP concludes that no agricultural leases are anticipated during the term of the INRPM; however, it does not indicate whether there are any plans to resume grazing or whether grazing may be compatible with other planned land uses on the BBRC. The INRMP should specifically identify which practices are and are not consistent with the mission of the BBRC. Grazing of delicate shrub-steppe habitats may facilitate the spread and establishment of non-native weedy species through destruction of the

CTUIR DNR Letter to Commander Mehl, U.S. Navy
Re: Draft INRMP for Boardman Bombing Range Complex
July 8, 2010
Page 4 of 4

cryptogamic soil crust. While the INRMP indicates that no agricultural leases are anticipated, it should identify whether or not leases are possible or whether they should be prohibited as incompatible with the mission of the facility to “ensure the sustainability of all ecosystems” on the installation. INRMP, page 1-1.

In Appendix A, Table A-1 (no page number), the Fire Management section needs to propose funding to provide necessary protection to facility habitats from natural and operationally caused wildfires. Failure to adequately address wildfires places important habitats at risk to short- and long-term degradation from wildfires. The Navy needs to remedy this situation.

As to technical changes, the last full paragraph on page 1-5 starts with “Over the last several years . . .” It should read “Over the last 20 years . . .” On page 3-3, the title of Section 3.2.5 inserts an extra space in the word “Protection.”

As noted above, the CTUIR requests government-to-government consultation on the INRMP. The initial government-to-government consultation will occur at the staff level between the Navy and DNR. Thereafter, DNR will brief the CTUIR Board of Trustees (BOT), the tribal governing body, on the project in preparation for a meeting between the policy leadership of the Navy and the BOT to occur after the staff meeting. The CTUIR Consultation Policy explaining this process is attached.

The CTUIR DNR will continue to review the INRMP until our staff meeting to identify any additional potential concerns. Such concerns may be raised in future meetings between the Navy and the BOT as well. I recommend that the issues identified in this letter and explored in our government-to-government meetings be included and addressed in the Environmental Assessment or Environmental Impact Statement for the INRMP. Please have your staff contact Audie Huber, Intergovernmental Affairs Manager of DNR, at 541-429-7228 to schedule the staff-to-staff meeting.

Sincerely,

Eric Quaempts, Director
Department of Natural Resources.

Attachments:

East Oregonian Article, Morrow County Leaders talk Navy swap, May 28, 2010
CTUIR Paper on Consultation

Rainfall nears record

By DEAN BRICKY
Staff Oregonian

Those who remember wet Memorial Day weekend outings of the past — have coverage. Sunday may be the first dry day in a week.

May has been wet in Pendleton, and it's drawing close to the record. Records show 2.65 inches

of precipitation through Wednesday. The record was 2.38 inches in 1961.

Thursday did set an individual record for the date at .55 inches of rain in Pendleton. The previous record of .54 inches was set in 1906.

Meteorologists at the National Weather Service Forecast Office in Pendleton predict

See RAIN/3A

Morrow County leaders talk Navy swap

County will trade energy for use of bombing range land

By KATH MILLS
Staff Oregonian

The Navy may be getting more flexible on issues surrounding the Boardman bombing range.

After a Tuesday meeting with Rear Adm. James Symonds, commander of the Navy's northwest region,

Morrow County Judge Jerry Tallman and others went away hopeful the Navy may step up fire control and restoration on the range, allow the county to manage Bombing Range Road and perhaps even allow a transmission line or two.

Tallman also is hopeful of a plan to swap land for so-

ary with the Navy, and federal government is requiring the Department of Defense to use more energy from renewable sources such as wind. Morrow County could supply some of that energy to the Navy in exchange for access to the bombing range,

See MORROW/3A

House races in Eastern Oregon tops in re

Candidates spend more cash than any other races in state

Campaign

By PHIL WRIGHT
Staff Oregonian

Eastern Oregon's two key races for the state House were the most expensive representative campaigns in this year's primary. Only statewide races reported spending more on primary campaigns.

Rep. Bob Jensen narrowly defeated challenger Mike Mathison to earn the Republican nomination for House District 58, and Rep. Greg

Smith outbilled Colleen MacLeod to win the spot on the Republican ticket in the House District 57 race.

With the latest expenditures in ORESTAR, Oregon's online campaign finance database, shows spending in the House District 58 race topped \$118,000. Smith alone, however, outspend that, and he and MacLeod shovled almost \$200,000 into their race.

Jensen has reported spending \$80,000, and Mathison paid out almost \$22,476. Jen-

son won 2,587-2,200. On a cost-per-vote basis, though, Mathison was the winner, spending just \$6.27 per vote while Jensen spent \$4.15 per vote.

That doesn't take into account the nearly \$5,000 Mathison still owes.

Smith's reported expenditures this year of \$117,386 is tops among Oregon lawmakers in the primary. MacLeod, though, was no slouch, spury-

Below is the campaign

As a comparison, he

candidate John Kitchel

Greg Sm

Bob Jens

Colleen MacLo

Mike Mathis

See CAMPAIGN/3A

East Oregonian Daily

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BREAKING NEWS — 24 hours a day, seven days a week

near 75. There's not a peep about wind or rain, so con-

cloudy with the high temperature about 75.

MORROW: Roads in range are of concern to county

Continued From 1A

which the county would use to grow a crop, Tallman said.

"(Symonds') indications were that he was very positive toward that possibility," he said.

In the past, Morrow County officials have been frustrated with the Navy's lack of communication concerning the bombing range. Not only does it take more than 46,445 acres of land out of the county's economy, wildfires on the range are a nearly annual occurrence.

Two years ago, blowing sand after a wildfire became so bad that road crews had to repeatedly close Bombing Range Road. The Navy finally agreed to help the county put up a silt fence along a portion of the range, but only after Sen. Ron Wyden, D-Ore., sent a letter to the Navy — Tallman's letters to the military were disregarded.

Officials would also like to see the Navy allow transmission lines, such as Idaho Power's Boardman-to-Hemingway line, to cross the northern edge of the range.

Portland General Electric wants the Navy's cooperation with its Cascade crossing transmission project, a 500-kilovolt line that will run from Boardman to Salem.

Both Idaho Power's and PGE's line will meet at a substation near the Boardman Power Plant, not far

from the bombing range. Two PGE representatives, Mike Mikolaitis and Mike Livingston, attended the meeting with Morrow County officials at the Naval air base on Whidbey Island.

Tallman said that, prior to the meeting, the Navy's response to PGE concerning the transmission line was an absolute no.

"(But) at the end of the meeting, alternatives were discussed," Tallman said. "It kind of opened it up again, so maybe that could happen."

The director of the Morrow County Public Works Department, Burke O'Brien, also attended the Whidbey Island meeting. His concern was primarily roads: Bombing Range Road and Juniper Canyon Road, which runs into the bombing range from the south.

The petition for Juniper Canyon road was filed in 1886, O'Brien said, which makes it an historic route of traffic. County road crews are not allowed on the range, however, and it needs repair.

"We told the Navy we felt we should do some house-keeping," O'Brien told the county court at its Wednesday meeting. More discussion on the topic needs to happen, he added.

**Get The
Facts On
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*See if
it's right*

Anthony Lakes
RD PASS SALE

The Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation

Consultation: Government to Government (or otherwise)

WHAT IS CONSULTATION?

CONSULTATION. Deliberation of persons on some subject. State District Court of Third Judicial Dist. in and for Powell County, 85 Mont. 215, 278 P. 122, 125. A conference between the counsel engaged in a case to discuss its questions or arrange the method of conducting it. In French Law. The opinion of counsel upon a point of law submitted to them. Black's Law Dictionary, DeLuxe Fourth Edition. West Publishing Co., (1951).

CONSULTATION \,kan(t)-sel-'ta-shen\ n **1:** COUNCIL, CONFERENCE; *specif.* a deliberation between physicians on a case or its treatment **2:** the act of consulting or conferring. Webster's New Collegiate Dictionary, G & C MERRIAM COMPANY, (1979).

Consultation is the formal process of negotiation, cooperation and policy-level decision-making between the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation (CTUIR) and the United States federal government. As such, consultation is the bilateral decision-making process of two sovereigns: the Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation and the United States Government.

It is critical to understand that consultation is not just a process or a means to an end. Rather, consultation is the process that ultimately leads up to and includes a **decision**. *The most important component of consultation is the ultimate decision*. Consultation then is the formal effort between two sovereigns of making policy level decisions.

It is equally important to understand what consultation is not. Consultation is not notifying a Tribal government that an action will occur, requesting written comments on that prospective action, and then proceeding with the action. In this scenario the decision is not affected. This is not consultation.

WHAT ARE THE OBJECTIVES OF CONSULTATION?

- a. Assure that CTUIR Board of Trustees understands the technical and legal issues necessary to make an informed policy decision.
- b. Improved policy-level decision making of both CTUIR and federal government.

- c. Bi-lateral decision making among sovereigns (co-management).
- d. Protection of CTUIR lifestyle, culture, religion, economy.
- e. Compliance with Tribal laws.
- f. Compliance with federal Indian law; federal statutes; federal policy.
- g. Develop and achieve mutual decisions.
- h. Improve the integrity and longevity of decisions.

HOW DOES CONSULTATION WORK?

Consultation works through the same procedures and steps that are common-place for most federal agencies: technical meetings and policy meetings. From a practical standpoint, consultation requires an ability to differentiate between technical and policy issues; this allows for proper technical level staff consultation and then policy-level consultation for those issues that remain unresolved or for those issues that are clearly only resolvable at the policy level. Consultation is the process of coming to common understanding of the technical and legal issues that affect or are affected by a decision. Consultation is using this common understanding to make a decision.

Consultation does not portend to mandate a certain decision; most Tribal governments are much more willing to address cooperatively a decision that on the surface is distasteful than if they had not been thoroughly consulted with prior to facing that distasteful decision.

Meaningful consultation requires that federal agencies and Tribes understand respective roles and have a basic understanding of the legal underpinnings of the government-to-government relationship, including the responsibility of the federal government under the Trust doctrine. In addition, federal agencies will benefit from some understanding of tribal culture, perspectives, world view, and aboriginal rights. Tribal governments must understand the policy decision-making authority of the federal agency. Tribal governments must understand the non-tribal politics of the federal agency decision that consultation will affect.

Tribal governments must also understand the federal and state laws within which the agency must operate. In these examples, it is critical to note that a Tribal government cannot understand the politics of the federal agency decision without personal communications. Similarly, the federal agency cannot understand the Tribe's world view unless agency staff meet with the Tribe to discuss that world view. The lesson here is that consultation has a foundation of communication. Without communication, consultation is thwarted and a mutual decision is impossible.

Thus in a hypothetical example, consultation works like this:

1. Federal agency contacts Tribal government to advise of an impending project proposal or to conduct an activity that may or may not impact a tribal resource or issue.¹
2. CTUIR responds back that this issue is important and that it would like to initiate consultation. CTUIR requests federal agency technical experts meet with CTUIR technical representatives (or CTUIR requests a policy level meeting).
3. Consultation has been initiated. Technical staffs meet. Technical and legal issues are discussed; the result is that CTUIR staff understand the proposal and federal agency staff understand at technical level why this proposed activity is of concern. This allows respective technical staff to brief respective policy entities and to provide informed opinions and recommendations.
4. CTUIR staff brief the proper Tribal policy entity. Consultation steps are defined, written down and then transmitted to federal agency.² Agreement is reached upon this consultation process.
5. Additional meetings are held, if necessary, leading up to the decision.
6. Federal agency and CTUIR formulate a decision. Ultimately and optimistically this decision is consistent with federal laws and tribal laws and policies. This means the decision is consistent with applicable natural and cultural resource laws and policies, with the Doctrine of Trust Responsibility and with federal Indian law. For the CTUIR specifically, it means the decision protects the resources to which the CTUIR has specific aboriginal and treaty reserved rights, protects the unique culture and world view and enables continued practice of the Tribal religion.

Most important is that leading up to the decision, the Tribal Government and the federal government have communicated. Mutual understanding and trust have been developed. Without mutual understanding and mutual trust a mutual decision is nearly unthinkable. History is replete with examples of such failures. In any event, the CTUIR perspective regarding the decision to formally consult or not to consult is that those entities required by law or policy to consult with Tribes is obviously to consult, or at the minimum, ask the CTUIR. The consequences of consulting when not required is preferred to the consequences of misjudging and not consulting when required.

¹ It is crucial to note here that the federal agency contacted the CTUIR because of an impending *decision* that the federal agency will have to make in the near future. Remember, it is that *decision* that consultation is focused upon. Also note that, depending upon the issue, the CTUIR could have contacted the federal agency to initiate consultation.

² These steps are usually no more complicated than additional technical level meetings, later policy level meetings, potential mutual measures to obtain additional information, and finally a policy level meeting to make the ultimate decision.

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
3730 NORTH CHARLES PORTER AVENUE
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

IN REPLY REFER TO :
5090
Ser N44/0248

February 25, 2011

Mr. Eric Quaempts
Director, Department of Natural Resources
Confederated Tribes of the Umatilla Indian Reservation
46411 Timine Way
Pendleton, OR 97801

Dear Mr. Quaempts:

This responds to your letter dated July 8, 2010, in which you reviewed and provided comments on the January 2010 draft Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman and includes dialog from a meeting between our natural resources staff held on August 26, 2010. The below information is provided addressing specific issues identified in your letter. The Navy greatly appreciates your assistance in developing natural resources management strategies for NWSTF Boardman. Navy INRMPs guide natural resources management actions on NWSTF Boardman as required under the Sikes Act. Working with our federal, state and tribal management partners helps us improve and develop a better natural resources management plan.

The Navy recognizes the relationship with Confederated Tribe of the Umatilla Indian Reservation (CTUIR) especially in respect to treaty-reserved resources, which is why you have been engaged in preparation of the INRMP. It is our policy to pursue this coordination. Executive Order 13175 is an important guiding document and will be included by reference.

There has been a small informal and intermittent hunting program since the late 1990s at NWSTF Boardman for Sailors stationed at the range and their guests. As discussed in the August 2010 meeting, the Navy issued new access regulations for NWSTF Boardman, in August 2009 (NASWHIDBEYINST 8020.8), to meet safety requirements for an active military bombing range. This regulation restricts access to NWSTF Boardman to military training and direct training support activities. Access for hunting on NWSTF Boardman is not consistent with these safety and access requirements. Therefore, hunting access has been immediately closed for all participants. The hunting section in the INRMP is being changed accordingly.

The Navy recognizes the CTUIR's reserved right to hunt on unclaimed federal lands through the Treaty of 1855 and wording to that effect will be placed in the Environmental Management Strategy section of the plan that describes legal requirements and mandates. Should hunting become a suitable use for the range at anytime in the future,

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February 25, 2011

we will notify CTUIR of this change and modify the INRMP to outline and codify requirements for that access.

The draft INRMP does not address cultural resources management, although, it recognizes that natural resources actions may impact cultural resources. An Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) for NWSTF Boardman is being developed and CTUIR will be engaged in that process when a draft is ready for review. The INRMP is a strategic plan that identifies broad strategies and actions. Right now, those actions are not sufficiently defined to evaluate their individual or cumulative impacts to cultural resources. The Navy will fully comply with the National Historic Preservation Act, Navy tribal coordination policy and any future ICRMP for each of these actions before they are implemented. The Navy will provide a list of projects and actions to the CTUIR each fiscal year for review and comment. Sufficient detail will be available to evaluate impact to cultural resources at that point.

Washington ground squirrels (WGS) are a major management focus of the INRMP, and we recognize that NWSTF Boardman plays a very important role to the success of that species. Air-to-ground training has occurred with less frequency over the last several years, especially when compared to the 1970s-1980s. Future air-to-ground training may increase as new types of aircraft enter into service. Future changes in training will be analyzed separately as they emerge and will be addressed in future INRMP updates to include complete impact analysis to natural resources including WGS. The WGS locations presented in the draft INRMP graphic is a compilation of all monitored WGS locations, including all colonies and incidental sightings data up to the 2006 property-wide survey done in cooperation with the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife. This is the last property-wide survey conducted for the species. This discussion will be modified to better describe data presented in that graphic.

The draft INRMP describes natural resources management plans for current training activities. Future activities are not finalized and cannot be described to develop natural resources management actions at this time. The previous Oregon Military Department proposal and Environmental Assessment that you referenced was never finalized or implemented. The Navy is currently assessing overall training needs for NWSTF Boardman, including those of the Oregon National Guard. The CTUIR will be part of this planning process for the Environmental Impact Statement and fully engaged in reviewing and commenting on those training proposals. Following the Record of Decision, any new training actions will be incorporated into the INRMP, and new management actions will be developed for natural resources at NWSTF Boardman.

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Your letter referenced an article published in the East Oregonian on May 28, 2010, that stated the Navy was talking with Morrow County about a land swap. You asked if any land was available for use by outside organizations. The article is misleading. Morrow County has approached the Navy to lease and/or use portions of NWSTF Boardman for agriculture and aquifer recharge. The Navy has informed Morrow County that the proposal is not compatible with military training requirements of the range and that no land is currently under-utilized or in excess at NWSTF Boardman that would be available for lease or disposal. Because of your trust resource status with NWSTF Boardman, CTUIR will be notified if any land becomes available for lease or disposal.

All grazing and agriculture out-leases were terminated in 2002 and the Navy does not anticipate any leases during the five-year planning scope of the draft INRMP. The INRMP does not make permanent land use changes to NWSTF Boardman, but sets the natural resources management goals and objectives for the five-year period. Grazing may be a viable management tool if conditions, needs and safety requirements change in the future. Re-initiation of a grazing or agriculture program will receive a full environmental review to evaluate impacts and determine when, where and what size of a program is suitable.

Fire suppression is a very important component to the management of NWSTF Boardman and has a large impact on natural resources. However, fire suppression is not a natural resources program within the Navy. Appendix A has several pre- and post-fire related projects, but funding for protection is not included because it is not provided in the natural resources budget. Navy Region Northwest is developing a fire management plan for its installations. The natural resources program for NWSTF Boardman will provide input to protect important natural resources, to ensure firebreaks are constructed and placed with the least amount of natural resource impact and to establish post-fire restoration objectives. The fire management and natural resources programs are coordinating to better protect natural resources on the range.

The Navy greatly appreciates your willingness to review and comment on the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. This will help improve the natural resources program on the range and foster a working relationship between our two organizations. The changes discussed will be incorporated and the INRMP finalized for NWSTF Boardman.

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February 25, 2011

Should you desire a meeting with the CTUIR Board of Trustees, have further questions or wish to have further discussion please contact my Natural Resources Manager, Mr. John Phillips at (360) 257-8873 or john.r.phillips1@navy.mil.

Sincerely,

G. J. JOHNSTON
Captain, U.S. Navy
Commanding Officer

Copy to:
Ms. Audie Huber (CTUIR, DNR)

From: Phillips, John R CIV NAVFAC NW, Environmental
To: ["Audie Huber"](#)
Cc: [Haussamen, Walter CIV NAVFAC NW, PRW4](#)
Subject: RE: Boardman Bombing Range INRMP
Date: Tuesday, January 25, 2011 14:59:00

Hi Audie,

I have been recently sidetracked on other Navy projects here in WA and have just recently got back to the Boardman INRMP. Yes, the Command has finished its review of the suitability of a hunting program on the bombing range in light of their new access instruction. We owe you a written response to the questions in your original letter and I am coordinating that right now for the Commanding Officers signature. I hope to have that out to you soon. I will keep you updated on the status of that.

From our meeting, you guys were going to send me some preferred wording on Tribal trust resources treaty rights that I could fit into the INRMP requirements section. Are you still going to be able to do that?

Yes, my understanding is the Navy is also working on an Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan for NWSTF Boardman. I am not quite sure what the actual status of that document is, but I am sure they will be engaging you soon on review of that.

I hope this helps update you on where we are with the INRMP review. I do have a question for you. Once we finish up INRMP discussions, do you see a formal G2G meeting between the CO and your Council closing this all off or will completion of our discussions suffice at this point. The reason I ask is that our Navy G2G policy has formal CO/Council meetings being initiated by letter exchanges between the CO and Chair and that hasn't occurred to date. What are your thoughts. Thanks for the help.

John Phillips
Natural Resources Manager
NAS Whidbey Island
(360) 257-8873

-----Original Message-----

From: Audie Huber [<mailto:AudieHuber@ctuir.org>]
Sent: Tuesday, January 25, 2011 13:35
To: Phillips, John R CIV NAVFAC NW, Environmental
Subject: RE: Boardman Bombing Range INRMP

John, I just spoke to Amy Bert regarding the EIS and that reminded me about our discussions on the INRMP. I was curious how the project was going and whether there was any movement regarding our questions on hunting on the BBRC, cultural resource management planning, wildlife management coordination and fire management funding. I believe the Navy had planned an integrated cultural resource management plan but I was unclear whether that was going through or whether it was related more to the EIS or the INRMP. Thanks.

A

Naval Air Station Whidbey Island

Kimberly A. Martin
Public Affairs Officer
(360) 257-2286 FAX (360) 257-3972
E-mail: whdb_naswi_pao@navy.mil

NEWS

FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

**RELEASE 11-03
Mar. 11, 2011**

Comments requested on Environmental Assessment

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND, Wash. – The Navy is preparing an Environmental Assessment (EA) for the development of an updated Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman in Boardman, Ore. Per the Sikes Act, an INRMP is prepared to guide the management of natural resources on NWSTF Boardman. INRMPs are broad-scoped strategic management plans that set the goals and objectives for the natural resources program. The INRMP currently in place was signed and approved in 1999 and requires update to comply Department of Defense and Navy policies and be consistent with current natural resource issues and military training uses of the range.

The EA addresses a variety of Action Alternatives with associated impact levels on the land condition and wildlife resources on the Boardman range. The No Action Alternative continues implementation of the objectives and practices outlined in the existing INRMP of 1999. On-going practices used for natural resources management at NWSTF Boardman would continue as well as annual reviews and updates.

The Navy would like to incorporate and consider the public's comments and concerns as they prepare the EA and finalize the INRMP. A copy of the final draft of the Boardman INRMP dated January 2010 can be reviewed on the NAS Whidbey Island web site:

<https://www.cnic.navy.mil/Whidbey/Programs/DepartmentsSpecialAssistants/PublicWorksEnvironmental/PublicNotices/index.htm>

Submit comments by Mar. 25, 2011 to:

NAS Whidbey Island
Public Works Department, Natural Resources Management Program
1115 W. Lexington Street, Bldg. 103
Oak Harbor, WA 98278-3500

Please direct questions to John Phillips, Natural Resources Program Manager at (360) 257-8873.

Navy asks opinions on management plan

Posted: Sunday, March 13, 2011 3:13 am

BOARDMAN — The U.S. Navy is preparing an environmental assessment in preparation for updating its management plan for the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility near Boardman.

The plan will guide management of natural resources on the Boardman Bombing Range, which is south of Boardman.

John Phillips, the Navy's natural resource manager, said the current plan was approved in 1999. It must be updated to comply with federal policies.

He said the environmental assessment addresses a variety of alternatives with varying impacts on the land and wildlife resources.

"The Navy would like to incorporate and consider the public's comments and concerns," Phillips said.

A copy of the final draft of the management plan dated January 2010 can be reviewed at the Naval Air Station Whidbey Island website: www.cnmc.navy.mil.

Comments should be submitted by March 25 to NAS Whidbey Island, Public Works Department, Natural Resources Management Program, 1115 W. Lexington St., Building 103, Oak Harbor, Wash. 98278-3500.

—Dean Brickey

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APPENDIX D. Sikes Act Cooperative Agreement

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**WILDLIFE COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT
FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF WILDLIFE RESOURCES
AT NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY BOARDMAN**

PURPOSE AND AUTHORITY

This tripartite agreement is made and entered into by and between Naval Air Station Whidbey Island, hereinafter referred to as NAS Whidbey Island, acting by and through its authorized representative; the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, hereinafter referred to as the Service, acting by and through its authorized representative; and the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife, hereinafter referred to as the State, acting by and through its authorized representative. This agreement is entered into by NAS Whidbey Island under the authority of OPNAVINST 5090.1B, Sections 19-3.9 and 19-4.6.4; by the Service under the authority of the Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act, as amended (16 U.S.C. 661 *et seq.*), Fish and Wildlife Act of 1956, as amended (16 U.S.C. 742a-742j), and the Fish and Wildlife Improvement Act of 1978 (16 U.S.C. 7421); and by both parties under the authority of the Sikes Act, as amended (16 U.S.C. 670a-670o) and the Economy Act (31 U.S.C. 1535). This agreement is entered into by the State under the authority of RCW 39.29. This agreement documents the responsibilities of NAS Whidbey Island, the Service, and the State in coordinating and developing a Sikes Act Cooperative Conservation and Management Plan for Fish and Wildlife Resources, hereinafter referred to as the Cooperative Plan.

The purpose of this agreement is to provide a framework for the Service and the State to assist NAS Whidbey Island in the coordination, development and implementation of a Cooperative Plan for the protection, enhancement, restoration, and management of wildlife resources of state and national significance, and their habitats, at the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility Boardman installation, hereinafter referred to as NWSTF Boardman. This cooperative agreement, together with the Fish and Wildlife Management Section of the NWSTF Boardman Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan, hereinafter referred to as the NWSTF Boardman INRMP, constitutes the Cooperative Plan for wildlife management pursuant to the Sikes Act. The NWSTF Boardman INRMP will be available for review and approval by all signatory parties.

This agreement is within the purview of the National Environmental Policy Act (Public Law 91-190); the Endangered Species Act, as amended (Public Law 96-366); the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (16 U.S.C. Sections 703-711); Executive Order 11990 (Preservation of Wetlands); Conservation Programs on Military Reservations (Public Law 90-465); and Conservation and Rehabilitation Programs on Military and Public Lands (Public Law 93-452).

EXPLANATORY RECITALS AND MUTUAL AGREEMENTS

Whereas, wildlife species of national and state significance utilize lands of NWSTF Boardman to a significant extent; and,

Whereas, NWSTF Boardman through NAS Whidbey Island is responsible for the wise management of its fish and wildlife resources, and their habitats, as set forth in OPNAVINST 5090.1B, Chapter 22; and,

Whereas, the Sikes Act requires that fish and wildlife resources on military reservations be cooperatively managed by federal and state agencies having responsibilities for conservation and management of fish and wildlife resources; and,

Whereas, the Service is an agency of the U.S. Department of the Interior, a federal government entity responsible for conserving, protecting, and enhancing fish and wildlife resources and their habitats for the continuing benefit of the public; and

Whereas, the Service has national and regional policies to establish formal partnerships with other Federal, state, tribal, and private entities to guide the conservation, development, and management of the nation's fish and wildlife resources; and,

Whereas, the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife (ODFW) was created under the laws of the State of Oregon to protect, enhance, control, regulate, and manage fish and wildlife resources in Oregon; and,

Whereas, it is of mutual interest and benefit to NAS Whidbey Island, the Service and the State to work cooperatively for the common purpose of protecting, enhancing, and managing the wildlife resources at NWSTF Boardman for the best interest of the people of Oregon and the United States.

Therefore, it is mutually agreed that:

1. The signatory parties shall assist each other in development and implementation of a Cooperative Plan.
2. The Service and the State shall cooperate in providing an advisory role to NAS Whidbey Island in the preparation and periodic revision of the NWSTF Boardman INRMP.
3. The parties shall meet as necessary to coordinate, review, and update programs and objectives of the NWSTF Boardman INRMP. Proposed revisions to the INRMP will be made by mutual agreement of the signatory parties.
4. The parties shall review this agreement for adequacy and compliance not later than five years following the date it becomes effective and every five years thereafter.
5. Wildlife management programs resulting from the Cooperative Plan shall be coordinated to the maximum extent possible with other existing natural resource, outdoor recreation, and cultural/historical management programs at NWSTF Boardman.

6. The parties shall regulate hunting at NWSTF Boardman subject to applicable federal and state regulations.
7. Transplanting of wildlife species to NWSTF Boardman shall be consistent with applicable federal and state regulations and policies, and shall be authorized only by mutual consent of the signatory parties. Such authorization is to be based on appropriate supportive documentation such as capture/transplant plans, species recovery plans, and monitoring and management plans. Reintroduction of species once indigenous to NWSTF Boardman will be given strong consideration in the development of plans to transplant wildlife species.
8. The use of chemical toxicants for controlling nuisance wildlife species on NWSTF Boardman lands will be in accordance with current federal and state laws, regulations, and policies.

SPECIFIC RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE PARTIES

Section I. NAS Whidbey Island Responsibilities

Within the limitations of the assigned military mission and the availability of funds and personnel, NAS Whidbey Island shall:

1. Manage the natural resources program to protect wildlife resources and maintain favorable habitat for indigenous species of wildlife.
2. Strive to enhance wildlife habitats to the maximum extent possible and in accordance with objectives of the wildlife section of the NWSTF Boardman INRMP.
3. Protect threatened and endangered species, other species of concern, and their habitats, in accordance with federal and state laws.
4. Provide, as necessary, information, expertise, personnel, and equipment, and otherwise cooperate with the Service and the State in the management of wildlife resources on lands of NWSTF Boardman.
5. Provide a description of those areas where wildlife management activities are restricted due to NWSTF Boardman's mission (including a description of the restrictions), as well as a description of those areas suitable and available for use under the management plan without restrictions.
6. Provide, as may be necessary and if available, law enforcement assistance from designated NWSTF Boardman Security officers.
7. In a manner consistent with mission requirements, grant access to NWSTF Boardman to Service and State personnel, including law enforcement officers, upon receiving permission

from the NWSTF Boardman Security Department, and upon coordinating in advance with the NAS Whidbey Island Environmental Affairs Department.

8. Regulate hunting at NWSTF Boardman according to applicable federal and state laws and NWSTF Boardman policies. Participate, as necessary, in regulation development with ODFW staff, and subject to Fish and Wildlife Commission and ODFW Director approval.

Section II. Service Responsibilities

Consistent with its primary objectives and responsibilities and within the limitation of available funds and personnel, the Service shall:

1. Provide technical assistance to NAS Whidbey Island in the development and implementation of the Cooperative Plan and in the preparation of specific management plans for wildlife species of national significance and their habitats.
2. Provide, as necessary, information, expertise, personnel and equipment, and otherwise cooperate with NAS Whidbey Island and the State in the management of wildlife resources on NWSTF Boardman lands.
3. Provide technical assistance to plan and/or conduct surveys of wildlife resources and habitat delineation on NWSTF Boardman.
4. Provide technical assistance in the identification, protection, and restoration of endangered and threatened flora and fauna, and their habitats and/or plant communities on NWSTF Boardman.
5. Further the understanding of wildlife conservation by conducting related research to solve field problems and assisting in related training programs.
6. Provide, as necessary, law enforcement and permitting assistance in upholding federal and state endangered species regulations.
7. Identify Service wildlife technical training courses available to NAS Whidbey Island, NWSTF Boardman, and other Department of the Navy personnel.

Section III. State Responsibilities

Consistent with its primary objectives and responsibilities and within the limitation of available funds and personnel, the State shall:

1. Provide technical assistance to NAS Whidbey Island in the development and implementation of the Cooperative Plan and in the preparation of specific management plans for wildlife species of state significance and their habitats.

2. Provide, as necessary, information, expertise, personnel and equipment, and otherwise cooperate with the Service and NAS Whidbey Island in the management of wildlife resources on NWSTF Boardman lands.
3. Provide technical assistance to plan and/or conduct surveys of wildlife resources and habitat delineation on NWSTF Boardman.
4. Provide technical assistance in the identification, protection, and restoration of endangered and threatened flora and fauna, and their habitats on NWSTF Boardman.
5. Further the understanding of wildlife conservation by conducting related research to solve field problems and assisting in related training programs.
6. Provide, as necessary, law enforcement and assistance in upholding state laws, as applicable to natural resource management.
7. The State shall furnish, on an annual basis, current state hunting regulations.
8. Identify state-sponsored wildlife technical training courses available to NAS Whidbey Island, NWSTF Boardman, and other Department of the Navy personnel.
9. Assist NAS Whidbey Island, as necessary, in managing resident game populations to minimize animal damage control claims.

GENERAL PROVISIONS

1. Implementation of this agreement shall be subject to and consistent with the availability of personnel and appropriated funds.
2. The agreement recognizes the mission of NWSTF Boardman through NAS Whidbey Island to carry out its military function. Except as required by specific federal and state regulations, the implementation of this agreement shall in no way interfere with the mission of NWSTF Boardman.
3. This document, with its references, constitutes the entire agreement between the signatory parties and supersedes any previous written or oral agreements or understandings concerning this cooperative effort.
4. This agreement may be modified or amended only in writing and by mutual consent of all signatory parties. Furthermore, any modification or amendment of this agreement is not effective or binding unless made in writing and signed by all signatory parties.

5. This agreement shall be in force and effective upon the date of the last signatory and shall continue in effect unless terminated by one of the parties upon 90 days written notice of termination to the other parties.

SIGNATORIES

In witness whereof, the parties have executed this agreement as of the last date written below.

Commanding Officer
Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
Oak Harbor, Washington 98278-5000
(360) 257-1009 (Environmental Affairs
Department)

Date

Acting

Regional Director, Western Region
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
911 N.E. 11th Avenue
Portland, Oregon 97232-4181
(503) 231-6828

Date

Director
Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife
2501 SW 1st Avenue
Portland, Oregon 97207
(503) 229-5400

Date

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DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY

NAVAL AIR STATION WHIDBEY ISLAND
OAK HARBOR, WASHINGTON 98278-5000

5090

Ser N44/ 0744

JUL 26 2004

From: Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station Whidbey Island
To: Mr. John Phillips, Ecologist

Subj: APPOINTMENT AS INSTALLATION NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGER/COORDINATOR

Ref: (a) OPNAVINST 5090.1B, CH-4, 22-13.5e

1. Per reference (a), as the trained natural resources management professional in the Environmental Affairs Department, you are assigned the duty as Natural Resources Manager/Coordinator for Naval Air Station Whidbey Island properties/ranges and Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility Boardman, effective the date of this letter.

2. As the Natural Resources Manager/Coordinator, you are required to ensure that the Commanding Officer is informed regarding natural resource issues, conditions of natural resources, objectives of the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan, potential or actual conflicts between mission requirements and natural resources mandates. You are also responsible for the inherently governmental decisions made on behalf of the installation and the Commanding Officer with regards to Sikes Act compliance.

3. This appointment shall remain in effect until specifically revoked by the Commanding Officer.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Stephen P. Black".

STEPHEN P. BLACK

APPENDIX E. Research Natural Areas

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The Nature Conservancy in Oregon
Columbia Basin Office
PO Box 314
The Dalles, OR 97058

tel (541) 298-1802
(541) 980-3633
fax (541) 298-1802
nature.org

April 18, 2012

John Phillips
Natural Resources Manager, N442
Environmental Division
Public Works Department
NAS Whidbey Island
1115 W. Lexington St., Bldg. 103
Oak Harbor, WA 98278-3800

Re: Boardman NWSTF Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

Dear Mr. Phillips,

I am writing on behalf of The Nature Conservancy to offer our cooperation and support in implementing the 2012 Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman. As you know, The Nature Conservancy is a non-profit conservation organization whose mission is to conserve the lands and waters on which all life depends. The Conservancy has an organization-wide commitment to working with partners to accomplish this mission in a science-based, collaborative manner.

The Conservancy has worked closely with the Navy under a cooperative management agreement to co-manage three Research Natural Areas (RNAs) on the NWSTF since their designation in 1978. We also coordinate with the Navy on various natural resource issues, ranging from invasive species control to developing and conducting wildlife and habitat research and surveys within the RNAs and throughout the NWSTF. The Conservancy also manages the 22,642-acre Boardman Conservation Area (BCA) immediately to the west of the NWSTF.

We have reviewed the final 2012 INRMP and commit to follow and advance the goals of the plan in our management of the RNAs, under our current cooperative management agreement with the Navy, to protect the unique and irreplaceable native ecosystems represented on the installation while ensuring no net loss of the capability of the installation lands to support the Department of Defense mission.

Sincerely,

Leslie Nelson
Columbia Basin Project Manager
The Nature Conservancy

COOPERATIVE MANAGEMENT AGREEMENT

between

U.S. Department of the Navy, Boardman, Oregon

and

The Nature Conservancy

I. Purpose

This Cooperative Management Agreement is made by and between The Nature Conservancy, hereinafter called the Conservancy, and the U. S. Department of the Navy, hereinafter called the Navy. The purpose of this agreement is to define the cooperative arrangement between the Navy and the Conservancy in managing the Research Natural Area (RNA) at the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility at Boardman, Oregon.

II. Background

The Navy established The Boardman Research Natural Area on September 1, 1978 to preserve high-quality examples of Columbia River Basin grassland and steppe vegetation communities and associated wildlife. For the subsequent 10 years, The Nature Conservancy, under the auspices of the Northwest Interagency Research Natural Area Committee, has fenced and managed the area for the Navy. Many research projects have been undertaken on the RNA since its establishment. In 1987, the Conservancy proposed a boundary change to transfer a fair condition grassland site for an excellent quality shrub-steppe plant community and to include better examples of some of the other already protected communities.

III. Authority

- A. Office of the Chief of Naval Operations Instruction (OPNAVINST) 5090.1, 26 May 1983.
- B. Naval Facilities Engineering Command (NAVFAC) P-73 Procedural Manual vol. 2, May 1987.

IV. Provisions

- A. The Conservancy will:
 - 1. Establish permanent plots and monitor vegetation trend within the RNA.
 - 2. Control noxious weeds within the RNA boundaries.

3. Encourage the use of the RNA for educational and research purposes.
4. Maintain the RNA fences.

B. The Navy will:

1. Review all Conservancy proposed management activities on the RNA.
2. Provide fire suppression on the RNA.
3. Control visitation on the RNA.

C. The Conservancy and the Navy mutually agree:

1. That nothing in this agreement shall limit or compromise the policies and authorities of the Navy or the Conservancy.
2. That this Cooperative Agreement shall become effective upon signing by the Navy and the Conservancy.
3. That amendments to this Cooperative Agreement may be proposed at any time by either party and shall become effective upon written approval of both parties.
4. That this agreement shall continue in full force until termination by mutual agreement or by either party. Termination shall require 30 days notice in writing to the other party of the intention to terminate upon a date indicated.
5. That the boundaries of the RNA shall be changed and that the new area should be fenced (See Exhibit A).

Department of the Navy
Western Division
Naval Facilities Engineering Command
P. O. Box 727
San Bruno, CA 94066-0720

Manager, Natural Resources

3/7/88
Date

The Nature Conservancy
Oregon Field Office
1205 NW 25th Avenue
Portland, Oregon 97210

Executive Director

2-12-88
Date

Boundaries of existing and proposed Boardman Research Natural Area (RNA)

MORROW County
T2N, R25E
T3N, R25E

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RNA FILE

ESTABLISHMENT REPORT

RESEARCH NATURAL AREA
NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS
TRAINING FACILITY
BOARDMAN, OREGON

243F:DCR:pr
11015
Ser 243F/222
1 Sep 1978

ESTABLISHMENT REPORT

for

RESEARCH NATURAL AREA

at

NAVAL WEAPONS SYSTEMS TRAINING FACILITY, BOARDMAN, OREGON

(Controlled by: Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island, Oak Harbor, WA)

Prepared by:

Donald C. Rappel
Staff Forester
Seattle Branch, Western Division
Naval Facilities Engineering Command

Date: 1 September 1978

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 AND GEOLOGY OF THE BOARDMAN
 NAVAL BOMB RANGE, OREGON

- Qfg Fluvioglacial deposits
- Qgls Glacial lake sediments
- Ts Sedimentary rocks

SOIL MAP OF CENTRAL TARGET
OCTAGON

SOIL SERIES

Dunes

Royal

--- ROADS

Koehler

Warden

Quincy

Sagehill and Taunton

SCALE: 1" = 1 MI.

PHOTO #1

False color infra-red satellite photo. Large octagonal target area of the Boardman Bombing Range is readily distinguished from the surrounding basin lands. Red circles are irrigated lands from 120 to 160 acres each. Non-irrigated agricultural development is mainly to the South and East of the Bombing Range. Since this photo was taken, irrigation circles have been developed up to the West boundary of the Boardman Bombing Range. The central bombing octagon stands out from space because it has never been plowed and has been free of grazing for nearly forty years.

PHOTO #2

The area left of the fence line is within the target octagon of the Bombing Range. This area has not been grazed and consists of bluebunch wheatgrass and Sandberg's bluegrass. It is within the proposed Research Natural Area "C". The area to the right of the fence line has been grazed and consists of cheatgrass and sagebrush.

2. - PHOTOGRAPHS

PHOTO #3

The Northern Long-billed curlew Numenius americanus parvus nest on the range and the proposed Research Natural Area. This bird, along with others listed in this report, are considered to be rare and will be protected if the Research Natural Area is established.

PHOTO #4

The undisturbed ground cover of the target area octagon shows lush growth of bluebunch wheatgrass, phlox and cover of cryptogam (mosses and lichens). This area is located in the proposed Research Natural Area "C".

2. - PHOTOGRAPHS

PHOTO #5

Agropyron dasytachyum-Stipa comata (downy wheatgrass-needlegrass) community on Sage hill and Taunton soils.

PHOTO #6

Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii (needlegrass-Sandberg's bluegrass) community on Koehler soil.

PHOTO #7

Agropyron spicatum-Poa sandbergii (bluebunch wheatgrass-Sandberg's bluegrass) community on Warden soil

PHOTO #8

Stipa comata-POA sandbergii (needlegrass-Sandberg's bluegrass) community on Quincy soil.

3. - DESIGNATION ORDER

By virtue of the authority vested in me by the Secretary of Defense under regulation 36 CFR 251.23, I hereby propose the Boardman Bombing Range Research Natural Area as an Ecological Reserve Area. The lands described in the attached report by Donald C. Rappel, Seattle Branch, Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, dated 1 Sep 1978, shall hereafter be administered as an ecological reserve area, subject to the said regulations and instructions thereunder.

Date

Commanding Officer

4. - TEXTA. INTRODUCTION

The Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility at Boardman, Oregon is a component of the Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island, Oak Harbor, Washington. The Boardman Facility consists of 47,432.07 acres - see Map 1. This land was acquired by transfer from the Department of the Air Force on 22 November 1960. Of the 47,432.07 acres of land, 10,111.76 acres are Navy owned and 37,320.31 acres have been withdrawn from the public domain. The Facility is divided into six general areas:

Administrative Area	640 acres
North End	9429 acres
Mobile Target	1150 acres
Target Octagon	20,994 acres
South End	15,001 acres
Road Easement	218 acres

The North and South Areas have been outleased for livestock grazing since 1963. The remaining areas have not been grazed since acquisition of the range by the Navy Department. It is believed that these areas have not been grazed since the acquisition of the property by the Air Force Department in 1943.

In early 1975, the WESTNAVFACENGCOCM Staff Forester took a group from the Oregon Natural Area Preserves Committee on a tour of the range. At that time no interest was expressed in preserving any of the range area.

In 1977 the grazing leases for the North and South ends expired and it was decided to include the Target Octagon in the new grazing leases.

After the new leases were advertised and awarded, the WESTDIV Staff Forester was contacted by the Oregon Natural Area Preserves Committee and the Nature Conservancy. As a result of this contact, this request for the establishment of the Research Natural Area is being made. The Research Natural Area being proposed consists of three areas:

Area "A" is 2,560 acres in size and is located within the ungrazed Target Octagon, as shown on Map 2. It is not included in the grazing lease and has been fenced by the lessee.

Area "B" is 196 acres in size and is located outside of but immediately adjacent to the Target Octagon as shown on Map 2. It is included in the grazing lease; however, no grazing will be done on the area since it is a dune stabilization area. It is fenced separately from the remaining grazing lease area.

Area "C" is 2,420 acres in size and is located within the ungrazed Target Octagon as shown on Map 2. It is included in the grazing lease and will be grazed if it is not established as a Research Natural Area. It is not separately fenced from the remaining grazing lease area.

All of the proposed Research Natural Areas are located on land which has been withdrawn from Public Domain.

B. JUSTIFICATION

In the Pacific Northwest (Oregon and Washington) a comprehensive system of Research Natural Area needs has been outlined in the publication "Research Natural Area Needs in the Pacific Northwest," U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service Pacific Northwest Forest and Range Experiment Station General Technical Report PNW-38 1975. See Appendix I. The Boardman sites are the only areas that can adequately fill a number of these needs as described in the sections on the Washington and Oregon portions of the Columbia Basin physiographic provinces. The Boardman Bombing Range contains the only known high quality examples of flood deposit (sandy soil) shrub and bunchgrass communities remaining in Oregon or Washington.

The proposed Research Natural Area on the Boardman Bombing Range would protect high quality examples of the following Research Natural Area cells or needs:

1. Stipa comata - Poa sandberii (Needle and thread grass - Sandberg's bluegrass) on a range of soil types. See Photos 6 and 8.
2. Agropyron spicatum - Poa sandbergii (Bluebunch wheatgrass - Sandberg's bluegrass) See Photo 1.
3. Artemisia tridentata - Stipa comata (Big sagebrush - Needle and thread grass)
4. Columbia River sand dunes in various stages of stabilization.
5. Agropyron dasystachyum - Stipa comata (Downy wheatgrass - Needle and thread grass) While this community is not described as a need, it is the best habitat for the Washington ground squirrel. See Photo 5.

The following species of flora and fauna are of concern:

Astragalus succumbens - Crouching or columbia milk - vetch.

Numenius americanus parvus - Northern long-billed curlew.

Speotyto cunicularia hypugasa - Western burrowing owl.

Buteo regalis - ferruginous hawk.

Buteo swainsoni - Swainson's hawk.

Aquila chrysaetos - Golden eagle.

Spermophilus washingtoni - Washington ground squirrel.

C. PRINCIPAL DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

As discussed in Section 4B, quality representatives of Columbia Basin ecosystems are now quite rare. The Boardman Bombing Range contains the last high-quality representative of the native shrub-steppe vegetation that formerly covered millions of acres of the central Columbia Basin. In the remainder of the basin, the native ecosystems have been substantially altered by decades of grazing and, more recently, by irrigated and non-irrigated agriculture.

Beyond this general distinguishing feature, the spectrum of sandy soils and sandy soil ecosystems is well represented. A number of species of concern are represented.

At present, research on the long-billed Curlew by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service is in progress, permanent vegetation transects have been emplaced, and preliminary investigations of the Washington ground squirrel population has been made.

The extraordinary cryptogam (mosses and lichens) cover in the Agropyron spicatum-Poa sandbergii community of RNA "C" is of great interest - see Photo 4. The proposed Research Natural Area holds an irreplaceable opportunity to study the effects of this cover on a variety of ecosystem characteristics, such as nitrogen fixation, erosion control, moisture relationships, and control of invasion by weedy, exotic species. High cryptogam cover is invariably accompanied

by almost complete absence of the typical weedy annuals such as Bromus tectorum-cheatgrass, Erodium cicutarium-storksbill alfilaria, and Sisymbrium altissimum-Tumble mustard.

In the proposed Research Natural Area "B", grazing occurred up to about three years ago. Cryptogam cover is much lower in this area and weedy species are much more abundant. At the same time, the cover of Agropyron and Poa is comparable to Area "C".

D. LOCATION (See Map 1)

1. The Northern boundary of the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility is located two miles due South of the town of Boardman, Oregon and Interstate Highway 80 N. The Research Natural Areas are located as shown on Map 2.

2. The Research Natural Area is located at 45°41'05" Longitude and 119°42'33" Latitude.

3. The legal description of the Research Natural Area is as follows:

Area "A" - S 1/2 Sec 15, S 1/2 Sec 16, Sec 21, Sec 22
N 1/2 Sec 27, N 1/2 Sec 28, all in T. 3 N.,
R. 25 E., Willamette Meridian

Area "B" - Beginning at the Northeast Corner of Section 36, T. 3 N., R. 25 E., Willamette Meridian, thence Southwesterly along the existing Target Area fence for a distance of 6487 feet to its intersection with the South boundary fence of the dune stabilization area, thence Easterly along the existing South boundary fence for a distance of 4978 feet to its intersection with the Facility's boundary fence, thence North along the boundary fence for a distance of 3470 feet to the Point of Beginning.

Area "C" - Beginning at the Northeast corner of Section 3 T. 2 N. R. 25 E., Willamette Meridian, thence due South 3922 feet to the intersection of the Target Area Fence, thence due East along the existing fence for a distance of 9806 feet to the angle point in the Target Fence, thence Northwesterly along the existing fence for a distance of 13,064 feet, thence due North 3960 feet, thence due East 6600 feet thence due South 2640 feet thence due East 2640 feet thence due South 5280 feet thence due East 10,560 feet to the Point of Beginning. ck

4. Total Acreage of Area - The Research Natural Area is composed of three separate areas, all within the boundaries of the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility, Boardman, Oregon.

Area "A"	2,560 acres
Area "B"	196 acres
Area "C"	<u>2,420 acres</u>
Total acreage	5,176 acres

5. Access Routes - The following access routes may be used to reach the Research Natural Areas:

Area "A" - From the town of Boardman 3.75 miles East along Interstate Highway 80 N. to the Boardman Junction, then South along the Boardman-Heppner County Road for 5.5 miles to the road to Tower #5, then Westerly past Tower 5 along the unpaved Target Area Perimeter Road for 3.1 miles to the Mobile Target Control Tower, then South along the unpaved road immediately East of the Tower for 2 miles to the North Boundary of Area "A".

Area "B" - From the town of Boardman, 3.75 miles East along Interstate Highway 80 N. to the Boardman Junction, then South along the Boardman-Heppner County Road for 9 miles. Area "B" is adjacent to the road on the West side. An unpaved road is located along the South Boundary of the Area.

Area "C" - From the town of Boardman 3.75 miles East along Interstate Highway 80 N. to the Boardman Junction, then South along the Boardman-Heppner County Road for 9.5 miles then Westerly on unpaved road along the South Boundary of Area "B" for 0.5 mi. to "Y" in road, then Southwesterly along the left fork of the "Y" for 2 miles to Tub Springs, then Northwesterly 0.5 mi. to the Target Area Boundary fence and the South Boundary of Area "C". A road follows the Target Area Fence West and Northwest to the West Boundary of the Facility.

(See Map 2 for above routes.)

E. AREA BY GENERAL COVER TYPE.

Of the 5175 acres within the proposed Research Natural Area, approximately 4825 acres are taken up by the sandy soil flood deposits and associated vegetation. These deposits support a general cover type of needle and thread grass, bearded wheatgrass and sagebrush communities of undetermined individual extent. The remaining 350 acres are a lacustrine terrace sediment which supports a Bluebunch wheatgrass - Sandberg's bluegrass community.

F. PHYSICAL AND CLIMATIC CONDITIONS.

The site consists of a moderate series of ravines. The largest and most obvious of these is referred to as Juniper Canyon. Although referred to as "canyons", they are not in the true sense in that the contours of the surrounding area are composed of broad flat plateaus with rounded hillsides dropping into the valleys at moderate slopes. Larger valleys are generally flat across the bottom for several hundred feet and the drainage channel in most areas is undefined.

Contours of the site rise gently from approximately 400 feet elevation (MSL) at the North end to 900 feet elevation at the South end.

Climatological Data has been obtained from the following three stations:

1. Heppner, Oregon Weather Station located 40 miles south of Boardman.
2. Hermiston, Oregon Weather Station located 24 miles east of Boardman.
3. Pendleton, Oregon Weather Station located 44 miles east of Boardman.

Table I lists the elevations, length of records and monthly precipitation. Since the Hermiston station is at 624 foot elevation, its records are most similar to conditions on the facility.

Table 2 lists temperature extremes and Table 3 lists average days of High and Low temperatures.

Average Days of High and Low Temperature Extremes
Based on Mid-Columbia U.S. Weather Stations

Number of days in which Temperature is equal or Greater than the Following Average.....		Number of Days in Which Temperature is below Freezing.....	
Average Temp.	Number of days greater than average	Degrees below freezing	Number of days given low temp.
65° F.....	186 days	32° or less	112
70	161	20° " "	27
75	135	10 " "	9
80.....	104	0 " "	3
85.....	74		
90.....	47		
95	24		
100.....	8		

Temperature Extremes, Mid-Columbia U.S. Weather Stations

	Heppner 1938-1967 Elev. 1978 MSL		Hermiston 1942-1971 Elev. 624 MSL		Pendleton 1928-1971 Elev. 1482 MSL	
	<u>Record High</u>	<u>Record Low</u>	<u>Record High</u>	<u>Record Low</u>	<u>Record High</u>	<u>Record Low</u>
Jan.	70° F.	-19° F	72° F	-35° F	67° F	-22°
Feb.	72°	-21°	71°	-29°	66°	-18°
Mar.	78°	-6°	84°	6°	79°	10°
Apr.	92°	9°	96°	14°	89°	18°
May	100°	21°	102°	22°	99°	25°
June	105	32°	108°	33°	108°	36°
July	108	36°	112°	38°	110°	42°
Aug.	110	35°	113°	35°	113°	41°
Sept	99	19°	102°	21°	102°	30°
ct.	89	10°	92°	6°	86°	11°
Nov.	80	-8°	79°	-12°	74°	-6°
Dec.	75	-18°	70°	-37°	67°	-12°

Note: For additional data, refer to Umatilla Weather Station for records.

Monthly Mean Precipitation at Mid-Columbia U.S. Weather Stations

	Heppner 1938-1967 <u>Elev. 1978' MSL</u>	Hermiston 1942-1971 <u>Elev. 624' MSL</u>	Pendleton 1928-1971 <u>Elev. 1482' MSL</u>
Jan.	1.29 inches	1.22 inches	1.42 inches
Feb.	1.16	0.82	1.18
Mar.	1.28	0.73	1.20
Apr.	1.27	0.57	1.09
May	1.42	0.72	1.12
June	1.30	0.73	1.17
July	0.40	0.20	0.22
Aug.	0.49	0.18	0.28
Sept.	0.76	0.46	0.63
Oct.	1.27	0.86	1.18
Nov.	1.55	1.18	1.40
Dec.	1.47	1.24	1.49
Annual Average	13.66	8.91	12.38
Highest Annual Ave. on Record	19.23 (1942)	14.00 (1957)	17.73 (1942)
Lowest Annual Ave. on Record	7.81 (1939)	4.43 (1967)	6.77 (1967)

G. DESCRIPTION OF ECOLOGICAL VALUES.1. Flora

The only species of concern is Astragalus succumbens - Crouching or Columbia milk-vetch. The plant communities which would be protected by the establishment of the Research Natural Area are listed in section 4 B. The following is a list of common species found on the area:

Chrysothamnus nauseosus - Gray Rabbitbrush

Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus - Green Rabbitbrush

Purshia tridentata - Antelope Bitterbrush

Agropyron spicatum - Bluebunch Wheatgrass

Stipa comata - Needle and thread grass

Oryzopsis hymenoides - Indian Rice grass

Agropyron dasystachyum - Thickspike Wheatgrass

Festuca idahoensis - Idaho fescue

Poa sandbergii - Sandberg's bluegrass

Agropyron cristatum - Crested wheatgrass

Bromus tectorum - Cheatgrass

Phlox longifolia - Phlox

Erodium cicutarium - Storksbill alfilaria *or crows' bill*

Descurainia pinnata - Tansymustard

Astragalus purshii - Pursh's milk-vetch

Salsola kali - Russian thistle

Sisymbrium altissimum - ^{to make} ~~Tube~~ mustard *or Jim Hill mustard*

Achillea millefolium - Western yarrow

Erigeron linearis - Fleabane

Zygadenosus venosus - Deathcamas

Psoralea lanceolata - Lanceleaf scurp^Fpea

Balsamorhiza spp. - Balsamroot

Cymopterus terebinthinus - Turpentine cympterus

Hieracium spp. - Hawkweed

Draba verna - Spring whitlow grass

Lomatium macrocarpum - Long-fruited parsley

Holosteum umbellatum - holosteum

Fritillaria pudica - Yellowbell

Phacelia linearis - thread-leaf phacelia

Delphinium spp. - Larkspur

Layia glandulosa - tidy tips

Oenothera spp. - Primrose

Aster canescens - hoary aster

Lomatium cous - Biscuitroot

Amsinckia lycopsioides - tarweed fiddlersoch

Juniperus occidentalis - Western Juniper

Opuntia polycantha - prickly pear

Wyethia amplexicalis - Smooth mule ears

Sitanion hystrix - squirrel tail grass

Verbascum thapsus - Mullein

Artemisia tridentata - Big Sagebrush

Madia glomerata - Tarweed

References:

Daubenmire, R. 1970. Steppe Vegetation of Washington

Wash. Agric. Exp't Station Tech. Bulletin 62

Franklin, J.F. and C.T. Dyrness 1973.

Natural Vegetation of Oregon and Washington.

USDA For. Ser. Gen. Tech. Rep't PNW-8

Pac. N.W. For & Range Exp't Sta. Portland, OR

Nature Conservancy Transect plots inventoried April 1978

Gibbs, Jacy USDA Soil Conservation Service,

Range Inventory June 1977

2. Fauna

The species of concern are listed in Section 4B. The raptors feed on the small mammals of the proposed Research Natural Area while nesting in nearby areas. Long-billed curlews nest in the grassland communities throughout the bombing range including the proposed RIA. See photo 3. The population of the Washington Ground Squirrel is the first one found in Oregon for over 30 years.

The following is a list of common species found on the area:

- Odocoileus hemionus* - Mule deer
- Sylvilagus nuttallii* - Cottontail rabbit
- Lepus californicus* - Blacktail jackrabbit
- Phasianus colchicus* - Ring-necked pheasant
- Centrocercus urophasianus* - Sage grouse
- Lophortyx californicus* - California quail
- Zenaidura macroura* - Mourning dove
- Canis latrans* - Coyote
- Taxidea taxus* - Badger
- Lynx rufus* - Bobcat
- Perognathus parvus* - Great Basin pocket mouse
- Peromyscus maniculatus* - Deer mouse
- Sturnella neglecta* - Western meadowlark
- Pica pica* - Black-billed magpie
- Sturnus vulgaris* - Starling

Charadrius vociferus - Killdeer

Circus cyaneus - Marsh hawk

Falco sparverius - Sparrow hawk

Pituophis melanoleucus - Yellow-bellied racer

References:

1. Federal Research Natural Areas in Oregon and Washington. A guidebook for Scientists and Educators. USDA For. Ser. Pac. N.W. Forest & Range Exp. Sta. Portland, OR 1972
2. Personal Observations by D. Rappel over the period 1966 to present.

3. Geology

The majority of the proposed Research Natural Area is underlain by quaternary flood deposits from one or more episodes of the Missoula or Spokane floods. A small section of the site is underlain by old quaternary terrace deposits that are lacustrine in origin. These deposits are overlain by a mantle of loess. See map 4 for locations and contours. The Warden soil series marks the extent of these deposits on the proposed Research Natural Area. See map 3 for soil types.

4. Soils

Six soils series are represented on the proposed Research Natural Area. Five of these are flood deposit soils and increase in sandiness from top to bottom.

Royal fine sandy loam

Taunton fine sandy loam

Sagehill fine sandy loam

Koehler loamy sand

Quincy fine sand

The sixth soil series is the Warden silt loam developed in lacustrine terrace sediments. These soils are shown on map 3. U.S. Soil Conservation Service descriptions of these soils are included as Appendix IV.

H. IMPACTS AND POSSIBLE CONFLICTS

1. Cultural Value - The establishment of the proposed Research Natural Area does not involve any lands which are of known cultural or historic value. A 7-mile segment of the Oregon Trail lays 2 to 4 miles South of Area "C". It has been nominated for designation as a National Historic Site. Neither the Research Natural Areas or the access routes to them will impact on the Oregon Trail.

2. Mineral Value - There are no known mineral deposits located within the proposed Research Natural Areas or for that matter anywhere on the entire Facility. Mineral development, especially within the Target Octagon, would not be compatible with the military use of the area.

3. Grazing - Area "A" was not included in the grazing lease - is separately fenced, and there is no impact or conflict with grazing values. Area "B" was included in the grazing lease; however, it is an area of active blowsand and is of no value for grazing. Sand stabilization efforts are being made which preclude the grazing of livestock in Area "B". This Area is separately fenced from the rest of the grazing area. Area "C" is part of the grazing lease, and is only partially fenced. If the Research Natural Area is approved, approximately 7 miles of fence must be constructed. The estimated cost of the required fencing is \$24,000. The Oregon Natural Area Preserves Committee and the Nature Conservancy will pay the cost of the fencing. The Navy is presently receiving \$12.11 per AUM (Animal Unit Month). The withdrawal of Area "C" from the grazing lease will result in an annual loss in revenue to the Navy of

approximately \$2400. The present grazing lessee has verbally agreed to the withdrawal of Area "C" from his grazing lease.

4. Watershed Value - Due to the relatively high porosity of the soil, the short duration of most rainstorms, and the relatively flat topography of the Research Natural Areas, there are no watershed values involved. Since the proposed research will be non-destructive in nature, there will be no change in surface runoff.

5. Recreational Value - There will be no impacts or conflicts with the recreational value since the entire facility is closed to the general public.

6. Wildlife Preserve - The establishment of the Research Natural Area would not impact or conflict with the wildlife population on the Facility. A number of rare and threatened species either breed on the Facility or breed nearby, and forage over the Facility. These include the prairie falcon, Swainson's hawk, Ferruginous hawk, burrowing owl, long-billed Curlew and the Washington ground squirrel. The Washington ground squirrel population is the only viable one known in Oregon and Area "C" will preserve their habitat.

7. Roads and Trails - Areas "B" and "C" contain no maintained roads or trails; however, Area "C" does have some abandoned roads within its boundaries. These are remnants of the Air Force's use of the Facility and are not used by the Navy. Area "A" is the main Target Area and several maintained roads are contained within it. These are necessary for the maintenance of the main Target and for unexploded ordnance disposal. These roads will continue to be used if the area becomes a Research Natural Area.

I. ADMINISTRATION RECORDS AND PROTECTION

The Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island (Oak Harbor, Washington) is the administrator and protector of the Research Natural Area at the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility at Boardman, Oregon.

The Officer in Charge (OIC) of the Naval Weapons^A Systems Training Facility, Boardman, Oregon is responsible for coordinating access to the Research Natural Area with the scheduled military use of the Facility. Access will not be granted during periods of military use of the Target Area.

The principal contact for approval and coordination of research on the Natural Area is the Staff Forester, Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Seattle Branch Office, Building 5B, Naval Support Activity, Seattle, WA 98115. Research requests will be forwarded to the Pacific Northwest Federal Research Natural Areas Committee for technical approval. Final approval of proposed research will be made by the Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island.

Scientists who wish to use the Research Natural Area must abide by the requirements listed in Appendices 2 and 3 of this report.

5. - APPENDICESAPPENDIX IRESEARCH NATURAL AREAS - PURPOSE, SELECTION AND MANAGEMENT

Purposes of the System

The land management agencies have been actively developing a national system of Research Natural Areas (RNA's) since 1927. This system has grown to the current 389 areas covering 4.4 million acres in 46 states and one territory. Each area is administered by one of eight cooperating agencies: Forest Service in the Department of Agriculture; Bureau of Indian Affairs, Bureau of Land Management, Fish and Wildlife Service and National Park Service in the Department of the Interior; Air Force in the Department of Defense; Energy Research and Development Administration; and the Tennessee Valley Authority.

From the inception of the program there have been two primary purposes for developing a comprehensive and representative system of Research Natural Areas:

1. To preserve a representative array of all significant natural ecosystems and their inherent processes as baseline areas. This action provides a potential range of diversity, including common, rare, and endangered species or disjunct populations.
2. To obtain through scientific education and research, information about natural system components, inherent processes, and comparisons with representative manipulated systems.

The system provides several specific advantages to the nation's scientific community which have not usually been available, namely:

1. The potential use of an area that has had minimal human interference and has a reasonable assurance of long-term existence.
2. The potential availability of diverse or multiple data sets for analysis of factor interrelationships or temporal sequences.
3. The potential association with scientists of different disciplines leading toward scientific discoveries unlikely to occur without such association.

These values not only assist the investigator and science, but also provide the administering agencies with an information base with which to optimize their resource management decisions.

Interrelated with system preservation and the intrinsic scientific information are the numerous future options the system provides to society, especially with respect to genetic and land resource potential.

Recommendation, Selection, and Establishment

The Research Natural Area designation is used by the Federal land administering agencies to establish areas on which natural features and processes are preserved with minimal human intervention for research and educational purposes. This designation differs from other classifications such as wilderness sanctuary, refuge, or preserve, in that the latter designations often have broader use-management objectives than the preservation/scientific applications of the RNA system.

As initially conceived by the system founders, an RNA should contain an exemplary tract of vegetation along with its major supporting factors. In recent years, however, the range of features designated has expanded to include: typical or unusual floristic and/or faunistic assemblages, characteristic or unusual geologic, pedologic, or aquatic features; or characteristic or unusual processes. At the time of designation, significant effort is expended to assure that adequate conditions are provided to insure longevity of the feature. Presently, a designated area may range in size from a few to several thousand acres and may possess one or more features of interest.

A point which should be documented is that the Research Natural Area system receives no special legislative protection. The additional protection afforded the areas is derived only from the individual agencies which designate them.

Each participating agency has a different procedure leading to the designation of an RNA. In general, the on-site staff inventories the land resources to identify potential sites. Each area recommended by the inventory is documented by an agency-provided establishment report which details the features and proposed management plan. Upon administrative approval, the site becomes an agency-recognized RNA. In some agencies, the establishment process includes a detailed withdrawal procedure; this administrative recognition is the strongest action available to insure the protection and management of the RNA.

Should a particular feature be identified that has not received designation, documentation supporting the feature may be submitted to the area manager as a recommendation for review and consideration. Proposing new sites for designation can encourage growth of the national system and also precipitate review of the existing RNA's.

Management and General Use

All agencies employ a similar set of regulations to insure the protection of the educational and scientific values in their management

and use. The Committee has developed a set of standards and policy guidelines to provide greater uniformity in system definitions, objectives, classification, selection, use, management and administrative policies. The underlying emphasis in RNA management is on preserving and protecting the features of each area by controlling any disruptive use, encroachment, and development.

An activity such as logging, grazing, burning or restocking is prohibited unless it replaces natural processes and thus contributes to the protection and preservation of the designated feature. Such a practice is invoked only after thorough research and testing indicate that it adequately or favorably benefits the feature. In such an instance, a portion of the tract is left untreated as a control to justify the practice.

Picnicking, camping, swimming, hiking, and gathering of rocks, plants, nuts, or berries are generally discouraged, and in some cases are prohibited if serious impairment is anticipated. Hunting, fishing, and trapping of fur-bearing animals are also not encouraged, but are permitted subject to State regulation except on restricted lands such as those within National Parks.

No agency has purposely encouraged public use of RNA's through publicity or recreational development. However, some peripheral nature trails and interpretive signs have been established and more can be anticipated as these undisturbed sites become subject to increased public attention.

Scientific Use

Scientific use of RNA's by responsible scientists and educators is encouraged, providing their activities will not impair or threaten the features of the area. The limitations on use vary with the particular tract, its features, and the managing agency's regulations. An agency may place increased restrictions on some areas or portions of areas that it deems fragile or hazardous.

Research activities must be essentially non-destructive in character. Felling of trees and tree ring analyses, manipulative studies requiring extensive community floor modification, and extensive soil excavation are generally not allowed. Collection of plant and animal specimens should be restricted to the minimum necessary for providing vouchers and other research needs. In no case should specimens be collected to a degree that significantly reduces species population levels. The collection should be carried out in accordance with applicable Federal and State agency regulations and the specimens should be deposited in some public holding institution.

Within these guidelines, the appropriate uses of RNA's are determined on a case-by-case basis by the administering agency.

APPENDIX III

REQUIREMENTS FOR SUBMISSION OF RESEARCH PROPOSALS

Proposals for use of the Boardman Research Natural Area will provide as a minimum, the following:

1. Name, address and telephone number of researcher.
2. Qualifications and/or educational background.
3. Sponsoring agency or institution.
4. Detailed description of research proposed:
 - A. Purpose of research
 - B. Methods to be used.
 - C. Expected results.
 - D. Duration.
 - E. Anticipated schedule of on-the-ground use of the area.
 - F. Disposition of collected materials, if any.

APPENDIX II

REGULATIONS COVERING USE OF BOARDMAN RESEARCH NATURAL AREAS

1. Approval of proposed research must be obtained from the Navy prior to using the area.
2. Proposed research must be essentially non-destructive.
3. Collection of plant and animal specimens will be restricted to a minimum and such collections must be deposited in a public holding institution.
4. A cooperative agreement between the Navy and the researcher must be entered in to prior to use of the area.
5. Researcher must obtain approval from the OIC NWSRF Boardman for access to the area prior to each use.
6. Periodic reports on the progress of the research and copies of published research results must be provided to the Navy.
7. Specific research must be compatible with the preservation of the ecosystem and maintenance of its processes.
8. Non-indigenous or exotic plant and animal species will not normally be introduced into the area.
9. Permanent structures will not be constructed within the Area. Minimal temporary research facilities may be approved by the Navy.
10. No interference with normal cycles and fluctuations of wildlife populations will be allowed.
11. Predator control will not be allowed within the Area without specific approval of the Navy.
12. No camping is allowed on the Area or the Navy Facility.
13. No services or support will be provided by the Navy.

TAUNTON SERIES

The Taunton series is a member of the coarse-loamy, mixed, mesic family of Xerollic Durorthids. Typically, Taunton soils have light brownish gray fine sandy loam Ap horizons, pale brown fine sandy loam B2 horizons, pale brown gravelly fine sandy loam Cca horizons, and a white strongly cemented duripan at depth of about 24 inches.

Typifying Pedon: Taunton fine sandy loam - cultivated
(Colors are for dry soil unless otherwise noted.)

- Ap 0-5"---Light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) fine sandy loam, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; weak fine granular structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; moderately alkaline (pH 8.0); abrupt smooth boundary. (3 to 8 inches thick)
- B2 5-18"---Pale brown (10YR 6/3) fine sandy loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; weak medium sub-angular blocky structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; few very fine tubular pores; moderately alkaline (pH 8.0); clear wavy boundary. (4 to 14 inches thick)
- Cca 18-24"---Pale brown (10YR 6/3) gravelly fine sandy loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; massive; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; few very fine tubular pores; 20 percent gravel-size fragments which are lime-silica cemented; strongly effervescent; strongly alkaline (pH 8.6); abrupt smooth boundary. (3 to 20 inches thick)
- C2casim 24"---White (10YR 9/2) strongly cemented duripan; upper surface has thin smooth laminar cap; laminar cap and matrix are violently effervescent.

Type Location: Adams County, Washington; 250 feet south and 50 feet east of the center of the northwest 1/4 sec. 16, T.15N., R.28E., WM.

Range in Characteristics: Solum thickness ranges from 10 to 20 inches. Depth to the duripan ranges from 20 to 40 inches. Taunton soils are usually dry in all parts between depths of 8 and 24 inches or the top of the duripan if shallower. The mean annual soil temperature at depth of 20 inches or the surface of the duripan if shallower ranges from 50 to 56 degrees F. The Ap or A1 horizon has value of 5 or 6 dry and chroma of 2 or 3 dry or moist. It is fine sandy loam or loamy fine sand. This horizon has weak granular or subangular structure. The B2 horizon has value of 6 or 7 dry, 4 or 5 moist and chroma of 2 or 3 dry or moist. The Cca horizon has the same color range as the B2 horizon. It contains 5 to 35 percent gravel-size lime-silica fragments.

Competing Series and their Differentiae: These are the Babcock, Burke, Crooked, Koehler, Prineville, and Royal series. Babcock and Burke soils have loam and silt loam control sections. Crooked soils are somewhat poorly drained and commonly have a high water table. Koehler soils have sandy control sections. Prineville soils are mildly alkaline above the duripan and have 5 to 25 percent sand-size pumice. Royal soils lack a duripan.

Setting: Taunton soils are on nearly level to sloping old high terrace tops and mesa-like areas between coulees, at elevations of 900 to 1,300 feet. They formed in old alluvium that has been reworked by wind. These soils occur in an arid climate with hot dry summers and cool moist winters. The mean annual precipitation ranges from 6 to 9 inches. The mean January temperature is 29 degrees F. The mean July temperature is 71 degrees F. The mean annual temperature is 50 degrees F. The frost-free season is 170 to 210 days.

Principal Associated Soils: These are the Wiehl soils and the competing Royal soils. Wiehl soils lack a duripan.

Drainage and Permeability: Somewhat excessively drained; slow runoff; moderately rapid permeability above the pan and very slow within the pan.

Use and Vegetation: Range and irrigated crops. Native vegetation is bluebunch wheatgrass, Sandberg bluegrass, buckwheat, rabbitbrush, and sagebrush.

Distribution and Extent: South-central Washington and north-central Oregon. Series is of moderate extent.

Series Established: Walla Walla County, Washington, 1960.

Remarks: Taunton soils were formerly classified as Sierozems.

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ROYAL SERIES

The Royal Series is a member of the coarse-loamy, mixed, mesic family of Xerollic Camborthids. Typically, Royal soils have light brownish gray fine sandy loam A1 horizons, and pale brown fine sandy loam B2 horizons over pale brown light gray, light brownish gray, and gray stratified fine sandy loam and loamy fine sand C horizons.

Typifying Pedon: Royal fine sandy loam - grassland
(Colors are for dry soil unless otherwise noted.)

- A1 0-5"--Light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) fine sandy loam, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; weak fine granular structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; many roots; mildly alkaline (pH 7.6); abrupt smooth boundary. (3 to 6 inches thick)
- B2 5-15"--Pale brown (10YR 6/3) fine sandy loam, brown (10YR 5/3) moist; weak medium prismatic structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; few very fine tubular pores; mildly alkaline (pH 7.8); clear wavy boundary. (6 to 18 inches thick)
- Clca 15-30"--Very pale brown (10YR 7/3) fine sandy loam, brown (10YR 5/3) moist; massive; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; few very fine tubular pores; strongly effervescent; moderately alkaline (pH 8.4); abrupt wavy boundary. (10 to 25 inches thick)
- C2 30-40"--Light gray (10YR 7/2) loamy fine sand, grayish brown (10YR 5/2) moist; massive; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; few roots; few very fine tubular pores; strongly effervescent; moderately alkaline (pH 8.4); abrupt wavy boundary. (6 to 12 inches thick)
- C3 40-46"--Light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) fine sandy loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; massive; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; few roots; few fine tubular pores; strongly effervescent; moderately alkaline (pH 8.4); abrupt wavy boundary. (6 to 12 inches thick)
- C4 46-57"--Gray (10YR 6/1) loamy fine sand, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; single grained; loose; nonsticky, nonplastic; few roots; interstitial pores; strongly effervescent; strongly alkaline (pH 8.6); abrupt wavy boundary. (6 to 12 inches thick)
- C5 57-70"--Light gray (10YR 7/2) fine sandy loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; massive; slightly hard, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; few roots; few very fine tubular pores; strongly effervescent; strongly alkaline (pH 8.7).

Type Location: Franklin County, Washington; Farm Unit 126 of Irrigation Block 16; 1,400 feet north and 200 feet west of southeast corner of sec. 28, T.11N., R.29E., WM.

Range in Characteristics: Solum thickness and depth to lime are 10 to 24 inches. The 10- to 40-inch control section averages sandy loam. Some pedons contain small pockets or thin strata of silt loam or very fine sandy loam. The soils are usually dry in all parts between depths of 8 and 24 inches. The mean annual soil temperature at a depth of 20 inches ranges from 50° to 56°F. The A1 horizon has value of 4 or 5 moist, and chroma of 2 or 3 dry or moist. It is fine sandy loam, loamy fine sand, or loamy sand. The B2 horizon has value of 6 or 7 dry and 4 or 5 moist, and chroma of 2 or 3 dry or moist. It is fine sandy loam or borderline fine sandy loam-loamy fine sand. The C horizon has value of 6 or 7 dry and 4 or 5 moist, and chroma of 1 through 3 dry or moist. It is stratified fine sandy loam and loamy fine sand.

Competing Series and their Differentiae: These are the Adkins, Clemar, Clems, Crestline, Deschutes, Ephrata, Prosser, Scootney, Timmerman, and Wiehl series. Adkins soils are uniform fine sandy loam and lack lime above depth of 30 inches. Cleman soils are noncalcareous in all parts. Clems soils are noncalcareous to depths of 45 to about 60 inches. Crestline soils have gravelly textures in the lower part of the control section and have heavy sandy loam B horizons. Deschutes and Prosser soils have bedrock at depths of less than 40 inches. Ephrata soils have contrasting textures within the control section. Scootney soils have more than 35 percent coarse fragments in the lower part of the control section. Timmerman soils have sandy control sections. Wiehl soils have a paralythic contact at depths of less than 40 inches.

Setting: Royal soils are on nearly level to gently sloping footslopes and terraces at elevations of 700 to 1,100 feet. They formed in wind modified glacio-fluvial sediments. These soils are in an arid climate with hot dry summers and cool moist winters. The mean annual precipitation is 6 to 9 inches. The mean January temperature is 27°F. The mean July temperature is 71°F. The mean annual temperature is 50°F. The frost-free season is 150 to 210 days.

Principal Associated Soils: These are the Taunton soils and the competing Wiehl soils. Taunton soils have a duripan at depths of less than 40 inches.

Drainage and Permeability: Well-drained; slow and medium runoff; moderately rapid permeability.

Use and Vegetation: Irrigated cropland and range. Native vegetation is needle-and-thread grass, bluebunch wheatgrass, Indian ricegrass, and big sagebrush.

Distribution and Extent: South-central Washington and north-central Oregon. Series is of moderate extent.

Series Established: Franklin County, Washington, 1971.

Remarks: Royal soils were classified as Sierozems.

Additional Data: S61 Wash, 11-13 (107) Riverside Lab. Nos. 61204-61210, and S61 Wash, 11-4 (1-6) Riverside Lab. Nos. 61211-61216.

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KOEHLER SERIES

The Koehler series is a member of the sandy, mixed, mesic family of Xerollic Durorthids. Typically, Koehler soils have coarse textured horizons over an indurated duripan at depth of about 2 1/2 feet.

Typifying Pedon: Koehler loamy sand - grassland
(Colors are for dry soil unless otherwise noted.)

- A1 0-4"--Grayish brown (10YR 5/2) loamy sand, very dark grayish brown (10YR 3/2) moist; single grained; loose, nonsticky, nonplastic; many roots; mildly alkaline (pH 7.8); clear wavy boundary. (2 to 5 inches thick)
- C1 4-12"--Light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) loamy sand, very dark grayish brown (10YR 3/2) moist; single grained; loose, nonsticky, nonplastic; common roots; moderately alkaline (pH 7.9); slight effervescence with dilute HCL; clear wavy boundary. (2 to 15 inches thick)
- C2ca 12-25"--Light brownish gray (10YR) loamy fine sand, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; single grained; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; few roots; 10 percent lime-silica duripan fragments; moderately alkaline (pH 8.2); violent effervescence with dilute HCL; abrupt wavy boundary. (10 to 15 inches thick)
- C3casi 25-31"--Light gray (10YR 7/2) loamy fine sand, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; massive; very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; few matted roots; 70 percent lime-silica duripan fragments; moderately alkaline (pH 8.2); violent effervescence with dilute HCL; abrupt wavy boundary. (0 to 6 inches thick)
- C4casim 31"--Indurated lime-silica cemented duripan.

Type Location: Benton County, Washington; 75 feet east of intersection of Umatilla Road and PSH #8, in the NW1/4 SW1/4 sec. 32, T.6N., R.28E., WM.

Range in Characteristics: Depth to the duripan ranges from 14 to 40 inches. The soils are usually dry between depths of 12 and 35 inches or to the duripan if shallower. The mean annual soil temperature at depth of 20 inches or at the top of the duripan if shallower is 50° to 56° F. After the upper 7 inches are mixed the soil is calcareous in all parts. The A1 horizon has value of 5 or 6 dry and 3 or 4 moist. It is loamy sand, loamy fine sand, or fine sand. The C and Cca horizons have value of 6 through 8 dry and 3 through 5 moist, and chroma of 2 dry or moist. They are loamy sand, loamy fine sand, or fine sand. Thin sandy loam lenses occur immediately above the duripan in some pedons.

Competing Series and their Differentiae: These are the Babcock, Prineville, Quincy, Taunton, and Winchester series. Babcock soils have medium textured control sections above the duripan. Prineville soils are mildly alkaline above the duripan and have 5 to 25 percent sand-size pumice in the control section. Quincy and Winchester soils lack a duripan within a depth of 40 inches. Taunton soils have moderately coarse texture in the control section.

Setting: Koehler soils are on nearly level to sloping terraces, at elevations of 300 to 1,000 feet. They formed in alluvial and colluvial materials mantled with eolian sand. Koehler soils occur in an arid climate with hot dry summers and cool moist winters. The mean annual precipitation is 6 to 8 inches. Mean July temperature is 76° F. The mean January temperature is 50° F. The mean annual temperature is 53° F. The frost-free season is 150 to 210 days.

Principal Associated Soils: These are the Burbank and Finley soils and the competing Quincy and Winchester soils. None of these have a duripan.

Drainage and Permeability: Somewhat excessively drained; slow runoff; rapid permeability above the duripan and very slow within the duripan.

Use and Vegetation: Native range. Vegetation is needle-and-thread grass, Indian ricegrass, cheatgrass, hop sage, rabbitbrush, and big sagebrush.

Distribution and Extent: South-central Washington and north-central Oregon. Series is of moderate extent.

Series Established: Franklin County, Washington, 1914.

Koehler Series

2

Remarks: Koehler soils were formerly classified as Regosols.

National Cooperative Soil Survey
U. S. A.

WARDEN SERIES

The Warden series is a member of the coarse-silty, mixed, mesic family of Xerollic Camborthids. Typically, Warden soils have light brownish gray very fine sandy loam Ap horizons, pale brown very fine sandy loam B2 horizons, pale brown and light gray silt loam and very fine sandy loam C horizons.

Typifying Pedon: Warden very fine sandy loam - cultivated
(Colors are for dry soil unless otherwise stated.)

- Ap 0-6"--Light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) very fine sandy loam, dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) moist; weak fine granular structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; many fine roots; mildly alkaline (pH 7.8); abrupt smooth boundary. (3 to 6 inches thick)
- B2 6-19"--Pale brown (10YR 6/3) very fine sandy loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; weak medium subangular blocky structure; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common fine roots; common very fine tubular pores; mildly alkaline (pH 7.8); abrupt smooth boundary. (11 to 24 inches thick)
- IIC1ca 19-40"--Pale brown (10YR 6/3) silt loam, dark brown (10YR 4/3) moist; massive but irregularly finely laminated; hard, firm, slightly sticky, slightly plastic; common fine roots; many very fine tubular pores; violently effervescent; moderately alkaline (pH 8.4); clear wavy boundary. (15 to 30 inches thick)
- IIC2 40-54"--Pale (10YR 6/3) very fine sandy loam, brown (10YR 5/3) moist; massive; soft, very friable, nonsticky, nonplastic; common fine roots; common very fine tubular pores; violently effervescent; strongly alkaline (pH 8.6); clear wavy boundary. (8 to 20 inches thick)
- IVC3 54-60"--Light gray (10YR 7/2) silt loam, light brownish gray (10YR 6/2) moist; massive; hard, firm, slightly sticky, slightly plastic; few roots; few very fine tubular pores; violently effervescent; strongly alkaline (pH 8.5).

Type Location: Adams County, Washington; 100 feet south and 500 feet east of northwest corner sec. 19, T.16N., R.29E., W.M.

Range in Characteristics: Thickness of solum and depth to lime range from 15 to 30 inches. Mean annual soil temperature ranges from 50° to 55° F. These soils are continuously dry in all parts between 4 and 12 inches from about May 1 to October 1. Colors are in 10YR or 2.5Y hue. The solum is neutral to mildly alkaline (pH 6.8 to 7.8). The Ap horizon has value of 5 or 6 dry, and chroma of 2 or 3. It has weak granular or subangular blocky structure. The B2 horizon has value of 5 or 6 dry, and chroma of 2 or 3. It is silt loam or very fine sandy loam and has weak subangular blocky or prismatic structure. The C horizon has value of 4 or 5 moist and 6 or 7 dry, and chroma of 2 or 3. It is stratified silt loam and very fine sandy loam in that portion within the control section, but may be sandy loam or loamy sand below the control section. Vertical or diagonal clastic dikes occur within the C horizon of some pedons.

Competing Series and their Differentiae: These are the Sagemoor, Shano, and Stingal series. Sagemoor soils have laminated, slowly permeable, calcareous sediments at depths of 15 to 30 inches. Shano soils have uniform nonstratified silt loam control sections. Stingal soils are calcareous in all parts.

Setting: Warden soils are on nearly level to gently sloping terraces at elevations of 500 to 1200 feet. These soils formed in lacustrine sediments with a loess mantle. Warden soils occur in an arid climate having an annual precipitation of 6 to 9 inches, with warm dry summers and cool moist winters; average January temperature is 27° F.; average July temperature is 71° F.; mean annual temperature is 50° F.; and frost-free season is 136 to 160 days.

Principal Associated Soils: These are the competing Sagemoor and Shano soils.

Warden Series

2

Drainage and Permeability: Well-drained; slow to medium runoff; moderate permeability.

Use and Vegetation: Dryland wheat and rye; range, and irrigated crops. Native vegetation is bluebunch wheatgrass, Sandberg bluegrass, needle-and-thread grass, and big sagebrush.

Distribution and Extent: South-central Washington. Series is of moderate extent.

Series Established: Columbia Basin Area (Reconnaissance), Washington, 1929.

Remarks: These soils were formerly classified as Sierozems.

Supporting Data: S61 Wash-13-11-(1-5):Riverside Lab Nos.61331-61336, S61 Wash 13-12-(1-7):Riverside Lab Nos.61337-61343, S61 Wash13-13-(1-7):Riverside Lab Nos.61344-61350.

National Cooperative Soil Survey
U. S. A.

QUINCY SERIES

X.m.c.

The Quincy series is a member of the mixed, nonacid, mesic family of Typic Torripsments. Typically, these soils are deep fine sands that range in color from grayish brown to pale brown and are noncalcareous or nearly so in the upper 20 inches.

Typifying Pedon: Quincy fine sand - grassland
(Colors are for dry soil unless otherwise stated.)

- C1 0-15" -- Grayish brown (10YR 5/2) fine sand, dark brown (10YR 3/3) moist; structureless, single grain; loose many roots; moderately alkaline (pH 8.0); clear wavy boundary. (5 to 20 inches thick)
- C2 15-60" -- Grayish brown (10YR 5/2) fine sand, dark brown (10YR 3/3) moist; structureless, single grain; loose common roots; slight effervescence; moderately alkaline (pH 8.2).

Type Location: Adams County, Washington; 100 feet north and 530 feet west of south quarter corner sec. 28, T.15N., R.29E., W.M.

Range in Characteristics: At a depth of 20 inches the mean annual soil temperature ranges from 47° to 59° F., and the mean summer temperature ranges from 66° to 78° F. These soils are usually dry in all parts between 7 and 20 inches. The surface soils have hues of 7.5YR, 10YR, or 2.5Y, and values of 4 through 7 dry and 3 through 5 moist, and chromas of 2 or 3. Organic matter content of the surface horizons when mixed to 7 inches is commonly very low and is everywhere less than 1 percent. Colors of the subsoil and substratum are similar to those of the surface soil, the difference is less than 1 unit of value. Texture of the 10- to 40-inch control section ranges from sand to loamy fine sand. Less than 75 percent of the sand is of the very coarse, coarse, and medium size classes if the clay content is less than 5 percent. If the clay content exceeds 5 percent more than 75 percent of the sand fraction can be in the very coarse, coarse, and medium size classes. In the upper 20 inches these soils are usually free of lime, except for small particles brought up by insects and animals; but the matrix below 20 inches may be slightly calcareous. Reaction in the upper 20 inches is slightly acid to moderately alkaline, and below 20 inches it is neutral to moderately alkaline. Some pedons have unconforming materials, including bedrock, at depths below 40 inches. *Depth to bedrock is commonly greater than 20 inches.*

Competing Series and their Differentiae: These are the Hazel, Koehler, Preston, Sheppard, Tipperary, and Winchester series. Hazel soils have medium and moderately coarse textured strata in the lower part of the control section. Koehler soils are calcareous and have a lime-silica cemented duripan. Preston soils have A1 horizons that are darker than the C horizon by at least one unit of value and they are not usually dry. Sheppard soils have 2.5YR thru 7.5YR hues and have chromas of 4 to 6 inclusive. Tipperary soils have Cca horizons. Winchester soils have textures in the control section of sand or loamy sand. More than 75 percent of the sand fraction is in the very coarse, coarse, and medium size classes, and clay content is less than 5 percent.

Setting: Quincy soils are on level to rolling uplands and terraces having a ridged, hummocky, or dune microrrelief. Many of the low rounded ridges are narrow and long. The soil formed in sands from mixed sources. Elevations range from 400 to 4,500 feet. The climate is arid or semiarid and summers are dry. Average annual precipitation is 4 to 12 inches, and the average freeze-free season is 100 to 180 days.

Those are the Burbank, Cencove, Feltham, Taunton, Burbank soils are loamy skeletal.

Principal Associated Soils: ~~Taunton~~, Esquatzel, Hazel, and Warden soils, ~~are in the~~ general area. Taunton soils have petrocalcic horizons and coarse-loamy texture and Warden soils have medium textured control sections. *Feltham soils are from the same parent material as Hazel soils and some are in the upper part.*

Drainage and Permeability: Excessively or somewhat excessively drained. Runoff is slow, and permeability is very rapid or rapid.

Use and Vegetation: Native rangeland and irrigated cropland. Irrigated areas are hay, pasture, small grains, grapes and deciduous fruits. The natural vegetation is native and introduced grass, thickspike wheatgrass, Indian ricegrass, rabbitbrush, horsebrush, and Russian thistle.

Distribution and Extent: California, Idaho, Nevada, Oregon, ~~Utah~~ and Washington. Distribution is moderately extensive.

Series Established: Grant County, Washington, 1911.

~~Remarks: The Quincy soils were formerly classified as Regosols.~~

National Cooperative Soil Survey
U. S. A.

M RA(S): 7, 11

D.C.LWR, 7-75

SAGEHILL SERIES

XEROLIC CAMBORTHIDS, COARSE-LOAMY, MIXED, MESC

THE SAGEHILL SERIES CONSIST OF WELL-DRAINED SOILS FORMED IN WIND-MODIFIED GLACIO-FLUVIAL SEDIMENTS. IT IS FOUND ON NEARLY LEVEL TO GENTLY SLOPING FOOTSLOPES AND TERRACES. THE VEGETATION IS MAINLY GRASSES AND SHRUBS. M.A.P. IS 6 TO 9 INCHES, M.A.A.T. IS ABOUT 50 F., AND THE F.F.S. IS 150 TO 210 DAYS. TYPICALLY, THE SURFACE AND SUBSOIL ARE BROWN, VERY FINE SANDY LOAM, ABOUT 19 INCHES THICK. THE SUBSTRATUM LAYERS ARE LIGHT BROWNISH-GRAY AND PALE BROWN VERY FINE SANDY LOAM AND SILT LOAM EXTENDING TO 60 INCHES. SLOPES RANGE FROM 0 TO 35 PERCENT.

ESTIMATED SOIL PROPERTIES (A)										
DEPTH (IN.)	USDA TEXTURE	UNIFIED	AASHTO	PERCENT OF MATERIAL LLSS > 3 IN. THAN 3# PASSING SIEVE NO.				LIQUID LIMIT	PLAS- TICITY	INDEX
				(PCT)	4	10	40			
0-8	VFSL, FSL	ML, SM	A-4	0-5	95-100	95-100	80-95	45-60	15-25	NP-5
8-19	VFSL	ML, SM	A-4	0-5	95-100	95-100	80-95	45-60	15-25	NP-5
19-60	VFSL, SIL	ML	A-4	0-5	95-100	95-100	80-95	50-65	15-25	NP-5

DEPTH (IN.)	PERMEABILITY (IN/HR)	AVAILABLE WATER CAPACITY (IN/IN)	SOIL REACTION (PH)	SALINITY (MMHOS/CM)	SHRINK- SWELL POTENTIAL	CORROSIVITY		EROSION FACTORS		WIND EROD. GROUP
						STEEL	CONCRETE	K	Y	
0-8	2.0-6.0	0.20-0.23	7.4-8.4	-	LOW	MODERATE	LOW	.49	5	3
8-19	2.0-6.0	0.20-0.23	7.4-8.4	-	LOW	MODERATE	LOW	.55		
19-60	0.6-2.0	0.20-0.25	7.9-9.0	-	LOW	HIGH	LOW	.55		

FLOODING			HIGH WATER TABLE		CEMENTED PAV.		BEDROCK		SUBSIDENCE		HYD POTENTIAL ACTION	
FREQUENCY	DURATION	MONTHS	DEPTH (FT)	KIND	MONTHS	DEPTH (IN)	HARDNESS	DEPTH (IN)	HARDNESS	INIT. (IN)		TOTAL (IN)
NONE			26.0					200				B MODERATE

SANITARY FACILITIES

SEPTIC TANK ABSORPTION FIELDS		ROADFILL		SOURCE MATERIAL	
0-8X: SLIGHT	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE	0-15X: FAIR-FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH	15-25X: FAIR-SLOPE, FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH	25+X: POOR-SLOPE	
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
SEWAGE LAGOON AREAS		SAND		UNSUITED	
0-2X: MODERATE-SEEPAGE	2-7X: MODERATE-SLOPE, SEEPAGE				
7+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
SANITARY LANDFILL (TRENCH)		GRAVEL		UNSUITED	
0-15X: SLIGHT	15-25X: MODERATE-SLOPE				
25+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
SANITARY LANDFILL (AREA)		TOPSOIL		0-8X: GOOD 8-15X: FAIR-SLOPE 15+X: POOR-SLOPE	
0-8X: SLIGHT	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE				
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
DAILY COVER FOR LANDFILL		POND RESERVOIR AREA		WATER MANAGEMENT	
0-2X: GOOD	8-15X: FAIR-SLOPE			0-2X: SEEPAGE	2+X: SLOPE, SEEPAGE
15+X: POOR-SLOPE					

COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

SHALLOW EXCAVATIONS		EMBANKMENTS DIKES AND LEVEES		PIPING, LOW STRENGTH, HARD TO PACK	
0-8X: SLIGHT	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE				
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
DWELLINGS WITHOUT BASEMENTS		EXCAVATED POND AQUIFER FED		DEEP TO WATER	
0-8X: MODERATE-FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE, FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH				
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
DWELLINGS WITH BASEMENTS		DRAINAGE		0-2X: FAVORABLE 2+X: SLOPE	
0-8X: MODERATE-LOW STRENGTH	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE, LOW STRENGTH				
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
SMALL COMMERCIAL BUILDINGS		IRRIGATION		0-2X: FAVORABLE 2+X: SLOPE	
0-4X: MODERATE-FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH	4-8X: MODERATE-SLOPE, FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH				
8+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
LOCAL ROADS AND STREETS		TERRACES AND DIVERSIONS		0-8X: ERODES EASILY, PIPING 8+X: SLOPE, ERODES EASILY, PIPING	
0-8X: MODERATE-FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH	8-15X: MODERATE-SLOPE, FROST ACTION, LOW STRENGTH				
15+X: SEVERE-SLOPE					
LAWNS, LANDSCAPING AND GOLF FAIRWAYS		GRASSED WATERWAYS			

REGIONAL INTERPRETATIONS

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DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
WESTERN DIVISION
NAVAL FACILITIES ENGINEERING COMMAND
SAN BRUNO, CALIFORNIA 94066

IN REPLY REFER TO:

243:MMS:po
RESEARCH NATURAL AREA
BOARDMAN
8 FEB 1979

FIRST ENDORSEMENT on NAVFACENGCOM ltr of 24 Jan 1979

From: Commanding Officer, Western Division, Naval Facilities
Engineering Command
To: Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island
Subj: Research Natural Area, Naval Weapons Systems Training
Facility, Boardman, Oregon; establishment of

1. Original letter not received. Copy of letter is forwarded concurring with approval for establishment of subject research natural area.
2. The subject area contains the last high-quality examples of the native shrub-steppe vegetation that formerly covered millions of acres of the central Columbia Basin. In the remainder of the basin the native ecosystems have been substantially altered by decades of grazing and, more recently, by irrigated and non-irrigated agriculture. In addition, the spectrum of sandy soils and sandy soil ecosystem is present and a number of plant and wildlife species of concern are represented.
3. It is understood that the fencing required to protect the subject area is being provided by the Pacific Northwest Branch of Nature Conservancy. This Command is initiating action to amend the affected grazing outleasing to exclude the subject area from the lease.

A. W. COLLINS
By direction

Copy to:
NAVFACENGCOM (Code 2042)
WESTNAVFACENGCOMBRO SEATTLE (Code 243F)
DASD (MRA&L)
CNO (Op-45)

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
NAVAL FACILITIES ENGINEERING COMMAND
200 STOVALL STREET
ALEXANDRIA, VA 22332

IN REPLY REFER TO

24 JAN 1979

From: Commander, Naval Facilities Engineering Command
To: Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidby Island, WA.
Via: Commanding Officer, Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command

Subj: Research Natural Area, NWSTF, Boardman, Oregon; establishment of

Ref: (a) NAS, Whidby Is. ltr Ser 3738 to CNO (Op-45) of 22 Sept 78
(b) CNO ltr Ser 453/722365 to COMNAVFACENGCOMHQ of 02 Nov 78
(c) COMNAVFACENGCOMHQ ltr Code 20R to CNO (Op-45) of 3 Jan 79

1. The designation of certain areas of NWSTF, Boardman Range as Research Natural areas submitted by reference (a), has been approved by reference (b) and concurred in by reference (c). Therefore, the designation is now official and requires no further approval action.

2. As a follow-up, a copy of the establishment Report is being forwarded to the Federal Committee on Ecological Reserves with the request that the area be made a part of the National system of Natural and experimental areas for environmental and ecological research and listed in the "Directory of Research Natural areas on Federal Lands".

H. R. Richard

H. R. RICHARD
By director

Copy to:
DASD (MRA&L)
CNO (Op-45)

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
 NAVAL FACILITIES ENGINEERING COMMAND
 200 STOVALL STREET
 ALEXANDRIA, VA 22332

IN REPLY REFER TO

Mike
Walt

From: Commander, Naval Facilities Engineering Command
 To: Chief of Naval Operations (OP-45)
 Subj: Research Natural Areas, Naval Weapons Systems
 Training Facility, Boardman, Oregon
 Ref: (a) CNO ltr Ser 453/722365 of 2 Nov 1978

1. As requested by reference (a) this Command concurs with the designation of portions of subject property as a Research Natural Area provided the Navy reserves the right to disestablish the area in the event that there is an operational or other requirement for its use at a future date. The Navy should further reserve the right to report as excess, transfer, convey, donate, exchange, outgrant or otherwise dispose of all or any portion of the property at which time it may also be disestablished as a Research Natural Area.

F. S. STERNS
 Deputy Assistant Commander
 for Real Estate

Copy to:
 OASN(MRA&L) (CAPT Macdonald)
 NAVMAT (044)
 NAVAIRSYSCOM (AIR 01B)
~~WESTNAVFACENGCOM (24)~~
 NAS Whidbey Is.

Reply Due _____

Copy in Reading File _____

CODE	INITIAL & DATE
→	
FILES	

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
 OFFICE OF THE CHIEF OF NAVAL OPERATIONS
 WASHINGTON, D.C. 20350

Dir, Seatile Branch

IN REPLY REFER TO
 Ser. 453/722363
 02 NOV 1978

From: Chief of Naval Operations
 To: Commander, Naval Facilities Engineering Command
 Subj: Research Natural Areas, Naval Weapons System Training
 Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, Oregon
 Ref: (a) NAS Whidbey Island ltr PWEC:psw ser 3738 of 22 Sep
 1978
 (b) OPNAVINST 6240.3E

1. By reference (a) a nomination for a portion of NAS Whidbey Island lands was proposed as a Research Natural Area in accordance with reference (b). Accordingly, it is requested that subject designation be concurred with and that coordination be accomplished with the Federal Committee on Ecological Reserves as also stipulated in reference (b).

R. E. Montoya
 R. E. Montoya
 By direction

Copy to:
 CHNAVMAT (MAT 044)
 NAVAIRSYSCOM (AIR 01B)
 COMNAVFACENGCOM (FAC 204)
 WESTNAVFACENGCOM ✓
 CO NAS WHIDBEY ISLAND

Copy in Reading File

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	<i>[Signature]</i>
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PWEC:psw
11011
Ser 2136
SEP 17 1978

From: Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island
To: Chief of Naval Operations, Washington, D.C. (OP-45)

Subj: Research Natural Area, Naval Weapons System Training Facility
(NWSIF) Boardman, Oregon; establishment of

Ref: (a) OPNAVINST 6240.3E, Environmental Protection Manual

Encl: (1) Establishment Report, Research Natural Area, Naval Weapons
Systems Training Facility, Boardman, Oregon (3 copies)

1. Enclosure (1), prepared by the Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, has been signed and is forwarded for final approval in accordance with reference (a). The portion of land designated in enclosure (1) is considered an Experimental Ecological Reserve Area as defined in Chapter 10, Part 5 of reference (a).

J. M. SEELY

Copy to: (w/o encl)
WESTNAVFACENCOM
Seattle Branch, WESTDIV
COMMATVAQWINGPAC

243F:DCR:pr
11015
Ser 243F/230
1 Sep 1978

From: Commanding Officer, Western Division, Naval Facilities
Engineering Command
To: Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island
Subj: Research Natural Area, Naval Weapons System Training Facility,
Boardman, Oregon; establishment of
Ref: (a) Meeting w/CO NAS Whidbey Is, 1300 14 Jun 78
(b) OPNAVINST 6240.3E of 5 Jul 77 (Part 5)
Encl: (1) Establishment Report for Research Natural Area at
NWSTF Boardman, OR (4 copies)

1. As a result of reference (a) and in accordance with reference (b), enclosure (1) has been prepared and is forwarded for your approval.
2. Page 3-1 requires the signature of the Commanding Officer, NAS Whidbey Island. Reference (b) requires forwarding of three copies of enclosure (1) to CNO (OP-45) for final approval. The extra copy is for your records.
3. The proposed Research Natural Areas must be fenced prior to grazing season. Since grazing season begins on or about 1 Nov 78, it is requested that enclosure (1) be forwarded as soon as possible so that fencing can begin as soon as approval is received.

DONALD C. RAPPEL
By direction

Copy to:
WESTNAVFACENCOM (243)
Dir, Nature Conservancy, NW Office
Portland (a.c. 5. 1. 78)

*Mailed
9/1/78 pr*

EDITOR'S FILE COPY

BOARDMAN RESEARCH NATURAL AREA

Supplement No. 17¹

Molly Morton Mayfield¹ and Janet Kjelmyr²

The Research Natural Area described in this supplement is administered by the Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island (Oak Harbor, Wash.). The Officer in Charge of the Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility, Boardman, Oreg., is responsible for coordinating access to the Research Natural Area for scientific and educational uses with scheduled military use of the facility. Scientists interested in using this Research Natural Area should prepare a written proposal that explains the nature, purpose, and duration of the proposed activities. The request should be addressed to the Staff Forester, Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command (Building 138, Room 215, Naval Station, Seattle, Wash. 98115). Requests to do research that is controversial or destructive in nature will be forwarded to the Pacific Northwest Federal Research Natural Areas Committee for its advice on the appropriateness of the particular research. Approval for any use of the area will be made by the Commanding Officer, Naval Air Station, Whidbey Island. For brief observational visits, permission may be obtained from the Officer in Charge at the Naval Facility, Boardman, Oreg.

The Boardman Research Natural Area is a part of a Federal system of RNA's established for research and educational purposes. In these areas, natural features are preserved for scientific purposes and natural processes are allowed to dominate. Their main purposes are to provide:

1. Baseline areas against which effects of human activities can be measured.
2. Sites for study of natural processes in undisturbed ecosystems; and
3. Gene pool preserves of organisms, especially rare and endangered types.

The Federal system is outlined in "A Directory of the Research Natural Areas on Federal Lands of the United States of America." Of the 96 Federal Natural Research Areas established in Oregon and Washington, 45 are described in "Federal Research Natural Areas in Oregon and Washington: A Guidebook for Scientists and Educators" (see footnote 1). Supplements to the guidebook describe additions to the system.

The guiding principle in management of Research Natural Areas is to prevent unnatural encroachments or activities that directly or indirectly modify ecological processes. Logging and uncontrolled grazing are not allowed, for example, nor is public use that might impair scientific or educational values. Management practices necessary for maintenance of the ecosystems may be allowed.

Federal Research Natural Areas provide a unique system of publicly owned and protected examples of undisturbed ecosystems where scientists can conduct research with minimal interference and reasonable assurance that investments in long-term studies will not be lost to logging, land development, or similar activities. In return, a scientist wishing to use a Research Natural Area is obligated to:

1. Obtain permission from the appropriate administering agency before using the area;⁴

¹Supplement No. 17 to "Federal Research Natural Areas in Oregon and Washington: A Guidebook for Scientists and Educators." by Jerry F. Franklin, Frederick C. Hall, C. T. Dymness, and Chris Maser (Pacific Northwest Forest and Range Experiment Station 1-72). The guidebook is available from the Superintendent of Documents, U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington, D.C. 20402; stock number 001-001-00225-9.

²Molly Morton Mayfield is a consulting biologist, P.O. Box 8457, Fort Collins, Colo., 80525. Janet Kjelmyr is a graduate student in ecology at the University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, 87131.

³Federal Committee on Ecological Reserves. A directory of the Research Natural Areas on Federal lands of the United States of America. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service; 1977.

⁴Six agencies cooperate in this program in the Pacific Northwest: U.S. Department of Agriculture-Forest Service; U.S. Department of the Interior-Bureau of Land Management, Fish and Wildlife Service, and National Park Service; the U.S. Department of Energy; and the U.S. Department of Defense.

2. Abide by the administering agency's regulations governing use, including specific limitations on the type of research, sampling methods, and other procedures; and
3. Inform the administering agency on progress of the research, published results, and disposition of collected materials.

The purposes of these limitations are to:

1. Insure that the scientific and educational values of the tract are not impaired;
2. Accumulate a documented body of knowledge about the tract; and
3. Avoid conflict between studies.

Research must be essentially nondestructive: destructive analysis of vegetation is generally not allowed, nor are studies requiring extensive modification of the forest floor or extensive excavation of soil. Collection of plant and animal specimens should be restricted to the minimum necessary to provide voucher specimens. Under no circumstances may collecting significantly reduce population levels of species. Collecting must also be carried out in accordance with applicable State and Federal agency regulations. Within these broad guidelines, appropriate uses of Research Natural Areas are determined by the administering agency.

AR

Native Columbia Basin bunchgrass communities on a mosaic of sandy flood-deposit and loamy lakebed-deposit soils with abundant dry prairie wildlife species.

The Boardman Research Natural Area (RNA) was established September 1, 1978, to preserve high-quality examples of Columbia River basin steppe vegetation communities and associated wildlife. The RNA has never been plowed and has not been grazed since 1948.⁵ Throughout much of the rest of the basin, however, such native communities have been significantly changed by grazing and agriculture.

Sandy flood-deposit and silt loam lakebed soils support bunchgrass communities over most of the Research Natural Area; dominant species include *Aquilegia scopulorum*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Stipa capillata*, and *Poa sandwicensis*. Portions of the RNA are devoid of vegetation where sand has formed into dunes or sandblows. A fragile cryptogam (moss and lichen) ground cover is associated with the bunchgrass communities on certain soil types.

Short-eared owls, long-eared owls, burrowing owls, Swainson's hawks, and ferruginous hawks nest in the vicinity of the RNA. Longbilled curlews nest in large numbers on the RNA and in surrounding areas, and the Washington ground squirrel, whose range appears to be diminishing in the Columbia Basin, has a thriving population in the RNA.⁷

The Boardman RNA is in Morrow County, north-central Oregon, and within the boundaries of the U.S. Naval Weapons Systems Training Facility, hereafter called the Bombing Range (fig. BD-1). The RNA is composed of three separate areas that total 2,196 ha (5,420 acres). RNA "A" located in the center of the Bombing Range, is 1,086 ha (2,660 acres); RNA "B," along the eastern boundary, is 79 ha

(196 acres); and RNA "C," to the southwest, is 980 ha (2,420 acres). The three sections are located in T. 2 and 8 N., R. 25 E., Willamette meridian (lat. 45°42' N., long. 119°42' W.). The entire Bombing Range and RNA's A, B, and C are fenced.

Access and Accommodations

To reach the RNA travel west from Boardman along Interstate 84 for 7.2 km (4.5 mi) to the Tower Road exit. Travel south on Tower Road for 1.6 km (1.0 mi), turn left onto a gravel road, and continue southeast for 1.4 km (0.9 mi) to the administration headquarters. The northern boundary of the Naval Bombing Range is 3.2 km (2 mi) south of Boardman, Oregon, and Interstate 84 (fig. BD-2). All visitors must contact the Officer in Charge prior to their visit and check in on arrival at the headquarters for clearance to enter the RNA.

RNA's A, B, and C may be reached either from headquarters or from the east side of the Bombing Range, via Highway 780, through locked gates. Mileages and routes are indicated in figure BD-2. A more detailed map of the area and complete directions can be obtained at headquarters when checking in.

Overnight camping is prohibited in the Bombing Range. Camping facilities and commercial accommodations are available in Boardman.

Environment

The Boardman RNA is part of the Umatilla Plateau in the central Columbia River basin. Most of the soils and topography are products of one or more episodes of the late-Pleistocene Missoula floods. Waters of Montana's glacial Lake Missoula poured from periodically retreating ice dams southwesterly into the Columbia Basin. At Wallula Gap, on the Oregon-Washington border, the floodwaters were impeded and reached a depth of 244 m (800 ft) (Bretz 1969). South of Wallula Gap, where the

⁵Much of the background information is derived from the "Establishment Report for the Boardman Research Natural Area," by Donald C. Happel (1978) on file at The Nature Conservancy, 1234 N.W. 25th, Portland, Oregon, 97210.

⁶Common names and scientific names of vascular plants are listed in table BD-1.

⁷Scientific names of birds and mammals are listed in tables BD-4 and BD-5, respectively.

Figure BD-1.—Location of the Boardman Bombing Range, south of Boardman, Morrow County, Oregon.

Columbia's channel turns west, floodwaters spilled south onto the Umatilla Plateau where soils and huge ice-raftered erratics were deposited. Most of the Boardman RNA is underlain by these flood deposits over which a variety of sandy soils differing in texture, depth, and other characteristics have formed. Portions of RNA's Band C to the south and east are underlain by older Pleistocene lake deposits over which loamy soils have formed.

The contours of the Boardman Bombing Range rise gently from 122 m (400 ft) in elevation at the northern boundary to 274 m (900 ft) at the southern. The RNA consists of broad,

flat plateau (2- to 5-percent slopes) changing in the south to rounded hillsides that drop into valleys at moderate slopes (5 to 12 percent). These valleys, generally broad and flat across the bottom, are dry most of the year because of the high porosity of the sandy soils and the short duration of rainstorms.

Juniper Canyon, in the eastern part of the Bombing Range (fig. BD-2), has more broken topography with deeper canyons and steeper slopes. Nearby Juniper Canyon provides nesting habitat for many avian species that use the RNA.

Figure BD-2.—Access routes to the Boardman Research Natural Area.

Climate

The climate of the Boardman RNA is semiarid with low precipitation, hot and dry summers, and relatively cold winters. The climate is similar to that of Hermiston, Oreg., 38.4 km (24 mi) to the east.

The following climatic data for the period 1942-1971 are from the U.S. Weather Station, at Hermiston:

Mean annual temperature	11.6 °C	(52.8 °F)
Mean January temperature	-0.1 °C	(31.8 °F)
Mean July temperature	22.6 °C	(72.7 °F)
Mean January minimum temperature	-4.6 °C	(23.7 °F)
Mean July maximum temperature	30.8 °C	(87.5 °F)
Mean annual precipitation (Rain+snow moisture)	22.6 cm	(8.9 in)
Mean annual snowfall (Depth)	22.6 cm	(8.9 in)

The mean annual precipitation for the period was 22.6 cm (8.9 in). Most of the precipitation (68 percent) occurs from October through March with November, December, and January being the wettest months. There are an average of 46 days annually with temperatures in excess of 32.2 °C (90 OF), and an average of 113 days annually with temperatures below 0 °C (32 OF). The maximum temperature recorded during this period was 45°C (113 OF) in August 1961; the minimum recorded was -38°C (-37 OF) in December 1919.

Southwesterly winds prevail most of the year. Wind records for 1942-1972 from the weather station in Pendleton, Oregon [74 km (46 mi) to the east of the RN A] show an average annual wind speed of 14.8 km/h (9.3 mi/h). March through July is the windiest period with velocities averaging 16.2 km/h (10.1 mi/h).

Soils

The soils of the Boardman Bombing Range have been mapped by the U.S. Soil Conservation Service. Six soil types are present on the RNA (fig. BD-3 and table BD-1). Five types (Quincy, Koehler, Sagehill, Taunton, and Royal) are products of the late-Pleistocene Missoula floods. These flood-deposit soils cover approximately 93 percent of the RNA and range from fine sands to fine sandy loams.

The Quincy fine sands or loamy fine sands and the Koehler loamy sands are mildly alkaline and highly permeable. The former, classified as Xeric Torripsamments, are formed in mixed sands and occur on RNA A, extending south into RNA C. The latter, Xerollic Durorthids, are formed in alluvial and colluvial materials mantled with eolian sand and are present on RN A A.

The Sagehill and Taunton fine sandy loams, classified as Xerollic Camborthids and Xerollic Durorthids, respectively, are found intermixed on RN A C. The Royal loamy fine sand or fine sandy loam soils are grouped with the Xerollic Camborthids and are present on RNA C. These three soil types are formed in windlaid materials, are mildly alkaline, and are moderately well-drained.

The sixth soil type (Warden), adjacent to the southern extremity of the soils deposited by the Missoula flood, is a very fine sandy loam or silt loam. The Warden soils are unique among the soil types of the RNA in that they are older, lacustrine-deposit soils. They are mildly alkaline, moderately well-drained sandy loams over silt loams, and formed in wind-laid sands and silts over calcareous lacustrine silts. They are classified as Xerollic Camborthids.

Wind erosion can be severe, particularly on the highly permeable Quincy and Koehler sandy soils, because of the region's low precipitation and high-velocity winds. Vulnerability to wind erosion is reduced in undisturbed areas where a thin surface crust has formed over the soils. Wind erosion is greatly diminished where there is a well-established cryptogam or moss and lichen ground cover. Cryptogam cover is most notable on Warden soils of RNAC.

Figure BD-3.—Soils of the Boardman Research Natural Area.

Table BD-1—General plant community-soil type associations found in the Boardman Research Natural Area

Soil type	Plant community
Warden	<i>Agropyron spicatum-Poa sandbergii</i>
Royal	<i>Agropyron spicatum-Poa sandbergii</i>
Sagehill and Taunton mosaic	<i>Agropyron dasytachyum-Stipa comata and Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii</i>
Koehler	<i>Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii</i>
Quincy	<i>Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii</i>

Unstable sand in the form of dunes or sandblows extends across portions of the Bombing Range and is present in RNA's Band C (fig. BD-3). These blows are thought to be accumulations of riverbed sand that originated from the shores of the Columbia River southwest of Boardman, Ore., and were spread by the prevailing southwesterly winds. In portions of RNA C, the blown sand has become stabilized, and a hummocky terrain has resulted. In one part of RNA B, efforts to stabilize the sandblows were undertaken in 1972 and 1973.⁸ Test plots were treated with a variety of stabilizers, such as shredded bark and papermill sludge, and were seeded with cereal rye. At present, the sand blows are largely stabilized.

Biota

Vegetation

The Boardman RNA is located in the central Columbia Basin region, which is classified as a sagebrush steppe (Daubenmire 1970, Franklin and Dyrness 1973, Kuchler 1965,

Poulton 1955). Despite these classifications, *Artemisia tridentata* is conspicuously absent from most of the RN A, and the perennial bunchgrass species *Agropyron spicatum*, *Agropyron dasytachyum*, *Stipa comata*, and *Poa sandbergii* are dominant.

Variations in plant community structure are associated with changes in soils (fig. BD-3 and table BD-1) and topography. In general, on the five sandy, flood-deposit soils (Quincy, Kuchler, Sagehill, Taunton, and Royal) that cover most of the RN A, *Stipa comata*, *Poa sandbergii*, and *Agropyron dasytachyum* dominate. Their representation and coverage vary among the soil types. On the older Warden lakebed soils, represented only on the southern fringe of RN A's Band C, *Agropyron spicatum* and *Poa sandbergii* are the dominant species. The few concentrations of *Artemisia tridentata* are found in RN A's Band C on a variety of soils where the topography is more broken. Other shrub species found in the RNA are *Purshia tridentata*, widely scattered on the northern portion of RN A, and *Chrysothamnus nauseosus* and *Cercocarpus betulifolius*, both represented in all RNA sections. A list of known shrubs, grasses, and forbs for the RN A is shown in Table BD-2.

⁹Much of the information on plant representation and coverage is derived from field notes of preliminary investigations conducted by William N. Copeland, on file at The Nature Conservancy office, 1234 N.W. 25th, Portland, Ore. 97210.

⁸Ward, George D. and others, 1974. "Engineering study and field demonstration trials for sand dune stabilization, U.S. Naval Bombing Range, Boardman, Oregon." Unpublished report to the Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Bldg. 138, [Room 215, Naval Station, Seattle, Wash. 98115.

Table BD-2—Plants found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}

Family	Scientific name	Common name
SANTALACEAE	<i>Comandra umbellata</i>	Bastard toad-flax
POLYGONACEAE	<i>Eriogonum</i> sp.	Buckwheat
CHENOPODIACEAE	<i>Salsola kali</i>	Russian thistle
CARYOPHYLLACEAE	<i>Holosteum umbellatum</i>	Jagged chickweed
RANUNCULACEAE	<i>Delphinium nuttallianum</i>	Upland larkspur
CRUCIFERAE	<i>Descurainia pinnata</i> <i>Draba verna</i> <i>Erysimum asperum</i> <i>Sisymbrium altissimum</i>	Western tansymustard Spring whitlow-grass Rough wallflower Jim Hill mustard
SAXIFRAGACEAE	<i>Lithophragma bulbifera</i>	Prairiestar
ROSACEAE	<i>Purshia tridentata</i>	Antelope bitter-brush
LEGUMINOSAE	<i>Astragalus purshii</i> <i>Astragalus sclerocarpus</i> <i>Astragalus succumbens</i> <i>Psoralea lanceolata</i>	Pursh's milk-vetch Stalked-pod milk-vetch Crouching milk-vetch Lance-leaf surf-pea
GERANIACEAE	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	Stork's-bill
CACTACEAE	<i>Opuntia polyacantha</i>	Starvation cholla
ONAGRACEAE	<i>Oenothera pallida</i>	Pale evening-primrose
UMBELLIFERAE	<i>Cymopterus terebinthinus</i> <i>Lomatium cous</i> <i>Lomatium macrocarpum</i>	Turpentine cymopterus Cous biscuit-root Large-fruited desert-parsley
POLEMONIACEAE	<i>Gilia minutiflora</i> <i>Microsteris gracilis</i> <i>Phlox longifolia</i>	Small-flowered gilia Pink microsteris Long-leaf phlox
HYDROPHYLLACEAE	<i>Phacelia linearis</i>	Threadleaf phacelia
BORAGINACEAE	<i>Amsinckia lycopsoides</i> <i>Cryptantha</i> sp.	Tarweed fiddleneck Cryptantha
SCROPHULARIACEAE	<i>Penstemon acuminatus</i> <i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	Sand-dune penstemon Common mullein

Table BD-2—Plants found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}—Continued

Family	Scientific name	Common name
PLANTAGINACEAE	<i>Plantago patagonica</i>	Indian-wheat
COMPOSITAE	<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	Common yarrow
	<i>Antennaria dimorpha</i>	Low pussytoes
	<i>Artemisia tridentata</i>	Big sage
	<i>Balsamorhiza careyana</i>	Carey's balsamroot
	<i>Chaenactis douglasii</i> var. <i>achilleaefolia</i>	Hoary chaenactis
	<i>Chrysothamnus nauseosus</i>	Gray rabbitbrush
	<i>Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus</i>	Green rabbitbrush
	<i>Crocidium multicaule</i>	Spring-gold
	<i>Erigeron filifolius</i> var. <i>filifolius</i> ³	Thread-leaf fleabane
	<i>Erigeron linearis</i>	Line-leaf fleabane
	<i>Gutierrezia sarothrae</i>	Snakeweed
	<i>Hemizonia pungens</i> var. <i>septentrionalis</i>	Common spikeweed
	<i>Hieracium</i> sp.	Hawkweed
	<i>Madia glomerata</i>	Cluster tarweed
	<i>Tragopogon dubius</i>	Yellow salsify
	<i>Wyethia amplexicaulis</i>	Northern mule ears
GRAMINEAE	<i>Agropyron cristatum</i>	Crested wheatgrass
	<i>Agropyron dasytachyum</i>	Downy wheatgrass
	<i>Agropyron spicatum</i>	Bluebunch wheatgrass
	<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	Cheat grass
	<i>Elymus mollis</i> ³	Dune wildrye
	<i>Festuca bromoides</i>	Barren fescue
	<i>Festuca idahoensis</i>	Idaho fescue
	<i>Oryzopsis hymenoides</i>	Indian ricegrass
	<i>Poa sandbergii</i>	Sandberg's bluegrass
	<i>Sitanion hystrix</i>	Bottlebrush squirreltail
	<i>Stipa comata</i>	Needle-and-thread grass
LILIACEAE	<i>Brodiaea douglasii</i>	Douglas' brodiaea
	<i>Calochortus macrocarpus</i>	Sagebrush mariposa
	<i>Fritillaria pudica</i>	Yellowbell
	<i>Zigadenus venenosus</i>	Meadow death-camas

¹Information supplied by William N. Copeland, consulting ecologist, Portland, Oreg.; Alan Copsey, Department of Biology, University of Oregon, Eugene; Donald C. Rappel, staff forester, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Seattle, Wash.; and the authors.

²Nomenclature follows Hitchcock and Cronquist (1973).

³Species are tentatively identified for the RNA.

One of the most striking characteristics associated with the *Agropyron spica.turn-Poo sandber'g?:1:* community on Warden soils of RNA's Band C is the fragile and colorful cryptogam (moss and lichen) ground cover. Cryptogam cover is unusually high for the area and is believed to play a role in nitrogen fixation, erosion control, and moisture relationships. Because of the dense ground cover of cryptogams there is a nearly complete absence of weedy grasses and forbs such as *Bmmus tectorum*, *Erolhum c1'cutorium*, *SI'symbn'um alh's.(!l:murn*, and *Am.'J:nckia lycopsoides*. A list of moss and lichen species on the Bombing Range is in table BD-3.

RNA A.-RNA A is composed of two sandy soil types, Koehler and Quincy, both of which support a *Sh:pa. coma.ta-Poa sandbe1'gi1:* community and differ primarily in the cover of the dominant grasses. On the Koehler loamy sands, which extend over all but the southwestern quarter of RNA A A (fig. BD-3), cover of *S. comata*. is relatively high, at 25 to 30 percent (fig. BD-4), *Poa sandbe1'gi1'* is less prevalent, with a cover of 10 percent. *Bnnnus tectorum* is distributed in patches with cover averaging 20 percent. Other grasses such as *Agropyron s7n'cahlm*, *Agropyron dasytochyum*, *Oryzopsis hymenn'des*, and *Festuca* sp. are each present with a cover of less than 5 percent. The shrubs *Chrysothamn/us nauseosus* and *Chl7/sothamnU8 Vi8Cid1;t70r'l.S* both show a low cover of 1 percent, and *Purs/n'a tn:dentata* occurs only as scattered individuals.

Within the southwestern quarter of RNA A, on sandier Quincy loamy fine sands, *Stipo comata* has a lower cover of 10 percent, and *Poa sandbm'gi1:* cover is higher at 12 to 15 percent. *Bnnnus tectorum* is present in local concentrations with a cover of 15 percent. The four other grass species listed above are again present with cover of less than 5 percent. *Chl'Y8othamn1Ui nOU8e0811S* and *Chrysothll'lnnus /J1'scidiflorus* have slightly higher cover values, 2 to 3 percent and 1 to 2 percent, respectively.

Cryptogam cover on both Koehler and Quincy soils is low, at 1 percent.

Table BD-3—Mosses and lichens found in the Boardman Bombing Range¹

Mosses	Lichens
<i>Aloina pilifera</i>	<i>Acarospora schleicheri</i>
<i>Bryum</i> sp.	<i>Dermatocarpon</i>
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	<i>hepaticum</i>
<i>Didymodon australasii</i>	<i>Diploschistes scruposa</i>
<i>Didymodon brachyphyllus</i>	<i>Lecanora muralis</i>
<i>Encalypta</i> cf.	<i>Leptogium byssinum</i>
<i>rhaptocharpa</i>	<i>Polychidium</i>
<i>Funaria hygrometrica</i>	<i>albociliatum</i>
<i>Grimmia montana</i>	<i>Psora luridella</i>
<i>Phascum cuspidatum</i>	
<i>Pseudocrossidium</i>	
<i>revolutum</i>	
<i>Pterygoneurum ovatum</i>	
<i>Tortula brevipes</i>	
<i>Tortula princeps</i>	
<i>Tortula ruralis</i>	

¹Based on information compiled by John A. Christy; on file at The Nature Conservancy, 1234 N.W. 25th, Portland, Oreg. 97210.

Figure BD-4.—*Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii* community on Koehler soils, RNA A.

Common forbs within RNA A are *Holosteum umbellatum.*, *Draba verna*, *Astragalus sclerocarpus*, *Cymopterus terebinthinus*, *Phlox longifolia*, *Achillea millefolium.*, *Antennaria dimorpha*, *Crocidium multicaule*, *Gutierrezia sarothrae*, and *Fritillaria pudica.*

RNA B.-RNA B, the smallest of the RNA sections, contains a wide range of soil types and vegetation from sandblow areas dominated by weedy species to a relatively undisturbed *Agropyron spicatum.-Poa sandbergii* community on Warden very fine sandy loam or silt loam soils.

Within the sandblows, vegetation cover ranges from 5 to 50 percent. Where cover is low, *Salsola kali* and *Chrysothamnus nauseosus* are the primary species. On older, more stabilized surfaces where cover is higher, additional species include *Bromus tectorum.*, *Sisymbrium altissimum.*, *Descurainia pinnata*, and *Hieracium* sp. Along the sandblow margins, additional species include *Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus*, *Gutierrezia sarothrae*, and scattered *Artemisia tridentata* and *Secale cereale*. The *Secale* was seeded during a 1972-1973 effort to stabilize the dunes, and only dispersed individuals now remain.

Undisturbed areas of Warden and Sagehill-Taunton soils in RNA B support a community of *Agropyron spicatum.-Poa sandbergii-Stipa comata* with coverage of 20 to 25 percent, 10 to 15 percent, and 15 to 20 percent, respectively. *Bromus tectorum.* is present in scattered patches. Cryptogam cover is relatively high at 10 to 15 percent.

Common forbs in RNA B include *Holosteum umbellatum.*, *Astragalus purshii*, *Lomatium acrocarpum.*, *Phlox longifolia*, and *Antennaria dimorpha.*

RNA C.-RNA C contains a mosaic of soil types and a corresponding mixture of plant communities. The northwestern portion of RNA C, composed of sandy Quincy soils, has little or no slope. It supports a *Stipa comata-Poa sandbergii* community similar to the one described for Quincy soils on RNA A.

In the southwestern portion of RNA C, topography ranges from flat in the west to hummocky and gently rolling in the east, and the soils are Sagehill and Taunton fine sandy loams. There is a mixture of two bunchgrass

communities: an *Agropyron dasycachyum-Stipa cornata* community with cover values of 10 to 15 percent and 1 percent, respectively, and a *Stipa comata.-Poa sandbergii* community with cover of 15 percent and 8 percent, respectively. *Poa sandbergii* is present in the former with cover of 1 percent. In both communities, shrub cover is low, at 2 percent, with equal distribution of *Chrysothamnus nauseosus* and *C. viscidiflorus*. Cryptogam cover is 1 percent. An area of *Artemisia tridentata* occurs in the rolling, southeastern part of this section of RNA C and is associated with a variety of grasses and forbs.

Another tract of Sagehill-Taunton soils occurs along the rolling eastern margin of RNA C, and the bunchgrass community is similar to the one described above. *Artemisia tridentata* is present along hillsides and in bottoms.

In the central portion of RNA C, on Royal fine sandy loam soils, is a community of *Agropyron spicatum.* and *Poa sandbergii* (cover values 15 to 20 percent and 10 to 15 percent, respectively). *Stipa comata* is present at 5 percent cover. The slopes range from 2 to 5 percent, and *Bromus tectorum.* occurs along hillsides and bottoms. *Chrysothamnus nauseosus* and *Artemisia tridentata*, with an estimated cover of 15 to 20 percent, are distributed in concentrated patches throughout this community.

Along the southern edge of RNA C, flanking the southernmost extension of flood-deposit soils on the RNA A, is a rolling area of Warden very fine sandy loams and silt loams on slopes of 3 to 12 percent. These lakebed-deposit soils support an *Agropyron spicatum.-Poa sandbergii* community with its associated cryptogam ground cover (fig. BD-5). Cover values are 25 percent for *Agropyron spicatum.* and 20 percent for *Poa sandbergii*. *Stipa comata* is present in localized sandier areas. Cryptogam cover is high, estimated at 45 percent, making this community quite different from the RNA communities present on flood-deposit soils. Throughout much of this community, where cryptogam cover is well-established, cover of weedy grasses and forbs is low. Scattered patches, where weedy species such as *Bromus tectorum.*, *Descurainia pinnata*, and *Erodium cicutarium.* replace the cryptogam as dominants, indicate areas of past disturbance. On

Figure BD-5.—*Agropyron spicatum*-*Poa sandbergii* community on Warden soils, RNA C.

the Warden soils described earlier in RNA B, cryptogam cover is lower, at 10 to 15 percent, reflecting past disturbance by grazing which occurred intermittently until 1975. The plant communities on Warden soils that extend south of the boundaries of RNA A's Band C have been heavily grazed since 1963. They show a prominence of weedy species and very little cryptogam ground cover.

On Warden soils in RNA C, *Artemisia tridentata* is largely restricted to draws or to slopes associated with *Borrerlis tectonili*.

Associated forbs within RNA C include *Holosteum umbellatum*, *Diploplopia nana*, *Astragalus purshii*, *Lorrtium cowii*; *Phlox longifolia*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Balsamorhiza hirsuta*, *Eriogonum* and *sonchifolium*.

Fauna

Although the Boardman RNA is limited in diversity of habitat, the bunchgrass communities and associated shrubs provide valuable foraging and nesting sites for many species of animals. Bird, mammal, amphibian, and reptile species observed in the Bombing Range and the RNA are summarized in tables BD-4, BD-5, and BD-6. Those species observed in the Bombing Range but not in the RNA are footnoted.

Bird species that are year-round residents of the Bombing Range include raptors such as the Northern harrier, American kestrel, golden eagle, long-eared owl, and short-eared owl. Other resident species include gray partridge, horned lark, black-billed magpie, common raven, sage sparrow, and western meadowlark.

A notable spring migrant to the RNA is the long-billed curlew; notable because the RNA supports one of the highest densities of breeding curlews in North America (Pam push 1980). Other spring and summer residents include the turkey vulture, common nighthawk, loggerhead shrike, vesper sparrow, and savannah sparrow. The rough-legged hawk is a common winter resident.

Mammals commonly found in the RNA include the Ord kangaroo rat, Great Basin pocket mouse, and deer mouse. Common lagomorphs include Nuttall's cottontail and the black-tailed jackrabbit. Badger, long-tailed weasel, coyote, and an occasional bobcat are the local mammalian predators.

Species of concern known or expected to use the RNA (tables BD-4 and BD-5) include Swainson's and ferruginous hawks, which nest in Juniper Canyon and utilize portions of the RNA as their home range.¹¹ Burrowing owls nest in cheat grass and bitter brush habitat types on the Bombing Range,¹² and northern

¹⁰Species of concern are species considered rare, threatened, or endangered—either in Oregon or throughout their range—by the authorities cited in tables B-4 and B-5.

¹¹Unpublished data on competitive interactions among raptors in the grassland region of North America. Personal communication from Stewart W. Janes, Department of Biology, University of California at Los Angeles, Los Angeles 90024.

¹²Personal communication regarding the ecology of the burrowing owl in the Columbia Basin from Gregory A. Green, Department of Fisheries and Wildlife, Oregon State University, Corvallis—173:31.

Table BD-4—Birds found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}

Order	Scientific name	Common name
ANSERIFORMES	<i>Branta canadensis</i> ³	Canada goose
	<i>Anas crecca</i> ³	Green-winged teal
	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> ³	Mallard
FALCONIFORMES	<i>Cathartes aura</i>	Turkey vulture
	<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	Northern bald eagle
	<i>alascanus</i> ^{3 5 6 7}	
	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	Northern harrier
	<i>Buteo swainsoni</i> ⁵	Swainson's hawk
	<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Red-tailed hawk
	<i>Buteo regalis</i> ⁵	Ferruginous hawk
	<i>Buteo lagopus</i>	Rough-legged hawk
	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	Golden eagle
	<i>Falco sparverius</i>	American kestrel
	<i>Falco mexicanus</i> ⁵	Prairie falcon
GALLIFORMES	<i>Perdix perdix</i>	Gray partridge
	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	Chukar
	<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>	Ring-necked pheasant
	<i>Callipepla californica</i>	California quail
CHARADRIIFORMES	<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>	Killdeer
	<i>Numenius americanus</i>	Long-billed curlew
	<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Ring-billed gull
COLUMBIFORMES	<i>Zenaidura macroura</i>	Mourning dove
STRINGIFORMES	<i>Athene cunicularia</i> ^{3 4}	Burrowing owl
	<i>Asio otus</i>	Long-eared owl
	<i>Asio flammeus</i>	Short-eared owl
CAPRIMULGIFORMES	<i>Chordeiles minor</i>	Common nighthawk
PASSERIFORMES	<i>Sayornis saya</i>	Say's phoebe
	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>	Horned lark
	<i>Pica pica</i>	Black-billed magpie
	<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	American crow
	<i>Corvus corax</i>	Common raven
	<i>Sialia currucoides</i>	Mountain bluebird
	<i>Turdus migratorius</i>	American robin
	<i>Anthus spinoletta</i>	Water pipet
	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	Northern shrike
	<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	Loggerhead shrike
	<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	European starling
	<i>Poocetes gramineus</i>	Vesper sparrow

Table BD-4—Birds found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}—Continued

Order	Scientific name	Common name
	<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>	Lark sparrow
	<i>Amphispiza belli</i>	Sage sparrow
	<i>Passerculus sandwichensis</i>	Savannah sparrow
	<i>Ammodramus savannarum</i> ⁵	Grasshopper sparrow
	<i>Zonotrichia leucophrys</i>	White-crowned sparrow
	<i>Sturnella neglecta</i>	Western meadowlark

Birds listed are believed to use the Natural Area at some time of the year. Information supplied by: Charles Bruce (Corvallis) and Ronald Rohweder (La Grande), Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife; Stewart W. Janes, Department of Biology, University of California, Los Angeles; Donald C. Rappel, staff forester, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Seattle, Wash.; and the authors. All species have been verified by sighting or sound. Species of concern are footnoted.

~Nomenclature follows Eisenmann and others (1982).

;JSpecies is documented for the Bombing Range but not for the RNA itself.

IDyrness and others (1975).

;Marshall (1969).

tilJ.S. Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service (1982).

~(I'eg'(n Department of Fish and Wildlife (1978).

Table BD-5—Mammals found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}

Order	Scientific name	Common name
LAGOMORPHA	<i>Lepus californicus</i>	Black-tailed jackrabbit
	<i>Sylvilagus nuttalli</i>	Nuttall's cottontail
RODENTIA	<i>Spermophilus washingtoni</i> ³	Washington ground squirrel
	<i>Thomomys talpoides</i>	Northern pocket gopher
	<i>Dipodomys ordii</i>	Ord kangaroo rat
	<i>Perognathus parvus</i>	Great Basin pocket mouse
	<i>Onychomys leucogaster</i> ⁴	Northern grasshopper mouse
	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>	Deer mouse
	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i>	Porcupine
CARNIVORA	<i>Canis latrans</i>	Coyote
	<i>Mustela frenata</i>	Long-tailed weasel
	<i>Taxidea taxus</i>	Badger
	<i>Lynx rufus</i>	Bobcat
ARTIODACTYLA	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	Mule deer

Mammals listed are believed to use the Natural Area at some time of the year. Information supplied by Charles Bruce (Corvallis) and Ronald Rohweder (La Grande), Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife; Donald C. Rappel, staff forester, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Seattle, Wash.; B. J. Verts, Department of Fisheries and Wildlife, Oregon State University; and the authors. All species have been verified by sighting, sound, or sign. Species of concern are footnoted.

²Honaki and others (1982).

^aOlterman and Verts (1972).

⁴Dyrness and others (1975).

Table BD-6—Amphibians and reptiles found in the Boardman Research Natural Area^{1 2}

Order	Scientific name	Common name
ANURA	<i>Scaphiopus intermontanus</i>	Great Basin spadefoot toad
SQUAMATA	<i>Sceloporus graciosus</i>	Sagebrush lizard
	<i>Uta stansburiana</i>	Side-blotched lizard
	<i>Phrynosoma douglassi</i>	Short-horned lizard
	<i>Coluber constrictor</i>	Yellow-bellied racer
	<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i>	Gopher snake
	<i>Crotalus viridis</i>	Western rattlesnake

1Amphibians and reptiles listed are believed to use the Natural Area at some time of the year. Information supplied by Charles Bruce (Corvallis) and Ronald Rohweder (La Grande), Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife; and from personal observations by the authors. All species have been verified by sighting.

2Nomenclature follows Stebbins (196G).

bald eagles have been observed at its northern end.!' Breeding pairs of grasshopper sparrows, about whose status in Oregon little is known, have been observed in the RNA (Janes 1983). Mammal species of note include the locally rare northern grasshopper mouse and the Washington ground squirrel (fig. BD-G), which is abundant in RNA C despite a reduced range in the Columbia Basin,14

History of Disturbance

The Boardman Bombing Range was acquired by the Department of the Air Force in 1943 and, through subsequent transfer, by the Department of the Navy in 1960. One-third of the Bombing Range is now owned by the Navy and two-thirds by the Department of the Interior Bureau of Land Management.

From 1943 to 1963 no livestock grazing occurred on the Bombing Range. Since 1963 the northern and southern ends of the range, outside the central fenced octagon (refer to fig.

Figure BD-6.—Washington ground squirrel in RNA C.

¹Personal communication from Donald C. Rappel, Staff Forester, Western Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, Bldg. 1, 8th Room 215, Naval Station, Seattle, Wash. 98115.

²Carlson, Leif; Geoff Geupel; and others. HJ80. "Geographic range, habitat requirements and a preliminary population study of *Spermophilus lateralis* in the Columbia Basin." Unpublished report, on file at The Nature Conservancy, 1284 N.W. 25th, Portland, Oreg. 97210.

BD-2), have been leased by ranchers for grazing cattle and sheep. After the three RNA sections were established and fenced in 1978, the central octagon was opened for grazing. RNA's A and C have not been grazed since the original acquisition of the Bombing Range by the Air Force in 1948. Grazing occurred in RNA B until 1975.

RNA A contains the main target area of the Bombing Range, and several roads are maintained within it. Soil disturbance from the impact of nonexplosive practice bombs is limited to the centermost target portion. RNA A is subject to fires caused by the bombing practice. Fires usually spread to the north and east; because of their rapid movement very little damage is done to the vegetative root systems.

Sandblows in RNA B were the focus of a dune stabilization program carried out in 1972 and 1978. At present, the sandblows are largely stabilized. RNA C is the least disturbed section of the Natural Area and has only a few abandoned roads within its boundaries.

Portland General Electric Co. (PGE) operates the Boardman Coal-Fired Power Plant located approximately 4.8 km (8 miles) west of the Bombing Range boundary. This plant burns low-sulfur subbituminous coal and was operational 162 days from October 1981 through September 1982 (Portland General Electric Co. 1982). Possible environmental impacts of the power plant on the Natural Area are deposition by the prevailing southwesterly winds of fugitive plant emissions or of dust from the coal yard onto the RNA, and incorporation of the emissions or dust into soils, plants, or animals. PGE maintains an ecological monitoring site on the Bombing Range to assess environmental conditions and to detect ecological impacts in the vicinity of the coal plant. To date, PGE has found no evidence of such impacts (Portland General Electric Co. 1982).

Research

The Boardman RNA, protected from the pressures of grazing and agricultural development that are occurring in much of the Columbia Basin, offers researchers an opportunity to study high-quality examples of native bunchgrass communities and their associated wildlife. Previous research on the flora and fauna

of the Boardman Bombing Range and RNA, in addition to the studies mentioned in the text, includes plant succession after natural disturbances by resident burrowing mammals, the effects of grazing on breeding passerines; and the ecology of the Great Basin pocket mouse (Small and Verts 1988).

Additional opportunities for research on the RNA include the establishment of permanent vegetation transects for long-term study of the structure of the different bunchgrass communities. Concurrent monitoring of the plant communities and soils in grazed areas outside the RNA boundaries would offer valuable management information on the effects grazing has on species representation, substrate quality, and erosion. The RNA offers a unique opportunity to study how the cryptogam ground cover of the Warden soils affects a variety of ecosystem characteristics such as nitrogen fixation, erosion control, moisture relationships, and control of invasion by weedy plant species. In addition, long-term monitoring of the moss and lichen species could serve as an indicator of possible air quality changes resulting from emissions at the Boardman Coal-Fired Power Plant. Other research possibilities include primary plant succession on sand blows of RNA's Band C, successional stages of vegetation reestablishment in burned areas, and continued monitoring of sensitive species such as Swainson's and ferruginous hawks, grasshopper sparrow, and Washington ground squirrel.

Maps and Aerial Photographs

Maps applicable to Boardman Research Natural Area are: Topographic-Well Springs, Oregon quadrangle, scale 1:24,000, issued by the U.S. Geological Survey in 1968; Strawberry Canyon NE, Oregon quadrangle, scale 1:24,000, issued by the U.S. Geological Survey in 1968; and Geologic-Geologic Map of Oregon East of the 121st Meridian, scale 1:500,000 (Walker 1977). The Naval Facilities

"Personal communication from Alan Cropsey, Department of Biology, University of Oregon, Eugene, 97403.

"Janes, Stewart. W. 1981. "Effects of grazing upon the breeding avifauna of the Boardman Naval Weapons Training Facility." Unpublished report. on file at. The Nature Conservancy office, 1224 N.W. 25th, Portland, Oregon. 97210 ..

Engineering Command in Seattle, Washington, can provide details on the most recent aerial photo coverage for the area. In addition, Pacific Gas and Electric makes monthly flights at 2700 m (9,000 ft) over the RNA taking true color and color infrared photographs. Photographs are available on request from Richard Davis, Department of Environmental Sciences, Pacific Gas and Electric, 121 S.W. Salmon Street, Portland, Oreg. 97204.

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The Forest Service of the U.S. Department of Agriculture is dedicated to the principle of multiple use management of the Nation's forest resources for sustained yields of wood, water, forage, wildlife, and recreation. Through forestry research, cooperation with the States and private forest owners, and management of the National Forests and National Grasslands, it strives - as directed by Congress - to provide increasingly greater service to a growing Nation.

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Pacific Northwest Forest and Range

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APPENDIX F. Vegetation Monitoring Program

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3. RANGE MONITORING PROGRAM 1987

The range monitoring program developed for the station is a procedure that consists of two phases, one conducted annually and one periodically over a span of years.

The annual phase consists of interpreting patterns of utilization that exist following the livestock grazing season. The procedure involves judging five classes of utilization on key species, mapping use zones within a pasture, and evaluating these zones to determine the effects that the current grazing system and existing facilities and improvements collectively are having on the resources within the pasture. This entire procedure is outlined in an article written by:

Anderson, E. William and W.F. Currier. 1973. Evaluating zones of Utilization. *Journal of Range Management* 26(2) 87-91.

The periodic phase consists of interpreting data collected on permanent plots. The objective of this procedure is to measure changes that occur in the plant community. These measured changes consist of the following: floristic composition; canopy cover; litter; plant vigor; and forage production. In this procedure, each permanent plot consists of three components: a 3 foot square plot marked by steel pegs which serves as a close-up photo point; a 25 foot line plot marked by a steel fence post to encompass the photo plot, which serves as a general aspect photo line; and an unmarked plot approximately 50 feet in radius centered on the smaller photo plot which serves as the area where all plant species are recorded and canopy coverage determined. Data collection begins by listing all species that occur within the 50 feet circle and then estimating the canopy cover and dominance rating for each individual species. Determinations are also made for bare ground, litter and mulch, rocks, and mosses and lichens. Estimations are made on forage production, and apparent vigor of key species. This entire procedure is outlined in a manuscript written by:

Anderson, E. William. 1987. Canopy cover as a method of monitoring trend in ecological and soil status. Submitted to *Rangelands*.

The periodic phase of this monitoring program was initiated in early May and the annual phase in early June after the cattle were removed from the station. The information obtained from this program is contained herein.

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE FIELD DATA SHEET

PLANT & SPECIES	DATE: May 4, 87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Barren Ground	XXX	60	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones <i>Celiche chips</i>	XXX	3	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	1	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Stems & Fibers	1	T						
<i>Cheatgrass</i>	1	35						
Grass & Grass-like								
<i>Buckwheat, snow (tail)</i>		1						
<i>Chicory</i>		1						
<i>Desert Parsley, chimaya</i>		1						
<i>Mustard, Jim Hill</i>		1						
<i>Fiddleneck</i>		1						
<i>False yarrow</i>		1						
<i>Phlox, longleaf</i>		1						
<i>Chickweed, jagged</i>		10						
<i>Sand verbenas, white</i>		2						
<i>Milk vetch, Columbia</i>		1						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Trees								
<i>Bitterbrush</i>	5	10						
<i>Rabbitbrush, green</i>	4	1						
<i>Rabbitbrush, (gray) rubber</i>	1	5						
Total Cover:	XXX	73	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	18	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day	Mo. Av. : Day
Kat. lbs/acre air dry: For. Grass & Forbs:	0							
Shrubs:								
Apparent vigor (key species):	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L
<i>B. Her brush</i>	X							
Seedlings:	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some
<i>Buckwheat</i>	X							
NAME IN UNIT: Boardman Bomb Range HT: McClelland - Anderson PWI: 1 EDUL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon POOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace PLANT/MAP: PLANT LOCATION: Approx 70 yds south from 0.5 mile post east of Navy Hdqtrs in Pasture 5 (over) 25-30' S of tall steel fencepost.								

Plot #1 is in Pasture 5 south of the main road going SE from Navy Headquarters. It is located about 70 yd. south of the 0.5 mile marker (a post marked 5). The plot, which is marked with a 6' steel fencepost and lies about 25-30 feet south of this post, consists of a 3-foot-square marked at each corner by a steel rod painted red. A fifth steel rod slightly south of the plot is the photo point for the camera tripod from which photos are taken of the plot itself and of the site aspect with the steel post in the middle.

The soil at this plot is Koehler loamy sand

0-30" loamy sand 30" + calcareous pan

Cover data represents the area approximately 50 feet radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 1

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

Plot #2 is in Pasture 1 east of the N-S road that bisects the pasture and about 0.3-0.4 mile south of the north boundary fence. The plot lies about 70 feet east of the road on a hummock which is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of a 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50 ft. radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Hezel loamy sand (0-12" loamy sand; 12-42: sandy loam laminated calcareous, hard; 42" + soft silt loam).

PLOT 2

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

MONITORING FORM FOR FEDERAL & BUREAU OF LAND MANAGEMENT FIELD DATA SHEET

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 5/5/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	30	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stone	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	20	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	5	1						
Cheatgrass	5	50						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	3-	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Scurfpea	3	5						
Filaree	3	7						
Mustard, Jimhill	3	T						
Pricklypear	2	T						
Aster, hoary	1	T						
Fiddleneck	1	T						
Desert parsley, Chimeya	1	T						
Lettuce, prickly	1	T						
Buckwheat, snow	1	T						
Farrow	1	T						
Sandverbena, white	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Rabbitbrush, rubber	3	2						
Rabbitbrush, Douglas green	3	T						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	65	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	7	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv	
Kat. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	0							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H M L		H M L		H M L		H M L	
Sandberg bluegrass	X							
Seedlings:	abun some		abun some		abun some		abun some	
NAME IN UNIT: Boardman Bombing Range BY: McClelland & Anderson PLANT: 3 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon ECOL. SITE: PLANT/MAP: PLANT LOCATION: See reverse side								

Plot #3 is in Pasture 1. It is located north of the road that parallels the south fence about 0.3 mile west from the east gate and 100 yds. north of the road. The plot is marked with a steel fencepost which is about 30 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel pegs. A fifth steel peg south of the plot marks the photo point from which the 3-foot-plot and the site aspect were photographed.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

PLOT 3

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 5/5/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	70	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	25	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	1	T						
Needle-and-thread	5	1						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	3	1						
Cheatgrass	3	7						
Grass & Grass-like								
Elyce	5	3						
Prickly pear	2	T						
Lettuce, prickly	2	T						
Phacelia, threadleaf	1	T						
Mustard, Jimball	3	T						
Yarrow	1	T						
Scarfpea	3	T						
Desert parley, chimaya	1	T						
Sand verbena, white	2	T						
Popcorn flower, slender	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Rabbitbrush, rubber	5	20						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	37	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	23	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(b, av) Av : Day		Abav: Av : Day		Abav: Av : Day		Abav: Av : Day	
Kat. lbs/acre air dry: Per, Grass & Forbs:	50							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	N	M	L	N	M	L	N	M
Needle-and-thread			X					
Sandberg bluegrass	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
NAME (in unit): Boardman Bombing Range HT: McClelland & Anderson PLOT: 4 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon SCOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace PLOT/MAP: PLOT LOCATION: See reverse side								

Plot #4 is located in Pasture 2, 0.4 mile west and 100 yds. south of the gate in NW corner of Pasture 2C where it joins Pasture 2. The plot is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg just south of the 3-foot square is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents the area approximately 50 feet radius from the 5-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

PLOT 4

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE FIELD DATA SHEET

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 6/5/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	30	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens		10						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	3	2						
Cheatgrass	5	20						
Grass & Grass-like								
Scurf pea	4	30						
Prickly pear	3+	5						
Filaree	3+	10						
Desert parsley, chimaya	1	T						
Phacelia, threadleaf	1	T						
Popcornflower, slender	1	T						
Flax, longleaf	1	T						
False yarrow	1	T						
Fiddleneck	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Rabbit brush, rubber	WNY	1						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green		T						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	67	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	37	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv	
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	20							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H M L		H M L		H M L		H M L	
Sandberg bluegrass	X							
Seedlings:	abun some		abun some		abun some		abun some	
NAME ON UNIT: Boardman Bombing Range HT: McClelland & Anderson PLT: 5 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon ECOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace PHOTO/MAP: PLANT LOCATION: See reverse side								

Plot #5 is located in Pasture 2C on the west side of the N-S road through the middle of the pasture and 0.3-0.4 mile south of the north boundary fence. It is marked by a steel fencepost 40-50 yds. west of the road which is about 20 ft. north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg south of the 3-foot-plot is the photo point for photos of the 3-foot plot and the site aspect. Data represents the area within about 50' radius of the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

PLOT 5

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

TAXA & SPECIES	DATE: 5/5/07		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	75	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	15	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	5	1						
Needle-and-thread	5	7						
Cheat grass	8	7						
Blue grass, Sandberg	3	2						
Grass & Grass-like								
Scurf pea	3	2						
Fiddle neck	1	T						
Agoseris, annual	1	T						
Mustard, Jim Hill	1	T						
Desert parsley, chimaya	2	T						
Prickly pear	2	T						
Phlox, longleaf	3	T						
Yarrow	2	T						
Buckwheat, snow	1	T						
Milk vetch, stalked	1	T						
Popcorn flower, slender	1	T						
Forbs								
Rabbit brush, rubber	1	3						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green	1	T						
Shrubs								
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	22	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	15	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	0.45 Av : 0.45		0.45 Av : 0.45		0.45 Av : 0.45		0.45 Av : 0.45	
Kat. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	250							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Needle & Thread	X							
Sandberg blue grass	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
Yarrow		1						
RANGE (IN UNIT): Boardman Bombing Range			PILOT: McClelland & Anderson			PLANT: 6		
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon			ECOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace					
PHOTO/MAP:			PLANT LOCATION: See reverse side					

Plot #6 is located in Pasture 4B about 0.3 mile south of the buried pipeline that runs diagonally NW to SE across the pasture. It is located about 100 feet west of the N-S road through center of pasture and is marked by a steel fencepost that is about 30 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel rods pointed red. A fifth steel rod slightly south of the 3-foot plot is the photo hub from which color photos of the 3-foot plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents an area about 50 feet radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

PLOT 6

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 6/5/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	80	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	20	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	2	2						
Cheatgrass	4	15						
Needle-and-thread	2	T						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	2	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Scarf pea	3	2						
Mustard Jimbill	3	T						
Filaree	3	T						
Agoseris, annual	1	T						
Fiddle neck	2	T						
Aster?	3	2						
Lettuce, prickly	1	T						
Indian wheat, woolly	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Rabbit brush, rubber	4	5						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green	4	6						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	35	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	15	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab. Av) Av : BcAv		ABAv: Av : BcAv		ABAv: Av : BcAv		ABAv: Av : BcAv	
Rat. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	10							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Sandberg blue grass	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
Aster?		X						
NAME (IN UNIT): Boardman Bombing Range			HT: McClelland & Anderson			PLANT?		
ECOL. DIVISION: Columbia Basin - Oregon			ECOL. SITE: Light Loamy Terrace					
PHOTO/MAP:			PLANT LOCATION: See reverse side					

Plot #7 is located in Pasture E about 0.6 mile south of the gate in NW corner of Pasture E. It is located east of the road about 100 yds. where the road bends to the SE. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg slightly south of the 3-foot square plot is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents an area about 50 ft. radius from the 3-foot square plot.

Soil is Royal loamy very fine sand.

PLOT 7

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

TYPES & SPECIES	DATE: 6/5/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER						
Bare Ground	XXX	70	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	15	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Grasses & Grass-like								
Needle-and-thread	3	15						
Cheat grass	5	15						
Fescue, pacific	2	T						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	1	T						
Ricegrass, Indian	1	T						
Wheatgrass, beardless bluebunch	1	T						
Forbs								
Scarf pea	3	T						
Yarrow	2	T						
Popcorn flower	1	T						
Mustard, Jimhill	1	T						
Indian wheat	3-	T						
Phacelia, thread leaf	1	T						
Aster?	1	T						
Fiddleneck	1	T						
Fillares	2	T						
Aquilegia, annual	1	T						
Shrubs								
Rabbit brush, rubber	3	1						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green	3	T						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	35	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	19	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	Ab: Av: B: Av: B: Av							
Ret. lbs/acre air dry: Forb, Grass & Forb:	350							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Needle-and-thread	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
NAME IN UNIT: Boardman Bomb Range BY: MacClelland & Anderson PLOT: B ECOL. PROJIN: Columbia Basin - Oregon ECOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace PLOT/REP: PLOT LOCATION: see reverse side								

Plot #8 is located in the SW portion of Pasture 3. It is located about 50 yds. north of the E-W road about 0.2 mile east of the main N-S grave road. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg slightly south of the 3-foot plot is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represent an area about 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Koehler loamy sand (36" caliche).

PLOT 8

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

Plot #9 is located in Pasture 4A about 0.3 mile south of the gravel road in the NW portion of the pasture. The plot lies about 50 yds. west of the N-S road, in the west half of Pasture 4A. The plot is marked with a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

The soil is Quincy loamy sand (over 54" deep). Note that the soil map rates this area as Koehler but no duripan was encountered at the plot site in 54 inches.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 9

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

SPECIES & SPECIES	DATE: 5/6/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Upland Ground	XXX	80	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stone	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Herbs & Forbs	2	2						
Needle & Thread	3	T						
Cheatgrass	4	15						
Ricegrass, Indian	1	T						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	2	T						
Wheatgrass, beardless blinch	1	T						
Wheatgrass, Thickspike	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Desert parsley	3	5						
Scurf pea	3	2						
Yarrow	3	1						
Phacelia, linleaf	3	1						
Phlox, longleaf	2	T						
Flaree	3	5						
Riddleneck	3	T						
Prickly pear	3	T						
Mustard, Jim hill	2	T						
Balsamroot, Carey	3	T						
Milkvetch, longstem stalkpod	1	T						
Wallflower	1	T						
Popcorn flower	2	T						
Buckwheat, snow	1	T						
Sandverbena, white	1	T						
Lettuce, prickly	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Trees								
Bitter brush	1	T						
Rabbitbrush, Douglas green	3	T						
Rabbitbrush, rubber	4	2						
Total Cover:	XXX	33	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	11	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab. Av) Av : BeAv		ABAV: Av : BeAv		ABAV: Av : BeAv		ABAV: Av : BeAv	
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	10							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Bluegrass Sandberg	X							
Needle-and-thread	X							
Wheatgrass, beardless blinch	X							
Seedling:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
MAP: IN UNIT: Boardman Bomb Range			BY: McClelland & Anderson			PLANT: 10		
ECOL. PLANTING: Columbia River - Oregon			ECOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace					
PLANTING: See reverse side								

Plot #10 is located in Pasture (Mobile Target Area) about 100 yds. SW from the gate in the north boundary fence on the N-S road in the center of the pasture. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 30' north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

The soil is Quincy loamy sand over 54" deep.

Note that this area is used to have a stand of bitterbrush as evidenced by some burned stubs and standing skeletons visible.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 10

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 5/6/57		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	60	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	T	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	15	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	3	1						
Needle-and-thread	5	15						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	3+	10						
Cheatgrass	3+	20						
Wheatgrass, crested	2	T						
Ricegrass, Indian	2	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Scurfpea	3	3						
Indianwheat, woolly	3	1						
Phlox, longleaf	3	1						
Pussytoes	1	T						
Balsamroot, Carey	1	T						
Stoneseed	1	T						
Agoseris, annual	1	T						
Yarrow	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Trees								
Rabbit brush, rubber	4	5						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green	3-	T						
Total Cover:								
Perennial Cover:	XXX	85	XXX		XXX		XXX	
	XXX	34	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	Ab. Av	Av	BoAv	AbAv	Av	BoAv	AbAv	Av
Est. lbs/acre air dry: Forbs, Grasses & Forbs:	260							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Needle & Thread	X							
Crested wheatgrass	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	X	abun	some		abun	some
Balsamroot, Carey								
NAME: Boardman Bombing Range BY: McClelland & Anderson PLOT: 11 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon SCOL. SITE: Loamy Sand Terrace PLOT/MAP: PLOT LOCATION: See reverse side								

Plot #11 is in proposed Pasture 4C about 0.75 mile south of the graveled road that runs diagonally NW to SE in the northern portion of the pasture. It is located about 100' east of the N-S road and 100' south of W-E target approach line in the center of Pasture 4C.

The soil is Koehler loamy fine sand (42" to gravelly, calcareous duripan).

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 11

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

TAXA & SPECIES	DATE: 5/6/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	50	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	20	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	3	10						
Needle-and-thread	4	5						
Cheatgrass	4	25						
Wheatgrass, blue bunch	1	T						
Bluegrass, Gandberg	2	T						
Wheatgrass, Thickspike	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Salsify	1	T						
Mustard, Jimhill	1	T						
Lettuce, prickly	1	T						
Filaree	1	T						
Mariposa lily	1	T						
Phlox, longleaf	1	T						
Indianwheat, woolly	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	50	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	5	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	Ab, Av	Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv	AbAv: Av : BcAv
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	100							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L
Needlegrass	X							
Seedlings:	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some
Blue bunch wheatgrass		X						
RANCH OR UNIT: Boardman Bombing Range			BY: McClelland & Anderson			PLOT: 12		
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon			SOIL SITE: Light loamy Terrace					
PHOTO/MAP:			SITE LOCATION: See reverse side					

Plot #12 is located in Pasture 1A about 0.25 mile south of the north gate of the N-S road in the pasture. It is about 200 ft. west of the road and is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

Soil is Royal fine sandy loam (over 48' deep).

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 12

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 5/6/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	16	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens		40						
Wheatgrass bluebunch	5	15						
Blue grass Sandberg	3	20						
Needle-and-thread	2	T						
Cheatgrass	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Indianwheat mostly	3-	1						
Polygon spreading	3	T						
Maniposa	1	T						
Lomatium (gray carrot leaf)	2	T						
Pussytoes	1	T						
Yarrow	1	T						
Forbs								
Snakeweed	3	1						
Shrubs								
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX		XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX		XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv	
Rat. lbs/acre air dry: Per, Grass & Forbs:	300							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L
Wheatgrass, bluebunch	X							
Seedlings:	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some
Bluegrass Sandberg		X						
Wheatgrass, bluebunch		X						
NAME IN UNIT: Boardman Bomb Range		NT: McClelland & Anderson		PLANT: 13				
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon		POOL SITE: Silty Terrace						
PHOTO/MAP:		PLANT LOCATION:		See reverse side				

Plot #13 is in Pasture B. It is located 0.5 mile west from the gate in the SE corner and 0.2 mile north from the south boundary fence. It is marked with a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of a 3-foot-square plot marked with 4 steel rods painted red.

The soil is Warden silt loam.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 13

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

WILDLIFE TOWN IN EXPERIMENTAL & SOIL STUDIES FIELD DATA SHEET

TOWN & SPECIES	DATE: 5/6/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	40	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	3+	30						
Needle-and-thread	1	5						
Wheatgrass, blue bunch	3	1						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	1	20						
Cheatgrass	3	2						
Grass & Grass-like								
Phlox, spreading	3	1						
LS Hues, prickly	2	1						
Salsify	3	1						
Filaree	3	2						
Indianwheat, woolly	3+	10						
Fleabane, cushion	1	1						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Synake weed	3	1						
Rabbitbrush, rubber	3	1						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	48	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	III	29	III		III		III	
Growing season this year:	Ab. Av	Av : BeAv	AbAv:	Av : BeAv	AbAv:	Av : BeAv	AbAv:	Av : BeAv
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For. Grass & Forbs:	80							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H M L	A	H M L		H M L		H M L	
Seedlings:	abun some		abun some		abun some		abun some	
NAME ON UNIT: Boardman Bomb Range			BY: McCliland & Anderson			PLANT: K1		
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon			ECOL. SITE: Silty Terrace					
PHOTO/MAP:			PLANT LOCATION: See reverse side					

Plot #14 is located in the west central portion of Pasture 2A. It is 0.5 miles east from the main N-S road and about 10 ft. north of the E-W road through the middle of the pasture. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

Soil is Warden silt loam.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 14

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

ITEMS & SPECIES	DATE: 5/7/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	1	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Herbs & Forbs	3+	35						
Wheatgrass, blue bunch	4	3						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	4	20						
Cheatgrass	3	6						
Squirrel tail	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Pilarce	3	15						
Fleabane, cushion	1	T						
Fleabane, shaggy	1	T						
Pussy toes	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Trees								
Sagebrush								
Sagebrush, Basin big	3	8						
Rabbit brush, rubber	1	T						
Rabbit brush, Douglas green	2	T						
Total Cover:	XXX	86	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	35	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BAv		ABAV: Av : BAv		ABAV: Av : BAv		ABAV: Av : BAv	
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	200							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L	H M L
Wheatgrass bunch	X							
Bluegrass Sandberg	X							
Seedlings:	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some	abun some
MAN: UN UNIT: Boardman Bombing Range			BY: McClelland & Anderson			PLNT: 15		
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon			ECOL. SITE: Silty terrace					
PLNT/MAP:			PLNT LOCATION: 300 reverse side					

Plot #15 is located in Pasture 2B south of the Old Oregon Trail and in the SE portion of the pasture. It is located about 0.1 miles south of the road E-W which is about halfway between the south boundary and the Old Oregon Trail. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4-steel pegs painted red.

The soil is Warden silt loam.

PLOT 15

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

MONITORING TOWER IN ECOLOGICAL & SOIL STATUS FIELD DATA SHEET

TYPE & SPECIES	DATE: 5/7/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER						
Bare Ground	XXX	7	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens		30						
Wheatgrass, bluebunch	3	2						
Needle-and-thread	5	7						
Bluegrass, Sandberg	3	80						
Cheatgrass	3	10						
Grass & Grass-like								
Indianwheat woolly	3	1						
Filaree	3	3						
Phlox, spreading	3	5						
Lettuce, prickly	1	T						
Penstemon	1	T						
Lomatium (gray carrotleaf)	2	T						
Fleabane, woolly	1	T						
Maniposa	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Sagebrush, basin big	3	T						
Shake weed	2	F						
Rabbitbrush, Douglas green	1	T						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	53	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	14	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	Ab: Av: Be: Av							
Est. lbs/acre air dry: Per, Grass & Forbs:	180							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Wheatgrass bluish	X							
Needle-and-thread	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
HANDBOOK UNIT: Boardman Bombing Range BY: McClelland & Anderson PLOT: 16 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon ECOL. SITE: light loamy Terrace PHOTO/MAP: PLOT LOCATION: See reverse side								

Plot #16 is located in Pasture 2B, NE quarter north of the Old Oregon Trail. It is located about 1.0 miles north of the main E-W road which is north of the Old Oregon Trail. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked with 4 steel rods painted red.

Soil is Warden very fine sandy loam.

PLOT 16

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

TYPES & SPECIES	DATE: 5/7/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	95	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	10	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Rhizomes & Tubers	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like	Needle-and-thread	5	15					
	Bluegrass, bluebunch	3	2					
	Fescue, 3-leaved	3	2					
	Heat grass	3	3					
	Ricegrass, Indian	1	T					
	Wheatgrass, bluebunch	3-	1					
Forbs	Indianwheat, woolly	3	1					
	Phlox, longleaf	3	T					
	Aster	2	T					
	Piddle-neck	2	T					
	Mustard, Jim Hill	2	T					
	Mariposa	2	T					
	Sand verbena, white	1	T					
	Pussytoes	2	T					
	Milkvetch striated	1	T					
	Lettuce, prickly	2	T					
	Prickly pear	2	T					
	Scurf pea	2	T					
	Milkvetch, Columbia	1	T					
	Desert parsley, chimya	2	T					
	Salicy	1	T					
Trees	Rabbit brush, rubber	1	T					
	Rabbitbrush, Douglas green (burned stumps scattered)	1	T					
Total Cover:	XXX	30	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	22	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv		AbAv: Av : BeAv	
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	250							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (key species):	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M
Needle-and-thread	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
HATCH OR UNIT: Bogardman Geopline Camp			BY: McClelland & Anderson			PLWT: 17		
ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon			ECOL. SITE:					
PLOT/MAP:			PLOT LOCATION: see reverse side					

Plot #17 is located in Pasture 3A about 1.4 miles east of gate at SW corner of Main Target area and 0.2 mile on a road NE-SW of the Main Target south boundary fence. The plot is marked by a steel fencepost about 50' east of the road which is about 25' north of the 3-foot-square plot marked with 4 steel rods painted red.

The soil is Koehler loam fine sand (30" to gravel and fragments of calcareous duripan).

PLOT 17

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

BRITISH COLUMBIA HERBARIUM & SOIL SERVICE FIELD DATA SHEET

TYPES & SPECIES	DATE: 5/7/87		DATE:		DATE:		DATE:	
	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER	DOMI-NANCE	CANOPY COVER
Bare Ground	XXX	40	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Gravel & Stones	XXX	0	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Litter & Mulch	XXX	20	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Mosses & Lichens	2	3						
Needle-and-Thread	5	15						
Bluegrass Sandberg Sandberg	3	15						
Wheatgrass	1	10						
Wheatgrass, bluebunch	1	T						
Gquirreltail	1	T						
Grass & Grass-like								
Aster?	2	T						
Indian wheat woolly	3	T						
Salsify	1	T						
Mustard Jim Hill	1	T						
Le Muce, prickly	1	T						
Filaree	1	T						
Mariposa	1	T						
Phlox, long leaf	1	T						
Loce, woolly pod	1	T						
Forbs								
Shrubs								
Rabbitbrush, rubber	5	2						
Rabbitbrush, Douglas green	3	T						
Trees								
Total Cover:	XXX	49	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Perennial Cover:	XXX	82	XXX		XXX		XXX	
Growing season this year:	(Ab, Av) Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv		AbAv: Av : BcAv	
Est. lbs/acre air dry: For, Grass & Forbs:	150							
Shrubs:	0							
Apparent vigor (any species):	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L	H N L
Needle & Thread	X							
Bluegrass, Sandberg	X							
Seedlings:	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some	abun	some
MAP: IN WHITE: Boardman Bombing Range UT: McMillan-Bedell-Anderson PLOT: 18 ECOL. PROVINCE: Columbia Basin - Oregon SCOL. SITE: Light Loamy Terrace FINISH/MAP: PLANT LOCATION:								

Plot #18 is located in the east portion of Pasture 3A about 1/4 mile from the Bombing Range road. It is 0.3 mile west on the E-W road that enters the pasture near the potato shed east of the highway and 0.2 mile south of this road on a N-S road that skirts several dune areas. The plot is located 50 yds. east of this road that goes up a hill. It is marked by a steel fencepost about 25 ft. north of the 3-foot-square plot marked with 4 steel pegs painted red.

The soil is Sagehill very fine sandy loam (32" to silt loam).

Cover data represents the area approximately 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

PLOT 18

CLOSE-UP PHOTOGRAPH

ASPECT PHOTOGRAPH

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Changes in vegetation on range monitoring plots at Naval Weapon Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman from 1987-2008

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January 2009

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Conservancy
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Appendices

- Appendix A. 1987 and 1988 descriptions of range monitoring plot locations at NWSTF Boardman
- Appendix B. Range monitoring plot datasheets for NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008
- Appendix C. Range monitoring plot photos for NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008

1. Introduction

The Naval Weapon Systems Training Facility (NWSTF) Boardman, combined with the adjacent Boardman Conservation Area and other private lands, contain some of the best remaining grassland and shrub-steppe in the Columbia Plateau ecoregion (Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife 2005). Grasslands and shrub-steppe at NWSTF Boardman provide important habitat for sensitive wildlife including the Washington ground squirrel, a candidate species under the Federal Endangered Species Act and listed species under the Oregon Endangered Species Act; and the loggerhead shrike, sage sparrow, ferruginous hawk, burrowing owl, and northern sagebrush lizard, all listed as a species of concern under the Federal Endangered Species Act, and critical or vulnerable under the Oregon Endangered Species Act (Oregon Natural Heritage Information Center 2004).

To track changes in grassland and shrub-steppe condition, a range monitoring program was developed at NWSTF Boardman in 1987. Data was last collected in 1987, and since then, several large fires have burned through the site, military training activities have been reduced, and the grazing program has ceased. In 2008, range monitoring plots were re-surveyed to document the changes in vegetation that have occurred over the last twenty-one years. The purpose of this report is to summarize the 2008 survey results and evaluate changes in grassland and shrub-steppe condition.

2. Methods

2.1 Site description

The 47,400 acre NWSTF Boardman is located in Morrow County, Oregon. Vegetation on the property is composed of a mosaic of grassland and shrubland plant communities. Dominant native vegetation includes bunchgrass communities composed of bluebunch wheatgrass (*Pseudoroegneria spicata* ssp. *spicata* (*Agropyron spicatum*)), needle and threadgrass (*Hesperostipa* (*Stipa*) *comata*), and Sandberg's bluegrass (*Poa secunda*); and shrubland communities dominated by big sagebrush (*Artemisia tridentata*), antelope bitterbrush (*Purshia tridentata*), rabbitbrush (both *Ericameria nauseosa* and *Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus*) and western juniper (*Juniperus occidentalis*). Large portions of NWSTF Boardman have been invaded by cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), a non-native annual grass. In most areas, cheatgrass occurs within a matrix of native vegetation, but some heavily disturbed areas are dominated by cheatgrass and other non-native species. A more detailed description of plant community types at NWSTF Boardman is available in Miller et al. (2007).

Several large-scale disturbances at NWSTF Boardman have influenced vegetation composition in recent history, including livestock grazing, military activities, and wildfires. Prior to purchase by the U.S. military, NWSTF Boardman was heavily grazed by horses and sheep, and cattle and sheep continued to graze large portions of the property until the grazing lease was terminated in 2002 (Miller et al. 2007). From 1943 to 1996, NWSTF Boardman was actively used by the military for aerial bombing and gunnery training but since 1996 has only been used infrequently for military training (Miller et al. 2007). Within the last ten years, several large wildfires have burned across the property. In 1998, 17,000 acres burned, in 2002, 5,000 acres burned, and in 2007, 11,600 acres burned (Miller et al. 2007). Another large wildfire burned in

July 2008, after range monitoring plots were re-surveyed. All of these disturbances have likely contributed to the establishment and spread of non-native plant species at NWSTF Boardman.

2.2 Vegetation sampling

In 1987, eighteen 50 ft. radius range monitoring plots were established at NWSTF Boardman (Figure 1) and data were collected following the methods described in Anderson (1986) and Anderson (1988). Between May 12th and 20th 2008, the eighteen plots were re-located and data were collected using the same methodology used in 1987. Data collection in both years consisted of estimating the percent cover of each plant species and ground surface category (bare ground, litter, and mosses and lichen), assigning a dominance rating to each plant species, estimating vigor and the number of seedlings for key species, and estimating perennial grass and forb biomass. In addition, two photographs were taken at each plot- one of the permanently marked 3 foot square subplot, and another of the permanently marked 25 foot line subplot.

Specific methods for estimating perennial grass and forb biomass were not outlined in Anderson (1986) or Anderson (1988). Therefore, in 2008, the field methods described in Brencé and Sheley (2003) were used to collect biomass samples. Within each plot, a 92 inch circumference hoop was thrown in four random locations, and all perennial grasses and forbs within the hoop were clipped and combined into one paper bag. Samples were then air-dried for several weeks and weighed in grams. Weights for each sample were divided by four to obtain the average weight per hoop, and then multiplied by twenty to obtain pounds of perennial grass and forb forage per acre.

Unknown plants were keyed to species using Hitchcock and Cronquist's (1973) Flora of the Pacific Northwest.

2.3 Data analysis

To compare changes across all eighteen plots between 1987 and 2008, average plant cover by species and plant guild, and average cover of ground surface categories were calculated. Average percent cover was calculated by summing the total cover of each species or plant guild and dividing the value by the total number of plots (18). Plant species were assigned to one of the following guilds: shrubs, native perennial grasses, native perennial forbs, native annual forbs, and exotic annual forbs. Biennial species were treated as annuals for analysis. Species nativity and duration followed USDA (2008).

Paired t-tests were used to compare changes in plant guild cover, *Bromus tectorum* cover, cover of dominant native perennial grasses (*Pseudoroegneria spicata* ssp. *spicata*, *Hesperostipa comata*, and *Poa secunda*), species richness, and ground surface categories across all plots between 1987 and 2008. All statistical analyses were performed in SAS JMP version 7.0, with significant p-values set at 0.05.

2.4 Plot re-establishment

In 2008, many of the plots were missing one or more of the four pieces of rebar that marked the 3 foot square photoplot or were missing the rebar that marked one end of the 25 foot line plot (the other end is the plot monument, marked with a railroad tie). To re-establish the plot

markers, a metal detector was used to determine whether the missing rebar was buried under the soil surface. When the missing rebar was detected, a new piece of rebar was pounded into the ground at the same location that the missing rebar was detected. When the metal detector was not successful in detecting the missing rebar, a tape measure and compass was used to determine the original location of the rebar. A new piece of rebar was pounded into the ground at that location, and distances and directions from the rebar to the plot monument were recorded (Table 1). At one plot (plot 12), the railroad tie marking the plot was also reset because it had been upended.

At all plots, GPS points were taken from the plot monument using a Trimble Juno GPS unit (Table 1). Additional information from 1987 and 1988 regarding plot locations is provided in Appendix A.

3. Results

3.1 Changes in vegetation across all plots from 1987 to 2008

There have been substantial changes in plant species abundance and composition over the past 21 years. Total plant cover averaged across all plots significantly increased from 45% in 1987 to 78% in 2008 ($p < 0.0001$, Figure 2). Increases in plant cover were largely driven by *Bromus tectorum* and native perennial grasses (Figure 3). *Bromus tectorum* cover averaged across all plots significantly increased from 14% in 1987 to 26% in 2008 ($p = 0.0138$), and native perennial grass cover averaged across all plots increased from 18% in 1987 to 27% in 2008, although increases in native perennial grasses were not significant ($p > 0.05$). The native perennial grass that experienced the greatest increase in cover was *Hesperostipa comata* (Figure 4). *Hesperostipa comata* cover averaged across all plots significantly increased from 6% in 1987 to 12% in 2008 ($p = 0.0161$). Native perennial forb cover also significantly increased, from 7% in 1987 to 10% in 2008 ($p = 0.0008$). There were no significant differences in the cover of native or exotic annual forbs or shrubs from 1987 to 2008 (Figure 3).

In addition to increases in plant cover, a greater number of plant species were found on plots in 2008. Species richness averaged across all plots significantly increased from 15 species/plot in 1987 to 18 species/plot in 2008 ($p = 0.0007$; Figure 6). Increases in species richness were largely driven by increases in native perennial forbs (Table 3).

Corresponding with the overall increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground and an increase in litter cover (Figure 2). Bare ground cover averaged across all plots significantly decreased from 52% in 1987 to 23% in 2008 ($p = 0.0001$; Figure 2), and litter cover averaged across all plots significantly increased from 14% in 1987 to 26% in 2008 ($p = 0.0025$). There were no significant differences in the cover of mosses and lichens from 1987 to 2008 (Figure 3).

Perennial grass and forb biomass estimates were substantially greater in 2008 than 1987 (Table 2). Perennial grass and forb biomass estimates averaged across all plots were 138 lbs./acre in 1987 and 317 lbs./acre in 2008. However, because the method used for estimating biomass in 1987 was not recorded, it cannot be assumed that the same method was used in both 1987 and 2008. Although results from 1987 and 2008 are not directly comparable, it is likely that perennial grass and forb biomass was greater in 2008, since both perennial grass and forb cover increased.

3.2 Changes within each plot from 1987 to 2008

Data collected at each plot in 1987 and 2008 are provided in Appendix B, and photos taken at each plot in 1987 and 2008 are provided in Appendix C. Summarized below are the major changes in cover that occurred within each plot from 1987 to 2008.

Plot 1

Plant cover at this plot in both 1987 and 2008 was dominated by *Purshia tridentata* and *Bromus tectorum*. Major changes that occurred included an increase in *Purshia tridentata* cover (from 10% in 1987 to 25% in 2008) and a decrease in bare ground cover (from 50% in 1987 to 15% in 2008) (Table B1, Figure C1). *Bromus tectorum* cover also increased, but only slightly (from 35% in 1987 to 40% in 2008). Several additional native annual and perennial forbs were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987 (Table B1), although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover).

Plot 2

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Ericameria nauseosa* and *Bromus tectorum* in 1987. Major changes that occurred included a decrease in *Ericameria nauseosa* cover (from 15% in 1987 to 5% in 2008), and an increase in *Bromus tectorum* (from 15% in 1987 to 40% in 2008) and *Purshia tridentata* cover (from 3% in 1987 to 10% in 2008; Table B2). Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 80% in 1987 to 30% in 2008 (Figure C3). Several additional native annual and perennial forbs were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987 (Table B2), although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover).

Plot 3

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Bromus tectorum* in 1987. Major changes that occurred included an increase in *Erodium cicutarium* (from 7% in 1987 to 50% in 2008), *Poa secunda* (from a trace amount in 1987 to 15% in 2008), and *Psoralidium lanceolatum* cover (from 5% in 1987 to 18% in 2008), and a decrease in *Bromus tectorum* percent cover (from 50% in 1987 to 30% in 2008; Table B3).

The wildfire that burned through this plot in 2007 probably consumed the few shrubs that were present in 1987 (Figure C6).

Plot 4

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Ericameria nauseosa* and *Bromus tectorum* in 1987. Major changes that occurred included a decrease in *Ericameria nauseosa* (from 20% in 1987 to a trace amount in 2008) and an increase in *Bromus tectorum* (from 7% in 1987 to 25% in 2008) and *Erodium cicutarium* cover (from 3% in 1987 to 30% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B4).

The wildfire that burned through this plot in 2007 probably consumed the *Ericameria nauseosa* shrubs that were present in 1987 (Figure C8). *Hesperostipa comata* clumps were also burned, but many of these were starting to resprout in 2008.

Plot 5

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Bromus tectorum* and *Psoralidium lanceolatum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included an increase in *Bromus tectorum* (from 20% in 1987 to 38% in 2008) and *Poa secunda* cover (from 2% in 1987 to 12% in 2008), and a decrease in bare ground cover (from 30% in 1987 to 15% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B5).

The wildfire that burned through this plot in 2007 probably consumed the few shrubs that were present in 1987 (Figure C10).

Plot 6

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Both of these species substantially increased in cover. *Hesperostipa comata* increased from 7% in 1987 to 35% in 2008, and *Bromus tectorum* increased from 7% in 1987 to 40% in 2008. Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 75% in 1987 to 12% in 2008 (Figure C12). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B6).

Plot 7

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included an increase in *Bromus tectorum* (from 15% in 1987 to 60% in 2008) and a decrease in bare ground cover (from 80% in 1987 to 5% in 2008). There was also a decrease in cover for both species of rabbitbrush (Figure C14). *Ericameria nauseosa* cover decreased from 5% in 1987 to 1% in 2008, and *Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus* cover decreased from 6% in 1987 to 1% in 2008.

Plot 8

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Both of these species substantially increased in cover (Figure C16). *Hesperostipa comata* cover increased from 15% in 1987 to 30% in 2008, and *Bromus tectorum* cover increased from 15% in 1987 to 55% in 2008. Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 70% in 1987 to 10% in 2008. Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B8).

Plot 9

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Elymus lanceolatus*, *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in 1987. Major changes that occurred included a decrease in *Elymus lanceolatus* (from 10% in 1987 to a trace amount in 2008) and *Hesperostipa comata* (from 7% in 1987 to 2% in 2008) and an increase in *Bromus tectorum* cover (from 10% in 1987 to 15% in 2008) (Figure C18). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B9).

This plot burned in the 2007 wildfire, and in 2008, there was evidence of resprouting *Hesperostipa comata* as well as many *Hesperostipa comata* seedlings- therefore it is likely that the cover of this species will increase in future years.

Plot 10

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included increases in the cover of *Psoraleidium lanceolatum* (from 2% in 1987 to 10% in 2008) and *Erodium cicutarium* (from 5% in 1987 to 22% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B10).

The wildfire that burned through this plot in 2007 probably consumed the few *Ericameria nauseosa* shrubs that were present in 1987 (Figure C20).

Plot 11

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Both of these species decreased in cover. *Hesperostipa comata* cover decreased from 15% in 1987 to 4% in 2008 and *Bromus tectorum* decreased from 20% in 1987 to 6% in 2008. Other changes included increases in *Poa secunda* (from 10% in 1987 to 20% in 2008) and *Phlox longifolia* (from 1% in 1987 to 10% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B11).

The wildfire that burned through this plot in 2007 probably consumed the few *Ericameria nauseosa* shrubs that were present in 1987 (Figure C22).

Plot 12

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included large increases in both of these species (Figure C24). *Hesperostipa comata* cover increased from 5% in 1987 to 25% in 2008 and *Bromus tectorum* increased from 25% in 1987 to 50% in 2008. Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 50% in 1987 to 5% in 2008. Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B12).

Plot 13

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Pseudoroegneria spicata* and *Poa secunda* in both 1987 and 2008 (Figure C26). The major change that occurred in this plot was a large increase in *Hesperostipa comata* cover, from a trace amount in 1987 to 15% in 2008. Mosses and lichens cover was relatively high in both years, although there was a decrease in cover from 40% in 1987 to 20% in 2008. In contrast to most of the other range monitoring plots, only trace amounts of *Bromus tectorum* were detected in 1987 and 2008. Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B13).

Plot 14

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Poa secunda* and *Plantago patagonica* in both 1987 and 2008. Neither of these species changed in cover, but there were increases in *Hesperostipa comata* (from 5% in 1987 to 15% in 2008), *Pseudoroegneria spicata* (from 1% in 1987 to 8% in 2008), and *Gutierrezia sarothrae* cover (from 1% in 1987 to 10% in 2008; Figure

C28). Mosses and lichens cover was relatively high in both years, and increased from 30% in 1987 to 40% in 2008. *Bromus tectorum* cover was low in both years (2% in 1987 and 3% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B14).

Plot 15

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Poa secunda* and *Erodium cicutarium* in 1987. Major changes that occurred included increases in *Pseudoroegneria spicata* (from 3% in 1987 to 28% in 2008), and decreases in *Erodium cicutarium* (from 15% in 1987 to a trace amount in 2008), and *Bromus tectorum* cover (from 6% in 1987 to 3% in 2008) (Figure C30). Mosses and lichens cover was relatively high in both years (35% in 1987 and 30% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B15).

Plot 16

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Poa secunda*, *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included decreases in *Poa secunda* (from 30% in 1987 to 20% in 2008), and increases in *Hesperostipa comata* (from 7% in 1987 to 15% in 2008), *Pseudoroegneria spicata* (from 2% in 1987 to 10% in 2008), and *Artemisia tridentata* cover (from a trace amount in 1987 to 18% in 2008) (Figure C32). Mosses and lichens cover was relatively high in both years (30% in 1987 and 25% in 2008). Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B16).

Plot 17

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Poa secunda*, *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. All of these species increased in cover between 1987 and 2008. *Poa secunda* increased from 3% in 1987 to 10% in 2008, *Hesperostipa comata* increased from 15% in 1987 to 25% in 2008 and *Bromus tectorum* increased from 3% in 1987 to 30% in 2008 (Figure C34). Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 75% in 1987 to 20% in 2008. Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B17).

Plot 18

Plant cover at this plot was dominated by *Poa secunda*, *Hesperostipa comata* and *Bromus tectorum* in both 1987 and 2008. Major changes that occurred included increases in *Hesperostipa comata* (from 15% in 1987 to 35% in 2008) and *Ericameria nauseosa* cover (from 2% in 1987 to 8% in 2008; Figure C36). Corresponding with the increase in plant cover was a decrease in bare ground cover, from 40% in 1987 to 8% in 2008. Several additional native forb species, both annual and perennial, were found in 2008 that were not detected in 1987, although these species were only present in trace amounts (<1% cover; Table B18).

4. Discussion

Plant species abundance and composition changed significantly over the last 21 years on range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman. Total plant cover was substantially greater in 2008

than in 1987, with increases largely driven by the native perennial grass *Hesperostipa comata*, native perennial forbs, and the non-native annual grass *Bromus tectorum*. There were also a greater number of plant species found on plots, primarily native perennial forbs. Other changes included a decrease in the amount of bare soil and an increase in the amount of litter.

Although the increases in native species cover and species richness indicate an improvement in condition since 1987, the associated increase in *Bromus tectorum* cover is not encouraging. This species alters natural fire regimes by creating more abundant and continuous fine fuels that can result in more intense, larger, and frequent fires, and after a series of intense fires high quality native habitats can be converted to a monoculture of cheatgrass and other non-native species. Reducing *Bromus tectorum* once it is well-established is difficult and costly; thus management strategies should focus on preventing further *Bromus tectorum* establishment in high-quality areas. The few range monitoring plots that did not experience large increases in *Bromus tectorum* were associated with high lichen and moss cover (i.e. plots 13-16); therefore preventing trampling of the biological soil crust may be an important strategy for minimizing further *Bromus tectorum* increases.

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6. Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Location of range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman.

Figure 2. Total plant cover and cover of ground surface categories on range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008. Values are averages \pm SE; * represents significant differences between years (paired t-test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 18$).

Figure 3. Plant guild and *Bromus tectorum* cover on range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008. Values are averages \pm SE; * represents significant differences between years (paired t-test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 18$).

Figure 4. Native perennial grass cover on range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008. Values are averages \pm SE; * represents significant differences between years (paired t-test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 18$).

Figure 5. Plant species richness on range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008. Values are averages \pm SE; different letters represent significant differences between years (paired t-test, $p < 0.05$, $n = 18$).

Table 1. Location of range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman. GPS datum are in NAD 1983, UTM zone 11.

Plot	Northing	Easting	Plot marker information
1	284459.5212	5076010.6508	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar.
2	288813.1238	5074094.9413	Reset all 4 rebar marking the 3 foot square photoplot. Center of photoplot is 180° from the center of the monument (railroad tie).
3	288384.1736	5059783.7060	
4	292851.9509	5069848.2526	
5	291406.2497	5065169.6690	
6	294603.4683	5061802.5544	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar at 34' 6" and 172° from the monument center (railroad tie).
7	294665.4984	5058057.9713	
8	286815.4557	5060111.3088	
9	287893.7427	5067235.6898	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar at 32' 3" and 155° from the monument center (railroad tie).
10	287941.0083	5070676.7667	Reset one rebar marking the 3 foot square photoplot and the 25 foot line plot rebar.
11	295392.9575	5065255.1156	
12	288162.1390	5075457.7114	Reset all 4 rebar marking the 3 foot square photoplot and the 25 foot line plot rebar. Reset plot monument (railroad tie).
13	290996.3173	5073397.6448	Reset one rebar marking the 3 foot square photoplot.
14	292368.0480	5073671.3042	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar.
15	294151.7775	5072550.8612	
16	294368.6810	5068237.2113	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar at 30' 9" and 167° from the monument center (railroad tie).
17	287126.7000	5071688.7052	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar at 39' 6" and 156° from the monument center (railroad tie).
18	287668.9405	5063004.3892	Reset the 25 foot line plot rebar at 32' and 166° from the monument center (railroad tie).

Table 2. Perennial grass and forb biomass estimates for range monitoring plots at NWSTF Boardman in 1987 and 2008. Different methods were likely used each year; therefore results between years are not comparable.

Plot	1987 (lbs./acre)	2008 (lbs./acre)
1	0	30
2	10	55
3	0	695
4	50	185
5	20	830
6	250	300
7	10	60
8	350	540
9	300	135
10	10	530
11	250	835
12	100	40
13	300	300
14	80	290
15	200	215
16	150	255
17	250	165
18	150	245
Average	138	317

Table 3. Plant species found on NWS TF Boardman range monitoring plots in 1987 and 2008 (N=ative, I=introduced, P=perennial, A=annual, B=biennial).

Scientific name	Common name	Family	Origin	Duration	Growth form	Present 1987	Present 2008
<i>Abronia mellifera</i>	sandverbena, white	Nyctaginaceae	N	P	forb	x	
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	yarrow	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Achnatherum hymenoides</i>	ricegrass, indian	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Agoseris heterophylla</i>	Agoseris, annual	Asteraceae	N	A	forb	x	x
<i>Agropyron cristatum</i>	wheatgrass, crested	Poaceae	I	P	grass	x	x
<i>Alyssum alyssoides</i>	pale madwort	Brassicaceae	I	A	forb		x
<i>Ambrosia</i> sp.	bursage	Asteraceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Amsinkia</i> sp.	fiddleneck	Boraginaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Antennaria dimorpha</i>	pussytoes	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Artemisia tridentata</i>	sagebrush, basin big	Asteraceae	N	P	shrub	x	x
<i>Astragalus purshii</i>	loco, woolly pod	Fabaceae	N	P	forb	x	
<i>Astragalus sclerocarpus</i>	milkvetch, stalked pod	Fabaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Astragalus succumbens</i>	milkvetch, Columbia	Fabaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Balsamorhiza careyana</i>	balsamroot, Carey	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	cheatgrass	Poaceae	I	A	grass	x	x
<i>Calochortus macrocarpus</i>	mariposa lily	Liliaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Camissonia contorta</i>	plains evening primrose	Onagraceae	N	P	forb		x
<i>Centaurea diffusa</i>	diffuse knapweed	Asteraceae	I	A	forb		x
<i>Chaenactis douglasii</i> var. <i>achilleifolia</i>	false yarrow	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus</i>	rabbitbrush, Douglas green	Asteraceae	N	P	shrub	x	x
<i>Crepis atribarba</i>	slender hawksbeard	Asteraceae	N	P	forb		x
<i>Cryptantha flaccida</i>	weakstem cryptantha	Boraginaceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Elymus elymoides</i>	squirreltail	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Elymus lanceolatus</i>	wheatgrass, thickspike	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Epilobium brachycarpum</i>	tall annual willowherb	Onagraceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Ericameria nauseosa</i>	rabbitbrush, gray rubber	Asteraceae	N	P	shrub	x	x
<i>Erigeron filifolius</i>	fleabane, cushion	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Erigeron pumilus</i>	fleabane, shaggy	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Eriogonum niveum</i>	buckwheat, snow	Polygonaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	filaree	Geraniaceae	I	A	forb	x	x
<i>Erysimum capitatum</i>	wallflower	Brassicaceae	N	P	forb	x	
<i>Gutierrezia sarothrae</i>	snakeweed	Asteraceae	N	P	shrub	x	x
<i>Hesperostipa comata</i>	needle-and-thread	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Heterotheca villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	hairy false golden aster	Asteraceae	N	P	forb		x
<i>Holosteum umbellatum</i>	chickweed, jagged	Caryophyllaceae	I	A	forb	x	x
<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	mouse barley	Poaceae	I	P	grass		x
<i>Hymenopappus filifolius</i>	hymenopappus, fineleaf	Asteraceae	N	P	forb		x
<i>Lactuca serriola</i>	lettuce, prickly	Asteraceae	I	A	forb	x	x
<i>Layia glandulosa</i>	white tidy-tips	Asteraceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Lithospermum ruderales</i>	stoneseed	Boraginaceae	N	P	forb	x	
<i>Lomatium macrocarpum</i>	Lomatium (gray carrot leaf)	Apiaceae	N	P	forb		x
<i>Machaeranthera canescens</i>	Aster, hoary	Asteraceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Madia glomerata</i>	cluster tarweed	Asteraceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Microsteris gracilis</i>	Microsteris	Polemoniaceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Oenothera pallida</i>	pale evening primrose	Onagraceae	N	P	forb		x

Table 3. (cont.)

Scientific name	Common name	Family	Origin	Duration	Growth form	Present 1987	Present 2008
<i>Opuntia polyacantha</i>	prickly pear	Cactaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Penstemon acuminatus</i>	penstemon	Scrophulariaceae	N	P	forb	x	
<i>Phacelia linearis</i>	phacelia, threadleaf	Hydrophyllaceae	N	A	forb	x	x
<i>Phlox longifolia</i>	phlox, longleaf	Polemoniaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Plagiobothrys tenellus</i>	popcorn flower, slender	Boraginaceae	N	A	forb	x	
<i>Plantago patagonica</i>	indianwheat, woolly	Plantaginaceae	N	A	forb	x	x
<i>Poa bulbosa</i>	bulbous bluegrass	Poaceae	I	P	grass		x
<i>Poa secunda</i>	bluegrass, Sandberg	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Pseudoroegneria spicata</i>	wheatgrass, bluebunch	Poaceae	N	P	grass	x	x
<i>Psoraleum lanceolatum</i>	scurfpea	Fabaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Pteryxia terebinthina</i> var. <i>terebinthina</i>	desert parsley, chimaya	Apiaceae	N	P	forb	x	x
<i>Purshia tridentata</i>	bitterbrush	Rosaceae	N	P	shrub	x	x
<i>Salsola kali</i>	Russian thistle	Chenopodiaceae	I	A	forb		x
<i>Sisymbrium altissimum</i>	mustard, Jim Hill	Brassicaceae	I	A	forb	x	x
<i>Stephanomeria paniculata</i>	skeleton weed	Asteraceae	N	A/P	forb		x
<i>Tragopogon dubius</i>	salsify	Asteraceae	I	A/B	forb	x	x
<i>Triteleia grandiflora</i>	largeflower triteleia	Liliaceae	N	A	forb		x
<i>Vulpia microstachys</i>	Fescue, pacific	Poaceae	N	A	grass	x	
<i>Vulpia octoflora</i>	Fescue, six weeks	Poaceae	N	A	grass	x	

**Appendix A: 1987 and 1988 descriptions of range monitoring plot locations at
NWSTF Boardman**

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
WESTERN DIVISION
NAVAL FACILITIES ENGINEERING COMMAND
PACIFIC NORTHWEST BRANCH
P.O. BOX 2366
3505 N.W. ANDERSON HILL ROAD
SILVERDALE, WA 98383

MEMORANDUM

IN REPLY REFER TO:
22 APRIL 1988

From: 243NW
To: 243

Subj: NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN FOR NWSTF BOARDMAN, OREGON
NOVEMBER 1987

Ref: (a) Site visit to subject installation 11-14 April 1988
(b) Appendix F of subject plan

1. During reference (a), the 18 permanent inventory and monitoring plots described in reference (b) (pgs 110 et seq.) were located and monumented. Some difficulty was experienced in locating several of the plots. This was due to errors in the Plan map showing plot locations and inaccurate text descriptions of those locations. The following comments and suggestions for map and text revisions should make it much easier to re-locate plots for future examinations. The yellow diamond signs referred to are the "US NAVY Natural Resources Project Do Not Disturb" type. Bearings are magnetic.

PLOT #1. Located in the NE 1/4 of the NE 1/4 of Section 26, T4N, R24E, WBM; 0.5 mile east of the main compound fence, about 150 feet south of road. Railroad tie with yellow plastic top set with 24" showing above grade. Plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N. side of tie. Small (1.75") oval aluminum tag #1 nailed to side of tie. Pins are south of tie.

PLOT #2. Located in the SW 1/4 of the NW 1/4 Section 29, T4N, R25E, WBM; located 30 feet East of the road running N-S along the West side of Section 29. Railroad tie with yellow plastic top set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small oval aluminum tag #2 nailed to W side of tie. Pins bear S 9 E from the tie. This N-S road is 0.6 mile West of the gate in the SE corner of pasture #1. The map used in this plan and the grazing outlease plan erroneously show that the fenceline and gate are located close to a full mile East of the N-S road. Based on observations and measurements of the locations of Plots #2 and #3, the gate/fenceline locations are mapped incorrectly, i.e., the SE'ly fence of pasture #1 is shown East of its true location.

PLOT #3. Located in the NE 1/4 of the NW 1/4 of Section 32, T4N, R25E, WBM; approximately 0.3 mile West of the gate in the SE corner of pasture #1; located 200 feet N of road (not 300 as the Plan says). Railroad tie with yellow plastic top set with 24" showing above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign nailed to N side of tie; small aluminum tag #3 nailed to W side of tie. Pins bear S 10 W from the tie.

PLOT #4. Located in the SW corner of the SW 1/4 of the NE 1/4 of Section 34, T 4 N, R 25 E, WBM. Map shows location incorrectly; plot is located south of the site indicated on the map; plot is 200 feet North (not South as the text says) of the road running NWW-SEE parallel (+/-) to the South fence of pasture #2, not north of the road (runs NEE-SWW) leading to the old tower site. Railroad tie with yellow plastic top set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #4 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 2 W from tie.

PLOT #5. Located in the NE corner of the NW 1/4 of the NE 1/4 of Section 2, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 120 feet West of road. Railroad tie set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #5 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 13 W from tie.

PLOT #6. Located in the SE corner of the SE 1/4 of Section 10, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 75 feet West of dirt road running N-S. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #6 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 10 W from tie.

PLOT #7. Located in the NE corner of the SW 1/4 of the SW 1/4 of Section 13, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 175 feet East of the dirt road. Railroad tie with yellow cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #7 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 11 W from tie.

PLOT #8. Located in the NW corner of the SW 1/4 of the SE 1/4 of Section 6, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 150 feet North of the road. Railroad tie set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #8 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 2 W from tie.

PLOT #9. Located in the SE 1/4 of the NE 1/4 of Section 7, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 180 feet West of the dirt road. Railroad tie set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #9 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 7 E from the tie.

PLOT #10. Located in the NE 1/4 of the SE 1/4 of Section 33, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot bears S 50 W 250 feet from the West gate post of the gate in the center of the North side of pasture 2B. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #10 nailed on the W side of the tie. Pins bear S 10 E from the tie.

PLOT #11. Located in the NW corner of the SW 1/4 of Section 20 , T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 100 feet East of the dirt road, 100 feet South of the airplane run-in line. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #11 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 3 E from the tie.

PLOT #12. Located in the NE corner of Section 6, T 2 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 160 feet West of the dirt road that runs N-S. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #12 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 10 W from tie.

PLOT #13. Located in the SE corner of the SW 1/4 of Section 7, T 2 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located approximately 0.15 mile North of the South fence of pasture 1B. This plot was re-established using the pins and the photos in the Plan. No steel fence post was present. However, the grass clumps shown in the photo, the distance from the pins given in the text and disturbed soil at what appeared to be the spot from which the steel post was removed, combined to aid re-establishment with a very high degree of confidence that the original posting has been duplicated. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #13 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 8 W from the tie.

PLOT #14. Located in the NE corner of the NW 1/4 of Section 17, T 2 N, R 25 E, WBM; located 0.4 to 0.45 mile East of the N-S road running along the West side of Section 17; located 100 feet North of the E-W running road. Railroad tie with yellow cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #14 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 3 W from tie.

PLOT 15. Located in the NW corner of the NE 1/4 of the NW 1/4 of Section 24, T 2 N, R 25 E, WBM; located about 350 feet South of the road. This plot is in pasture 2C, not 2B as the text states. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #15 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 4 E from tie.

PLOT #16. Located in the NE corner of the NW 1/4 of Section 12, T 2 N, R 25 E, WBM. This plot is located 0.9 mile North of the E-W running road cited in the text. A newly bladed road (2/88) over an old track runs North and ends at the plot. The plot is 35 feet East of this dirt road. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #16 nailed on W side of the tie. Pins bear S 4 E from the tie.

PLOT #17. An understatement would be to say that this plot was difficult to find using the map. It is actually about 1/2 mile from the spot indicated on the map. Plot is actually located in the NW corner of the SE 1/4 of the SW 1/4 of Section 27, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot is located 20 feet East of the dirt road, 0.25 - 0.27 mile South of the Main Target fenceline. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #17 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear S 11 E from tie.

PLOT #18. Located in the SW corner of the NE 1/4 of the NE 1/4 of Section 25, T 3 N, R 25 E, WBM; plot located 150 feet East of the dirt road 0.1 mile (not 0.2 mile as the text says) South of the E-W road entering off the Heppner Highway. Railroad tie with yellow plastic cap set with 24" above grade; plot tag and yellow diamond sign on N side of tie; small aluminum tag #18 nailed on W side of tie. Pins bear due South from the tie.

2. The above information should be combined with the text descriptions given in reference (b) to generate more accurate and complete. If you do issue an addendum to the Plan, please send me a copy.
3. If there are any questions about the above descriptions, please call me.

Walter Briggs
WALTER BRIGGS
Staff Forester

3. RANGE MONITORING PROGRAM 1987

The range monitoring program developed for the station is a procedure that consists of two phases, one conducted annually and one periodically over a span of years.

The annual phase consists of interpreting patterns of utilization that exist following the livestock grazing season. The procedure involves judging five classes of utilization on key species, mapping use zones within a pasture, and evaluating these zones to determine the effects that the current grazing system and existing facilities and improvements collectively are having on the resources within the pasture. This entire procedure is outlined in an article written by:

Anderson, E. William and W.F. Currier. 1973. Evaluating zones of Utilization. Journal of Range Management 26(2) 87-91.

The periodic phase consists of interpreting data collected on permanent plots. The objective of this procedure is to measure changes that occur in the plant community. These measured changes consist of the following: floristic composition; canopy cover; litter; plant vigor; and forage production. In this procedure, each permanent plot consists of three components: a 3 foot square plot marked by steel pegs which serves as a close-up photo point; a 25 foot line plot marked by a steel fence post to encompass the photo plot, which serves as a general aspect photo line; and an unmarked plot approximately 50 feet in radius centered on the smaller photo plot which serves as the area where all plant species are recorded and canopy coverage determined. Data collection begins by listing all species that occur within the 50 feet circle and then estimating the canopy cover and dominance rating for each individual species. Determinations are also made for bare ground, litter and mulch, rocks, and mosses and lichens. Estimations are made on forage production, and apparent vigor of key species. This entire procedure is outlined in a manuscript written by:

Anderson, E. William. 1987. Canopy cover as a method of monitoring trend in ecological and soil status. Submitted to Rangelands.

The periodic phase of this monitoring program was initiated in early May and the annual phase in early June after the cattle were removed from the station. The information obtained from this program is contained herein.

Plot #1 is in Pasture 5 south of the main road going SE from Navy Headquarters. It is located about 70 yd. south of the 0.5 mile marker (a post marked 5). The plot, which is marked with a 6' steel fencepost and lies about 25-30 feet south of this post, consists of a 3-foot-square marked at each corner by a steel rod painted red. A fifth steel rod slightly south of the plot is the photo point for the camera tripod from which photos are taken of the plot itself and of the site aspect with the steel post in the middle.

The soil at this plot is Koehler loamy sand

0-30" loamy sand 30" + calcareous pan

Cover data represents the area approximately 50 feet radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Plot #2 is in Pasture 1 east of the N-S road that bisects the pasture and about 0.3-0.4 mile south of the north boundary fence. The plot lies about 70 feet east of the road on a hummock which is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of a 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red.

Cover data represents the area approximately 50 ft. radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Hezel loamy sand (0-12" loamy sand; 12-42: sandy loam laminated calcareous, hard; 42" + soft silt loam).

Plot #3 is in Pasture 1. It is located north of the road that parallels the south fence about 0.3 mile west from the east gate and 100 yds. north of the road. The plot is marked with a steel fencepost which is about 30 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel pegs. A fifth steel peg south of the plot marks the photo point from which the 3-foot-plot and the site aspect were photographed.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

Plot #4 is located in Pasture 2, 0.4 mile west and 100 yds. south of the gate in NW corner of Pasture 2C where it joins Pasture 2. The plot is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 20 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg just south of the 3-foot square is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents the area approximately 50 feet radius from the 5-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

Plot #5 is located in Pasture 2C on the west side of the N-S road through the middle of the pasture and 0.3-0.4 mile south of the north boundary fence. It is marked by a steel fencepost 40-50 yds. west of the road which is about 20 ft. north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg south of the 3-foot-plot is the photo point for photos of the 3-foot plot and the site aspect. Data represents the area within about 50' radius of the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

Plot #6 is located in Pasture 4B about 0.3 mile south of the buried pipeline that runs diagonally NW to SE across the pasture. It is located about 100 feet west of the N-S road through center of pasture and is marked by a steel fencepost that is about 30 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel rods pointed red. A fifth steel rod slightly south of the 3-foot plot is the photo hub from which color photos of the 3-foot plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents an area about 50 feet radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Quincy loamy sand.

Plot #7 is located in Pasture E about 0.6 mile south of the gate in NW corner of Pasture E. It is located east of the road about 100 yds. where the road bends to the SE. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot which is marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg slightly south of the 3-foot square plot is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represents an area about 50 ft. radius from the 3-foot square plot.

Soil is Royal loamy very fine sand.

Plot #8 is located in the SW portion of Pasture 3. It is located about 50 yds. north of the E-W road about 0.2 mile east of the main N-S grave road. It is marked by a steel fencepost which is about 25 feet north of the 3-foot-square plot marked by 4 steel pegs painted red. A fifth steel peg slightly south of the 3-foot plot is the photo hub from which photos of the plot and site aspect were taken. Vegetation data represent an area about 50' radius from the 3-foot-square plot.

Soil is Koehler loamy sand (36" caliche).